

BSc DEGREE IN

Computer Science

PROJECT REPORT

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Project Title: Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool For
Group Presentations

Project Supervisor: Professor Graeme Jones

Please complete your chosen Mark Allocation Model below. The "fixed" sections may not be changed. In the other sections, you may choose only ONE of them to assign only one (1) single point. Half points may not be allocated. The total must add up to 10 and the two fixed sections may not be changed. If this is not completed or not completed correctly, the default model will be used. See Canvas and lecture notes for more information about Mark Allocation Models.

Section	Points Allocated
Introduction and Literature Review	1
Methodology and Analysis	2
Design	2
Prototype/Implementation	3
Validation and Testing	1 (fixed)
Critical Review and Conclusion	1 (fixed)
Total	10

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Date: Monday 24th April 2023

Signature: Tug Fergus O'Flaherty

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Contents

Acknowledgement	2
Abstract	6
1 Introduction.....	7
1.1 Background and Context	7
1.2 Project Solution and Significance	8
1.3 Aims and Objectives	10
1.4 Constraints and Scope	10
1.5 Project Methodology.....	11
1.6 Project Schedule	13
1.7 Ethics	13
1.8 Organisation	17
2 Literature Review	20
2.1 Introduction.....	20
2.2 User Authentication	20
2.3 HTTP Authentication	23
2.4 Request Authorisation.....	24
2.5 Role-Based Access Control (RBAC)	24
2.6 Request Validation	25
2.7 Conclusion	25
3 Requirements Analysis	26
3.1 Introduction.....	26
3.2 Stakeholder Analysis.....	27
3.3 SWOT Analysis	30
3.4 User Analysis	33
3.5 Use Case Analysis	36
3.6 System Requirements.....	42
3.7 MoSCoW Prioritisation	44
3.8 Conclusion	44
4 Design.....	46
4.1 Introduction.....	46
4.2 User Interface Accessibility	46
4.3 User Interface Presentation	49
4.4 User Interface Components	55
4.5 API Endpoints	62
4.6 Data Modelling	68
4.7 Process Modelling	73

4.8	Conclusion	76
5	Implementation.....	78
5.1	Introduction.....	78
5.2	Architecture.....	79
5.3	Technologies.....	82
5.4	Tools	84
5.5	Libraries and Frameworks	87
5.6	Database Implementation.....	89
5.7	Backend Implementation	108
5.8	Frontend Implementation	129
5.9	Refactoring	185
5.10	Coding Principles	203
5.11	Security.....	204
5.12	Conclusion	206
6	Validation	209
6.1	Introduction.....	209
6.2	Testing Strategy.....	209
6.3	Integration Testing	211
6.4	Performance Testing	216
6.5	Load Testing	220
6.6	System Testing.....	225
6.7	Usability Testing	229
6.8	Conclusive Recommendations	246
6.9	Conclusion	247
7	Critical Review	248
7.1	Introduction.....	248
7.2	Aims and Outcomes	248
7.3	Summary of Achievements.....	251
7.4	Reflections.....	254
7.5	Future Work	257
7.6	Conclusion	260
	References.....	261
	Appendix	268
	Appendix A – Project Schedule.....	268
	Appendix B – Sprint Breakdown.....	270
	Appendix C – Weakness and Threat Mitigation	271
	Appendix D – User Personas	273
	Appendix E – User Stories	279

Appendix F – Use Case Textual Descriptions	282
Appendix G – Functional Requirements	314
Appendix H – Non-Functional Requirements	318
Appendix I – MoSCoW Prioritisation	320
Appendix J – Initial Sketches	324
Appendix K – Medium Fidelity Wireframes.....	340
Appendix L – Navigation Diagrams.....	360
Appendix M – Reusable Component and Container Sketches	363
Appendix N – Endpoint Syntax Designs	371
Appendix O – Initial Request/Response Body Objects	380
Appendix P – Final Request/Response Body Objects	393
Appendix Q – Entity Relationship Diagrams (ERD)	401
Appendix R – Data Dictionaries	409
Appendix S – Activity Diagrams	428
Appendix T – Sequence Diagrams	468
Appendix U – Integration Testing.....	478
Appendix V – Performance Testing	499
Appendix W – Load Testing	505
Appendix X – System Testing.....	509
Appendix Y – Usability Testing Consent Collection	514
Appendix Z – Usability Testing Results Tables.....	523

Abstract

Many university courses have incorporated module assessments involving the delivery of a live presentation to a panel of assessors, where both the student's understanding of their produced works and their presentation skills are reviewed, resulting in the student obtaining feedback and credit towards a student's module grade.

However, assessors within a panel are given freedom to deliberate and record their feedback, leading to a lack of consistency, hindering student feedback and grades. Assessors within a panel may make digital or paper notes during the presentation individually, before discussing their ideas with the other panel members to produce a unified feedback document, which can lead to inexperienced assessors struggling, or a lack of consistency or best practice within the feedback produced.

As panels gain experience with the assessment format and generating feedback comments, through assessing multiple groups, their feedback consistency and accuracy typically improves. Panels generally lack time between talks to fully discuss each group's performance and feedback, often leading to rushed and inaccurate feedback, or a delayed start to the next presentation, disrupting the event's schedule. Feedback collation from panels, to disseminate to each group and formally assign students' grades, is a lengthy process for the lead assessor.

The project seeks to resolve these issues, through creating a common platform to address the lack of standardisation and consistency across feedback gathering methods currently used, and promote consistent marking and feedback from assessment panels when assessing student presentations. The solution would facilitate collaboration between panel members during assessments to better support inexperienced panellists and enable the creation of consistent, agreed feedback and grades during the presentation, without contributing to delays to presentation schedules. The common platform would make it easier and faster for feedback to be disseminated to students.

This document explores the process of producing such tool, including gathering the necessary information to produce the required designs, creation and testing of such an application, and review of the work undertaken.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Context

Universities collectively strive to offer students an enhanced understanding and experience across both core academic domain-specific knowledge, and within industry-favoured interpersonal skills, allowing students to develop their employability (Kornelakis and Petrakaki, 2020). Employers commonly expect prospective candidates to already possess strong presentation and public speaking skills, a mainstay of their organisation, as typically noted within job descriptions, thus allowing newly hired employees to perform necessary roles with reduced training. To prepare students for such careers, and facilitate the demands of industry, many university undergraduate degree courses incorporate assessment elements encompassing the delivery of a live presentation to a panel of assessors.

Through assessments incorporating the research, production and performance of a presentation, students' understanding of desirable presentation and public speaking skills may be evaluated, with students frequently being assessed within a group, to enable the assessment of teamwork skills (Joughin, 1998). It is beneficial for assessments to be simultaneously marked by a minimum of two assessors, to ensure accuracy and consistency across provided feedback, thus providing the student with a clear outline of both their positive aspects and areas for future improvement.

Whilst it is deemed necessary for groups to be assessed by two or more assessors, the processes and logistics involved in coordinating and collating such assessors and their resulting feedback must not be understated. It is widely accepted that it is the sole responsibility of an assessment setter, commonly a role fulfilled by the topic's lead lecturer, to provide assessors with a form of, typically digital, documentation for assessors to complete and return, offering a consistent mechanism for the receipt of generated group assessment feedback. Although the reporting of provided feedback mandates consistency, assessors are offered complete freedom in their approaches of deliberation and approach to marking. This granted independence may lead to a lack of consistency across provided feedback, with assessors utilising customised approaches to produce suitable grades and feedback.

A common approach to collaborative panel-based assessment marking involves assessors independently creating notes throughout the group's presentation, using either digital or paper mediums, with a panel discussion occurring following the presentation's conclusion (Joughin, no date). Although discussions may result in consistency across the panel, each panel member is expected to produce their own feedback report, for increased accuracy and accountability. With multiple feedback reports being produced, the production of a single unified feedback document, containing all provided panel members' feedback, may contain inconsistencies and opposing statements, a reflection of the struggles of inexperienced assessors, hindered by a lack of knowledge surrounding marking best practice, or conflicting opinions of panel members.

Arguably, consistency can be improved through defining standards and training all assessors, to become better prepared and more knowledgeable on marking standards and grade boundaries (Joughin, no date). However, it is often difficult to provide definitive or clear guidance as to the feedback expected from assessors, and with some panel members often being alumni working in industry, there is commonly limited time to sufficiently train assessors within best practice.

It is usual for panels to gain experience with the assessment format and marking best practices during the undertaking of the assessment event, through developing skills after assessing multiple groups, thus their feedback accuracy and consistency typically improves over the duration of such occasion. As such, initial assessments, conducted by a potentially inexperienced panel, can severely undermine assessment integrity, with students who were assessed during the commencement of the assessment process risking receiving either advantageous or detrimental grades and feedback, as a result of the panel's lacking experience.

Due to the limited availability and commonly full schedules of assessors, and to prevent particular groups from being unfairly advantaged by having an increased amount of time to prepare their presentations prior to assessment, presentations typically occur with five minutes allocated for panel discussion, preceding the commencement of the following presentation (Joughin, no date). Consequently, panels commonly lack the required time between presentations to suitably discuss the group's performance and feedback, increasing the likelihood of provided feedback being rushed, inaccurate or inconsistent. In the case of panels utilising effective discussion between presentations, delays to the commencement of the following presentation are commonplace, disrupting the event's schedule, causing inconsistency across panels, and disrupting the upcoming groups.

Although inaccuracies within panels and their provided feedback significantly hinder student experience and undermine assessment accuracy (Grieve *et al.*, 2021), the effect of the assessment logistics on the assessment setter should not be underestimated. With each assessor within a panel completing a feedback report for each group, the process of collating such received feedback and calculating marks to disseminate to each group, and produce a formative grade, is lengthy, although integral to the assessment (Joughin, no date).

As feedback being sensitive, the importance of ensuring academic integrity and minimising the potential of unauthorised grade modifications being critical, and training of additional personnel being lengthy, it is commonly the sole responsibility of the assessment setter to compile feedback reports from their received feedback reports. This moderation and publishing process, from received feedback into formats accepted by learning management systems (LMS) such as Canvas, is time consuming, reducing morale, and causing some assessment setters to consider modifying assessment types, to prevent undertaking it (Ostafichuk and Jaeger, 2016).

1.2 Project Solution and Significance

The proposed system seeks to mitigate against the identified issues, through investigating the feasibility of an application to promote marking and feedback consistency within assessment panels, during their process of assessing group presentations. Through producing a common platform for assessors to record their initial thoughts and submit a final feedback report using, such application attempts to address the lack of standardisation and consistency across feedback gathering methods currently used. With assessors being provided with a universal method of recording their thoughts, this alleviates their choice in using a bespoke format to generate feedback comments, aiming to mitigate against identified consistency problems.

The developed system would endeavour to facilitate the organisation and logistics of all current components during the undertaking of the assessment event, including the creation of assessments and dissemination of their relevant tasks and submission instructions and rubric. Assessment setters would be provided with functionality to create external assessor accounts, to allow external markers, such as alumni, to assess group presentations, with both university lecturers and students having existing accounts linked to the university IT systems, upon enrolment within the organisation.

Following the creation of an assessment, assessment setters would be able to assign panels to assess groups, being allocated a timeslot based on the presentation length and required discussion time between presentations, with timeslots being efficiently distributed to panels and groups via the system, streamlining logistics processes.

Users would be offered the ability to create profile biographies, to inform others of their hobbies, interests or learning journeys. It would be encouraged that groups create biographies, to share to the panel, in advance of the presentation, their collective interests and any supporting information. Similarly, panels should detail their credentials, experience and background within their biography, to inform group members of their journeys, thus disseminating careers and employability knowledge, and providing a connection between the group and their panel, prior to the assessment being undertaken.

Upon commencement of a group's assessment, real-time collaboration and communication between panel members would be facilitated, providing assessors with a mechanism to view their other panel members' provided feedback, and send direct messages to better support inexperienced panellists, and enable the creation of consistency across feedback and grades, without contributing to unnecessary delays to presentation schedules. Due to the reduction in the required time between presentations, it may be possible to increase the number of assessed groups during one assessment event, thus better utilising assessors' time.

The system would provide the assessment setter with the capability of creating pre-configured feedback statements for each assessment rubric criterion, thus improving feedback consistency and standardisation, through ensuring all provided feedback is relevant and of a high quality. Furthermore, standardised feedback would allow for students' easier interpretation of feedback reports, with a clear alignment to the provided assessment rubric.

Support for free-text comments would be included, permitting customised feedback statements to be included, where relevant, thus increasing the relevancy and accuracy of provided feedback. Such an approach ensures collaboration between assessors throughout the assessment process, as opposed to individually marking and reviewing ideas after the presentation has finished.

Following the creation of assessment reports from each panel member, the system would automatically collate the provided feedback from all assessors into a single unified document, calculating the average marks for each rubric criterion across all assessors, and an overall formative grade. This feedback may be published, allowing students to view and download their feedback reports and grades, or exported, for use within a learning management system (LMS).

All feedback would be stored and accessible from a centralised location, allowing the assessment setter to view and distribute grades from one source, negating the requirement to collate provided feedback and manually disseminate it to students. Such process seeks to reduce the time required to collate received feedback, thus reducing demand on assessment setters' schedules, and ensure students obtain feedback in a timely manner.

It is intended that the solution would be centrally adopted by universities, providing lecturers involved in the setting of panel-based collaborative assessment of presentations delivered by groups of students of any discipline to utilise the tool. The assessment setter would be expected to manage the assessment's preparatory tasks and dissemination of feedback, whilst panellists, whether external or university lecturers, would be placed on panels, provided with access to record feedback for provided groups. Students would be placed within groups, utilising the solution to view assessment information, feedback and grades, for the assessments they have partaken in.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

1.3.1 Project Aims

The project's primary aim is to develop a university-oriented collaborative solution for the purposes of stimulating consistency and conforming to good practices within assessment panels partaking in collaborative marking. The secondary project aim is to reduce the time required for assessors to summarise and discuss assessment feedback after the conclusion of the assessment, increasing assessment throughput and minimising delays or inaccurate feedback given. Both aims seek to mitigate against the previously detailed issues with the existing mechanisms during collaborative assessment processes and logistics.

1.3.2 Project Objectives

The project's main objectives are detailed below:

- Review current technologies and development platforms to identify the most suitable environment for a modern, cross-platform, scalable application
- Evaluate existing assessment and feedback platforms to determine their strengths and limitations
- Catalogue requirements elicited from meetings with the client, stakeholders and target demographic, to determine the necessary assessment marking features expected by users
- Produce clear and creative wireframes and prototypes to obtain both client and target audience feedback, assisting in refining the usability aspects of the frontend design
- Creating an ER diagram capable of accurately modelling the database, required to store necessary data including users, panels, groups, assessments and feedback
- Create a user-friendly frontend to allow students, assessors and the wider module team to view, record or export assessment feedback
- Create a suitably scalable backend API with a series of endpoints to facilitate frontend data retrieval for displaying data on-screen, with persistence to permanently save necessary data to the database for later retrieval
- Produce an authentication system to ensure the application is compliant with Data Protection Act (2018) regulations, facilitating secure and accurate data access and storage
- Ensure the backend API and database mitigates against common cyber security threats
- Perform extensive testing of the application to ensure it both fulfils all necessary client requirements and is fully functional
- Deploy the application to allow it to be accessed and used by the client and intended users

1.4 Constraints and Scope

Prior to the project's commencement, the client mandated constraints that governed development. Due to the client's necessity for a web-based solution, to ensure compatibility across all hardware and software platforms, and desire for maintainability and modern, scalable web applications, for application futureproofing, a single-page application (SPA) and representational state transfer (REST) application programming interface (API) approach, using React, Express, SCSS and MySQL, was specified. Consequently, the developed application was required to implement such structure and technologies, to meet the specified requirements of the client. Further information regarding the mandated architecture and technologies' definitions, purpose and benefits is contained within Section 5.2.1 – Separate Frontend/Backend, 5.2.2 – Representational State Transfer (REST) API and 5.3 – Technologies .

The project's scope is intended to involve the specific development of a standalone collaborative marking and feedback tool, accessible via a desktop or laptop web browser. Due to the potentially wide nature of the application's domain, the application will be limited to the specific area of marking group presentations within panel-based assessments. The project is limited to not utilise further complex technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI) or deep learning, to offer assessors appropriate suggestive feedback comments, based on their selected or inputted feedback.

Areas encompassing development of applications for integration within learning management systems (LMS) such as Canvas are beyond the project's scope, with such technologies requiring vast in-depth knowledge of specific plugin development. It must also be noted that the project is limited to group marking, therefore ancillary functionality, such as that of creating randomised groups, or weighted groups based on similar students' attendance and previous assessment grades, is outside of the defined project scope.

The tool is concerned with the creation of feedback for university group presentations assessed by panels, therefore assessment reports for individuals, or those made by singular assessors, are beyond the scope of the project. It must be noted that although collaborative assessment may be used in other domains or contexts, such as for reviewing candidate performance in job interviews, the developed system will only facilitate collaborative assessment in the discipline of university undergraduate courses at a single university, with modular structures.

The developed system will only support textual feedback comments, lacking support for audio or video-based feedback reporting, due to the constraints surrounding panel-based assessment of live presentations. Additionally, the tool will not allow for the upload of supporting presentation files or documentation, such as presentation slides or scripts, as such functionality does not directly relate to the collaborative marking process. Consequently, there will be no ability to integrate the system with any other third-party services or tools, such as plagiarism detection tools, to verify the integrity of submitted work.

As the tool is concerned with the recording of feedback, independent of the method of presentation, such as via videoconferencing or face-to-face, no tools will be provided for videoconferencing, therefore existing platforms, such as Microsoft Teams or Zoom, must be utilised. It must also be noted that full accessibility and internationalisation features, such as support for audio description, screen readers, high contrast, increased font size, and multiple languages and regional date formats, will not be implemented.

It is essential to mention that due to the constraints imposed upon the project by the client, the developed solution will not be natively available, via means of an installed application, for platforms such as Microsoft Windows, MacOS, iOS or Android.

1.5 Project Methodology

The project utilised a hybrid project management approach, consisting of principles from both DSDM, alternatively referred to as AgilePM, and Scrum. Although DSDM is intended for use within large-scale software development projects (Anwer *et al.*, 2017), and Scrum is involved in managing software development teams (Hossain, Babar and Paik, 2009), both methodologies contain elements that may be successfully applied to this individual project.

The implemented methodology sought to incorporate the DSDM principles of frequent delivery and incremental development (Highsmith and Cockburn, 2001), with new user stories and designs proposing implementation, being validated with the client every three weeks. Such process ensures rapid adaptation to potential requirements changes, to safeguard against the successful implementation of the client's expected features, resulting in the development of a suitable solution, regardless of the client's changing requirements.

It is anticipated that, due to lecturers being a key stakeholder and intended system user type, requirements will likely change, as a result of modifications to assessment formats. As lecturers better understand and recall the challenges faced during collaborative assessment marking, based on their previous experience, additional requirements are likely to be proposed and elicited, thus it is crucial that the project is safeguarded against scope creep and functional requirements are appropriately prioritised.

The DSDM concept of MoSCoW prioritisation will be used to facilitate the successful prioritisation of functional requirements, mitigating against changing elicited requirements and ensuring the solution contains the client's most important requirements, enhancing the likelihood of the project's success (Highsmith and Cockburn, 2001). MoSCoW prioritisation is crucial to delivering a suitable solution to the aforementioned problem, as meetings with lecturers will likely increase the project's scope, with the aim of wishing to automate further aspects of the assessment process, to reduce the required time for assessment preparation. Such functionality, potentially encompassing user stories including automated, randomised or academically-weighted group formation, would be beyond the scope of the project, and could risk the failure of implementation of all core system functionality.

Scrum's iterative development approach will be utilised (Highsmith and Cockburn, 2001), embodied through the use of sprints during project development, to facilitate the successful implementation of user stories. Each sprint will commence with the selection of the user story to be implemented, decided upon through reviewing the MoSCoW-prioritised list of requirements with the client, to prioritise the implementation of the critical user stories.

Following the selection of the desired user story, designs will be produced for the data model, backend API endpoint and data storage medium interaction, frontend user interface designs, and code. After approval from the client, the produced designs will be realised during the implementation phase, in which the user story functionality will be fulfilled within the system. The sprint will conclude with refactoring any developed code, to ensure the developed code is clean, thus increasing maintainability and future sprint development time.

An iterative development approach will allow the design and testing of each user story to be suitably validated by the client and target demographic, university lecturers, due to their demanding schedules. Through fulfilling a minimal subset of requirements in every four-week sprint, it is expected that lecturers will be offered the necessary time to evaluate each proposed feature within their schedules, in contrast to using the Waterfall approach, where lecturers would likely lack sufficient time to suitably review the design and validation phases in their entirety, thus leading to a lack of project direction and client input, increasing the risk of development of an unsuitable system.

The sprint format will be consistent, thus increasing the development team's efficiency, and providing the client with clear processes surrounding the application's development. During each sprint, the sprint's goals will be discussed, deliverables produced, and necessary client validation will be performed based on the produced artefacts.

As expected within the Scrum methodology, each sprint will be reviewed with the client to showcase the completed user stories and receive feedback, allowing the client to steer the course of the project, and ensuring the project team are aware of misdirection at the earliest opportunity, to prevent the development of an unsuitable system (Hossain, Babar and Paik, 2009). In the case of the client concluding that a sprint's produced artefacts are unsuitable, such artefacts will be revisited and modified in the subsequent sprint, ensuring they meet the client's requirements and expectations.

At the conclusion of each sprint, a sprint retrospective will be completed individually, documenting the sprint's outcomes, success and potential improvements, to ensure further sprints may be conducted more effectively. Such process seeks to help with project progress analysis and provide a more accurate gauge of the number of user stories the project will likely complete, aiding the client in selecting the most suitable user stories to implement.

1.6 Project Schedule

Prior to the project's commencement, a complete project workplan was created, defining the expected completion dates for key project milestones. This workplan allows the project's progress to be continually monitored by both the project team, client and stakeholders, to ensure the project is expected to meet imposed deadlines, whilst providing all involved parties with an indication of the predicted schedule. All milestones were expected to be presented to the client on-time, based on the mutually agreed date contained within the workplan. A breakdown of the activities completed within each sprint was produced, to inform the development team of the necessary tasks requiring completion, and their order, thus facilitating the successful accomplishment of each sprint.

The complete project workplan is contained within Appendix A, whilst the sprint breakdown is contained within Appendix B.

1.7 Ethics

1.7.1 Project Ethical Considerations

Throughout the project, it is necessary to consult both the client, stakeholders, and real users of all types, such as students and lecturers, to better understand the current pitfalls of assessment marking and feedback, aid in the elicitation of requirements, and validate the designed and developed system. All participants must consent to their involvement and their responses must be anonymised, to prevent the accidental or unintentional data leakage of responses associated with participants. Ethically, such information must not be shared, and all language used throughout such meetings should remain professional and related to processes, rather than critiquing any individual responsible for assessment setting or providing feedback.

Assessment can be a particularly stressful process for certain students (Grieve *et al.*, 2021), therefore appropriate mechanisms must be in place during all engagement with participants, including termination of meetings, referral to additional support services, or withdrawal from the study. Students who have faced challenges in past groupwork activities, or received negative feedback for previous assessments, may feel sensitively about this topic, therefore they must feel supported throughout their interview and only feel obliged to share what they are comfortable with saying.

It would be unethical to interview past external project assessors, as they will be preoccupied in their employment roles and will not have time to provide feedback on the developed application, or on problems they have had when marking assessments in the past. As such, only participants who will reasonably have spare time to participate in the study, without negatively affecting their existing roles, personal life, or mental health, should be approached.

When creating and testing the application, no factual data should be used, especially assessment details and rubrics, persons or feedback, in order to prevent the impact of potential data breaches or unauthorised users from viewing live, sensitive information. Furthermore, it would be unethical to entrust such data with participants when performing usability testing, due to the negative mental health impact such responsibility may cause.

Upon the successful deployment and real-world use of the application, all users must ensure their usage of the system is ethical, including not screenshotting or sharing any pictures or information such as contact details, assessment information, feedback, or grades, as this could compromise the assessment's integrity or a user's personal information. Although measures are unable to be implemented to mitigate against the occurrence of such activity, users should be reminded that they are bound by the acceptable usage and behaviour policies enforced by their organisation, such as Kingston University.

It is ethically important that the solution be created in a way that is accessible to all users, including those who are neurotypical or colourblind. Due to the wide-ranging demographic of students and assessors who will use the application, it is important that no users are unfairly disadvantaged or hindered in their usage of the application, as detailed by the Equality Act (2010).

1.7.2 Collection of Participants' Informed Consent

To ensure participants are informed to consent in the study, a Participant Information Sheet (PIS) will be constructed, outlining the project's purpose and duration, expected participant commitment, potential risks involved in participating in the study, the required data that will be gathered, and how and by whom collected data will be used.

The participant information sheet will also detail data retention, compliance with the Data Protection Act (2018) and the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR), security mechanisms to protect collected data, data confidentiality, and the process for withdrawing from the study, including what happens to participant data if consent is withdrawn.

The participant information sheet will be provided to prospective participants, in combination with a consent form, to brief users and gather their consent to take part in the study. Should participants have any questions prior to, during, or after conclusion of the study, they are able to contact the research team, to become better informed. Prospective participants will be given adequate time to digest the participant information sheet and consent form, ensuring they are able to provide informed consent.

1.7.3 Ethical Data Collection

Consenting participants should expect to receive links to online surveys, sent to their provided email address, from a reputable GDPR-compliant survey company, Microsoft Forms (Microsoft, 2018), ensuring collected data is collected and held securely, reducing the impact of data theft. Following the completion of all surveys, the data will be exported from the survey application, for anonymised use in the project. For participants without an email address, a paper version of the survey will be provided, which should be completed and returned to the research team. Response data will be associated with participants through means of a provided ID, preventing responses from being directly linked to an individual.

Individual interviews will be conducted with individual participants, with structured and semi-structured interviews being used. Additionally, focus groups, consisting of groups of participants, will be used to gather information, with participants being asked questions and providing responses.

Interviews and focus groups will collect data through the use of transcription, with the interviewer manually recording response information in a Microsoft Word document.

No audio or video recording techniques will be used, and interviewees are free to review, or request copies, deletion, or modification of the transcribed document at any time. Through not recording interviews or focus groups, this provides an intrinsic anonymity, with the identity of participants being unable to be directly associated with their responses. Response data will be associated with participants through means of a provided ID, preventing responses from being directly linked to an individual. Interviews and focus group meeting invitations will be sent to participants via organisational email messages, ensuring secure means of communication.

Photographs may be taken of key documentation, or other such items, provided by the interviewee during an interview or focus group, although no participants or identifiable information will be included within a taken photograph. Screen recordings, including static screenshots, will be taken of a participant's screen whilst they are using the prototype application, for testing and validation purposes of the produced application, although no participants or identifiable information will be included within a taken screen recording. As such, anonymity of participants is protected.

Email communications will be used, with any messages being sent or received from the research team to participants being recorded, for the purposes of keeping them informed about the status of the study. These will be stored and treated securely and in confidence. In the event an email address has not been provided, telephone communications will be used.

1.7.4 Ethical Data Storage and Usage

The study uses the lawful basis of consent, with the project complying with the Data Protection Act (2018) and GDPR, as participants will be fully aware of the data that will be collected and stored on them, the purposes of this data collection, and any processing that will occur on their data. Only the basic information required on a participant will be collected on them, including their name and email address, for contact purposes with regards to engaging in the project, and their response data, associated with them for the purposes of removal upon withdrawal of consent. Response data will be associated with participants through means of a provided ID, preventing responses from being directly linked to an individual.

All collected data will only be accessible by the project leader, and will be stored securely in an encrypted, password-protected directory on a University-owned, managed device. Participants must consent to their information being collected and used, after they are appropriately informed to make a decision through reading the participant information sheet and completing the consent form. Data will only be stored for as long is necessary, which is detailed as the duration of the project.

Collected participant data will only be used for the purposes of gathering and validating user requirements and validating any produced application implementations or features contained within these. Any published data, such as in a report, will be fully anonymised and, where appropriate, aggregated, to ensure confidentiality and prevent identification of participants.

Interview textual data and pictures taken will be securely and confidentially contained in encrypted, password-protected Microsoft Word documents stored locally on secure device. These documents will be stored in a private directory, only accessible by the researcher, and the document passwords will not be stored, and only known by the researcher, preventing unauthorised access.

Documents will only be accessed and viewed in private locations, from a password-protected, encrypted device, where unauthorised persons are unable to inadvertently view the content of the documents. Upon completion of accessing the documents, the device will be locked, to prevent unauthorised access. Documents will not be copied, duplicated, or sent to any other locations or devices.

Stored data recorded on the website of Microsoft Forms, a reputable GDPR-compliant survey company (Microsoft, 2018), will be contained in accordance with their terms and conditions and privacy policy, which will be outlined to the user prior to taking the survey. Should participants not consent to these policies, or not provide a contact email address, paper copies of the survey will be provided to participants.

All paper copies of completed surveys will be held in a locked bag on the researcher's person and processed securely. During this process, the document will only be visible to the researcher, who will enter the form data into an encrypted, password-protected Microsoft Word document stored securely on the managed device, within two working days of receiving the paper form in a private location. Upon successful entry of the paper survey into the Microsoft Word document, within two working days of receiving the paper form, the paper document will be securely destroyed.

1.7.5 Secure Data Destruction

Upon project conclusion, all Microsoft Word documents, screen recording, screenshot, email messages, telephone call history logs, and associated data contained within the secure directory of the managed device, and survey responses contained within Microsoft Forms, will be securely destroyed, in line with industry best practice and the recommended guidance of the software provider.

Following receipt of a participant's withdrawal of consent, all Microsoft Word documents, screen recording, screenshot, email messages, telephone call history logs, and associated data related to the withdrawing participant, identified through their provided ID value, contained within the secure directory of the managed device, and survey responses contained within Microsoft Forms, will be securely destroyed, in line with industry best practice and the recommended guidance of the software provider.

No audio or video recording techniques will be used, and interviewees are free to review, request copies, deletion, or modification of the transcribed document at any time. Photographs, screen recordings and static screenshots will not include participants or identifiable information.

Photographs will be taken using a smartphone device and transferred to the managed device containing the Microsoft Word document, before being inserted into the associated Microsoft Word document, within two working days. Any copies of the photograph stored within the smartphone or managed device will be securely destroyed upon successful insertion into Microsoft Word document. Screen recordings and screenshots will be saved to encrypted, password-protected secure directory contained within the managed device.

Email communications will be used, with any messages being sent or received from the research team to participants being recorded, for the purposes of keeping them informed about the status of the study. These will be stored and treated securely and in confidence. In the event an email address has not been provided, telephone communications will be used. Email communications will be stored securely via on Microsoft Outlook's email servers in the cloud, whilst telephone call logs will be retained on the telephone used to make the call to the participant.

1.8 Organisation

This report is divided into a number of chapters, denoted by whole chapter numbers, such as 1 Introduction, for collation of different project phases, and ease of reading. Each chapter contains a number of sections, denoted by single decimal place identifiers, such as 1.3 Aims and Objectives. Chapters may be further separated into subsections, signified by decimal place identifiers, such as 1.3.1 Project Aims. Sections and subsections contain closely related project information, for ease of location of specific information. Within chapters, singular figures may be contained, as denoted by their figure number displayed within the associated caption, with further figures available in the specified appendix. References may be viewed using the associated references list. This subsection details an overview of the information contained within each chapter.

1.8.1 Introduction

The introduction chapter examines the context and motivation behind the project, including the identified solution and its significance to the target userbase. The project's aims and objectives are detailed, prior to outlining mandated aspects of the project, as stated by the client. The scope of the project is outlined, to outline the limits of the project, prior the explanation of the project's methodology and schedule. The ethical considerations and proposed mitigations surrounding the project are investigated, before the structure of the report is listed.

1.8.2 Literature Review

The literature review chapter details the results of comprehensive research conducted on the selected theme of best practice for securing RESTful APIs. After introducing the chapter, user authentication is discussed, including mechanisms such as API keys, single sign-on (SSO) and HTTP authentication methods. Request authorisation is presented, including the use of role-based access control (RBAC) methods, and request validation, before the conclusion summarises the discussed authentication and authorisation approaches.

1.8.3 Requirements Analysis

The requirements analysis chapter details the results of requirements elicitation from the client, key project stakeholders, and potential users from target user groups. After introducing the chapter, stakeholder analysis is provided, listing the key stakeholders identified, and their associated power and interest in the project. SWOT analysis is conducted, with the results of a SWOT matrix forming the basis for the project recommendation and weakness and threat mitigation.

User analysis is performed, resulting in the creation of user personas and user stories, before use case analysis is used to determine the system actors and their associated requirements, presented in use case diagrams and textual descriptions. The system functional and non-functional requirements are presented, prior to being prioritised using MoSCoW prioritisation, to determine the requirements and their associated order, in which to be implemented within the system, before the conclusion summarises the discussed elicited requirements.

1.8.4 Design

The design chapter details the results of the application's data model, code and frontend user interface design, formed from the previously elicited requirements. After introducing the chapter, user interface accessibility mechanisms are discussed, including the consideration of the use of colour, icons, font, navigation and the impact of neurodiversity on the suitability of the system.

The user interface presentation is listed, including the implications of responsive design, and the produced initial sketches, medium fidelity wireframes, and navigational hierarchies. The design of the user interface components required, including horizontal cards and draggable items, including their potential reusability, are examined.

The design of the endpoint syntax and HTTP request and response bodies, in addition to handling of sorting, pagination and conditional searching, are presented, prior to the conducted data modelling being detailed, including the creation of entity relationship diagrams (ERD) and a data dictionary. The outcomes of process modelling, represented through using UML activity and sequence diagrams, were displayed, before the conclusion summarises the system designs produced.

1.8.5 Implementation

The implementation chapter details the results of realising the designs within the developed application. After introducing the chapter, the system architecture, including the use of a separate frontend and backend and representational state transfer (REST) application programming interface (API) is explained.

The technologies used, including React, SCSS, Express, MySQL and Git, are examined, including their purpose and benefits to the project. Similarly, the tools used, including Microsoft Visual Studio Code, Windows PowerShell, XAMPP, phpMyAdmin, Postman and the Mozilla Firefox web browser with React Developer Tools extension, are detailed. The utilised existing libraries and frameworks, including react-flatpickr, react-router-dom, cors, joi and mysql2, used in the creation of the application, were examined.

A thorough discussion on the implementation of the database, including the choice of platform, creation, population and querying of the database, is discussed, with a similar discussion evaluating the backend implementation platform choice, creation of request validation, data access and conformance, returned responses, database connection and backend structure, following.

The frontend implementation, examining the choice of platform, creation of reusable React components, implementation of existing React components, management of component state and hooks, form input validation and conformance, backend API fetch, page navigation, styling and structure, is detailed. The coding principles, including a sprint-based implementation and refactoring process, were examined, prior to a discussion on the implemented database and backend security mechanisms, before the conclusion summarises the system implemented.

1.8.6 Validation

The validation chapter details the results of extensive validation and verification performed on the developed application, to ensure the system was fully functional and suitable for the client's requirements. After introducing the chapter, the produced testing strategy was detailed, investigating the importance of creating a testing strategy.

The goals, design, data collection, analysis, evaluation and conclusive recommendations for the performed integration, performance, load, system and usability testing, were examined, including a discussion on the collection of informed consent from usability test participants. The list of conclusive recommendations obtained from the conduction of all testing methods was provided, before the conclusion summarises the testing performed and results obtained.

1.8.7 Conclusion

The conclusion chapter critically reviews the success and outcomes of the project, evaluating the development team's performance and learning journey. The project's aims and objectives are stated, alongside a discussion as to the project's level of success as to which the aims and objectives were met. The project and project team achievements, including project management and communication, analysis, design, technologies used, development practices, validation and transferrable skills, were subsequently examined.

A range of reflections were made, including on the implementation of collaboration mode, searching, refining and pagination, system data export, mobile device support, deployment, create new assessors functionality, and general project struggles, detailing project failings and offering reasons for the shortcomings.

The chapter details the future work required on the system, such as implementation of a collaboration mode, direct messaging, export of grades and feedback, import of groups and panels, emailing of alerts, feedback reports and password reset links and integration with learning management systems, Microsoft identity platform and OAuth2, to improve functionality and offer an enhanced feature set, thus benefitting user experience.

1.8.8 References

The references section contains a detailed Harvard reference list of all the information sources used during the compilation of the report. It allows for the cross-referencing of presented ideas, information and arguments used, for which additional reading may be conducted, to gain a further understanding into the discussed subject area or argument.

1.8.9 Appendix

The appendix section contains further material relating to information presented in all chapters throughout the report. Often, chapters contain numerous data tables and figures that would hinder the readability of the main text, therefore such cases present a subsection of the produced data within the section, for the purposes of explanation and analysis, with the remaining data contained within the appendix. Although not mandatory, it is strongly recommended that appendix data is reviewed, to obtain a more detailed understanding of the chapter explanations. Content contained within the appendix is referenced in the associated location of the chapter, and is subsequently labelled, for ease of identification.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The following section seeks to address the increasingly important issue of securing RESTful APIs, through detailing best practice for securing RESTful APIs. The web application intended to be implemented as the proposed solution to the problem previously outlined, will likely utilise a separate frontend and backend architecture, with the latter utilising a RESTful API architecture. It is paramount that an investigation into the best practice for securing RESTful APIs is conducted, to ensure the produced solution does not suffer from unauthorised access, increasing data integrity and potential system reliability.

This report will detail industry-recognised approaches to securing RESTful APIs from unauthorised access or data modification, including the ways in which these methods can be implemented, and their strengths and weaknesses. It should be noted that whilst this report details popular approaches to RESTful API security, there are too many different approaches used to successfully detail in such a report. As technology, implementation methods and attacks evolve, best practice may also change, therefore the reader must be aware that the relevancy of this report may be short-lived beyond the time of writing.

The following report will outline current widely-adopted approaches to user authentication regarding RESTful APIs, including API keys, single sign-on methods, such as OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect, and HTTP authentication, with methods including basic authentication, bearer authentication, and cookie-based authentication. The subsequent section will focus on request authorisation methods, such as role-based access control and request validation, before summarising.

2.2 User Authentication

User authentication involves the process of verifying that a user is who they are claiming to be, based on the request they are making to access a service. There are typically three methods able to be used to identify a user – what a user knows, such as a password, what a user has, such as an access token, or what a user is, such as biometric data (Bilal *et al.*, 2020). Authentication is a crucial aspect of restricting access to only authorised users, through proving a user's identity before providing access to a RESTful API and must occur before API data may be exchanged. At the core of authentication is the concept of a user and RESTful API being aware of and exchanging secret information, only known by both parties (Brachmann, Dittmann and Schubert, 2012).

Modern web-based solutions are typically being produced using a separate frontend and backend, with backend applications, typically RESTful APIs, containing logic, functionality and facilitating database interaction (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021). These RESTful APIs allow frontend applications to persistently store data, which may be viewed across multiple devices. To protect an application's critical backend RESTful API infrastructure, user authentication must be implemented, safeguarding against data loss or system failure, which damages a user's experience of an application, and risks loss to the API's owner (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021).

Although RESTful API user authentication is important, its implementation is inherently difficult, due to the RESTful architecture being stateless, with no concept of sessions. The notion of state persistence may only be emulated via the transmission of data within an API request, as no session data is contained within the server, unlike PHP, which offers session variables. Although there are many techniques available in the user authentication domain, API keys, single sign-on (SSO) and HTTP authentication remain the most prevalent in industry, therefore these authentication methods will be explained in greater detail.

2.2.1 API Keys

One common method of user authentication is achieved by utilising API keys, which are passed in user requests to the RESTful API server. Upon receipt of a request, the server retrieves the API key and cross-references an authentication database, to verify the user's identity, based on an associated record in the database (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021). Should the database lack a record containing the API key received, the API will refuse to process the request and will instead block access to the user (Modi, Chourasia and Pandey, 2022). API keys are generated and uniquely assigned to users by the RESTful API upon user registration, and typically remain constant throughout the lifespan of the user's registration to the API.

API keys are typically used for simplicity and efficiency when creating a user authentication system for an API, being appended as a request parameter, passed in request headers, or transferred via cookies. As any client providing a request containing a valid API key may be successfully authenticated and access the API, API keys lack the reliability provided by other user authentication methods. API keys may be passed as string values (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021) or encrypted using an MD5 hashing algorithm (Modi, Chourasia and Pandey, 2022), although both of these methods requires the security provided via HTTPS, using TLS, otherwise the key may be intercepted and decoded as it traverses the internet to reach the RESTful API server.

2.2.2 Single Sign-On (SSO)

Single sign-on, often abbreviated to SSO, is becoming an increasingly popular method of user authentication, allowing a user's single set of login credentials to authenticate them to provide access to multiple services, with user authentication occurring via an alternative, trusted application (Arshad, Benolli and Crispo, 2022). This trusted third party is commonly a major technology provider, with whom significant numbers of users have an existing account with.

One of the most prevalent issues plaguing unauthorised system use is credential theft, involving the use of stolen or unencrypted login information being used by third parties to make illicit RESTful API requests (Singh, Patel and Chaudhary, 2022). Single sign-on approaches seek to mitigate credential theft, with users being provided with a method to authenticate and access applications, without the need to share any login credentials (Roger A Grimes, 2019). Bilal *et al.* (2020) believes SSO will become increasingly relevant, mitigating APIs against both phishing attacks and session hijacking, due to the reduction in user credentials being required to be transmitted to authenticate users across multiple services.

SSO may be implemented via a range of frameworks, including OAuth 2.0, OpenID Connect, SAML 2.0 (Security Assertion Markup Language), RADIUS and Kerberos (Singh, Patel and Chaudhary, 2022), although the underlying principle of the authentication method used remains common. If a user wishes to access an application using SSO, the application must request user authentication from the SSO login provider, through sending a user information token, containing information such as the user's email address (Fruhlinger, 2022). The SSO provider identifies if the user is already logged into their service, otherwise requesting the user to login via their standard account credentials, before sending a token to the application, with the application then validating this token based on the trust configuration it has with the SSO provider (Fruhlinger, 2022).

OAuth 2.0 is one of the most ubiquitous implementations of the single sign-on approach, being an open standard used to offer delegated authorisation to RESTful APIs, with users using third-party logins to access services provided by other organisations (Brachmann, Dittmann and Schubert, 2012). OAuth 2.0 allows users to authenticate with a service, without requiring them to enter login credentials, via obtainment and subsequent transmission of an access token from a third-party application to the RESTful API. Access tokens may be acquired via one of four methods – resource owner password credentials, client credentials, implicit or authorisation code, with tokens being provided by organisations including Facebook (Arshad, Benolli and Crispo, 2022).

OAuth 2.0 provides scalability, security and ease of implementation, as the user authentication is being provided by a third party, rather than involving implementation as part of the development of the RESTful API. With major organisations providing SSO via OAuth 2.0, it is likely these third parties will have implemented stronger security measures than plausibly integrated into a RESTful API user authentication mechanism, however if the SSO provider is vulnerable or attackers exploit OAuth 2.0 weaknesses, unauthorised users may still be wrongfully authenticated (Fruhlinger, 2022). It should be noted that OAuth 2.0 only works over HTTPS (Roger A Grimes, 2019), although is available for a variety of devices, include mobile, web and desktop applications.

OAuth 2.0 involves a resource owner, which is used to provide access to a service such as a RESTful API, a resource server, which provides a resource and can authenticate requests based on request access tokens received, a client, which requests resources for the resource owner, and an authorisation framework, which issues tokens to clients upon successful authentication (Singh, Patel and Chaudhary, 2022).

OpenID Connect is an increasingly widespread decentralised authentication method, using the underlying OAuth 2.0 technology and JSON Web Tokens (JWT), due to their ease of implementation and small size overhead (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021). As a standardised approach, OpenID Connect is available for clients of all types, including machine-clients such as JavaScript or web clients, whilst offering the ability to identify a user in the frontend application, as well as the backend API, using an identity layer over OAuth 2.0 (Singh, Patel and Chaudhary, 2022).

OpenID Connect seeks to address the problem of users requiring a separate user profile per website or application they login to, with OpenID Connect being provided by organisations including Google and Microsoft. Through being combined by a randomly and securely-generated one-time password (OTP), OpenID Connect may be used to securely authenticate users of a RESTful API, however if the one-time password is obtained by an unauthorised party, access may still be granted to the attacker (Bilal *et al.*, 2020).

OpenID Connect builds upon the OAuth 2.0 framework, through transmitting an openid scope value in each authorisation request, whilst storing user information, such as their email address, in a JWT known as an ID Token (Arshad, Benolli and Crispo, 2022). A random string value is generated from an authorisation request, called a nonce, which connects a session with the created ID Token, which may be included in the ID Token to reduce the risk of replay attacks, by ensuring the token remains consistent with the original request (Arshad, Benolli and Crispo, 2022).

2.3 HTTP Authentication

HTTP, or Hypertext Transfer Protocol, is used to transmit requests from a client to a server, such as a RESTful API. HTTP offers inbuilt methods to provide user authentication within requests made to the server, contained within the request header field (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021). HTTP provides two underlying forms of authentication, from which many different implementations are available – basic authentication and digest authentication (Nakhuva and Champaneria, 2017). A further authentication method, transmitted using HTTP requests although implemented using alternative request headers, is cookie-based authentication. These three forms of authentication represent the most widely-used RESTful API user authentication methods, without the involvement of third-parties.

2.3.1 Basic Authentication

The simplest form of HTTP authentication is the implementation of basic authentication, which involves sending a Base64-encoded username and password string in the HTTP request header to the RESTful API server for user authentication (Nakhuva and Champaneria, 2017). Upon receipt of a request, the RESTful API server retrieves the username and password string from the request, contained in the form Basic <username: password>, and queries the user authentication database for such data. If a matching user record is found, the request is valid and the server returns a HTTP status code 200, whereas if no record is found, the user has been unable to be authenticated and the server returns a HTTP status code of 401.

Basic authentication is more advantageous than digest authentication, due to its simplicity to implement (Nakhuva and Champaneria, 2017), although HTTPS with TLS must be used to send the HTTP requests from the client to the RESTful API server, due to the username and password being sent using Base64, which is easy to decrypt (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021).

2.3.2 Bearer Authentication

Bearer authentication, also referred to as token-based authentication, is a HTTP authentication method involving the transmission of a server-signed token contained within a request. Once a user has been registered to a RESTful API service, a unique token is provided to identify their requests. This token is contained within an authentication database, with API requests receiving the authorisation request and querying the authentication database to identify if there is a matching token record to grant the user access to the system (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021). Furthermore, the RESTful API server ensures the token has not expired, as tokens may be given a suitable expiry date, to further increase security, should a token be intercepted and attempted to be continually used to authenticate an unauthorised third party.

The bearer authentication system may either be used independently, as a standalone user authentication system, or in conjunction with a single sign-on service, such as OAuth 2.0 or OpenID Connect, although HTTPS should be used to ensure the token is securely transmitted to the server, and cannot be easily decrypted and used by an attacker (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021). Tokens may be transmitted in HTTP requests in the form of a query parameter, such as `/api/users?token=x`, or as a header parameter, such as `Authorization: Bearer <token>` (Corradini *et al.*, 2022).

2.3.3 Cookie-Based Authentication

Cookie-based authentication is a HTTP authentication method which utilises browser cookies to store session information. User-identifiable information is contained within a cookie, received from the RESTful API server upon a user successfully authenticating with the system through their login credentials. This cookie is separate to the HTTP request, although each request to the RESTful API must include the Set-Cookie field in its header, containing reference to the stored browser cookie (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021). Each request made to the API server must pass identification of the saved cookie, such as `Cookie: sessionId = 1`. The RESTful API will, upon receipt of a request, inspect the cookie value, reference a mechanism for associating cookies with sessions and, if appropriate, grant the user access to the resource.

As cookies are being transmitted from the client to the server, HTTPS, using TLS, should be used to encrypt the request data. To further enhance security, a CSRF security token may be appended to the HTTP request header, in the form `X-Csrf-Token: token_value`, to mitigate vulnerabilities stemming from the use of cookies for the purposes of authentication (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021).

2.4 Request Authorisation

Request authorisation is the concept of managing permissions and access rights to a resource, as particular users may have certain access levels to be able to create, view, update or delete data from a RESTful API, through appropriate HTTP requests (Brachmann, Dittmann and Schubert, 2012). Authorisation involves restricting the resources users can access based on their user type, as even if a user has been successfully authorised, their request may not be allowed based on their permissions. Through appropriately managing resource access, this can significantly enhance the security of a RESTful API, due to preventing users with no requirement for particular data from accessing, modifying or deleting it, increasing data integrity.

API security must be underpinned by authorisation, registration and access rights separation, preventing users from having access to resources that they otherwise do not require, as failure to do so is one of the most dangerous API vulnerabilities (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021).

2.5 Role-Based Access Control (RBAC)

Role-based access control, also known as RBAC, is a core concept in the permissions management of resources in a system. Typically, users are categorised by user groups, which reflect a user type or position in an organisation's hierarchy, and such user groups are mapped to roles within a system, to provide access to resources for certain user groups (Brachmann, Dittmann and Schubert, 2012).

Role-based access control must be in place for all separate RESTful API endpoints, as request authorisation must be managed at the resource itself. It can be advantageous to create a database containing a RoleAreaConnection relation, associated with a user group, role and resource, to manage user group access to resources, based on their roles (Brachmann, Dittmann and Schubert, 2012). Upon the API receiving a request, the user's group is referenced to their user role, to identify if the user has suitable permissions to access the resource, and grant access if required.

2.6 Request Validation

Request validation is a key technique to improve RESTful API security, through preventing unauthorised or malformed requests from being fulfilled. Typically, requests follow a normal case, with data being transmitted to the endpoint in a suitably-defined format, based on the endpoint's requirements. Request validation seeks to mitigate issues arising from input data not conforming to the defined specification, but instead leading to exceptional data flows and flaws in the underlying RESTful API implementation (Corradini *et al.*, 2022).

To resolve the risks associated with unconforming requests, all requests should be validated before they are executed, with constraints being associated with data inputs, including enforcing mandatory request data to be sent, or defining schema values' data types and number ranges (Corradini *et al.*, 2022). Validation rules should check request content types, sizes, lengths, and run parameterised queries on the database, as opposed to manual statements (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021). Requests which do not adhere to the validation schema should not be executed, but errors should be returned to the client, according to the OpenAPI specification.

Request validation is key to preventing potential internal server errors, if data attempting to be referenced is of the wrong data type, is out of range, or is missing, which may significantly reduce data security. Validation methods used should be those integrated with the programming language used for the implementation of the RESTful API, to further enhance security, as bespoke implementations may be vulnerable to attacks (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021).

2.7 Conclusion

It can be concluded that there are wide range of approaches available and used within industry to protect RESTful APIs against unauthorised access. As outlined in this report, user authentication is particularly important, and may be implemented through methods including API keys, single sign-on, through OAuth 2.0 or OpenID Connect, or HTTP authentication, such as basic authentication, bearer authentication, or cookie-based authentication. The role of request authorisation, such as role-based access control and request validation, must also be considered when implementing a secure RESTful API.

Although comprehensive, this report was unable to review all approaches to RESTful API security, with information regarding data transmission, such as through HTTPS, data encryption, runtime environments and endpoint design being unable to be explained in detail. RESTful API security is an ever-evolving sector, with future developments likely to include updates to the popular single sign-on protocols, due to their ubiquity in industry, whilst basic, less secure authentication methods including basic authentication, are likely to see a diminishing use.

3 Requirements Analysis

3.1 Introduction

The requirements chapter will examine the processes undertaken to determine the requirements of the system, through requirements elicitation, and their respective priorities. It will first highlight the key stakeholders identified as having being impacted by the project, and seek to understand their requirements and views surrounding the important aspects of the system, assisting with scoping the project and ensuring it is fit for purpose, with the resulting analysis being placed in a power-interest matrix.

A SWOT matrix will provide further insight into the potential benefits and risks within the project, with a project recommendation being produced based on its findings. The SWOT matrix will form the basis of weakness and threat mitigation, to attempt to minimise the potential risks and problems with the project, namely relating to scoping.

User personas will provide a detailed insight into the target userbase of the system, ensuring it is being designed and implemented with its audience in mind, assisting with preventing unnecessary requirements being elements of focus. User stories will offer a broad insight into the system requirements elicited from the users, which are refined and expanded upon within the use case textual descriptions, highlighting system flows and alternative flows.

The list of system actors and associated use case diagram show the users' high-level requirements from the system and ensure the system will meet the needs of all user types, with key functionality being implemented across all user groups.

The functional requirements will provide the basis for MoSCoW prioritisation, in which the order of requirement implementation will be detailed, with the aim of ensuring all key requirements are successfully implemented, thus seeking to guarantee a minimum viable product is produced. The associated non-functional requirements seek to affirm the constraints on the produced system, impacting its method of implementation.

The project management methodology used utilises an amalgamation of principles from both DSDM (also known as AgilePM) and Scrum. The approach uses DSDM's frequent delivery and incremental development to validate produced deliverables with the client on a weekly basis, ensuring the project adapts to any changes.

MoSCoW prioritisation is used to ensure the system will contain the most important requirements, increasing its potential for success. Scrum's iterative development is encompassed, through delivering features using a series of sprints. At the start of each sprint, the user story is selected, the system workflow and designs are produced, and the feature is implemented.

Testing is performed on the implemented requirement, followed by refactoring, to ensure the code is maintainable. A sprint retrospective is completed at the end of each sprint, to detail the outcomes and potential improvements to be followed through into the next sprint.

3.2 Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholders are organisations or individuals who are impacted by the developed system, thus having an interest in its development, and often potentially strong opinions or ideas surrounding its functionality or operation. Internal stakeholders are individuals directly working for the organisation, who may have a strong influence on the developed system, whilst external stakeholders are those who are not directly working for the organisation, although use or rely on it, thus having an interest in the project (Marshall, 2018).

It is critical to attempt to ensure all stakeholders are in support of the project and its decisions, as stakeholder conflict can often lead to project failure, or certain stakeholders may attempt to disrupt the implementation of the system. To gather stakeholders' views and attempt to gain their support and associated requirements, stakeholder analysis was performed. This included identifying the key stakeholders and producing a power-interest matrix based on their presented views.

3.2.1 Key Stakeholders

Key stakeholders were identified, to provide an insight into their roles, their relationship with the organisation, and their views or ideas surrounding the implementation of the system. These stakeholders were analysed, to ensure the system would fulfil their purpose and provide them with suitable benefit, in an attempt to gain their support. By gaining knowledge surrounding the key stakeholders, the system requirements could be tailored to benefit all user groups and those impacted by the project. It was identified that there would be four internal stakeholders and five external stakeholders, with all internal stakeholders being direct users of the system.

Internal Stakeholders:

Course Leader:

Course leaders are responsible for managing degree courses within the University. As part of this role, they are expected to oversee and support all modules and assessments across their course. The course leader would be able to create, view, edit and delete modules, assessments and users, in the event there are problems with the system data that the module leader has failed to resolve. Furthermore, it is their responsibility to create new modules, as their course dictates.

Module Leader:

Module leaders are responsible for managing assessments and lecturing within their module. This role sees them liaising with the module delivery team, coordinating module assessments, and supporting students within the module. The module leader would be able to create, view, edit and delete assessments and users within their module, in the event there are problems with the system data that the assessment leader has failed to resolve.

Assessment Leader:

Assessment leaders are responsible for managing their assessment and delivering content within their set assessment. This role sees them liaising with the creating and organising the assessment for their lecturing block. The assessment leader would be able to create, view, edit and delete their assigned assessments.

Lecturer:

Lecturers are responsible for providing feedback and grades to students, through marking their assigned assessment. This role sees them creating, editing and deleting marks for a group assessment they are assigned to assess.

Student:

Students are responsible for presenting their produced work during the assessment, to receive a suitable mark. This role sees them viewing the assigned assessments they are required to partake in, to be assessed.

External Stakeholders:

External Assessor:

External assessors are responsible for providing feedback and grades to students, through marking their assigned assessment, although they do not work for the University directly. This role sees them creating, editing and deleting marks for a group assessment they are assigned to assess.

Professional Body:

Professional bodies are responsible for overseeing and regulating the taught University degree course content, and its method of teaching and assessment, although they do not work for the University directly. They are interested in ensuring the course is delivered and assessed in a suitable manner, although do not interact with the system directly.

Central Government:

Central Government is responsible for overseeing and regulating the taught University degree course content, and its method of teaching and assessment, and for University funding, although they do not work for the University directly. They are interested in ensuring the course is delivered and assessed in a suitable manner, although do not interact with the system directly.

Parent/Guardian:

Parents and guardians wish to see their children succeed, achieve high grades, and have a positive journey through University, although they do not work for the University directly. They are interested in ensuring their children are happy and supported throughout their course and assessments, although do not interact with the system directly.

3.2.2 Power-Interest Matrix

Upon identifying the key stakeholders impacted by the project, a power-interest matrix was produced. The power-interest matrix was used to outline both the level of power the stakeholder has over the project, including their ability to delay or cancel the project, and the levels of interest and engagement different stakeholders have within the project (Bryson, 2004).

To ensure the project is successful, it is important to focus on stakeholders with high levels of power, as these stakeholders can influence project decisions and hinder project progression. It is advisable to ensure stakeholders with high interest are suitably informed on the project's progress and, due to their high interest, they often provide a useful resource for system requirements.

The power-interest matrix was used to identify the most important stakeholders, who are required to be kept informed, and those who may offer insight into the system, to assist in the successful completion of the project.

It was identified that parents and guardians have the lowest power and interest, as they are unable to directly change the project, and typically are uninterested in the method of assessment, unless there are problems which affect their children. Parents and guardians would not directly use the system. Students have low power, as they are typically unable to change the assessment methods and are only given access to view the system.

External assessors have high interest, as they would be required to use the system to assess groupwork, although their power is limited as they volunteer their services and do not work for the University. Professional bodies have low power, as they can choose to de-accredit degree courses, although this would not prevent the course from being taught, and they would not use the system directly.

Central Government has relatively moderate power, as they have the ability to change University funding and fail to accredit degree courses, although they do not take much interest in the forms of assessment used, and would not use the system directly. Lecturers have moderate interest, as they will use the system they have been provided with to assess students, although they have a moderate interest in ensuring their role can be fulfilled efficiently.

Module, course and assessment leaders have high power and interest, as they would use the system to assess students and collate feedback, therefore have the power to change the requirement scope of the project to fit their needs. Consequently, students, parents and guardians, professional bodies and Central Government may be monitored, with typically low effort being required to engage these user groups in the project.

Lecturers and external assessors must be kept informed of new developments in the project, to satisfy their interest in the project's development. Assessment leaders, course leaders and module leaders must all be managed closely, to ensure they are in support of the project and their requirements are fulfilled.

Figure 3.1 Power-Interest Matrix

3.3 SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis is a method of capturing the potential strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that may arise during the project's duration (Leigh, 2009). Strengths provide the benefits behind the project, which may be communicated to high-risk stakeholders, in an attempt to gain their support for the project.

Weaknesses provide risks that may occur as a result of the project, deeming it less successful than it could be. Opportunities outline the potential plans and options that may be undertaken, to further benefit the project outcome, whilst threats outline issues that may arise, and should be mitigated against.

From producing a SWOT matrix, a recommendation may be made as to decisions which should be undertaken before the project design and development commences. Furthermore, weakness and threat mitigation may be taken, to prevent issues from disrupting the course of the project, and causing its failure.

3.3.1 SWOT Matrix

The SWOT matrix details the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats identified as potentially impacting the project. Strengths provide the project with valuable insight into the potential success and pitfalls of aspects within the project, including the project team's skills available resources, whilst weaknesses highlight poor skills or issues that may affect the project.

Opportunities outline external considerations that may be applied to your project to improve it, such as new technologies or ways to apply strengths, with threats detailing the external risks to the project, such as those associated with using other organisations' services.

The SWOT matrix offered an insight into potential success factors of the project, which were communicated to the stakeholders and client, for them to better understand the benefits of undertaking the project. The strengths and weaknesses influenced the technologies used to produce the system, due to the development team having a particular understanding and skillset of React web development. The opportunities and threats affected the design decisions taken, due to offering an insight into the potential external implications on the project.

Figure 3.2 SWOT Matrix for Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool Project

3.3.2 Project Recommendation

From the SWOT matrix produced, it was identified that the project's strengths and opportunities outweigh the weaknesses and threats. The project offers the potential to save assessment leaders time and increase feedback consistency through collaboration. It may be implemented in different applications, such as to assess candidates applying for a job, or could be used by other Universities who partake in panel-based assessment. Furthermore, it may be integrated with an LMS, such as Canvas, expanding its uptake in the education sector.

On the other hand, assessment leaders or assessors may not wish to undertake the learning necessary to adopt the tool, due to feeling comfortable with using their own method of recording assessment feedback. Additionally, stored assessment data may become corrupted, or there could be a lack of time to implement all features. The threat of data loss or data integrity issues must not be understated, and tools such as Canvas may later decide to integrate its collaborative marking feature into their tools as standard, due to the rise in collaborative apps in recent years.

However, these weaknesses and threats are not likely to affect the project's development, as it is expected that assessors will appreciate the convenience and functionality of the tool, so will be willing to learn how to use it. Furthermore, measures will be taken to secure the database and its associated application to prevent data loss or data integrity issues. The system features will be implemented using MoSCoW prioritisation and a sprint-based approach, ensuring all key features are contained within the application.

It may be concluded that the project provides numerous benefits, and with the outlined risk mitigation, it is advisable that the project be developed in its proposed form, without changes being required to the underlying concept. It must be noted that, due to the methodology used, based on DSDM and Scrum, the requirements will evolve and change, meaning the final developed system may be different to that which was proposed, due to changing client requirements.

3.3.3 Weakness and Threat Mitigation

Based on the identified weaknesses and threats from the SWOT matrix, weakness and threat mitigation was employed, to better understand methods to reduce or prevent these risks or minimise their impact.

The risk's likelihood was detailed, alongside its potential impact on the project, mitigation methods to prevent or reduce the risk, and a contingency plan, in the case of issues with the risk mitigation method. These will be used to steer the project around any issues faced, ensuring the project remains successful and achieves its aims.

The plan will be used to continue to monitor risks classified with a high likelihood of occurring, to ensure preventative action or mitigation is enacted as soon as the risk is detected, further ensuring the risk will not disrupt the project's success.

A comprehensive risk management mitigation strategy is contained within Appendix C.

ID	Risk Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation	Contingency
R1	Assessment leaders may not wish to adopt the tool	Low	Low	Explain strengths and benefits of tool	Offer to demonstrate tool in-person
R2	Stored assessment data may become corrupted	Low	High	Ensure database is backed up regularly to an external location to be restored in the event of corruption of data	Ensure assessment leaders export all important assessment data frequently

Figure 3.3 Weakness and Threat Mitigation Methods

3.4 User Analysis

User analysis was conducted to provide a reference to the types of user who would be expected to use the system to achieve their goals. To fully understand the system's users, user personas were produced, detailing the user's profile, goals and current frustrations. The creation of user personas aided in extracting the user stories for each user type, extracting their goals to form the appropriate user story. User stories were created to define the high-level tasks that users expect to be able to perform on the system. The creation of user stories formed the basis of extracting and producing functional requirements, which define the required functionality to be implemented in the system.

3.4.1 User Personas

Through creating user personas for the identified user types, the users could be represented from a personal level, rather than being seen as independent to the system (Miaskiewicz and Kozar, 2011). Furthermore, developing an understanding of their goals and frustration, as well as a relatable backstory, assists in ensuring that the implemented features would assist them in achieving their goals (Junior and Filgueiras, 2005).

Two user personas were created for each user type, to ensure that each user type would be suitably represented, and features would be more generic to the user type, rather than crafted towards the specific user persona representing the user type.

A comprehensive set of user personas are contained within Appendix D.

Figure 3.4 User Persona for Student User Type

Figure 3.5 User Persona for Assessment Leader User Type

Figure 3.6 User Persona for Assessor User Type

3.4.2 User Stories

User stories were produced based on the identified user personas and their goals. These capture the fundamental goals and aims each user type expects the system to fulfil, ensuring an understanding of the system functionality is gathered from an early stage (Lucassen *et al.*, 2016). Each user story outlines the user type who expects to achieve the aim, aiding in the creation of a use case diagram and use case descriptions, and in defining system permissions for different users (Lucassen *et al.*, 2016).

The use of additional contextual information about why the functionality is required aims to provide additional backstory behind the feature. This assists in extracting further requirements based on other aspects of the user story, whilst simplifying the process of MoSCoW prioritisation of the requirements, as important features must be implemented first (Abrahamsson *et al.*, 2011).

A comprehensive set of user stories are contained within Appendix E.

Students:

- “As a student, I want to view my upcoming assessments, so I can prepare for them in order to get a good grade.”
- “As a student, I want to view my past assessment feedback, so I can understand my strengths and weaknesses and rectify these in the future.”
- “As a student, I want to see my assessment setter’s profile, so I can contact them if I have any concerns regarding the feedback I have received.”

Assessment Leaders:

- “As an assessment leader, I want to create a new assessment event, so I can easily disseminate assessment information to students and assessors.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view assessment groups of students, so I can view students who worked together on a project.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to edit assessment panels for an assessment, so I can change which assessors will work together to produce feedback in an assessment event.”

Assessors:

- “As an assessor, I want to create assessment feedback for the groups I am required to assess, so I can report my feedback and grades to students.”
- “As an assessor, I want to edit the assessment feedback I have provided, so I can rectify any errors I have made in assessment feedback and grades.”
- “As an assessor, I want to view the profiles of my co-assessors, so I can obtain a better understanding of the colleagues I am working with.”

3.5 Use Case Analysis

Use case analysis was conducted to fully discover the user requirements of the system, and potential workflows or alternative flows, to assist the user in achieving their goal. To perform use case analysis, identification of the system actors, and their appropriate user types and roles within the system was required. Based on the understanding of the identified user types and their associated high-level goals, these goals could be refined and examined in more detail, through the creation of use case textual descriptions.

3.5.1 System Actors

Identification of the core system actors involved analysing the user personas and stakeholders, being determining the different types of users, based on the core goals they wished to achieve, and actions undertaken to accomplish these. It was identified that there were three main collections of goals and accompanying functionality – students, assessment leaders and assessors.

Assessment leaders incorporated course leaders, module leaders and assessment leaders, as all users required full functionality within the system. Assessors were formed of lecturers and external assessors, as both users were accomplishing the task of providing assessment feedback.

Through grouping system actors based on their goals, this assisted in better defining the user roles and aiding to produce a core set of functionality within each role, which helped to produce the functional requirements, and give appropriate system access based on user type permissions.

Identified User Types:

- Students
- Assessment Leaders
- Assessors

User Roles:

Students:

Students must be able to view their current and upcoming assessment event schedule, and feedback and grades for their completed (past) assessments.

Assessment Leaders:

Assessment leaders must be able to add assessment events, pre-configure an assessment rubric, build student groups, create assessment panels, and assign panels to assess groups. After assessment events have occurred, assessment leaders must be able to view and publish student assessment feedback and grades.

Assessors:

Assessors must be able to view their current and upcoming assessment event schedule, record assessment feedback and grades for students partaking in an assessment event, and view the feedback comments entered by their co-assessors in real-time.

3.5.2 Use Case Diagram

The use case diagrams for each user were produced based on the user stories and system actors identified. These diagrams provided a graphical overview as to the core functionality expected by each user type, making it easier to view the overall high-level requirements to be implemented for each group (Shen and Liu, 2003).

Through viewing all high-level requirements graphically, similar requirements across different user types could be more easily identified (Shen and Liu, 2003), such as all user types being required to view assessments, therefore aiding in the identification of the core functional requirements and prioritisation of requirements. Requirements shared by all user types were more likely to be implemented first, due to being important to all users.

Student:

Figure 3.7 Use Case Diagram for Student User Type

Assessment Leader:

Figure 3.8 Use Case Diagram for Assessment Leader User Type

Assessor:

Figure 3.9 Use Case Diagram for Assessor User Type

3.5.3 Use Case Textual Descriptions

Use case textual descriptions offer a valuable insight into the potential workflow of an implementation of the identified use case from the use case diagram (Geppert and Schmid, 2002). The use case diagram offered an excellent high-level view of each requirement to be implemented, whilst the creation of use case textual descriptions for each use case identified, provided a deeper understanding of the purpose and goal of the use case, and its possible actors. Use case textual descriptions were produced for all use cases.

Through outlining the pre-conditions and post-conditions, the user stories could be better contextualised within the system, and user story to implement during each sprint could be identified based on the required pre-conditions, such as implementing the 'Create Assessments' requirement only after the system contains modules, otherwise this functionality would be unable to be implemented.

The basic path and alternative path of each use case textual description provided a high-level view of how the system should be implemented, and the desired functionality the user expects, especially in the case of exceptional data or flows.

The success and failure conditions were useful in providing a key insight into the expected outcome of each user case, providing an idea of what the successful implementation should accomplish. The performance criteria assisted with defining the non-functional requirements of the system, whilst the priority of each use case aided in the MoSCoW prioritisation of the requirements.

A comprehensive set of use case textual descriptions are contained within Appendix F.

Use Case Number:	2
Name:	View Assessment Feedback
Description:	The assessment feedback information from a past assessment is displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes assessment grade, mark breakdown and feedback comments.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to view an assessment's grade and feedback
Frequency:	Varied depending on assessment schedule; typically once per week
Pre-Conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User is logged in • User is a member of a module • Module contains assessments • Assessment has been completed • Assessment has been graded and had feedback published
Post-Conditions:	A user's assessment feedback is displayed on-screen to the user
Basic Path:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to the website's homepage 2. Click on a past (completed) assessment 3. User's assessment feedback and grade is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3a. If no assessments are available, appropriate message is displayed 3b. If assessment feedback is unpublished, 'unpublished' is displayed
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	User's assessment feedback is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to view their assessment feedback on-screen
Performance:	Assessment feedback should be displayed within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Table 3.10 Use Case Textual Description for View Assessment Feedback User Story

Use Case Number:	7
Name:	Create Group Profile
Description:	The group should be able to add relevant, descriptive information about themselves to their group profile. Information includes a customised profile picture and brief description about the group values and background.
Actor(s):	Student
Triggers:	Requirement to inform others of their values and background
Frequency:	Once per group
Pre-Conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User is logged in • User is a member of the associated group • Group has not previously created a profile
Post-Conditions:	The group's profile information is associated with their group and displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to the website's homepage 2. Click on 'assessments' 3. Click on 'group' tab 4. Click on 'profile' tab 5. Input group profile information 6. Click 'Save' button 7. Created group profile information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	7a. If group profile has already been created, do not create a second profile
Extensions:	When a group profile has been created, all group members are alerted, informing them of this.
Success End Condition:	Inputted group profile information is associated with group and displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to save group profile information
Performance:	Group profile information should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Table 3.11 Use Case Textual Description for Create Group Profile User Story

Use Case Number:	9
Name:	Create Assessment Group
Description:	The user should be able to create a new assessment group containing an appropriate number of users of type 'Student', associated with an assessment event. The assessment group should contain a name, for identification purposes.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to create a new group to assess students who have worked in teams
Frequency:	Varies; typically eighty times per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User is logged in • User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' • Assessment event has already been created • Group member accounts have already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment group information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to the website's homepage 2. Click on an existing assessment 3. Click 'Add Group' button 4. Input group name 5. Select group member accounts 6. Click 'Save' button 7. Created assessment group information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	7a. If assessment group cannot be created, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Inputted assessment group information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to create a new assessment group
Performance:	Assessment group information should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Table 3.12 Use Case Textual Description for Create Assessment Group User Story

3.6 System Requirements

An unordered list of system requirements was produced based on the use cases and flows identified in the use case textual descriptions. System requirements are integral to the system's design and development, ensuring it is fit for purpose and allows users to achieve their goals (Bijan *et al.*, 2013). Whilst the user stories outline the user-level goals, the use case textual descriptions seek to mediate between user-level goals and system-level functionality, which must be translated into full system requirements (Bijan *et al.*, 2013).

Both functional and non-functional requirements are key to understanding the system's functionality, and any constraints or aspects which define its use or implementation. The system requirements formed the basis of the design of the both the backend and system workflows, to allow users to achieve their goals.

3.6.1 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements define the functionality the system is required to be capable of providing to users, to ensure they can achieve their goals (Malan *et al.*, no date). These requirements are crucial to the system's design, as they contain the necessary or desired functions users expect the system to provide (Malan *et al.*, no date). The list of functional requirements was produced based on the workflows created in the use case textual descriptions, and the user stories.

Each functional requirement is accompanied by an owner, who is the identified owner based on the use case textual description. Some requirements may be expected to be implemented by all users, therefore 'All Users' are the owner of the functional requirement. The list of functional requirements must be used to ensure the system implements features required by the users.

A comprehensive list of functional requirements is contained within Appendix G.

ID	Functional Requirement Description	Owner
1	All users are able to view their enrolled assessments	All Users
17	Students are able to view their assessment panel	Students
24	Assessors are able to view their assessment panel's profile	Assessors
40	Assessment leaders are able to import assessment grades and feedback produced in other applications	Assessment Leaders

Table 3.13 Excerpt from System Functional Requirements

3.6.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements define the constraints on the produced system, including performance, compatibility and scalability (Malan *et al.*, no date). The list of non-functional requirements identified constraints from multiple categories, both affecting the user's experience of the system, and benefits to the development of the system, such as security and maintainability.

These non-functional requirements were produced based on the identified constraints in the use case textual descriptions, and considerations of the desired user experience. Non-functional requirements are critical to ensure the system provides accessibility to users, and offers a positive user experience, whilst meeting necessary legislation. These non-functional requirements form the basis of the security considerations and user interface design of the system.

A comprehensive list of non-functional requirements is contained within Appendix H.

ID	Category	Non-Functional Requirement Description
1	Performance	User interface must display requested page information within 5 seconds
3	Compatibility	System must run on all major desktop and mobile platforms, including a minimum of Windows 10, macOS 11 (Big Sur), Linux (kernel version 3.10), Android 10, and iOS 15
8	Scalability	System must support a minimum of 150 concurrent users
12	Reliability	Database must utilise transaction management to only permit successful transactions to enact persistent changes to the database
16	Maintainability	System components must have high cohesion, low coupling and be reusable, where possible, to support efficient upgradability
20	Security	System must only be accessible to users with valid login credentials, with a reliable authentication mechanism implemented in the frontend, backend, and database
27	Usability	User interface colour scheme be accessible to all users, including those with visual impairments, such as colour blindness
32	Localisation	System must abide by the appropriate legislation in the territory it is operating in, namely the Data Protection Act (2018) for use in the United Kingdom

Table 3.14 Excerpt from System Non-Functional Requirements

3.7 MoSCoW Prioritisation

MoSCoW prioritisation was used to prioritise the order in which the identified list of functional requirements should be implemented. MoSCoW uses a Must Have, Should Have, Could Have, and Won't Have structure. The Must Have requirements are critical to the success and functionality of the system, thus are implemented first, whilst the Won't Have requirements are desirable features, but are beyond the scope of the project and will not be implemented (Highsmith and Cockburn, 2001). To ensure project success, all Must Have requirements must be successfully implemented.

Due to the vast number of identified functional requirements, MoSCoW prioritisation was used to categorise these requirements and determine the order in which these requirements would be implemented, as it would not be possible to implement all identified requirements. Consequently, it is critical that the most important requirements are implemented, to ensure project success, users can achieve their goals and provide a minimum viable product. The list of prioritised requirements was used to ensure the development sprints focussed on the most important Must Have requirements first.

A comprehensive list of prioritised functional requirements is contained within Appendix I.

ID	Functional Requirement Description	Priority	Owner
1	All users must be able to view their enrolled assessments	MUST	All Users
3	Students must be able to view their past assessment grade and feedback	MUST	Students
8	Assessors must be able to assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	MUST	Assessors
22	Assessment leaders must be able to assign students to assessment groups	MUST	Assessment Leaders
61	Assessors should be able to edit their assessment panel's profile	SHOULD	Assessors
70	Assessment leaders should be able to re-assign assessors to assessment panels	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
88	All users could be able to search for a user	COULD	All Users
89	Assessors could be able to send assessment co-assessors direct messages	COULD	Assessors
93	Assessors won't be suggested feedback comments for an assessment based on AI predictions	WON'T	Assessors
94	Assessment leaders won't be able to export feedback and grades in an LMS-readable format	WON'T	Assessment Leaders

Table 3.15 Excerpt from MoSCoW Prioritisation for System Functional Requirements

3.8 Conclusion

This phase of the project sought to capture detailed and accurate information regarding both the potential stakeholders and users of the project, associated risks, and capture the user's requirements of the system. The stakeholder analysis assisted in ensuring the project's features would be prioritised based on the requirements of high power and high interest stakeholders, whilst threat mitigation through the SWOT analysis reduced the risks of project failure, through undertaking measures to reduce risk.

The user analysis formed the basis of identifying the user goals and desired functionality, from which system requirements features could be determined, to ensure the produced system meets user requirements. These requirements have been approved by the client and will be constantly evaluated and confirmed with the client, as the project is adopting a methodology based on DSDM and Scrum, therefore requirements may change during the project's lifecycle.

To ensure the project is on-track, client meetings will be critical, with less important requirements identified initially potentially not being implemented in favour of more crucial requirements elicited later in the project, based on both the development team and client having a stronger understanding of their requirements.

As the requirements analysis stage is arguably the most important aspect of the project, to ensure the developed system meets the client's requirements and is fit for purpose, the requirements will be constantly checked and confirmed with the client at the regular client meetings, to mitigate the risk of producing an unsuitable system.

4 Design

4.1 Introduction

The design chapter will focus on how the identified system requirements may be realised within a suitable system, highlighting the transformation stages performed to provide desired functionality within an application. It will first examine the heuristic design decisions undertaken, to ensure the system's user interface both invoked suitable emotive response from its users, and was accessible by all identified user groups.

The frontend user interface presentation will be discussed, highlighting the selected page layout and navigational workflows, to aid efficiency and usability when using the system. The identified user interface components will be examined, discussing their suitability in assisting users with accomplishing their user stories. The explanation on user interface code design provides an insight into the design decisions made to ensure the system provides reusability and maintainability.

The backend API endpoint syntax and request-response bodies offer insight into the system's alignment with industry best practices, whilst a discussion of validation and conformance rulesets examines how the system designs ensure data integrity is maintained, and facilitate compatibility with the frontend web application.

The data model will be examined, highlighting the initial entity relationship diagrams and assumptions, before focussing on the final data model design, exploring the modifications made to the original design as a result of refactoring, changes in requirements, and completion of further user stories within the performed sprints.

A discussion on the process modelling undertaken will examine the realisation of requirements into system workflows, enabling the frontend and backend to be suitably produced, based on the required navigational flow. The system architecture will be explored, assessing how architectural design patterns may be employed to further improve the maintainability and efficiency of the system.

As the project utilises an amalgamation of principles from both DSDM (also known as AgilePM) and Scrum, with frequent delivery and incremental development, the design of system workflows was conducted for each sprint upon its commencement. Following the sprint's process modelling phase, sketching and wireframing of the sprint's required frontend interfaces was performed, prior to the implementation of the frontend for the user story.

Upon completion of the frontend, the backend API syntax and data access SQL statement were designed, before the backend implementation was completed. As defined by the methodology, this process occurred iteratively, with designs being produced for the specified user story during each sprint, as opposed to using a Big Design Up Front (BDUF) approach, ensuring time was not wasted on designing features which would not be implemented.

4.2 User Interface Accessibility

Accessibility relates to ensuring users with disabilities or impairments, such as cognitive or physical, are able to use a system without boundaries, barriers or hindrance (Kulkarni, 2019). Websites must ensure adherence to accessibility guidelines to ensure the application is accessible by all, with accessibility standards being defined by international web standards (Kulkarni, 2019).

Accessibility is important to ensure inclusivity of the service, and is especially important in the context of this project, where with the vast numbers of expected users of system, it is likely that a number of students will require accessibility features, to improve their experience when using the system. It must be noted that website accessibility is mandatory within the United Kingdom, where websites must be suitably accessible, under the Equality Act (2010).

The importance of ensuring the user interface's accessibility was noted, with colours, icons and further design decisions being made, with both aesthetics and accessibility being considered.

4.2.1 Colours

The use of colour within the frontend was crucial to the design of the application. Colours have been shown to both impact user behaviour, and invoke emotions, therefore the use of colour and its impact must be considered whilst designing the user interface (Cyr, Head and Larios, 2010). The use of colour may also influence the accessibility of the website, with colour vision deficiency affecting some users' ability to differentiate between different colours.

Colours, especially those used for backgrounds and foreground text, must be readable by users with colour blindness. It was decided that the application's colour scheme would utilise a combination of blue and purple, for block background colour sections, and white, grey and black, for icons and text.

Blue was chosen, as it has been reported that it connotes calm and comfort, relaxing the user and providing them with a positive experience whilst using the application (Cyr, Head and Larios, 2010). A calm emotion is especially desirable within the context of an assessment feedback application, where student users may be anxious or disappointed in achieving a poor grade, and assessment leaders may become stressed over high assessment workloads. The blue colour scheme seeks to relax the user, providing them with a more positive user experience.

The use of purple invokes a feeling of luxury within the user interface, making it appear to be of high-quality (Cyr, Head and Larios, 2010). Blue and purple are analogous colours, making them look visually appealing when used together. When used together for differing sections of the application, it was noted that colourblind users were able to distinguish between the differing hues of purple and blue, regardless of their vision deficiency, ensuring the application was accessible by all users.

White, grey and black colours were used for text and icons, as appropriate, to offer significant contrast between the block section background colours and foreground objects. These ensure users with visual impairments are still able to view all components within the application. Red is used to emphasise error message text, to better convey issues to the user, and offer significant contrast to highlight them on the page. Gold is used to highlight key elements, such as a favourite item star on the homepage, to employ contrast and better focus the user's attention on these items.

4.2.2 Icons

Icons may be used to produce a visually appealing user interface, providing benefits including fast recognition and familiarity (Nielsen, 2005). As application users will likely be offered limited training and will often have significant breaks between application uses, due to the structure of assessment and the academic year, it is critical that the system offers fast recognition of core functionality.

Recognition is employed through the use of clear, consistent icons, which map to real-world objects and match conventions typically used by most websites or software applications (Nielsen, 2005). Such examples include the use of a trash can to provide the 'delete' function, plus symbol to offer 'add new' functionality, and pen icon to 'edit' items. These icons were chosen to provide a simple, consistent user interface, ensuring suitability for all user types.

The use of standard icons also ensures the system may be more easily used by users with English as a second language (ESL). These users may struggle with understanding verbose textual phrases associated with buttons or functions, or may take longer to understand the functionality of a button, meaning their user experience will be negatively impacted. Through using common, internationally recognised and language-independent icons, they may perform their desired user stories with minimal hindrance or delay, improving the system's usability.

4.2.3 Font

The font used can significantly impact the readability of text contained within the application, both increasing the difficulty of reading textual content for dyslexic users, and causing visually impaired readers to struggle to view the page content (Rello and Baeza-Yates, 2013). Font style, size and weighting must be strongly considered to ensure the website is readable by all users.

It is often more difficult for users to view serif fonts, therefore sans-serif fonts were selected throughout, to prevent the typeface from becoming a barrier to the use of the application (Rello and Baeza-Yates, 2013). All text uses a minimum of 12pt font size, ensuring all text may be readable by all users, through aiding with distinguishing letters for users with visual impairment or dyslexia. Bold text is used sparingly and only where the font size is suitably large enough to ensure the content is readable by all users, such as with large headings.

It should also be noted that it is often more difficult to read black text displayed with a white background, as the bright background can make the text appear hazy for readers with visual impairments (Ko, 2017). Consequently, a light grey background was chosen for the main content section of the webpage, softening the colour range, and negating the issues of blurred text for particular users.

4.2.4 Page Navigation

Users with reduced mobility or difficulty in interacting with computers through traditional keyboard and mouse devices often utilise alternative keyboards, trackballs, speech recognition, or may interact with the computer through solely the 'Tab' key within their keyboard. As such, it is important to consider alternative website interaction methods, to ensure the website may be successfully used by all user types without hindrance, to accomplish their goals (Kulkarni, 2019).

To ensure the pages may be successfully navigated, the design used as few button components as possible, to prevent users from being required to struggle to navigate to the appropriate button, if they are solely using a keyboard. All buttons were produced with an appropriate size, and thus selectable area, with adequate spacing surrounding buttons. This ensures users with reduced mobility would not accidentally click the wrong button, or struggle to click in the selectable area of the button, improving accessibility for all user types.

4.2.5 Neurodiversity

Neurodiversity relates to the notion that different conditions and people who think in different ways should be perceived as being standard human variation, including autism (Ortega, 2009). Often, users with autism benefit from a user experience with clear, concise and unambiguous language used throughout the system, informing them of their required user input or system output.

Necessary user textual input, such as form field input messages, must not be vague or unclear, as this can prevent neurodivergent users from understanding their required input, thus hindering their ability to use the system (Jang, 2021). The user interface must also be capable of highlighting key aspects within the page, without requiring the user to read significant amounts of text, otherwise users may miss key elements.

The created system designs utilise clear, concise and unambiguous form input fields and button names throughout, to better guide users through the journey of using the application. Within input forms, explanatory input field help messages are used to provide additional information to assist in informing neurodivergent users of their desired action and information to input into the relevant field. Unambiguous error messages are returned to the user and displayed in a clear format, to better meet the needs of neurodivergent users.

The natural hierarchy, and size and position of elements, such as headings, within the page conveys all key aspects, without requiring the user to read the contained text, thus ensuring all users may experience a clearer interaction with the user interface.

4.3 User Interface Presentation

The visual appearance and usability of both the webpage layout and contents, and navigation and workflow between pages within the website must be strongly considered, to ensure users are able to fully interact with the system to achieve their user goals (Bollini, 2017). The layout of page content both impacts the user's ability to view outputted data and perform system actions, whilst the workflow affects the efficiency with which user stories may be accomplished.

The page layout and navigability were heavily investigated, resulting in the creation of initial sketches, later being refined to produce more detailed medium fidelity wireframes. These serve to realise the captured user requirements, both to discuss and affirm with the client that the system produced will be fit for their identified needs and seek to inform the implementation of the system.

4.3.1 Responsive Design

It was initially expected that frontend user interface designs would be produced and subsequently implemented for both mobile, tablet and laptop and desktop devices. Due to time constraints, it was decided that there would likely not be sufficient time to design and implement user interfaces for all device types. Consequently, the client and appropriate stakeholders were surveyed to obtain the type of machine they typically access University-related materials using.

Through questioning users of all user types, it was discovered that assessors and assessment leaders rarely use mobile devices, and seldom for University-related work, instead using a University-provided desktop PC or laptop for managing their work. Although students frequently use mobile devices, they rarely use them for University work, such as checking Canvas, preferring to do so either by logging into a University lab PC or through their own desktop or laptop.

Consequently, it was decided that the project should focus on creating sketches and designs for a desktop and laptop user interface, as this is the device the vast majority of users would expect to access the website using. It was also identified that students prefer to use apps to access University-related work, such as Canvas, rather than websites through their mobile device's web browser.

As the designed user interface would be a website implemented using React, the further option for a React Native app to facilitate access to the service (Danielsson, no date) will be beyond the scope of this project. After creating a number of different screens for the laptop and desktop user interface, it was recognised that if mobile versions of these screens were to also be produced, there would likely be insufficient time to successfully implement both designs before the end of the project. As a result, the executive decision was opted to abolish plans for a mobile view, and only implement this if there was still time at the end of the project, after implementing and testing all other features.

4.3.2 Initial Sketches

Initial sketches offer a low detail, low fidelity overview as to the typical webpage layout and website structure, including the position of content blocks within the page, basic functionality within the webpage, and navigational flows between webpages (Newman and Landay, 2000). Sketches may be provided to the client, to establish whether the captured system requirements are fit for purpose, or if modification is required to either the initial designs or requirements.

Through visualising the requirements to the client, they are often more likely to be able to identify problems with the requirements, or update the prioritisation of requirements. These modifications may then be performed, with minimal invested time or effort being required to update the initial sketches, before producing the medium fidelity wireframes based on the agreed initial sketch user interface design (Newman and Landay, 2000).

Figure 4.1, displaying the initial sketch for the 'view assessment rubric' webpage, is one of a number of sketches produced to show the initial expected designs of the system's frontend interface. All initial sketches were presented to and discussed with the client, to validate whether the initial user interface designs were fit for purpose, navigable and easy to use. Based on the initial sketches, the client acknowledged that the screen designs were suitable, and that the requirements had been correctly captured and represented within the interface.

A comprehensive set of initial sketches are contained within Appendix J.

Figure 4.1 Initial Sketch for View Assessment Rubric Webpage

Within all initial screen designs, a page layout structure was employed, to ensure consistency across all pages. As is common with websites, a top-level navigation bar provides users with the ability to navigate between webpages, whilst the main content panel contains the appropriate page-specific information. A footer presents additional navigational links, unsuitable to be placed in the main navigation bar.

This standard approach ensures provides familiarity to users, ensuring they are more likely to be able to navigate throughout the site with little to no training. Across all assessment-specific pages, a secondary navigation bar provides users with a clear and consistent method to access assessment-specific pages, preventing user confusion with the primary navigation links.

4.3.3 Medium Fidelity Wireframes

Medium fidelity wireframes are visual representations of the user interface design, outlining the structure, visual hierarchy, and clear graphical elements within the webpages (Newman and Landay, 2000). After producing the initial screen design sketches for all user stories, the necessity to enhance the designs to produce more detailed and accurate representations of the interface was identified.

Medium fidelity wireframes provide further details into the appearance of on-screen elements, making them appear more closely aligned to the final implementation (Newman and Landay, 2000). This better conveys the design and style choices of the interface, ensuring the client can make a more informed decision as to whether the user interface design is fit for purpose, before proceeding with implementation. It also provides a clearer understanding and design, allowing the user interface implementation to be developed more easily, through following a more detailed plan.

It must be noted that although the wireframes appear to be of a high quality, they do not fully represent the final implementation, with placeholders being used for images and logos, and font and colour being independent of the final product.

Figure 4.2 shows the medium fidelity wireframe produced for the homepage. At the top of the page, it is expected that there would be a navigation bar, to allow the user to access the most frequently used pages. The top right user icon allows the user to login and manage their account. In the main content area, the user's enrolled assessments are displayed in a card view. At the top of the page, the user's favourite assessments are shown, denoted by a filled star icon within the card.

A subsequent list displays the user's upcoming assessments, whilst the final list contains their past assessments. A new assessment may be added via the appropriate button, whilst card functions offer favourite and delete functionality. The user interface cards provide an appropriate level of detail, whilst appearing aesthetically pleasing. To the bottom of the page, the footer contains navigational links to pages unsuitable to be contained within the navigation menu.

A comprehensive set of medium fidelity wireframes are contained within Appendix K.

Figure 4.2 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Homepage

Figure 4.3 shows the medium fidelity wireframe produced for the view assessment details page. In alignment with the homepage, a header and footer are provided, offering navigability. Within the content area, the selected assessment is displayed, alongside a secondary navigation menu to provide assessment-specific actions, navigating between displayed assessment pages. The assessment details are shown, with the assessment image increasing the aesthetics. The assessment feedback may be accessed via the appropriate button.

Figure 4.3 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Assessment Details Page

Figure 4.4 shows the medium fidelity wireframe produced for the edit group profile page. In alignment with the previous pages, a header and footer are provided. Within the content area, the edit group profile form is displayed, containing appropriate form input titles, help messages, input field, and error messages, where necessary.

At the bottom of the form, the cancel and save changes buttons provide the appropriate form functionality. Form input fields include single line text inputs, for group name and profile image URL, a multiline text input to enter the group’s biography, and a draggable component, to select group members. These provide the most efficient methods of data entry, with respect to the types of data requiring input into the form.

Figure 4.4 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Group Profile Page

4.3.4 Navigation

Navigation diagrams offer an insight into the hierarchal page structure of the website, and the available functionality within the application. The navigation diagram offers insights into the system workflows and user interactions between pages in the system, highlighting the directly accessible pages, and those which must be accessed via other pages (Fang and Holsapple, 2007). Through designing the page navigation structure, the appropriate navigation links can be implemented in the produced website, ensuring the system workflow is logical, and all produced pages are accessible via the root (homepage) by some means (Fang and Holsapple, 2007).

A comprehensive set of navigation diagrams for all user groups are contained within Appendix L.

Figure 4.5 displays the pages accessible by student and assessor user accounts. The system contains additional pages which are inaccessible to users with these levels of permissions, with navigation to these pages being disabled to these user groups.

Figure 4.5 Navigation Diagram for Student and Assessor

4.4 User Interface Components

User interface components are frontend React reusable webpage components, produced to provide users with a visual display output container or input element (Subramanian, 2019). Throughout the application, the same types of components are often required, to provide consistency across webpages, improving user interaction and aesthetics.

It was identified that a small set of components may be repurposed to provide desired functionality across all pages, independent of the type of data contained within the page. This facilitates maintainability, upgradability, and reduces development time, with components being able to be efficiently reused throughout the application after their initial creation.

4.4.1 Horizontal Cards

The user interface design utilises items presented in a list, with stretched horizontal card objects created for each item. A list view was chosen to best maximise the available width on a desktop screen, due to cards being able to fill the width with information. The use of traditional cards would require users to scroll further within the list, whilst the card size would mean they would display less information.

The traditional card layouts typically are more suited to viewing items on a mobile device, with less screen width and display space being more scarce, leading to less information being able to be displayed. To ensure the suitability of the design for the identified target laptop and desktop view, horizontal cards were selected.

Each card item contains a moderately-sized image, to allow the record to be more easily located, whilst increasing the aesthetics of the webpage, by preventing the page being overrun by pure text. Adjacent to the image, the item title and key information is displayed, allowing the user to quickly identify individual items within the list, without being required to click on the item itself.

Upon clicking on a card item, the appropriate item details page is displayed, whilst hovering the cursor over a card makes it hover, highlighting the currently selected card to the user. Card items also contain a range of action buttons, to perform functions such as editing or deleting the card item.

Horizontal cards are created with a focus on reusability, with the same card format being applied to lists containing items such as assessments, rubrics, students and groups. The card may be populated with the appropriate list data, allowing it to be displayed in a consistent format across the application, improving frontend aesthetics and usability. Furthermore, the creation of a reusable card aids in reducing development time, with the card being easily modified to accept different list data, rather than requiring new card items to be created each time.

Figure 4.6 demonstrates how horizontal cards may be populated to display student feedback for each rubric criteria, within a feedback report. In the feedback report cards, no images are present, due to them being unnecessary within a feedback report, with the text filling the content area of the card. The student’s mark for the rubric criteria is listed, alongside the delete button, to remove the feedback item from the report.

Figure 4.6 Horizontal Cards Displaying Student Feedback Items Within Student Feedback Report

Figure 4.7 demonstrates how horizontal cards may be populated to display the user’s list of enrolled assessments on the application’s homepage. In the assessment cards, images are displayed for each assessment, followed by the assessment title, assessment start and end date and time, module, and assessment leader. The favourites and delete buttons are present, to add the assessment to favourites, and thus display it at the top of the list within the homepage, and remove the assessment from the system.

Figure 4.7 Horizontal Cards Displaying Assessment Items on Homepage

4.4.2 Draggable Items

The user interface design utilises draggable items, with a searchable list of draggable items able to be dragged and dropped into a droppable panel to select items. A drag/drop component was chosen to better increase efficiency for selecting multiple items from a list, as the act of dragging items into a container is faster and more aesthetically pleasing, rather than using multiple dropdown lists. Dropdown lists would require users to select options manually, through an expanding number of dropdown form components, increasing time when selecting multiple options.

Each draggable component is formed of a draggable component, containing items that may be clicked, dragged and dropped into a droppable panel, which receives and handles identifying the dropped components. The draggable items may be searched using the associated search bar, increasing efficiency and assisting users with quickly locating items based on the search field. Selected items within the droppable panel may be removed via dragging the component back to the draggable panel, or clicking the delete icon adjacent to the item, for effective single-click removal of items.

Draggable components are created with a focus on reusability, with the same draggable and droppable panels and associated behaviour being applied to items such as groups, panels and feedback comments. The draggable component may be populated with the appropriate item data, allowing the draggable and droppable component to be displayed in a consistent format across the application, improving frontend aesthetics and usability. The creation of a reusable draggable component aids in reducing development time, with the drag/drop component being easily modified to accept different item data, rather than requiring new draggable components to be created each time.

Figure 4.8 demonstrates how draggable components may be utilised to select panel-group assignments. In this example, the draggable component is populated with group items, whilst the droppable component contains selected groups, with the appropriate heading, and designated timeslots.

Figure 4.8 Panel-Group Assignment Draggable Components

Figure 4.9 demonstrates how draggable components may be utilised to select assessors to add to a new assessment panel. In this example, the draggable component is populated with assessor items, whilst the droppable component contains selected assessors, with the appropriate heading, and designated panel leader, symbolised by the bold text and user icon adjacent to their name.

Figure 4.9 Panel Member Assignment Draggable Components

4.4.3 Reusability

During the design of the frontend user interface, reusable components were identified, with a view to producing a small collection of reusable components which may be repurposed and populated with different information, to reuse across pages containing different content. Through identifying and producing reusable components, these may be quickly and easily reused to display different information throughout the application, reducing development time and unnecessary duplicate code, improving maintainability (Subramanian, 2019).

Whilst reusable components offer benefit to the application's code, they also provide a more consistent user interface, as all implementations of the reusable component follow the same fundamental design and styling. This seeks to both improve the aesthetics of the website, with all pages appearing cohesive, whilst improving the usability of the website, as users may learn a single core set of functionalities within the application, which may be consistently applied to whichever page they interact with.

It was identified that the following minimum set of reusable components should be created, in order to achieve consistent user interaction across the application:

- Layout Container
- Dual-Panel Structural Container
- Section Container
- Tab Container
- Tab Item
- Horizontal Card Container
- Horizontal Card
- Form
- Form Item
- Select Input Form Input
- Text Input Form Item
- Multi-line Text Input Form Item
- Drag/Drop Input Container
- Draggable Input Form Item Container
- Draggable Input Form Item
- Droppable Input Form Item Container
- Button Container
- Button

The identified reusable components and associated component containers, used to position content and components within the screen, were sketched prior to implementation. This ensured the reusable component designs could be reviewed by the client, who appreciated the ability to provide consistency across the user interface, and provided a basic structure as to how reusable components may be implemented within the system.

Figure 4.10 shows that a form item reusable component may be created, containing a defined label, help message, child input component, and error message, where necessary. This may be repurposed to handle form inputs of any content and input component type.

A comprehensive set of reusable component and container sketches are contained within Appendix M.

Figure 4.10 Form Item Reusable Component Sketch

Figure 4.11 shows that a horizontal card reusable component may be created, containing an image, content and buttons, passable to the card as props. The horizontal card components may be nested within a reusable card container component, allowing the cards to be displayed within a list, whilst providing list button actions, such as the ability to add a new item to the list, and a counter displaying the number of returned records. This may be repurposed to handle data cards of any content and button types, and different item action buttons.

Figure 4.11 Horizontal Card with Card Container Reusable Component Sketch

Upon producing sketches for the identified reusable components and containers, two report data output pages and two form data input pages were sketched, demonstrating how the reusable components may be implemented within real pages of the application. This cemented that the produced components were successfully reusable, whilst providing a base understanding of the implementation of reusable components to take into the development of the frontend application.

As shown in Figure 4.12, a layout container reusable container may be created, to apply the header and footer to the page. A card container may be implemented, to display the list of horizontal card reusable components, display the number of returned records, and provide list controls, such as adding a new module or joining an existing module. Horizontal card components may be used to display module information, with buttons to favourite a module, or delete a module.

A comprehensive set of report and form implementations using the identified reusable components and containers are contained within Appendix M.

Modules Report :

Figure 4.12 Module Report Utilising Identified Reusable Components and Containers

As shown in Figure 4.13, a layout container reusable container may be created, to apply the header and footer to the page. A form component may be implemented, to contain the form item components and button actions. A section container component may be used to group form input components containing similar data input fields, with a form item component being used to facilitate the data input field and associated textual information. Form item components may be populated with the relevant form item input components, to allow users to input form data.

Module Form:

Figure 4.13 Module Form Utilising Identified Reusable Components and Containers

4.5 API Endpoints

Application programming interfaces (APIs) provide common rules to enable a client to request and access resources located on a server (Corradini *et al.*, 2022). This project utilises a separate frontend and backend architecture, with the backend API accepting HTTP requests to its defined URL endpoints, to request resource data. These requests typically occur from within the frontend application, with the application requiring returned data to populate the dynamic content within the webpage.

The backend API syntax design must be considered, to provide access to the required resource in a suitable manner, whilst the request and response bodies returned define the frontend data which may be displayed, and how new or existing records may be added or modified (Gräfe *et al.*, 2016). Data validation and conformance are crucial to facilitate data integrity of the contained database data, and provide communication with the frontend application. The backend API must be suitably designed, to ensure maintainability and reliability, whilst optimising performance to handle scalability and potential sizable request numbers.

4.5.1 Endpoint Syntax Design

Endpoint syntax is crucial to the successful identification of endpoints and their returned resources (Gräfe *et al.*, 2016). Should endpoints provide an unclear or incorrect resource identifier, this can significantly hinder the implementation of applications relying on calls to the API, due to potentially incorrect objects being returned. Consequently, endpoint syntax best practices were strongly considered when designing the endpoint URLs.

A comprehensive set of endpoint syntax designs are contained within Appendix N.

- `api/modules` – list all modules
- `api/modules/:mid` – return a module
- `api/users` – list all users
- `api/users/:uid` – return a user
- `api/users/:uid/modules` – list a user’s modules
- `api/modules/:mid/assessments` – list a module’s assessments
- `api/assessments/:aid/users` – list an assessment’s users
- `api/leader/:lid/assessments` – list an assessment leader’s assessments

Figure 4.14 Excerpt of Endpoint Syntax Designs

The endpoint syntax displayed in Figure 4.14 was chosen, due to this approach of expressing many to many relationships being favoured in industry. API endpoint best practice notes that endpoints should list collections, as opposed to the underlying SQL and joins used, therefore should list the main collection, followed by any sub-collections (Gräfe *et al.*, 2016). The chosen syntax fulfils this standard, listing the main collection, such as users, followed by the sub-collection, their modules.

These collections may become complex, such as listing the main collection of users, followed by the sub-collection of assessments, sub-subcollection of panels, sub-sub-subcollection of feedback and sub-sub-sub-subcollection of comments. In this case, to filter the search and return the requested resource, multiple ID values must be provided to the endpoint, to query the database and retrieve the specified resource. These are identified through the appropriate id, such as ‘uid’ or ‘aid’ in the above syntax.

Endpoints not offering an ID will return all appropriate records, whilst endpoints accepting an ID will only return records matching the provided ID. Should an endpoint specify an ID, providing the ID within the request is mandatory, otherwise the endpoint will return an error, as it cannot search for a matching record without a defined search value.

The industry-standard approach was taken, as it demonstrates a clear understanding of the agreed and common implementation of endpoint syntaxes in the context of the most widely used APIs. This syntax would theoretically allow the API endpoints to be distributed and used by additional frontends or API clients, produced by other developers. Different developers would be able to make API requests quickly and easily, as the syntax follows their existing knowledge, based on best practice.

4.5.2 Request/Response Bodies

API endpoints accept HTTP requests which, in the case of POST and PUT HTTP methods, to create new records and update existing records respectively, require the HTTP request body to be populated with the necessary record data. Upon processing the request, the endpoint will return a HTTP response, with a body containing the recovered record data. Returned data may use any supported format, although typically data is returned in a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format, due to its support across all programming languages (Sharieh and Ferworn, 2021).

The design of the API's request and response bodies was considered, to ensure the necessary data was received by the endpoint, and appropriate data was returned, maintaining data integrity and providing the frontend with the necessary data to display meaningful output. It was decided that the endpoints would return JSON formatted data, due to its popularity within industry.

Within the relational database, used to store data returned by the endpoints, data is normalised, with foreign keys being used to create relationships between relations, which store data on entities. Endpoints may either resolve these foreign key ID values, to return the associated data contained within the linked relation, as shown in Figure 4.15, or return the stored ID values contained within the database. There is no defined best practice regarding the level of which foreign keys should be resolved, therefore the API designer must define the degree of foreign key handling, to which data will be resolved.

A comprehensive set of initial request/response body objects are contained within Appendix O.

Initially, request and response body designs returned all data relating to the defined entity with each endpoint request, with foreign keys being fully resolved. In the case of the panel request/response body, panels are associated with assessments, modules, users (assessment leader) and a panelmembers association table.

Whilst resolving all foreign keys to obtain their referenced data allows the returned data to be suitably detailed, meaning only one request would be required to be sent to the API to populate an entire page's contents, this method has significant limitations.

As the database is handling a number of joins per request, which requires substantial database processing, the database's performance would be poor. Furthermore, the returned request would likely contain significant amounts of repeated data, and the majority of the returned data would typically be unused and not displayed within the frontend web application.

It is often desirable to balance the level of detail and resolution of foreign keys to return data from other relations with the sending of multiple requests to different endpoints to retrieve the same information, when required. Related data, or data frequently required to fulfil use cases, should be resolved as appropriate, to prevent multiple requests being sent to the server.

Multiple requests for related data would increase request traffic to the backend server, leading to performance degradation or downtime relating to load issues. Furthermore, multiple requests invoking request-response cycles for each request may cause the website to take longer to load on slower network connections.

```

Panel {
  "PanelID": "PanelID",
  "PanelName": "PanelName",
  "PanelImageURI": "PanelImageURI",
  "PanelBiography": "PanelBiography",
  "PanelAssessmentID": "PanelAssessmentID",
  "PanelAssessmentName": "PanelAssessmentName",
  "PanelAssessmentStartdate": "PanelAssessmentStartdate",
  "PanelAssessmentEnddate": "PanelAssessmentEnddate",
  "PanelAssessmentImageURI": "PanelAssessmentImageURI",
  "PanelAssessmentLeaderID": "PanelAssessmentLeaderID",
  "PanelAssessmentLeaderName": "PanelAssessmentLeaderName",
  "PanelAssessmentLeaderEmail": "PanelAssessmentLeaderEmail",
  "PanelAssessmentLeaderUserTypeID":
"PanelAssessmentLeaderUserTypeID",
  "PanelAssessmentModuleID": "PanelAssessmentModuleID",
  "PanelAssessmentModuleCode": "PanelAssessmentModuleCode",
  "PanelAssessmentModuleName": "PanelAssessmentModuleName",
  "PanelAssessmentCreatedDate": "PanelAssessmentCreatedDate",
  "PanelLeaderID": "PanelAssessmentLeaderID",
  "PanelLeaderName": "PanelLeaderName",
  "PanelLeaderEmail": "PanelLeaderEmail",
  "PanelLeaderUserTypeID": "PanelLeaderUserTypeID",
  "PanelMembers": [
    {
      "PanelMemberID": "PanelMemberID",
      "PanelMemberUserID": "PanelMemberUserID",
      "PanelMemberUserName": "PanelMemberUserName",
      "PanelMemberUserEmail": "PanelMemberUserEmail",
      "PanelMemberUserTypeID": "PanelMemberUserTypeID",
      "PanelMemberEnrolledDate": "PanelMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
  ],
  "PanelCreatedDate": "PanelCreatedDate"
}

```

Figure 4.15 Initial Panel Request/Response Body Design

It was therefore decided that common related data required to populate frontend content, would utilise foreign key resolution to return all appropriate data from the API, as shown in Figure 4.16. These include returning group members alongside requests for groups, and module and assessment leader information with assessment requests. Joining of tables to return repeated or infrequently used data alongside the request would not be implemented, as these are deemed unnecessary, and add additional load to both the database server, and increase response times, leading to increased page load times, and a worse user experience.

Unnecessary foreign key resolution includes returning rubric information alongside rubric comments, as this information would be repeated for each rubric comment, leading to vast amounts of redundant data, both unnecessarily increasing overhead on the database, and the response (body) size, increasing loading times. This data may be requested using a separate request to the appropriate endpoint, although it is unlikely to be required, as the necessary data may be passed to the desired React frontend page as a prop, with the page navigation.

A comprehensive set of final request/response body objects are contained within Appendix P.

```
Panel {
  "PanelID": "PanelID",
  "PanelName": "PanelName",
  "PanelImageURI": "PanelImageURI",
  "PanelBiography": "PanelBiography",
  "PanelAssessmentID": "PanelAssessmentID",
  "PanelLeaderID": "PanelAssessmentLeaderID",
  "PanelLeaderName": "PanelLeaderName",
  "PanelLeaderEmail": "PanelLeaderEmail",
  "PanelLeaderUserTypeID": "PanelLeaderUserTypeID",
  "PanelMembers": [
    {
      "PanelMemberID": "PanelMemberID",
      "PanelMemberUserID": "PanelMemberUserID",
      "PanelMemberUserName": "PanelMemberUserName",
      "PanelMemberUserEmail": "PanelMemberUserEmail",
      "PanelMemberUserTypeID": "PanelMemberUserTypeID",
      "PanelMemberEnrolledDate": "PanelMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
  ],
  "PanelCreatedDate": "PanelCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure 4.16 Final Panel Request/Response Body Design

Based on these endpoint data design decisions, the request and response body designs were modified to use the minimum number of table joins, increasing performance and reducing overhead on the database.

4.5.3 Sorting, Pagination and Conditional Searching

In future user stories, sorting data to display within the frontend may become necessary. Use cases such as viewing specific assessments, modules, students or feedback would be benefitted through having a form of sorting, pagination or conditional support. Often, assessment leaders may wish to sort assessments by date order, either ascending or descending, based on their personal preferences, or to more easily locate an assessment.

Pagination would provide an enhanced user experience, preventing the webpage from becoming very long, reducing navigability and increasing difficulty in locating data. Through dividing data amongst smaller pages of results, data would become easier to locate, and there would be a reduced page load time for users, preventing vast numbers of returned results from being requested and displayed. Users may desire a filter pane, to assist in locating records matching a specified criteria.

Such features may be handled through frontend manipulation of the returned JSON response data, implemented by JavaScript functions to sort the returned objects, divide them into separate arrays of a set number of objects to display on each page, or search through the returned array for matching records.

Alternatively, the produced API endpoints may offer sorting, pagination and conditional search support from within the endpoint syntax request. This would provide benefits such as offering this functionality to all implemented frontends, rather than requiring each developed frontend to implement their own version of these features.

Through paginating or conditionally searching data on the backend, this would prevent sending vast quantities of data to the client, as only the required data to fulfil the request would be sent. Data may be divided amongst multiple requests, as necessary, such as if the user wishes to view the next page of data. Additionally, rather than requiring client processing, which may cause the client's browser to slow down on older or lower-powered devices, server-side processing would prevent this issue.

Based on the benefits offered by supporting sorting, pagination and conditional searching on the backend, this would be the recommended component to implement these functionalities. It would be advantageous to include these features within all GET requests returning multiple records, such as assessments, modules, students or assessors. By supporting all these forms of GET requests, the API endpoints would provide standardisation and consistency, whilst offering support for handling of vast amounts of returned data. Sorting, pagination and conditional searching is not required for POST, PUT, DELETE or GET methods returning a single record, based on the provided ID.

The endpoint syntax would provide support for sorting, pagination and conditional searching simultaneously, or as required, through chaining of function commands, using the '&' keyword. Examples of handling sorting, pagination and conditional searching, and combinations thereof, are shown in Figure 17.

The proposed sorting, pagination and conditional searching endpoint syntax would allow sorting, pagination and conditional searching conditions to be appended to request URLs in any order, via appending an '&' keyword with the the appropriate criterion.

A ? follows the endpoint URL, indicating these are additional parameters appended to the URL for the purposes of manipulating the data returned. The sort_by keyword defines the attribute to sort by, either ascending or descending.

The page keyword denotes the page to be returned, whilst the items keyword denotes how many items to return, and one less than the index number associated with the first returned item. This was chosen to abstract the data storage implementation from the API endpoint, both increasing security, and ensuring the low coupling of the backend and database implementation. Consequently, if the database was migrated to a NoSQL database, the pagination would not be SQL-specific, increasing the maintainability and upgradability of the system.

Conditional searching criteria may be appended as many times as necessary, based on the selected filtering criteria used, with the filtering keyword and its associated value being attached. These functions support a relatively simple implementation, whilst providing a user-friendly and human-readable syntax.

Sorting:

- /api/modules?sort_by=module_code_asc
- /api/assessments?sort_by=start_date_desc

Pagination:

- /api/modules?page=1&items=50
- /api/assessments?page=2&items=25

Conditional Searching:

- /api/modules?role=module_leader
- /api/assessments?start_date>09_01_2023&end_date<31_02_2023

Sorting and Pagination:

- /api/modules?page=1&items=50&sort_by=module_code_asc
- /api/assessments?page=2&items=25&sort_by=start_date_desc

Sorting and Conditional Searching:

- /api/modules?sort_by=module_code_asc&role=module_leader
- /api/assessments?sort_by=start_date_desc&start_date>09_01_2023&end_date<31_02_2023

Pagination and Conditional Searching:

- /api/modules?page=1&items=50&role=module_leader
- /api/assessments?page=2&items=25&start_date>09_01_2023&end_date<31_02_2023

Sorting, Pagination and Conditional Searching:

- /api/modules?page=1&items=50& sort_by=module_code_asc&role=module_leader
- /api/assessments?page=2&items=25&sort_by=start_date_desc&start_date>09_01_2023&end_date<31_02_2023

Figure 4.17 Endpoint Sorting, Pagination and Conditional Searching Design

4.6 Data Modelling

Data modelling is the process of representing an underlying data structure, mapped from a set of defined requirements (Shipman, 1981). Data models are crucial to designing the fundamental structure of the data storage system. In the case of a relational database being used to store data, the data model must show the entities and their relationships, to establish how the data structure will be implemented (Shipman, 1981).

The process of data modelling must be undertaken with care, as incorrect or inefficient data models can lead to inconsistent data storage or significant performance overheads on the database. To ensure the data model was fit for purpose, and negate potential storage issues, an initial data model was produced, which was expanded and refactored, to create a fully suitable design. A data dictionary was produced to ensure the database stored data of the appropriate data type, and impose necessary constraints on attribute values, facilitating data integrity.

4.6.1 Entity Relationship Diagrams

Entity relationship diagrams (ERD) are used to graphically represent relationships between different entities, typically within a relational database (Li and Chen, 2009). ERDs provide a visual model of the required entities, and their attributes and relationships (Li and Chen, 2009). Through defining the associations and corresponding primary and foreign keys, the underlying data model may be designed, prior to implementation.

During the first sprint, an initial entity relationship diagram was produced to model the necessary user story implemented during that sprint, shown in Figure 4.18. This included users, user types, modules, assessments and their required association tables, to resolve the identified many to many relationships. This basic data model contained the necessary relations to facilitate the database implementation for the first sprint’s user stories.

It was decided that all table names would be plural, and would each have a unique ID to identify records. Composite primary keys were considered, although to ensure all data records would be unique, and prevent data loss should users be unenrolled and later re-enrolled, such as in a group or assessment, unique ID values were assigned to each record. All attribute names begin with their corresponding relation’s singular name, followed by the name of the data they contain.

With the exception of ID values, after the first word relating to the name of the data the attribute contains, all further words in the attribute names are lowercase. This naming convention was applied both to facilitate best practice, and ensure consistency across all tables in the database, aiding with referencing relations and attributes within the produced SQL commands.

A comprehensive set of entity relationship diagrams for all user stories are contained within Appendix Q.

Figure 4.18 Entity Relationship Diagram for Sprint 1 - “As a project assessor, I would like to see the assessments I need to mark”

Within each subsequent sprint, the data model was reviewed and updated, as necessary, to support the data required to be stored by the sprint’s user story, shown in Figure 4.19. Upon reviewing the data model, should new entities and accompanying relationships be required, these were included on the revised entity relational model for that sprint. The data model produced for the fourth sprint’s user story contains only the necessary entities required to fulfil the task of adding a new panel, from the perspective of an assessment leader user type.

Figure 4.19 Entity Relationship Diagram for Sprint 4 - “As an assessment leader, I would like to add a new panel”

After the completion of all sprints, with the relevant user stories being supported within the data model, the entity relationship diagram was updated to display the final structure of the database, shown in Figure 4.20. This entity relationship diagram reflects the final implementation of the database, and is normalised to 3NF to ensure there are no transitive dependencies. These can cause update anomalies, with a lack in referential integrity and duplicated data.

Figure 4.20 Final Entity Relationship Diagram for Implemented Database

4.6.2 Data Dictionaries

Data dictionaries are used to define the relations, their attributes, and the relationships between relations, which are required to be implemented in the database (IBM, 1993). The data dictionary also serves to record the data types used for each attribute, and constraints on the inputted data, such as preventing NULL values from being stored in an attribute, or providing a default value, should a value not be provided for an attribute.

Data dictionaries form an important resource when implementing the database, as they may be directly translated into SQL, to build the database relations. Furthermore, after database creation, they serve as a useful document to the internal structure of relations, assisting with defining data validation rulesets in the frontend and backend, to ensure data sent to the database will meet the attribute's expected format.

During the first sprint, an initial data dictionary was produced, based on the created entity relationship diagram, to model the user stories implemented, as shown in Figure 4.21. It was decided that This included users, user types, modules, assessments and their required association tables, to resolve the identified many to many relationships. This basic data model contained the necessary relations to facilitate the database implementation for the first sprint's user stories.

It was decided that all ID values for relations would use a maximum length of 5 numbers, leading to a theoretical maximum ID value of 99999, providing significant scope for futureproofing the system with large numbers of records over time. Should this need to be increased to handle more records in the future, it may be incremented to accept 6 numbers, although it is not expected that this would be necessary, due to the typical usage of the system.

The data dictionary utilises an INT data type for numerical values, a VARCHAR data type for textual data, and DATETIME data type to store date and time values, as these are the valid SQL data types available in MySQL. The length of the attribute was chosen to accept a theoretical maximum number of characters for the type of data stored, with additional length added for storing values for exceptional cases.

Database constraints were applied where necessary, although were often used sparingly, so as not to increase the performance overhead of validating data input on the database, as the only approved client to connect to the database is the backend API, which provides its own validation rulesets before transmitting data to the database.

NOT NULL constraints were used in exceptional cases, to ensure data integrity, should the backend API validation checks fail, whilst UNIQUE constraints were used to prevent duplicate data, as checking unique values on the backend would require a further call to be made to the database, to retrieve all records, followed by checking if the inputted data was contained within the returned data, leading to a significant overhead.

DEFAULT values were provided for fields which would otherwise hinder the user experience, such as inputting a new item without an image, meaning the frontend would have no image to render, thus negatively impacting aesthetics.

A comprehensive set of data dictionaries for all user stories are contained within Appendix R.

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Modules	ModuleID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	ModuleCode	VARCHAR	6	UNIQUE
	ModuleName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL DEFAULT (https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	ModuleImageURI	VARCHAR	500	
	ModuleLevel	INT	1	NOT NULL
	ModuleDescription	VARCHAR	500	
	ModuleLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Assessments	AssessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentName	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	AssessmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT (https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	AssessmentLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
AssessmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())	

Figure 4.21 Excerpt from Sprint 1 Data Dictionary - “As a project assessor, I would like to see the assessments I need to mark”

After the completion of all sprints, with the relevant user stories being supported within the data model, and the appropriate entity relationship diagram being completed, the data dictionary was updated to model the structure of the database. Figure 4.22 reflects the final implementation of the database, with suitable data types and constraints.

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Assessment rubric comments	AssessmentrubriccommentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentrubriccommentComment	VARCHAR	500	
	Assessmentrubriccomment			
	AssessmentrubricID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentrubriccommentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Assessment feedback item comments	AssessmentfeedbackitemcommentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackitemcommentAssessment			
	rubriccommentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackitemcommentAssessment			
	feedbackitemID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY

Figure 4.22 Excerpt from Final Data Dictionary for Implemented Database

4.7 Process Modelling

Process modelling is a method of establishing system workflows involved in the accomplishment of particular tasks (Aguilar-Savén, 2004). Each task, represented by a user story, has a defined workflow, or series of steps, required to complete the task. These steps may be modelled via Unified Modelling Language (UML) diagrams, including activity and sequence diagrams (Medvidovic *et al.*, 2002)m.

It is important to be fully aware of the workflow of each user story, in order to ensure all steps are appropriately handled and followed in the defined order within the developed system. Through conducting process modelling, the system can be validated, to ensure all stages with each task are completed, with appropriate frontend, page navigation, backend and data model supporting the task achievement. As part of the system process modelling, UML activity and sequence diagrams were produced.

4.7.1 Activity Diagrams

Activity diagrams are used to graphically display a series of actions taken to perform a task (Medvidovic *et al.*, 2002). They allow the system behaviour and workflows to be displayed in a readable format, which may be communicated to the client, to ensure the system requirements have been correctly understood (Medvidovic *et al.*, 2002). Through creating activity diagrams, the system workflow may be conceptualised, allowing the appropriate user interface webpages, backend API endpoints and data model to be designed based on the stages required to accomplish the task identified within the diagram.

Activity diagrams were produced for all user stories undertaken during each sprint, upon sprint commencement. These activity diagrams were verified by the client, before forming the basis of the produced frontend, backend and data model designs for that sprint. To allow the activity diagram to focus on the critical aspect of user story functionality, the activity diagrams make prior assumptions, such as that the user is logged in before proceeding to accomplish the user story. Prior assumptions are contained within the rectangular note connected to the starting circle via the dotted line. The direction of flow of steps is displayed via the directional arrows connecting the steps together.

Figure 4.23 outlines the workflow for editing an assessment rubric. It assumes that the assessment leader is already registered and logged into the application before completing the desired stages to edit the rubric. From the user being within the homepage, they must first select an assessment item to edit the rubric of. This will display the assessment item data, from which they can click on the 'Rubric' option in the secondary navigation bar.

The assessment rubric information will be displayed, from which the user must click the edit button next to their chosen rubric. The edit rubric form will be shown, prompting the user to enter the modified rubric information and click submit. The rubric information will be sent to the appropriate backend API endpoint, which will run the relevant SQL UPDATE command on the database. If this is successful, the rubric page will be updated with the changes made, while if an error has occurred, it will be displayed, prompting the user to retry the edit operation.

A comprehensive set of activity diagrams for all user stories are contained within Appendix S.

Figure 4.23 Activity Diagram for Edit Assessment Rubric Requirement

4.7.2 Sequence Diagrams

Sequence diagrams are used to graphically display the interaction between different actors or objects within a system, when performing a task (Nayak and Samanta, 2010). They allow the behaviour of the different (independent) components within the system to be modelled, showing how the components interact and communicate with each other to perform the desired result (Nayak and Samanta, 2010).

Through creating sequence diagrams, the system workflow and component interaction may be conceptualised, highlighting the required interactions between system elements, allowing the appropriate user interface webpages, backend API endpoints and data model to be designed based on the stages required to accomplish the task identified within the diagram.

Sequence diagrams were produced for all user stories with identified complex workflows, upon sprint commencement. These sequence diagrams formed the basis of the produced frontend, backend and data model designs for that sprint, including the stages of communication over time between these. To allow the sequence diagram to focus on the critical aspect of user story functionality, the sequence diagrams make prior assumptions, such as that the user navigates to the URL of the frontend webpage for the specific task they wish to complete, before proceeding to accomplish the user story.

The direction of flow of steps is displayed via the directional arrows connecting the steps together, with solid arrow lines representing call messages, and dotted arrow lines indicating return messages. Lifelines are displayed by vertical dotted lines, whilst activations are symbolised by rectangular time periods of operation on the lifeline.

Figure 4.24 outlines the workflow for creating an assessment rubric. It assumes that the assessment leader navigates to the edit assessment frontend web application URL. The user enters the URL within their web browser, with the browser requesting the webpage from the frontend web server, which subsequently returns it to the web browser, to be rendered and displayed on-screen.

The user inputs their rubric details in the web browser and submits the form, which the browser sends to the backend API web server. The backend server communicates with the database to store the inputted data, with the database saving the data and returning the save status. The save status is sent to the web browser from the backend API, with the frontend web application being re-rendered in the browser to display the new assessment rubric list to the user. Alternatively, if the save was unsuccessful, the resulting error message is displayed.

A comprehensive set of sequence diagrams for all complex user stories are contained within Appendix T.

Figure 4.24 Sequence Diagram for Edit Assessment Rubric Requirement

4.8 Conclusion

This phase of the project sought to translate the captured requirements into a graphical user interface and backend code design, which will resemble the final implementation of the system. The accessibility of the user interface was extensively investigated, to ensure that the use of colour, icons and page design were suitable for all users, regardless of disability or impairments. The creation of initial sketches, wireframes and navigation design ensures the frontend user interface may be sufficiently tested against the user requirements, without investing significant time in development of a potentially unsuitable system.

The identification of reusable components ensures the developed system will both appear consistent, promoting a more positive user experience, whilst reducing time and duplicate code during the creation of the frontend. Through analysing the required endpoints and their data objects, a greater understanding of scalable and effective backend API design was achieved, ensuring the developed backend would offer efficiency and conform to industry best practices.

Through performing extensive data modelling and refinement of entity relationship diagrams and data dictionaries, an accurate and effective data storage design was achieved, preventing data redundancy, update anomalies and enhancing database performance. Process modelling, through the creation of activity and sequence diagrams, provided a graphical representation of the system workflows. This affirmed with the client that the requirements were suitably fulfilled, and offered a base level of understanding into the frontend webpages, backend API endpoints, database, and their interactions, required to be produced.

The design chapter is critical to the success of the implementation of the system, and thus the final product, with poor or lack of designs contributing to uncoordinated development, or the creation of a system which does not correctly provide the functionality identified in the captured requirements.

5 Implementation

5.1 Introduction

The implementation chapter will focus on how the produced system designs may be developed into a working application, focussing on each stage required during conversion of static designs, into a dynamic web-based tool. The chosen system architecture will be discussed, highlighting the necessity to utilise a separate frontend and backend and representational state transfer (REST) API.

The chosen technologies, including React and SCSS to develop the frontend application, Express, to produce the backend REST API, and MySQL, for the creation of the database, in addition to Git version control, will be explored, evaluating their suitability to the project. The tools used during development will be discussed, examining the necessary software, including Microsoft Visual Studio Code and Windows PowerShell, used to create and test the frontend and backend, XAMPP and phpMyAdmin, used during the hosting and administration of the database, and the use of Postman and suitable browsers, for testing the developed application.

The libraries and frameworks utilised to assist in providing frontend and backend functionality will be discussed, including react-flatpickr, used for creating a React cross-platform date time picker, and react-router-dom, for navigating between frontend pages. The cors library, used for enabling backend cross-origin resource sharing, joi validation framework, used for validating backend request data, and mysql2 package, for connecting the backend API to the persistent database storage, will be examined.

A discussion on the implementation of the MySQL database undertaken will explore the process of creating the database using the phpMyAdmin database administration tool, before generating mock data to subsequently populate the database using, for the purposes of demonstration and testing. The database queries produced, for accessing the database to perform the desired user stories, will be examined.

The implementation of the backend API will be explored, discussing the request validation performed on received input data, to facilitate data integrity and security, and creation of data access methods, to interact with the database. The creation of data conformance functions, to manipulate received data into a database-compatible format, and transform database returned data into a transmissible format, will be discussed. The returned endpoint responses and connection to the database will be examined, before the structure of the backend and its importance to the maintainability of the API, will be explored.

The frontend application implementation will be examined, discussing the reusable React components created and existing third-party components used, and their corresponding benefit to the application's development. The required form input validation and data conformance functions created, to facilitate successful data communication with the backend API, will be examined, before the use of the JavaScript Fetch API, to connect to the backend API, is explored. The frontend page navigation, utilising the react-router-dom library, and frontend styling, utilising a combination of custom SCSS and the Bulma CSS framework, will be discussed, integral to the success of the frontend. The frontend structure will be examined, explaining its purpose of improving the application's updatability.

The coding principles utilised throughout the creation of the application will be explored, including the use of a sprint-based development, to improve development time and feature management, ensuring all key user stories were implemented. The use of refactoring, to improve code maintainability and increase future feature implementation times, will be discussed.

Security mechanisms implemented, both in the database and backend API, will be explored, detailing the importance of such measures, and how methods were undertaken to minimise the risks of many forms of attack, and system vulnerabilities.

5.2 Architecture

Application architecture is critical to the future scalability, maintainability and upgradability of a system. The application uses a separate frontend, backend and database structure, promoting scalability and upgradability, with the frontend application utilising a single-page application (SPA) architecture, communicating with the backend to transmit and receive JSON objects using an API.

This modern, modular approach to the website's architecture offers the potential to easily update and expand the system based on new requirements or future needs, whilst increasing the application's user experience and performance. The backend application's use of a RESTful API architecture increases the flexibility of the application, whilst providing the possibility of creating multiple frontend implementations.

5.2.1 Separate Frontend/Backend

The created web application uses a separate frontend, backend and database architecture, with each element being independent, and communicating to transfer necessary data between each aspect via HTTP requests (Kornienko, Mishina and Melnikov, 2021).

The frontend React web application provides the user with an easy-to-use graphical user interface (GUI), with suitably-displayed webpage content, to allow them to view, navigate and utilise the functionality and data contained within the system (Boduch, 2017). In contrast, the backend Express API offers a simple web mechanism to return, create, update and delete stored data within the system, agnostic of the underlying implementation used to store the data (Bangare *et al.*, 2016). The MySQL database is used to recover and persistently store data used within the application.

The frontend application runs on an independent HTTP server and communicates to the backend API through sending HTTP requests to the relevant API backend endpoint, exposed via a URL, with a request body containing the necessary data, in a JSON format (Hernandez-Mendez, Scholz and Matthes, 2018). The backend API responds to the frontend request via returning a HTTP response, containing the appropriate HTTP status code and JSON-encoded data or message within the HTTP response body (Hernandez-Mendez, Scholz and Matthes, 2018).

When the user wishes to view a webpage containing data items stored in the database, or add or edit records within the system, their client web browser sends a HTTP request to the frontend web server. The frontend server communicates to the backend API, running on a separate web server, via sending HTTP requests to return, insert, or modify the relevant data.

The backend REST API awaits HTTP requests and, upon receiving a request, handles the request using the appropriate endpoint controller, based on the request URL. Within the backend endpoint controller, a connection is made to the database, using mysql2. The database is contained within a separate database server, which persistently stores all inputted data.

Database SQL requests are received, with the query being run within the database server, and the result being returned via the database connection to the backend server. Upon receiving the requested data from the database, the backend server responds to the frontend server request with the returned data from the database. The frontend web application then re-renders to display the appropriate returned data.

Figure 5.1 System Architecture and Communication Process

Through separating the frontend, backend and database logic, the architecture facilitates scalability, with each element having the potential to be hosted on a separate server, meaning requests may be distributed to reduce request times and increase request capacity. By separating logic and making each aspect independent, upgradability is possible, as the frontend may be modified or remade at a later date, to reflect future application design best practices.

With a separated architecture, the existing system may continue to function, whilst a new frontend may be developed, utilising the existing backend and database, with minimal downtime. This would allow the system's frontend to be modernised, whilst not affecting the stored data within the database, and reducing the financial and time costs of having to rewrite the entire system.

The chosen architecture also supports the option to produce multiple different user interfaces to interact with the backend system, such as mobile or desktop apps. As the backend and database are independent, and may serve many clients, the backend API could be implemented within a mobile app, to provide additional flexibility to users, only requiring the development of an app-based frontend.

Alternatively, should the MySQL database lack capacity or performance, an alternative SQL-based database may be created, only requiring connection to the backend, as the backend SQL commands would still function. To provide this flexibility and future upgradability, due to the changing nature of the frontend features and design choices demanded by users, this architecture was decided upon to be the most suitable for this project. Suitable technologies that would support this architecture were employed, with React JS providing a compatible frontend solution, Express offering an independent backend API framework, and MySQL providing a separated database.

The frontend web application is a single-page application (SPA), meaning only one initial page request is made to the frontend web server, and all subsequent pages are formed by dynamically requesting and loading the necessary page content to display on-screen (Hernandez-Mendez, Scholz and Matthes, 2018). Through re-rendering specific components present on the webpage, rather than initiating another page reload cycle, the application offers significantly more performance.

Page reloads often significantly hinder performance, especially with slower internet connections, as all elements on the page must be re-requested. Additionally, they provide a significant overhead on the frontend web server, which receives significantly more requests, rather than users retaining unchanged content within their browser, and only requesting the different content to display on-screen. For this reason, a SPA was decided to offer the best architecture for the web application's frontend, for which React JS offered this functionality.

Upon completion of the frontend, backend and database components, the web application will be deployed on a remote server, to allow the system to be accessed and used by end users. It is expected that initially, a cloud-based web hosting service, such as Amazon AWS or Google Cloud, would host all application components. With web traffic to the application expected to be relatively minimal initially, a cloud service would provide a cost-effective and scalable solution to deployment, with high reliability.

As all users of the application would be interacting equally with the frontend, backend and database components, due to only having a singular developed frontend, these elements may be hosted on the same server to reduce costs. Should multiple frontend applications be produced, to facilitate the repurposing and customising of the application for different organisations and uses, or if the backend API is utilised by third-party interfaces or integrations with systems such as Canvas, each component would be deployed on a separate server.

Independent deployment of components would allow the individual scaling of the appropriate components to meet the required number of requests, as it is likely the backend would require increased capacity to handle the developed frontend and third-party frontend request traffic. Due to the system architecture, with the components being fully independent and communicating via HTTP requests, the system would natively support separated deployment, without requiring any modification to the produced application code.

5.2.2 Representational State Transfer (REST) API

The project involved the creation of a Representational State Transfer, or REST, API. REST defines an architecture that must be followed to create a RESTful API, although it is agnostic to language and technology (Hernandez-Mendez, Scholz and Matthes, 2018). REST APIs are stateless and lightweight, making them suitable for creating scalable backend applications (Brachmann, Dittmann and Schubert, 2012).

The backend API endpoints accept incoming HTTP GET, POST, PUT and DELETE requests to the specified URL on the defined port, with the request being handled by the appropriate controller, performing the relevant logic and returning a suitable HTTP response to the originating client, such as the frontend. The backend API URL defines the resource, such as assessments or students, being requested by the client. For each API URL, the four specified request types are handled by their associated handlers, allowing full create, read, update, delete and list (CRUDL) operations to be performed on the resource, to view or manipulate the stored data.

HTTP request methods are governed by best practice, with GET requests being used to retrieve resource data, POST requests creating a new data record in the specified resource, PUT requests updating a data record in the specified resource with the provided data, and DELETE requests deleting the specified resource. To conform with industry best practice, endpoints were created using these HTTP request methods, to perform the specified functionality.

API endpoint best practice notes that endpoints should list collections, as opposed to the underlying SQL and joins used, therefore should list the main collection, followed by any sub-collections (Modi, Chourasia and Pandey, 2022). The chosen syntax for the backend API fulfils this standard, through first listing the main collection, such as users, followed by the sub-collection, their modules.

Upon sending a HTTP GET request to the relevant backend API, should the resource be located, the HTTP status code of 200 OK is returned in the request header, alongside the requested resource in a JSON format, contained within the response body. If a HTTP POST request has been made, with the data record being successfully inserted into the database, the HTTP status code of 201 Created is returned, along with the data inserted into the database.

If a HTTP PUT request has been received, and the data has been successfully modified, the HTTP status code of 200 OK is returned, alongside the updated data record's new values. If a HTTP DELETE request has been made, with the record being successfully deleted, the HTTP status code of 200 OK is returned, alongside the deleted record.

If a request contains a client error, such as an unsuitable request syntax, the HTTP status code of 400 Bad Request is returned, alongside a JSON-encoded message containing the error. Should a request be made to a non-implemented URL or accompanying request method, the HTTP status code of 404 Not Found is returned, alongside a basic HTML page denoting that the resource is not found.

RESTful API best practice advises that the defined HTTP status codes should be returned to the client upon attempting to fulfil a request, to both inform the client of the success of their requested operation, and safeguard the API against malicious attacks (Corradini *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, industry best practice states that a RESTful API should always return a resource, typically JSON-encoded, regardless of the HTTP request method handled (Corradini *et al.*, 2022).

The industry-standard approach was taken to both endpoint syntax and HTTP request method handling, as it demonstrates a clear understanding of the agreed and common implementation of endpoint syntaxes, in the context of the most widely used APIs. This syntax and returned values would theoretically allow the API endpoints to be distributed and used by additional frontends or API clients, produced by other developers. Different developers would be able to make API requests quickly and easily, as the syntax follows their existing knowledge, based on best practice.

The produced RESTful APIs are exposed via a server, allowing them to be used by clients to transmit and return JSON-encoded data. JSON was chosen as the endpoint request and response body format, due to its ubiquity in industry, and its simple decoding and integration with JavaScript. As the frontend is built using React, a JavaScript library, it was simple and efficient to produce JavaScript objects to display on the frontend from the backend API's returned JSON object. The Express framework, as it is built using JavaScript, offers full support for JSON encoding and decoding, making it a suitable choice for creating the backend API.

5.3 Technologies

During the development of the application, a range of technologies were employed, each targeted at providing a specific set of functionality. React and SCSS were chosen to create the frontend web application, whilst Express and MySQL were used to handle backend requests and for persistent storage of data. Git was used as a version control system, to handle and track changes to the project's code over time. A range of material was used in the production of the implemented application, namely the weekly advice of the Final Year Project React Group (Jones, 2023).

5.3.1 React

React JS is a JavaScript library used to create user interfaces on a server, through producing components formed of JSX elements, which are imported and implemented across different pages of the application to produce webpages (Boduch, 2017).

React was used to create the frontend, or view, of the web application, due to it providing the ability to create reusable components. Reusable components improve development efficiency, as code does not have to be repeated or re-written each time it is required, and maintainability, as changes to a component will automatically be applied to all instances of it throughout the frontend.

React was chosen due to its ubiquity in industry for creating high-performance single-page applications (SPA), through only re-rendering components that have changed, rather than requiring a whole page reload cycle.

React JS was used to create all pages and their associated content within the frontend of the web application, based on the requests made to fetch the webpage on the appropriate port on localhost.

5.3.2 SCSS

SCSS is a CSS pre-processor, which provides added flexibility and functionality for styling using CSS (Prabhu, 2015). All React pages and components were styled using SCSS, to provide consistency and flexibility, whilst also improving the default HTML styling of elements, otherwise provided by browsers.

SCSS allows the use of mixins, which are defined 'functions' containing executable CSS, which may be called and 'inserted' into different SCSS files. These may be combined with parameters, allowing the output of the CSS to be modified, based on the desired function.

Mixins allow common CSS styles to be reused throughout the application. Much like reusable React components, they improve efficiency and maintainability, as statements can be modified in a centralised location and these changes are reflected across the whole application. Variables allow styling to be defined in one location, and applied to multiple locations, further improving CSS maintainability.

SCSS was used to style all React JS components contained across the website, providing a consistent set of styling rules, increasing the user experience of the application.

5.3.3 Express

Express.js is a JavaScript framework used to create backend API endpoints on a server, through opening a listener on a specified port and listening to HTTP requests on that port (Subramanian, 2019). The request to the defined route is then handled by a defined controller, with the appropriate response being formulated and returned to the client.

Express was used to create endpoints, due to it providing an efficient framework to create RESTful APIs quickly and easily, through abstracting the necessary code to create RESTful API endpoints. Express was chosen due to its ubiquity in industry for creating servers with Node.js, whilst offering minimal plugins, to offer high-performance and robustness.

Throughout the application, all data inputted or outputted on the frontend was sent or retrieved via the appropriate Express endpoint. Endpoints were established for returning appropriate data as JSON objects, with HTTP GET, POST, PUT and DELETE requests being handled by Express.

The Express backend initially received the request, validated the request using the joi JavaScript framework, make a database connection to return the appropriate request data using the mysql2 framework, and responded to the client with the fetched data.

Other backend RESTful API frameworks are available, such as Python Django, although Express was chosen, due to utilising the same language as the frontend, JavaScript, and its ubiquity in industry (Subramanian, 2019).

5.3.4 MySQL

MySQL is a relational database management system, which provides the ability to create and manage relational databases using SQL (DuBois, 2008). It offers the ability to persistently store data, and retrieve stored data, allowing it to be used to retain data sent to the backend API, for later retrieval.

MySQL offers good performance, and is regularly updated with security and stability updates, making it a reliable choice to use to store critical assessment data. It provides a powerful feature set and may be installed on a remote server. As it is open source, its use is free, unlike many competitors. Furthermore, it supports system scalability, handling database file sizes up to 256TB.

MySQL was used to create the backend database to persistently store the application's data. It was then accessed via the mysql2 package within the Express backend API, to send queries to return, insert, update or delete stored data.

5.3.5 Git

Git is a version control system, used for tracking and managing developed code (Loeliger and McCullough, 2012). Git is used as the underlying protocol of GitHub, a website used for storing and collaborating on coding projects. GitHub allows code to be saved on a remote server, accessible through the website, and downloaded onto a local machine, in a process known as 'Cloning'.

Changes to the code may be made, and the new code may be uploaded back to the GitHub project, known as 'Pushing Changes'. GitHub will store the new version alongside all past versions of the project.

GitHub was selected as it allows code to be stored on a remote location, meaning it can be accessed from any device. As the code was developed across both a Desktop computer and Laptop, it was important to ensure all copies of the code were updated across both machines, which Git offers. Furthermore, it saves the code so, in the event of a machine failure, the code is still retrievable from the server. Additionally, as all old versions of the project remain on the server, if any changes are made which cause the project to fail, the code may be reverted back to the last working version.

GitHub was used to save all frontend and backend application code implementations to the server, to access and manage across all development machines, track code changes, and safeguard against device failure.

5.4 Tools

A number of tools were used during the application's development, to produce, run and test the developed application and its associated code. Tools such as Visual Studio Code were used to write the frontend and backend application, whilst phpMyAdmin was used to produce the database. Windows PowerShell was used to start the application servers, whilst XAMPP was employed to host the database. Postman provided the ability to test the developed API endpoints and Mozilla Firefox with the React Developer Tools extension was used to test the application was functional.

5.4.1 Microsoft Visual Studio Code

Microsoft Visual Studio Code is a cross-platform text editing tool, with integrated code-specific editing and compilation features (Visual Studio Code, no date). It allows a wide range of programming language code to be inputted, with the language being recognised and appropriate colours being applied to code, based on its purpose.

Visual Studio Code was chosen as it is an industry standard editor, supporting multiple languages including JavaScript and SCSS, and features an integrated Windows PowerShell Terminal, allowing development servers to be started and packages installed directly from the application.

Furthermore, it provides autocomplete functionality, suggesting potential code statements to input, assisting with the development process.

It provides the ability to download Extensions, which may be used to enhance the development process, such as Prettier, to enhance code readability, Auto Rename Tag, to automatically rename HTML closing tags if the opening tag is modified, and Import Cost, to show the size of package imports within files. These assist with efficient development, ensuring code is readable, and the development process is as simple as possible.

Microsoft Visual Studio Code was used to create and edit all frontend React and SCSS, and backend Express code.

5.4.2 Windows PowerShell

Windows PowerShell is a command line shell used to execute commands within a Windows-based environment (Microsoft, no date). It provides the ability to run text-based commands within a Windows system, including directory traversal, management of development servers and installation of JavaScript packages, via npm.

Windows PowerShell was selected, as it offers a powerful environment to execute Windows command line commands, and is included within the integrated Terminal in Visual Studio Code. Furthermore, PowerShell is ubiquitous in industry, due to providing significantly more system control and commands than the included Windows Command Prompt.

PowerShell was used to start and stop the frontend and backend application development servers and install all required frontend and backend packages using npm.

5.4.3 XAMPP

XAMPP is a web server stack application, containing all necessary components to develop and host web applications on a local machine (XAMPP, no date). It offers Apache HTTP server, to host webpages based on received HTTP requests, MariaDB, for persistent data storage in a database, PHP, to parse PHP files into HTML to be sent to the client requesting the webpage, and Perl, a dynamic programming language.

XAMPP was chosen due to its ubiquity in industry, and it providing the phpMyAdmin database administration tool and associated database. This enabled a simple solution to provide the database environment within the local development machine, rather than creating an online or hosted database on a remote server. Additionally, due to XAMPP hosting the database locally, it meant development was able to take place without a network connection to a remote database server.

XAMPP was used to start the database server on the local machine, enabling the database to be accessed via the phpMyAdmin tool from within a web browser.

5.4.4 phpMyAdmin

phpMyAdmin is a database administration tool used to create and manage MySQL databases and their associated relations, structure and contained data (phpMyAdmin, no date). phpMyAdmin offers simple database management through an easy-to-use web browser user interface, making it highly efficient to use to produce databases.

phpMyAdmin was selected due to its portability, as upon deployment, the database can be managed remotely by any suitable device with a web browser. As it provides a clear and simple graphical user interface, it enabled the database to be produced quickly, without requiring the use of a command line interface to manage the system. Furthermore, its ubiquity in industry made it an excellent choice, to facilitate simple database management.

The phpMyAdmin tool was used to create the database and its relations, whilst also to test if the backend API was functioning correctly, by checking the database's stored data matched that returned via the API. When data was inputted via a frontend form or backend API endpoint request, phpMyAdmin was used to check that the data was stored within the database, ensuring the system was functioning correctly.

5.4.5 Postman

Postman is an application used to create and send HTTP requests to a server, via its URL (Postman, no date). It provides the ability to produce a wide range of HTTP requests, including GET, POST, PUT and DELETE requests, and send these with a JSON-encoded request body.

Postman was used, as it enables formulated HTTP requests to be saved for later use, meaning produced requests can be stored to enable them to be rerun at a later date, without requiring the request to be re-formulated. This saves significant time during testing of the API endpoints.

Furthermore, it offers the ability to test the API without requiring its connection to a frontend. This was especially useful, as during each sprint, the data model and backend API were implemented before the frontend user interface, so Postman enabled the backend to be tested, without having the frontend implemented.

Postman was used to test each produced endpoint in the backend API upon its implementation and any changes or modifications made to the endpoint, such as after the refactoring stage had occurred, to ensure the endpoint was functioning correctly and returning the appropriate requested data.

5.4.6 Mozilla Firefox with React Developer Tools Extension

Mozilla Firefox is a modern web browser, used to send requests to web servers and build a DOM based on the returned HTML, CSS, JavaScript and requested object components such as images or videos (Mozilla, no date). The returned DOM is displayed on-screen, allowing the user to view the page output. The React Developer Tools extension for Mozilla Firefox allows the user to view the React components and their location in the 'tree' contained on a webpage built with React (React, no date b).

Mozilla Firefox was used, due to it supporting both legacy and the latest JavaScript syntaxes, providing extensive 'Web Developer Tools' and offering the React Developer Tools extension. Mozilla Firefox was used to view and test that the frontend application was fully functional, whilst the React Developer Tools extension offered debugging to inspect the React components contained within the page and resolve any present errors.

The Mozilla Firefox Console, Inspector and 'Pick an element from this page' tools were used extensively to view errors within the frontend application, allowing these to be resolved. The final webpage was tested on a range of popular web browsers to ensure its compatibility, including Google Chrome, Microsoft Edge, Safari and Opera.

5.5 Libraries and Frameworks

The application employed a collection of libraries and frameworks to assist in providing application functionality. The react-flatpickr package was used to provide a datetime picker within frontend forms, with the react-router-dom offering React page navigation capabilities. The cors package was used to enable cross-origin resource sharing, whilst joi was used to validate input data from frontend input forms, and requests and their associated data received on the backend.

5.5.1 react-flatpickr

react-flatpickr is a JavaScript package used to create a datetime picker within a React frontend web application (Hao, 2023). It provides the ability to produce a datetime selector within an input form, with little additional code required to allow the component to display and manipulate its selected date and time values.

During the creation of the React form item components, the need for obtaining different (data) types of user input was identified. Whilst most form items may be accomplished via a dropdown list or text input, start and end date inputs are of a date time format, which required the importing of a third-party library, react-flatpickr, to handle the user input of this data.

As HTML input elements do not have a consistent datetime input which is compatible with all browsers or browser versions, the Flatpickr was the most suitable alternative, to ensure the date and time may be entered on all user platforms, meeting the compatibility non-functional requirements. Furthermore, the Flatpickr component is very user-friendly and aesthetically pleasing, allowing users to easily select dates and input times, improving usability and associated non-functional requirements.

5.5.2 react-router-dom

react-router-dom is a JavaScript package used to allow dynamic webpage routing within a React frontend application (React Router, no date). Webpages often require the navigation between different pages, although as React provides the ability to create a single page application (SPA), routing must be handled by manipulating the components displayed and rendered within the original page request.

The react-router-dom package was used as it provides the ability to navigate between 'pages' of the application via the provided URL, without requiring a page reload. This allows multiple pages to be displayed to the user, whilst only requiring an initial page load request, and further pages being displayed by sending individual requests to the server for the required components, decreasing page load times and the page request overheads on the frontend web server.

This package was used across all webpages, to facilitate the navigation between different pages, and routing to the desired webpage based on the requested URL.

5.5.3 cors

cors is a JavaScript package used to enable cross-origin resource sharing within a server (cors, 2023). It provides a simple to configure method of allowing connections to be made from within the same origin.

As Express prevents data from being requested from the same origin on the development machine, cors is used to enable cross-origin requests, meaning Express will respond to requests made from the same device. cors was chosen due to its efficiency and simplicity with enabling cross-origin requests on a JavaScript server.

5.5.4 joi

joi is a JavaScript package used to create data object schemas and validate data according to the defined schema (joi, no date). It provides a very flexible and efficient, shorthand approach to data validation, as validation rulesets are defined as functions and data is piped between these during the validation process.

The joi framework checks the provided data against the schema and, should the data not match the schema, the appropriate error messages are returned. joi was used to validate request data received by the Express endpoints, to ensure the endpoint only accepted valid request parameters and body data, assisting with storing accurate data within the database.

The joi framework was also used within the frontend of the application, to validate form data as it was inputted by the user. joi was used as validation is key to ensuring inputted and stored data is accurate, and to increase security, by escaping HTML tags to prevent cross-site scripting attacks.

The joi framework was selected as it reduces the time taken to create validation rulesets and leads to the code being more maintainable, as difficult to read, manual validation rules are not present. Furthermore, by using a defined validation framework, there is less chance of validation rulesets being incorrect, as errors can occur when attempting to manually create validation rules.

5.5.5 mysql2

mysql2 is a JavaScript package used to create MySQL database connections from a JavaScript client, such as an Express server (Sidorov, 2023). It provides the ability to open asynchronous connections with the database and send appropriate SQL commands to be run on a remote database. It handles the process of receiving the returned data or message from the database, placing it within an object that may be handled within the JavaScript application.

mysql2 was used within the Express backend to create a database connection with the Collabase database storing the application's data. It was used to send the relevant SQL commands, such as INSERT INTO, SELECT, UPDATE and DELETE commands and handle the returned data, to pass back to the client in the formulated Express HTTP response.

mysql2 was selected as it is simple to implement and configure connections to databases using, rather than manually making a database connection on the appropriate port. Furthermore, as it provides an efficient mechanism to create asynchronous database requests, this increases the performance of the backend implementation, as it may handle other requests rather than stalling whilst it awaits the returned data from the database.

5.6 Database Implementation

5.6.1 Introduction

Following the successful design of the application's underlying data model, the database required implementation, to provide a mechanism for the persistent storage of system data. As a result of extensive database design, through the precursory creation of ER diagrams and data dictionaries, the database implementation stage was accelerated. Within each sprint, the database was the first system element to be implemented, as a correct data structure is integral to the data access design of the backend API, and in turn the data displayed within the frontend application, thus being crucial to the successful creation of the product.

In this subsection, an evaluation of the different available database platforms will be conducted, before summarising with the platform identified as most suitable for this project. The stages undertaken to install the MySQL RDBMS and its associated platform and administration tools will be detailed, alongside the translation of the data model into an implemented database. The generation of mock data, and subsequent database population with the produced data, will be explored, in addition to queries created to retrieve and manipulate the stored data.

5.6.2 Database Platform Evaluation

After evaluating different database management systems (DBMS), it was decided that MySQL remained the most suitable database to store the required application data. Document-oriented NoSQL databases, such as MongoDB and RedisJSON, provide exceptional scalability and support for big data (Li and Manoharan, 2013). However, as the development team were already very competent in relational (SQL) databases, but lacked understanding of NoSQL, it was decided that the learning required to migrate to such technology would take too much time from an already constrained project. Based on the identified requirements, it was decided that the system was not expected to handle big data, due to the limited numbers of students and assessments conducted within Kingston University. It was therefore concluded that a relational database management system (RDBMS) would be more suitable.

Upon further investigation, MySQL was identified as being the most appropriate RDBMS for this project, due to being both free and supporting all typical SQL commands, offering excellent management of the database and its contained data. Its huge popularity in industry, frequently being ranked as the most widely used database, improves maintainability, as it is likely the RDBMS would continue to receive long term support and updates.

This popularity increases the likelihood of future developers working on the application having an existing comprehensive knowledge of the database used, whilst its integration with the phpMyAdmin database administration control panel, ensures the database may be successfully managed by even non-familiar developers. MySQL also offers high performance, reliability and availability, ensuring the application will meet its related non-functional requirements, and user experience is not hindered through significant system downtime (Li and Manoharan, 2013). Consequently, it was concluded that MySQL, alongside phpMyAdmin, would provide the most benefit to implementing the designed data model.

5.6.3 Database Creation

After finalising the data model, the database required implementation. As previously discussed, MySQL was chosen as the preferred database platform, alongside phpMyAdmin to facilitate simple database administration, via an easy-to-use graphical user interface. It was decided that the use of XAMPP would simplify the installation of the required database tools, through providing all necessary components in a single package.

Figure 5.2 XAMPP Control Panel

XAMPP is a free cross-platform web server, containing Apache HTTP Server, MySQL, PHP and Perl. Through installing XAMPP, the Apache HTTP Server and PHP is installed, allowing phpMyAdmin to be run, alongside the required MySQL database (XAMPP, no date). Upon installing XAMPP, the user is presented with the XAMPP Control Panel, used for managing the running of the provided services. It is necessary to ensure Apache and MySQL are both running at all times, to ensure the database and phpMyAdmin tool are always available and accessible.

Once these services are successfully running, as indicated by the green background around the 'Module', as shown in Figure 5.2, the developer may navigate to 'localhost/phpmyadmin'. As the database and phpMyAdmin installation is running on the local development machine, localhost is used to symbolise the connection must be made with the web service running within the device.

Figure 5.3 Creation of New Database in phpMyAdmin

After navigating to the phpMyAdmin homepage, a new database must be created. It was decided that the database be named 'Collabase', in reference to the collaborative marking and feedback tool the database is supporting. After inputting the database name and using the default file type, the 'Create' button was clicked.

Figure 5.4 Collabase Creation in phpMyAdmin

Upon creation of the Collabase database, no tables are found, therefore the first table is required to be created. Within phpMyAdmin, commands may be executed through the on-screen form components, which are in turn translated into SQL commands to be run on the database, or directly on the database, using custom SQL commands or scripts.

While the on-screen forms accelerate the process of table creation, and remove the requirement to have knowledge of SQL commands to manipulate the database, custom SQL commands offer additional flexibility. It was therefore decided that custom SQL commands would be used throughout, to ensure the created database would meet both the client and frontend requirements, and match the produced data model.

Figure 5.5 Usertypes Table Creation in phpMyAdmin

The order of table creation is significant and must be thoroughly considered before implementing tables. Tables referencing foreign keys may only be created after the parent table, containing the primary key being referenced, has been implemented, as a reference to a primary key cannot be made to a non-existent table. It was therefore decided that any ancillary tables, such as Usertypes, without foreign keys, would be created first, as shown in Figure 5.5.

```
CREATE TABLE Usertypes (  
    UsertypeID INT(5) NOT NULL,  
    UsertypeName VARCHAR(50) NOT NULL,  
    UsertypeDescription VARCHAR(150),  
    PRIMARY KEY(UsertypeID)  
);
```

Figure 5.6 Usertypes Table Creation SQL Command

The SQL 'CREATE' command is used to add a new object to the database schema. In Figure 5.6, 'CREATE TABLE Usertypes' specifies that a new table, called Usertypes, is to be created. Within the parenthesis, the attributes, their datatypes and any constraints are listed, separated by commas. Datatypes typically include 'INT', for storing numerical values, and 'VARCHAR', for textual data. 'NOT NULL' signifies that a value must be included for that attribute, and it cannot contain a null value. 'PRIMARY KEY' is used to signify that the UsertypeID attribute value is a unique identifier to reference an individual record.

Figure 5.7 Usertypes Successful Table Creation in phpMyAdmin

Figure 5.8 Usertypes Table Structure in phpMyAdmin

As shown in Figure 5.7, the Usertypes table was created successfully. The table structure may now be viewed within phpMyAdmin, as shown in Figure 5.8, and Usertype records may be inserted within the database.

```

CREATE TABLE Users (
    UserID INT(5) NOT NULL,
    UserTitle VARCHAR(9),
    UserFirstname VARCHAR(35) NOT NULL,
    UserMiddlename VARCHAR(35),
    UserLastname VARCHAR(35) NOT NULL,
    UserEmail VARCHAR(75) NOT NULL,
    UserImageURI VARCHAR(500) DEFAULT
'https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg',
    UserUsertypeID INT(5) REFERENCES Usertypes(UsertypeID),
    PRIMARY KEY(UserID)
);

```

Figure 5.9 Users Table Creation SQL Command

After creating the Usertypes table, the Users table, which references the Usertypes table, was able to be implemented. As shown in Figure 5.9, the 'DEFAULT' clause is used to set a default value to be applied to a row's attribute value, in the absence of provided data for that column. In the case of an image, to ensure image consistency within the frontend application, a default image URL is inserted. The 'REFERENCES' clause is used to define the home table's attribute for a foreign key column.

In the case of 'REFERENCES Usertypes(UsertypeID)', this denotes that the Users table's UserUsertypeID attribute is a foreign key linked to the UsertypeID primary key within the Usertypes table. This ensures referential integrity, as inserted values into the UserUsertypeID attribute must either have a corresponding record with the matching ID value within the Usertypes table, or the field must be null.

Figure 5.10 Collabase Database Tables

Following the previously outlined process, database tables were created within the collabase database for each table defined in the data model design, as shown in Figure 5.10. These followed the table names, attribute names, data types and constraints identified within the data dictionary.

During database development, a range of issues were noted with the original data model. One such issue was that the AssessmentTimeslotduration attribute was missing from within the Assessments relation. This column is defined within the ER diagram and data dictionary, and is crucial to calculating the panel-group assignment timeslots for assessments. Consequently, the AssessmentTimeslotduration attribute was added to the Assessments relation, with an 'INT(3)' datatype and 'DEFAULT 15' value.

CHECK constraints are defined in the data dictionary for attributes such as AssessmenttrubricWeighting in the Assessmenttrubrics relation. When attempting to implement this constraint, research was undertaken, and it was determined that 'CHECK' constraints are not supported within MySQL. Consequently, all CHECK constraints were unable to be implemented, thus were subsequently dropped from the final database implementation.

The Alerts relation was identified as being incorrect, due to it not containing any foreign key references to its linked Assessments relation. This was rectified within the database implementation, through the creation of an 'AlertsAssessmentID INT(5) FOREIGN KEY References Assessments(AssessmentID)' attribute. This correction to the original database design now allows the alert to be linked to an assessment.

It was also noted that the 'AlertUsergroupID' attribute within the Alerts relation did not match the standard attribute naming conventions, which typically match the referenced home table's primary key attribute name, unless otherwise nonsensical. Consequently, this attribute was renamed to 'AlertUserTypeID' in the database implementation, to better fit with naming conventions.

Figure 5.11 phpMyAdmin Export Function

During creation of the database, and at regular intervals upon stored data being manipulated, database backups are produced using the 'Export' feature of phpMyAdmin, as shown in Figure 5.11. In the event of a system failure, database error, or unwanted changes being made to the database, it is important that the database and its stored data may be restored. Clicking on the 'Export' button allows a complete SQL-based copy of the database schema and all associated data contained within the database to be downloaded and stored.

Figure 5.12 phpMyAdmin Import Function

The 'Import' function allows a file to be selected and the relevant SQL commands to be executed within the database. In the case of restoring the database state from a backup file, the 'Import' functionality should be used. Importing and Exporting data is especially useful during development across multiple development machines, as the most recent copy of the local database may be exported from one device, and sent to and imported within the other device, to ensure all machines contain the same database structure and data.

5.6.4 Database Population

Upon successfully implementing all database relations identified within the ER diagram, the database must be populated with sample data. Database population is a crucial stage, as it validates that the data model produced is correct, and that the implementation of the data model was successful. Through inserting data, issues and errors with the created database may be detected, as foreign key and other such constraint reference errors may be returned, or the inability to retrieve data, due to missing foreign keys, may highlight underlying data model problems.

Database population also serves to provide a set of sample data that may be used to test and demonstrate the frontend React application. Whilst testing the layout of the presented data within the frontend, retrieved data assists with determining stylistic design choices, and displaying typical data expected to be output within the frontend webpages, for assisting with user conceptualisation when demonstrating the produced system. Additionally, population of the database ensures frontend API calls to the backend, and their corresponding API functions, are fully functional, as the results of CRUD operations are visible across all system components.

It is beneficial to produce and populate the database with significant amounts of sample data, as this aids in identifying more realistic database performance upon application deployment. Whilst only a subset of the populated data will be visible and used for testing, a large stored data set much like that accumulated during real-world application use, seeks to identify database SQL query times, backend API performance, and the request-response time to fetch API data from the frontend. This allows the potential scalability, and expected performance to be evaluated against the defined non-functional requirement metrics.

Significant data population also invokes the necessity to produce a frontend application design capable of handling the display of vast amounts of returned data. In the case of an administrator or assessment leader with numerous assessments spanning several years, or a list of students to add to a group, lots of data requires webpage output. In such case, it is necessary that the frontend is suitably designed to allow the data to be easily viewed, searched or filtered. With minimal amounts of returned data, such issue is not present or able to be tested, meaning the created frontend can lack suitability for long term use.

It must be noted that the data created must be fictitious, in the case of its use for the purposes of demonstration and system testing. Whilst the system will be required to handle real, accurate data upon deployment, whilst in development, it is crucial that GDPR compliance measures are enforced to reduce the risk of data leaks.

During the development phase, no developers, testers, study participants or demonstration audience should be able to view real data, and as the system is not stored on a secured server, but rather a local development machine, the system environment security cannot be guaranteed. Additionally, as no production build has been produced, the development build of the application may contain bugs or security vulnerabilities.

As such, it is necessary to generate mock data to populate the database with. The process of producing fictitious data is lengthy when conducted by hand, with individual row and column data requiring manual input using improvised data. It was decided that the use of automated tools would seek to accelerate the data generation process, whilst providing more accurate mock data than can typically be thought up.

Mockaroo is an online automated data generator, which offers users the ability to generate SQL INSERT INTO commands containing mock data, based on a wide range of sample data types (Mockaroo, no date). With options including blank and custom values, data may be more realistically generated, to be inserted into the database. Mockaroo was used to generate sample data, due to the speed and ease at which thousands of rows of realistic mock data may be produced, thus saving time when populating the database.

Figure 5.13 Mockaroo Data Generation Process

As shown in Figure 5.13, to generate sample Mockaroo data, the field name must first be input. To produce a suitable SQL 'INSERT INTO' statement containing mock data using Mockaroo, the specified field names, ordering, data types and constraints must exactly match those contained within the corresponding database table.

When creating mock data, the column names were input, alongside the matching Mockaroo data type, ensuring realistic data was generated. ID columns utilised the 'Row Number' data type, which provides an autoincremented numerical value for each INSERT INTO statement. Titles, names and email addresses are all able to be generated, being selected at random from a list of appropriate values.

In the case of generating image URLs, the 'Dummy Image URL' data type produces a real image URL to a sample image of a size within the defined range. As shown, Mockaroo allows input fields to contain a percentage of blank values, which allows fields to be realistically mocked as, in the case of middle names, not all users may have a middle name. This feature, whilst providing a mechanism for the developer to test the handling of null values within the frontend application, also checks that database constraints have been implemented correctly, as attributes such as the middle name field must accept null values.

Figure 5.14 Mockaroo Association Table Data Generation Process

Figure 5.14 shows Mockaroo being used to generate data to populate association tables, such as the Userassessments table used when handling the many-to-many relationship between Users and Assessments. Prior to generating association table data, it is necessary for both referenced tables to be populated with their respective data, to provide records which can be joined.

To create association table data, the total number of records present within both parent tables must be recorded, with these forming the maximum number values in their respective fields in Mockaroo. This ensures referential integrity, as the random number generated by Mockaroo will be the primary key ID of a matching record in its home table. The 'Datetime' data type is used to create the enrolment date for the database entry, with the date format matching that accepted by MySQL.

Upon entering the appropriate field names, selecting the data type, and inputting any field constraints, the number of rows must be decided upon. To produce a large dataset as previously discussed, for representing real-world usage, substantial values should be used. In the case of having a free-tier Mockaroo account, the maximum number of rows able to be downloaded is 1,000, although the developer may choose to download multiple files of 1,000 rows, and run these separately within the database, as each download will contain different values.

Figure 5.15 Mockaroo Data Generation Output

The SQL format was selected, as it both tests that the database successfully handles INSERT INTO statements, which is necessary to create new rows from the backend API, and negates potential issues of phpMyAdmin incorrectly parsing CSV files to SQL commands to be run on the database. After inputting the appropriate table name, the 'Preview' button allows the sample SQL statements to be previewed before download, as shown in Figure 5.15. Clicking the 'Download Data' button downloads an SQL file containing the sample data, which may be run within the database.

Figure 5.16 phpMyAdmin Table Navigation and Toolbar

After the data has been successfully generated, it is necessary to import it into the database, to facilitate data population. This is achieved through navigating to the appropriate table within the phpMyAdmin database administration tool and clicking the 'Import' button, as shown in Figure 5.16.

Figure 5.17 phpMyAdmin Data Import

As shown in Figure 5.17, the data import screen will be displayed, from which the downloaded Mockaroo SQL file must be selected from the local storage. All default settings may be kept, before the 'Import' button is clicked.

Figure 5.18 phpMyAdmin Data Import Success

The SQL statements will then be pre-processed and run within the database, populating the table with the uploaded data file, as shown in Figure 5.18.

AssessmentID	AssessmentName	AssessmentStartDate	AssessmentEndDate	AssessmentImageURL	AssessmentLeaderID	AssessmentModuleID	AssessmentDescription	AssessmentTimeAllocation	AssessmentCreatedDate
1	React Native LFT App Assessment	2022-05-26 01:43:00	2022-10-29 01:00:00	http://dummyimage.com/160x100/png/6666/000000	1	4	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
2	Universal leading edge analyzer assessment	2022-06-19 17:18:00	2022-11-09 07:19:00	http://dummyimage.com/194x100/png/6666/000000	1	37	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
3	Centralized well-modulated paradigm assessment	2022-03-25-00:00:00	2022-10-15 08:56:00	http://dummyimage.com/160x100/png/0000/0000	1	1	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
4	Expanded disintermediate locker assessment	2022-09-23 21:01:00	2022-10-27 22:27:00	http://dummyimage.com/205x100/png/6666/000000	1	50	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
5	Proactive demand-driven architecture assessment	2022-10-05 18:15:00	2022-10-24 00:26:00	http://dummyimage.com/230x100/png/6666/0000	1	30	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
6	Impersonated cohesive GraphQL User Interface app	2022-10-08 23:20:00	2022-10-21 14:10:00	http://dummyimage.com/150x100/png/6666/0000	1	12	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
7	React Native App Demonstration	2022-11-09 09:20:00	2022-11-09 12:00:00	https://media.mediamarkt.com/ReactNativeApp4760x1000	1	40	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
8	Progressive 24 hour deliverywarehouse assessment	2022-09-17 18:40:00	2022-10-21 08:04:00	http://dummyimage.com/192x100/png/6666/0000	1	8	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
9	Modularly contextually-based customer loyalty app...	2022-03-23 14:03:00	2022-10-26 16:22:00	http://dummyimage.com/164x100/png/6666/0000	1	9	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
10	Dashboard bi-generated monitoring assessment	2022-02-29 00:54:00	2022-10-18 19:36:00	http://dummyimage.com/144x100/png/6666/0000	1	2	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
11	Function-based stable policy assessment	2022-09-10 21:49:00	2022-10-20 17:50:00	http://dummyimage.com/177x100/png/6666/000000	1	26	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
12	Automated SaaS-like medicine focus group assessment	2022-08-24 20:59:00	2022-11-11 17:27:00	http://dummyimage.com/145x100/png/0000/0000	1	41	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
13	Frontline demand-driven timeframe assessment	2022-10-08 05:34:00	2022-11-12 22:46:00	http://dummyimage.com/100x100/png/6666/000000	1	42	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
14	Universal dynamic GraphQL User Interface app...	2022-10-01 17:51:00	2022-10-20 05:16:00	http://dummyimage.com/124x100/png/6666/0000	1	5	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
15	Seamless bi-directional application assessment	2022-09-19 13:59:00	2022-11-04 23:34:00	http://dummyimage.com/178x100/png/6666/000000	1	19	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
16	Intrinsic multi-tiered alliance encryption assessment	2022-08-30 14:36:00	2022-10-28 13:44:00	http://dummyimage.com/230x100/png/6666/0000	1	47	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
17	Symmetrical object-oriented encryption assessment	2022-09-17 20:14:00	2022-11-01 07:36:00	http://dummyimage.com/240x100/png/6666/0000	1	7	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
18	User-centric interconnectable hub assessment	2022-09-17 14:58:00	2022-11-01 09:04:00	http://dummyimage.com/154x100/png/6666/0000	1	20	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
19	Team-oriented bi-directional access assessment	2022-09-27 17:58:00	2022-10-23 18:47:00	http://dummyimage.com/220x100/png/6666/0000	1	9	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
20	Persistent leading edge access assessment	2022-09-25 04:44:00	2022-10-15 14:34:00	http://dummyimage.com/100x100/png/6666/0000	1	35	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
21	Persevering directional adapter assessment	2022-09-20 14:41:00	2022-11-01 00:00:00	http://dummyimage.com/190x100/png/6666/0000	1	32	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
22	Cloud Managed Credential User Interface app...	2022-06-10 08:01:00	2022-11-04 16:38:00	http://dummyimage.com/180x100/png/6666/0000	1	20	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00
23	De-engineered 5th generation strategy	2022-06-10 17:31:00	2022-11-13 22:28:00	http://dummyimage.com/120x100/png/6666/000000	1	43	NULL	15	2022-11-10 00:00:00

Figure 5.19 phpMyAdmin Assessments Table Data Population

Such process was undertaken for all database tables created, with a suitable number of records being generated, as shown in Figure 5.19.

5.6.5 Database Queries

Once the database has been fully implemented and contains the generated sample data, queries may be produced to retrieve required data from the database. SQL commands may be categorised into four main collections – Data Definition Language (DDL), Data Manipulation Language (DML), Data Control Language (DCL) and Transaction Control Language (TCL). During the creation and management of the application’s database, only the DDL and DML categories of SQL command were required.

Data Definition Language involves the description of stored data within the database, handled through the creation of tables and schemas. This encompasses the CREATE command, used to add new tables to the database, ALTER command, used to edit existing tables, and DROP command, to delete tables. As previously discussed, the CREATE command was used to define the tables required to store data within the database. The ALTER command was frequently used to add constraints to the database tables, to ensure data integrity, and to rectify any errors within the data model, identified during implementation.

Figure 5.20 phpMyAdmin Userassessments Table Default Constraints

One such example involves the ‘delete assessment’ user story, for which the database required modification to the Userassessments relation constraints. Previously, all constraints were set as ‘ON DELETE RESTRICT’, meaning the deletion of the record would be restricted to only deleting the specified record directly, as shown in Figure 5.20.

Figure 5.21 phpMyAdmin Userassessments Table Modified Constraints

```
ALTER TABLE `userassessments` DROP FOREIGN KEY `userassessments_ibfk_1`; ALTER
TABLE `userassessments` ADD CONSTRAINT `userassessments_ibfk_1` FOREIGN KEY
(`UserassessmentAssessmentID`) REFERENCES `assessments` (`AssessmentID`) ON
DELETE CASCADE ON UPDATE RESTRICT;
```

Figure 5.22 Userassessments Table Constraint Modification SQL Command

This constraint was acceptable for the retrieval, addition and modification of records, however deletion of an assessment was impossible, due to a violation of foreign key constraints. To rectify this issue, as shown in Figure 5.21, the Userassessments relation's UserassessmentAssessmentID attribute was set to 'ON DELETE CASCADE' using the SQL command shown in Figure 5.22.

This means the deletion of a parent record in the Assessments relation would automatically remove all matching referenced records with the same AssessmentID foreign key in other relations. As the records would now be automatically deleted on their referenced record being deleted, the constraint would now not be violated if the parent record were to be deleted, thus resolving the issue of not being able to delete assessment records from the Assessments relation. Whilst the DROP command was used to remove constraints, to allow them to be updated, it was not used to delete tables or columns, as the database was created successfully originally.

Data Manipulation Language is used to handle data stored within the database, including data creation, retrieval, modification and deletion. SELECT statements are used to retrieve data, INSERT statements are used to create new records, UPDATE statements modify existing records, and DELETE statements are used to remove records from the database. As the created application requires full CRUD operations to be performed on the persistently-stored data within the database, all of these statements were used to provide such functionality.

```
SELECT Assessments.AssessmentImageURL, Assessments.AssessmentName,
Assessments.AssessmentStartdate, Assessments.AssessmentEnddate,
Modules.ModuleID AS AssessmentModuleID, Modules.ModuleCode AS
AssessmentModuleCode, Modules.ModuleName AS AssessmentModuleName, Users.UserID
AS AssessmentUserID, Users.UserTitle AS AssessmentLeaderTitle,
Users.UserFirstname AS AssessmentLeaderFirstname, Users.UserLastname AS
AssessmentLeaderLastname
FROM Userassessments INNER JOIN Assessments
    ON Userassessments.UserassessmentAssessmentID = Assessments.AssessmentID
LEFT JOIN Users
    ON Assessments.AssessmentLeaderID = Users.UserID
LEFT JOIN Modules
    ON Assessments.AssessmentModuleID = Modules.ModuleID
WHERE Userassessments.UserassessmentUserID = ${USERID}
ORDER BY Assessments.AssessmentStartdate;
```

Figure 5.23 Retrieve User's Assessments SQL Command

One example of a created SELECT statement is shown in Figure 5.23. This SQL command retrieves assessment, module and assessment leader information for each assessment a selected user is enrolled on. The SQL command utilises defined table names, such as 'Modules.ModuleName', where 'Modules' is the table containing the attribute, and 'ModuleName' is the attribute to be retrieved. This best practice ensures the database will always successfully return the attribute value from the correct table, in the case of multiple fields of the same name being present across different tables.

Attribute aliasing, represented by 'AS' in 'Users.UserTitle AS AssessmentLeaderTitle' ensures the returned data's field name is consistent with the naming conventions used for the other attributes in the table, making it easier to understand, whilst abstracting the underlying data model.

Joins were required across the majority of SQL data retrieval statements, to retrieve data stored across multiple tables in the database. As normalised relational databases store the required data in different tables, to prevent data redundancy and thus ensure data consistency, joins are required to rebuild the stored data objects requested. As discussed previously in Chapter 4 – Design, joins must be used sparingly and only where necessary, as they can significantly reduce database performance, especially with large numbers of records contained within the database, thus hindering scalability.

An 'INNER JOIN' was used to associate records within the Userassessments table with their corresponding records within the Assessments table, based on the matching AssessmentID values. Inner joins return only records contained within both the Userassessments and Assessments tables, which is crucial to ensuring the returned assessments both exist, and the user is correctly enrolled on them.

A 'LEFT JOIN' was used to associate records within the Assessments table with their corresponding records within the Users table, based on the matching AssessmentLeaderID values. Left joins return all records within the table defined on the left, in addition to matching all AssessmentLeaders with their corresponding User record.

This ensures all assessments will be returned, even if an assessment does not yet contain an assessment leader, as some assessments may be awaiting an assessment leader, but the user is nonetheless enrolled on them. Similarly, a left join is used to join the Assessment's module with its corresponding Module record.

A 'WHERE' clause is used to filter results and return only those matching a defined criteria. In the case of the user's assessments retrieval SQL command, the WHERE clause is used to only return assessments which the user is enrolled upon, meaning they will only see the assessments that are relevant to them. This ensures data security, as unauthorised users are unable to view irrelevant data, for which they do not have suitable permissions.

An 'ORDER BY' clause is used to order records by a defined attribute value. The ORDER BY clause was used to ensure the data was returned in an ascending order, based on assessment start date, making the data easier to manipulate and search from the backend API or frontend.

```

SELECT PanelID, PanelName, PanelImageURI, PanelBiography, PanelAssessmentID,
PanelLeaderID, CONCAT(UserTitle," ",UserFirstname," ",UserLastname) AS
PanelLeaderName

FROM Panels LEFT JOIN Users ON Panels.PanelLeaderID=Users.UserID [INNER JOIN
Userassessments ON
Panels.PanelAssessmentID=Userassessments.UserassessmentAssessmentID INNER JOIN
Assessments ON Panels.PanelAssessmentID=Assessments.AssessmentID INNER JOIN
PanelMembers ON Panels.PanelID=PanelMembers.PanelmemberPanelID]

[WHERE ${primaryWhereField}=${primaryId}]

[WHERE ${secondaryWhereField}=${secondaryId}]

[WHERE ${tertiaryWhereField}=${tertiaryId}];

```

Figure 5.24 Retrieve Panel(s) SQL Command

To retrieve one or many panel records, the SQL statement shown in Figure 5.24 was created. This statement returns a list of panel records or single panel record where the panel record's attributes are equal to the provided ID values. The retrieve panels SQL statement was chosen, due to it offering complete flexibility regarding the WHERE clause criteria, meaning this single SQL statement can be made to return panel records based on those a panel member is enrolled in, those assigned to an assessment, or those linked to a module.

Through passing the WHERE clause field and ID values to the statement, these may be modified to return different records, via the passed parameters. The SQL statements contained within the square brackets are optionally appended to the SQL command sent to the database, depending on the number of search criteria specified in the defined endpoint.

```

INSERT INTO Panels SET
PanelName=${PanelName},
PanelImageURI=${PanelImageURI},
PanelBiography=${PanelBiography},
PanelAssessmentID=${PanelAssessmentID},
PanelLeaderID=${PanelLeaderID};

```

Figure 5.25 Create New Panel SQL Command

SQL 'INSERT' statements are used to create new records within a database table, with the specified attribute values. In the statement shown in Figure 5.25, 'INSERT INTO Panels' states that that the command is expected to create a new record with the defined data into the Panels table. The 'SET' clause is used to specify the attributes and their corresponding values to be inserted. The creation of INSERT statements is crucial to allow records to be created for new data requiring storage within the database.

```
UPDATE Assessments SET
    AssessmentName="{AssessmentName}",
    AssessmentStartdate="{AssessmentStartdate}",
    AssessmentEnddate="{AssessmentEnddate}",
    AssessmentImageURI="{AssessmentImageURI}",
    AssessmentLeaderID={AssessmentLeaderID},
    AssessmentModuleID={AssessmentModuleID}
WHERE AssessmentID={id};
```

Figure 5.26 Modify Existing Assessment SQL Command

To modify data records, the 'UPDATE' SQL command is used, alongside the record's new attribute values. The SQL command shown in Figure 5.26 was created to update an assessment record's attributes, where the assessment record's AssessmentID attribute is equal to the provided ID value. 'UPDATE Assessments' states that that the command is expected to modify an existing record's attributes with the defined data in the Assessments table. The 'SET' clause is used to specify the attributes and their corresponding values to be inserted.

The 'WHERE' clause is necessary to ensure only the desired assessment record's attributes are updated. Quote marks are used to define String values to be updated, whilst no quotes are used to update numerical values. This statement requires the assessment record's full attributes, even if the attribute is not being changed. If one of the required attributes is not provided, the statement will result in an error.

```
DELETE FROM Assessments WHERE AssessmentID={id};
```

Figure 5.27 Delete Existing Assessment SQL Command

To delete data records, the 'DELETE' SQL command is used. The SQL command shown in Figure 5.27 was created to delete an assessment record where the assessment record's AssessmentID attribute is equal to the provided ID value. 'DELETE FROM Assessments' states that that the command is expected to delete an existing record within the Assessments table. The 'WHERE' clause is necessary to ensure only the desired assessment record is deleted, otherwise all records within the Assessments table would be deleted.

Data Control Language is used to grant and revoke database user permissions. In the case of the created application, no user permissions were required to be modified, as there is only a singular admin account created to manage the database. For security and to ensure data integrity, no users should be provided with database access, as all data retrieval and manipulation is performed via requests made to the backend API.

Transaction Control Language is used to define the handling of database transactions. Relational databases utilise transactions, which are formed of one or many units of work, such as SELECT or INSERT operations. If all units of work are completed successfully, the transaction is complete, although if one operation fails, the transaction must be aborted and the database must be restored to the previous consistent state, to ensure data consistency and integrity.

In the case of MySQL, transactions are set to auto commit by default, meaning upon successful completion of a transaction, the database state is automatically saved. For simplicity of database management, the default transaction settings were unchanged.

5.6.6 Conclusion

This subsection evaluated the different database platforms available, identifying MySQL as providing the most benefit to the project. The implementation of the MySQL database, used for persistently storing application data, was examined, whilst the generation of mock data and subsequent database population with the created data, was detailed. The SQL queries produced to access and manage stored database data were explored, offering a mechanism for data manipulation within the future backend API.

5.7 Backend Implementation

5.7.1 Introduction

After implementing the database, to allow application data to be persistently stored, this streamlined the creation of the backend API, necessary to allow the frontend application to securely interact with the database. The implementation of the database, alongside vast endpoint design, including the required endpoint syntaxes and returned objects, assisted in the implementation of the backend.

In this subsection, an evaluation of the different available backend API platforms will be conducted, before examining the steps required to produce Express API endpoints, which receive client requests, extract and process necessary request data, communicate with the database to perform the desired operation, and return the appropriate response data to the client.

5.7.2 Backend Platform Evaluation

After reviewing the produced endpoint syntax designs, and evaluating the technologies available to create RESTful APIs, Express was identified as still providing the most appropriate technology for backend API implementation. Although REST only defines principles an API must follow to comply with its architecture, ensuring consistency across all RESTful API services, and facilitating communication based on defined standards, it does not specify a technology to use to implement the API (Hernandez-Mendez, Scholz and Matthes, 2018). It is therefore important to ensure the technology selected is suitable for the desired application, with RESTful APIs being able to be produced in Java, using a framework such as Spring Boot, Python, using Flask or Django, or JavaScript, using Express.

Express was used to create endpoints, due to it providing an efficient framework to create RESTful APIs quickly and easily, through abstracting the necessary code to create RESTful API endpoints (Subramanian, 2019). It offers an easy-to-learn JavaScript framework for developing highly scalable, efficient and maintainable backend RESTful APIs, which runs within the Node.js environment.

Express was chosen due to its ubiquity in industry for creating servers with Node.js, whilst offering minimal plugins, to offer high-performance and robustness. As Express runs within Node.js, it may be integrated with a wealth of free libraries and packages, to support fast and efficient development of the backend, such as database connections, validation rulesets, Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS) middleware, and authentication and authorisation handlers. Due to the time constraints imposed on this project, it was deemed highly important that a range of existing functionality may be incorporated within the project, assisting with development, without requiring vast amounts of time to create a fully functional application.

The benefits of creating both the frontend and backend applications within the system using the same underlying programming language must not be understated. The development team may typically work more efficiently and obtain greater in-depth knowledge, as the same overall syntax is applied throughout the application, thus increasing familiarity across system components, and assisting with highlighting syntactical optimisation, refactoring opportunities and best practice. This also increases system maintainability, as future system developers would only require knowledge of JavaScript to support both aspects of the application.

HTTP GET, POST, PUT and DELETE requests were all handled within Express, as it enables easy integration with both the included JavaScript functions, improving efficiency when dealing with object conformance, and validation frameworks, such as joi. As explained within the Chapter 4 – Design, GET requests are used to retrieve data records, POST requests create new records within the database with the provided request body data, PUT requests update an existing data record with the new data provided within the request body, and DELETE requests delete an existing data record.

Express was used to validate API endpoint requests and, where necessary, request bodies and parameters, set the request body to the appropriate data type or input mask format to match that required by the database, make a database connection to perform the desired data storage operation, return the appropriate request data, and respond to the client with the requested or affected data, or relevant error message. It was therefore determined that Express would offer the most suitable solution to implementing the backend RESTful API.

5.7.3 Request Validation

When producing RESTful APIs, request validation must be considered, as the endpoint must only accept and handle valid data, based on the acceptable value range of the data object it supports. Data validation is critical to preventing errors from occurring during data processing, ensuring the data integrity of stored database data, and attempting to safeguard against malicious attacks on the endpoint. Although data validation may also be implemented within the database and frontend application, request validation is key to ensuring the validity of data before it is transmitted to be stored within the database.

As the application utilises a separate frontend and backend architecture, and the backend API endpoints are publicly exposed and accessible via an associated URL, it is possible for API requests to be made via an alternative client to the intended frontend React application. Whilst the frontend application's validation seeks to ensure the form-submitted data is acceptable before passing the data to the backend, if requests are made directly to the backend, or bugs are present in the frontend validation, meaning it does not correctly validate all inputted data, invalid data may be received by the backend.

Alternatively, in the case of the backend API being utilised by a third-party user interface, it must not be assumed that the third-party frontend would successfully implement all necessary validation. It must also be noted that the current database implemented, MySQL, does not support CHECK constraints, thus although data may be validated against data types, lengths and referential integrity, values cannot be checked against an acceptable range. It is therefore important to employ full validation within the backend, to ensure all stored values are acceptable for the defined object.

Validation may be implemented using third-party validation libraries, imported within the backend application using npm (npm, no date), or through the creation of application-specific validation ruleset methods. Whilst custom validation ruleset methods offer increased performance, there are potential bug and security risks within their use, as the developer may fail to implement a reliable validator, or miss crucial validation rulesets for a value.

As the backend is exposed, increasing its vulnerability, security and reliability are more valued than overall performance, therefore a trustworthy third-party validation library, joi, was used. The joi validation library offers a range of validation functions, which may be appended to produce a pipeline, including data type, length, acceptable values, regex and required, to validate data against a defined object schema (joi, no date).

```
import joi from "joi";
const assessmentIdSchema = joi.number().integer().min(1).max(99999).required();
```

Figure 5.28 Assessment ID JOI Validation Ruleset

```
const getAssessmentsController = async (req, res, variant, whereField) => {
  const id = req.params.pid; // Undefined for /api/assessments endpoint
  // Validate request
  if (variant !== 'assessments' || id) { //if /api/assessments then nullable
    const { error } = assessmentIdSchema.validate(id);
    if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});
  }
}
```

Figure 5.29 getAssessmentsController() Function ID Value Validation

All implemented endpoints use joi validation to ensure any request ID values are of type integer, have a minimum value of 1, and are required, where appropriate for the defined endpoint, as shown in Figure 5.28. Request ID validation rulesets may be called from controllers, passing the ID value to be validated, and returning an appropriate response, should the ID be invalid, as shown in Figure 5.29.

```
const getAssessmentsUsersController = async (req, res, variant, whereField) =>
{
  const id = req.params.pid;
  // Validate request
  const { error } = assessmentIdSchema.validate(id);
  if (error) return res.status(400).json({message: reportIdError(error)});
}
```

Figure 5.30 getAssessmentsUsersController() Function Mandatory ID Value Validation

Certain endpoints require an ID value, such as the `getAssessmentsUsersController()` function shown in Figure 5.30, otherwise the query would be unsuccessful in identifying which records to return. In this case of the endpoint used to return a user's assessments, the lack of an ID value would prevent the database from locating the user, for which to return their assessments.

Should a user send an incorrect ID to an endpoint as part of a request, the validation will return the appropriate error message to the user. This increases the scalability and performance of the API, as queries are only run on the database if they are valid, else an error is returned without the database requiring to be accessed. Furthermore, this protects the database from receiving invalid or potentially harmful data, as such data is filtered prior to being sent to the database.

```

const assessmentSchema = joi.object({
  AssessmentID: joi.number().integer().min(1).max(99999),
  AssessmentName: joi.string().min(1).max(75).required(),
  AssessmentStartdate: joi.string().regex(/^(?:\d{4})-(?:\d{2})-(?:\d{2})T(?:\d{2}):(?:\d{2}):(?:\d{2})(?:\.\d*)?Z$/).required(),
  AssessmentEnddate: joi.string().regex(/^(?:\d{4})-(?:\d{2})-(?:\d{2})T(?:\d{2}):(?:\d{2}):(?:\d{2})(?:\.\d*)?Z$/).required(),
  AssessmentImageURI: joi.string().uri().max(500),
  AssessmentLeaderID: joi.number().integer().min(1).max(99999),
  AssessmentModuleID: joi.number().integer().min(1).max(99999).required(),
  AssessmentCreateddate: joi.string().regex(/^(?:\d{4})-(?:\d{2})-(?:\d{2})T(?:\d{2}):(?:\d{2}):(?:\d{2})(?:\.\d*)?Z$/).required(),
}).unknown(false);

```

Figure 5.31 Assessment Object Schema JOI Validation Rulesets

POST and PUT endpoints must accept a request body JSON object, containing values to insert against a new or existing data record within the database. The joi validation framework allows an object schema to be produced, as shown in Figure 5.31, mapping the validation rulesets to the object attribute values. Incoming objects may be validated against the defined schema, increasing code maintainability.

Figure 5.31 demonstrates the joi validation object schema for an assessment object, utilised by PUT and POST `/api/assessments` requests. The `AssessmentID` value must be of type integer between 1 and 99999, whilst the `AssessmentName` must be of type string, between 1 and 75 characters in length, and is required to be present in the body of all requests to the endpoint.

The `AssessmentStartdate`, `AssessmentEnddate` and `AssessmentCreateddate` values must all be of type string, following the appropriate ISO 8601 date format as determined by a regex rule, and are required. The `AssessmentImageURI` must be of type string, be in a URL format, and be a maximum length of 500 characters. The `AssessmentLeaderID` and `AssessmentModuleID` values must be of type integer, between 1 and 99999, and the `AssessmentModuleID` value is required.

```

const postAssessmentsController = async (req, res) => {
  // Validate request
  if (req.body) {
    const { error } = assessmentSchema.validate(req.body, { abortEarly: false });
    if (error) return res.status(400).json({ message: reportErrors(error) });
  }
  if (!req.body) {
    return res.status(400).json({ message: 'Error - request body null' });
  }
}

```

Figure 5.32 postAssessmentsController() Function Request Body Validation

The created POST and PUT endpoints utilise created joi object schemas, in order to ensure the request body contains the appropriate data types and is of a suitable format to be stored in the database, such as the `postAssessmentsController()` function, as shown in Figure 5.32.

```
const reportIdError = (error) => `Request ID  
${(error.details[0].message).slice(8)} `;  
  
const reportErrors = (errors) => errors.details.map((detail) =>  
detail.message.replaceAll('"', ''));
```

Figure 5.33 reportIdError() and reportErrors() Validation Functions

The `reportIdError()` and `reportErrors()` functions, as shown in Figure 5.33, serve to return any joi request data validation error messages into a readable format, to be returned by the endpoint. These are called from within the controller, to ensure the endpoint response message is understandable, as shown in Figure 5.32.

The joi validation framework also escapes received HTML, converting characters within valid HTML into HTML entities. This ensures any HTML received within the request body, to be inserted into the database, will not be directly rendered as HTML elements within the frontend webpage, when retrieved from the database during subsequent GET requests. Malicious attacks may encompass sending valid HTML to an endpoint, to be stored within the database.

If the value is retained as HTML during database storage, and returned as such by the endpoint, the frontend application will render the HTML within the outputted browser view. Such renderings may include scripts, including JavaScript redirects, known as cross-site scripting (XSS) attacks, damaging the reputation and user experience of the website, and potentially causing harm to website visitors. The use of joi validation prior to storing data within the database, ensures HTML may not be stored in its raw form, thus preventing such attacks from occurring.

This validation ensures the endpoint can quickly determine if a request is suitable to be stored in the database, before sending a request to the database to execute the SQL query. This lowers the request overhead on the database, increasing its performance and ensuring it can likely handle a higher number of requests, whilst also returning an error message faster than the time required to execute the query on the database. The validation ruleset protects the database from receiving invalid or potentially harmful data, or storing inconsistent or unsuitable data, as this is filtered prior to being sent to the database to be stored.

5.7.4 Data Access

To successfully locate and return relevant records to the purpose of the endpoint, data access from the data storage medium is required. The developed application uses the MySQL database as the storage medium, which may be queried using SQL statements to perform CRUD operations on the stored data. To connect the backend API with the MySQL database, a third-party library such as `mysql2` may be used, explained within subsection 5.7.7 – Database Connection.

```

const buildAssessmentsSelectSql = (id, variant, whereField) => {
    let sql = '';
    const table = 'Assessments LEFT JOIN Users ON
Assessments.AssessmentLeaderID=Users.UserID LEFT JOIN Modules ON
Assessments.AssessmentModuleID=Modules.ModuleID';
    const fields =
['AssessmentID', 'AssessmentName', 'AssessmentStartdate', 'AssessmentEnddate', 'Ass
essmentImageURI', 'AssessmentLeaderID', 'AssessmentModuleID', 'ModuleCode AS
AssessmentModuleCode', 'ModuleName AS AssessmentModuleName', 'CONCAT(UserTitle, "
",UserFirstname," ",UserLastname) AS AssessmentLeaderName'];
    const extendedTable = `Userassessments INNER JOIN ${table} ON
Userassessments.UserassessmentAssessmentID = Assessments.AssessmentID`;
    (variant === 'users') ? sql = `SELECT ${fields} FROM ${extendedTable}` :
sql = `SELECT ${fields} FROM ${table}`;
    if (id) sql += ` WHERE ${whereField}=${id}`;
    return sql;
};

```

Figure 5.34 buildAssessmentsSelectSql() Function to Create SQL for Retrieving Assessment Records

To aid maintainability, the backend API data access methods should not be closely coupled to a specific data storage mechanism, such as an SQL-based database, as should the storage method be migrated in future updates, this would require significant re-write of the backend application. In this case, a buildSelectSql() function was created for each data retrieval method, as shown in Figure 5.34.

```

const getAssessmentsController = async (req, res, variant, whereField) => {
    ...
    // Access Data
    const sql = buildAssessmentsSelectSql(id, variant, whereField);
    const { isSuccess, result, message } = await read(sql);
    // Response
    isSuccess ? res.status(200).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});
};

```

Figure 5.34 getAssessmentsController() Function Calling buildAssessmentsSelectSql() Function

This buildSelectSql() function may be called to construct the necessary database SQL statement, in order to obtain the requested data, and may be modified to handle data access from an alternative source, without requiring the backend application structure to change. Figure 5.35 shows the getAssessmentsController() function calling the buildAssessmentsSelectSql() function, to build the required SQL statement to retrieve assessment records.

Depending on the data required to be returned by the endpoint, a suitable SQL statement was constructed using a prepared statement, before being sent to the database to be executed. The SQL statements constructed are examined thoroughly within subsection 5.6.5 – Database Queries.

Through using SQL prepared statements, this prevents SQL injection attacks from occurring. SQL injection attacks involve transmitting valid SQL commands within an endpoint request body attribute value, which would be executed directly on the database, potentially causing harm or unprivileged access to the database and its stored data.

The backend uses SQL prepared statements, which are valid SQL statements, containing placeholders represented by the required conformance object attributes, with which the values are added to the query upon execution, and treated literally, not as part of the SQL statement for execution itself. This ensures any SQL commands received by the endpoint would not be executed directly on the database, thus protecting against SQL injection attacks.

```
const table = 'Assessments';

const fields =
['AssessmentName', 'AssessmentStartdate', 'AssessmentEnddate', 'AssessmentImageURI',
'AssessmentLeaderID', 'AssessmentModuleID'];

let sql = `INSERT INTO ${table} SET
    ${fields[0]}="${conformanceObject['AssessmentName']}",
    ${fields[1]}="${conformanceObject['AssessmentStartdate']}",
    ${fields[2]}="${conformanceObject['AssessmentEnddate']}",
    ${fields[3]}="${conformanceObject['AssessmentImageURI']}",
    ${fields[4]}=${conformanceObject['AssessmentLeaderID']},
    ${fields[5]}=${conformanceObject['AssessmentModuleID']}`;
```

Figure 5.35 postAssessmentsController() Function Prepared Statements

In the case of a POST or PUT endpoint, the appropriate SQL prepared statement is constructed and passed the conformance object values, before being executed on the database server, as shown in Figure 5.35.

```

try {
    const status = await database.query(sql);

    const table = 'Assessments LEFT JOIN Users ON
Assessments.AssessmentLeaderID=Users.UserID LEFT JOIN Modules ON
Assessments.AssessmentModuleID=Modules.ModuleID';

    const whereField = 'AssessmentID';

    const fields =
['AssessmentID', 'AssessmentName', 'AssessmentStartdate', 'AssessmentEnddate', 'Ass
essmentImageURI', 'AssessmentLeaderID', 'AssessmentModuleID', 'ModuleCode AS
AssessmentModuleCode', 'ModuleName AS AssessmentModuleName', 'CONCAT(UserTitle, "
",UserFirstname, " ",UserLastname) AS AssessmentLeaderName'];

    const extendedTable = `${table}`;

    const extendedFields = `${fields}`;

    let recoverRecord = `SELECT ${extendedFields} FROM ${extendedTable}`;
    recoverRecord += ` WHERE ${whereField}=${status[0].insertId}`;

    [result] = await database.query(recoverRecord);

    if (result.length === 0) message = 'Failed to recover inserted record';
    else {
        isSuccess = true;
        message = 'Record successfully recovered';
    }
}

catch (error) {
    message = `Failed to execute query: ${error.message}`;
}

// Response
isSuccess ? res.status(201).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});

```

Figure 5.36 postAssessmentsController() Function Inserted Record Retrieval

For a POST request, upon successful insertion of a new record, a further SQL SELECT prepared statement is constructed to retrieve the record inserted into the database, and thus confirm that the record has been successfully added.

```

try {
    const status = await database.query(sql);
    if (status[0].affectedRows === 0) message = `Failed to update record
    ${id}`;
    const table = 'Assessments LEFT JOIN Users ON
    Assessments.AssessmentLeaderID=Users.UserID LEFT JOIN Modules ON
    Assessments.AssessmentModuleID=Modules.ModuleID';
    const whereField = 'AssessmentID';
    const fields =
    ['AssessmentID', 'AssessmentName', 'AssessmentStartdate', 'AssessmentEnddate', 'Ass
    essmentImageURI', 'AssessmentLeaderID', 'AssessmentModuleID', 'ModuleCode AS
    AssessmentModuleCode', 'ModuleName AS AssessmentModuleName', 'CONCAT(UserTitle, "
    ", UserFirstname, " ", UserLastname) AS AssessmentLeaderName'];
    const extendedTable = `${table}`;
    const extendedFields = `${fields}`;
    let recoverRecord = `SELECT ${extendedFields} FROM ${extendedTable}`;
    recoverRecord += ` WHERE ${whereField}=${id}`;
    [result] = await database.query(recoverRecord);
    if (result.length === 0) message = 'Failed to recover updated record';
    else {
        isSuccess = true;
        message = 'Record successfully recovered';
    }
}
catch (error) {
    message = `Failed to execute query: ${error.message}`;
}
// Response
isSuccess ? res.status(200).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});

```

Figure 5.37 postAssessmentsController() Function Inserted Record Retrieval

After performing a query operation on the database, a status object is returned containing detailed information regarding the query execution, and any requested records. This object contains an attribute storing the number of affected rows, as shown in Figure 5.37. In the case of a PUT request, this should be equal to one if the single existing record has been successfully located and updated with the new attribute values.

5.7.5 Data Conformance

Data conformance involves manipulating retrieved request data into a suitable format to be stored within the database, and converting returned database data into a valid, best-practice JSON format to be returned to the client. Data storage mediums, most notably SQL-based relational databases, accept data values in a specific format, as defined by the database engine, implementation of SQL, and current database settings. Although most JSON object values are understood by the database, including string and integer values, more complex data types such as dates, require conversion to be suitably understood by the database, backend and frontend applications.

Within the implemented GET request endpoints, conformance was considered, although there was no database-retrieved data that required conversion into a JavaScript format. Due to the database object conversion performed by the `mysql2` database connection library, all data returned from the database was already in a JavaScript format, which allowed it to be converted into a JSON object to be returned by the endpoint.

Theoretically, the only fields that may have required conversion would have been attributes such as `AssessmentStartdate` and `AssessmentEnddate` from the `Assessments` table, although the database returned these in ISO 8601 format, which is recognised as best practice when returning dates from RESTful APIs. All other attributes are stored as `VARCHAR` data types in the database, which automatically convert to `String` values when returned to the JavaScript backend API. Consequently, conformance was not required during this aspect of the endpoint implementation.

```
const putAssessmentsController = async (req, res) => {
  ...
  // Object conformance
  const conformanceObject = assessmentConformance(req.body);
// Build SQL
  const table = 'Assessments';
  const whereField = 'AssessmentID';
  const fields =
['AssessmentName', 'AssessmentStartdate', 'AssessmentEnddate', 'AssessmentImageURI', 'AssessmentLeaderID', 'AssessmentModuleID'];
  let sql = `UPDATE ${table} SET
    ${fields[0]}="${conformanceObject['AssessmentName']}",
    ${fields[1]}="${conformanceObject['AssessmentStartdate']}",
    ${fields[2]}="${conformanceObject['AssessmentEnddate']}",
    ${fields[3]}="${conformanceObject['AssessmentImageURI']}",
    ${fields[4]}=${conformanceObject['AssessmentLeaderID']},
    ${fields[5]}=${conformanceObject['AssessmentModuleID']}`;
  sql += ` WHERE ${whereField}=${id}`
```

Figure 5.38 `putAssessmentsController()` Function Calling `assessmentConformance()` Function

Within the implemented POST endpoint, conformance was considered, as there was JSON data retrieved from the request body that required conversion into a format understood by the database. POST request body date values, including the aforementioned AssessmentStartdate and AssessmentEnddate values, are received by the endpoint in an ISO 8601 date format, as defined by API date handling best practices. However, this date structure is in an inappropriate format to be inserted into the database, therefore the retrieved value requires conversion into an SQL-compatible format. This data manipulation is achieved through calling the assessmentConformance() function, passing the received body object to be manipulated, as shown in Figure 5.38.

```
const assessmentConformance = (obj) => {  
  return {  
    ...obj,  
    AssessmentStartdate: obj.AssessmentStartdate.replace('T', ' ').slice(0,  
19),  
    AssessmentEnddate: obj.AssessmentEnddate.replace('T', ' ').slice(0, 19)  
  }  
}
```

Figure 5.39 assessmentConformance() Function Data Manipulation

The createAssessmentConformance function is called with the request body object, which uses the spread operator to return a new object with the existing object rows, as shown in Figure 5.39. The AssessmentStartdate and AssessmentEnddate values are then overwritten with updated values in an appropriate format, through calling the .replace('T', ' ') and .slice(0, 19) methods on the date values.

Within the provided date, the 'T' must be removed from between the date and time in the ISO date, whilst the '.000Z' must also be removed from the end of the date string, to convert the date into a format decodable by the MySQL database. This object is then returned to the postAssessmentsController, which uses the new object's values within an SQL INSERT INTO prepared statement, to create a new assessment record within the database, as shown in Figure 5.38.

All other attributes are sent as string or integer data types in the request body, which automatically convert to INT or VARCHAR values when inserted into the database, as these are natively supported by the SQL database. Consequently, conformance was not required for these values.

5.7.6 Returned Responses

RESTful API returned responses should follow the specifications outlined by best practice, which states an appropriate HTTP status code and resource object should be returned to the client, upon receiving an endpoint request. This is used to both inform the requesting client of the status of, or actions taken as a result of, their request, and to impose security, aiding in preventing unauthorised requests which could compromise the backend application.

As such, all requests made to the backend API invoke a suitable response, containing a HTTP status code and JSON object, which aims to provide useful feedback to the client. In the case of all endpoints, any provided request parameter ID or body value is validated using the joi validation library, as discussed in subsection 5.7.3 – Request Validation.

```
const id = req.params.pid;
// Validate request
const { error } = assessmentIdSchema.validate(id);
if (error) return res.status(400).json({message: reportIdError(error)});
```

Figure 5.40 Request ID Validation

In the case of a provided value being invalid, or a required attribute value being omitted, a HTTP status code of 400 is returned to the client, alongside a constructed JSON error message, informing of the error(s) within their provided request value, as shown in Figure 5.40. This ensures the client is aware of the API's inability to fulfil the request, due to it being a 'Bad Request' with an invalid request value, meaning they may decide to re-send their request with valid request or attribute values.

```
if (req.body) {
    const { error } = panelSchema.validate(req.body, { abortEarly: false
});
    if (error) return res.status(400).json({ message: reportErrors(error)
});
}
if (!req.body) {
    return res.status(400).json({message: 'Error - request body null'});
}
```

Figure 5.41 Request Body Validation

POST and PUT HTTP methods must receive a request body containing the attribute values to be inserted or updated within the database. If no request body is sent with a POST or PUT request, the request is unable to be fulfilled within the database, as no object values are present. In this case, the endpoint will return a HTTP status code of 400, with a JSON error message, informing the client that the request body is null, as shown in Figure 5.41.

```

const read = async (selectSql) => {
  try {
    const [result] = await database.query(selectSql);
    return (result.length === 0)
      ? { isSuccess: false, result: null, message: 'No record(s) found' }
      : { isSuccess: true, result, message: 'Record(s) successfully
recovered' };
  }
  catch (error) {
    return { isSuccess: false, result: null, message: `Failed to execute
query: ${error.message}` };
  }
};
...
const { isSuccess, result, message } = await read(sql);
// Response
isSuccess ? res.status(200).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});

```

Figure 5.42 GET Endpoint Response

If a GET endpoint request passes data validation, the associated SQL statements will be executed within the database. If no records are found, a HTTP status code of 400 will be returned, alongside a JSON error message informing the user that no records were found, as shown in Figure 5.42. In the case of an error whilst attempting to execute the SQL statement on the database, a HTTP status code of 400 will be returned, accompanied by the error message returned by the database or mysql2 library. Should the request be executed successfully within the database, and records returned, a HTTP status code of 200 'OK' will be returned, alongside a JSON-encoded object array of retrieved database records.

```

let isSuccess = false;

let message = '';

let result = null;

try {

    const status = await database.query(sql);

    const table = 'Panels LEFT JOIN Assessments ON
Panels.PanelAssessmentID=Assessments.AssessmentID LEFT JOIN Users ON
Panels.PanelLeaderID=Users.UserID LEFT JOIN Modules ON
Assessments.AssessmentModuleID=Modules.ModuleID';

    const whereField = 'PanelID';

    const fields =
['PanelID', 'PanelName', 'PanelImageURI', 'PanelBiography', 'PanelAssessmentID', 'AssessmentName AS PanelAssessmentName', 'AssessmentModuleID AS
PanelAssessmentModuleID', 'ModuleCode AS PanelAssessmentModuleCode', 'ModuleName AS PanelAssessmentModuleName', 'PanelLeaderID', 'CONCAT(UserTitle, "
", UserFirstname, " ", UserLastname) AS PanelLeaderName'];

    const extendedTable = `${table}`;

    const extendedFields = `${fields}`;

    let recoverRecord = `SELECT ${extendedFields} FROM ${extendedTable}`;

    recoverRecord += ` WHERE ${whereField}=${status[0].insertId}`;

    [result] = await database.query(recoverRecord);

    if (result.length === 0) message = 'Failed to recover inserted record';
    else {

        isSuccess = true;

        message = 'Record successfully recovered';

    }

}

catch (error) {

    message = `Failed to execute query: ${error.message}`;

}

// Response

isSuccess ? res.status(201).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});

```

Figure 5.43 POST Endpoint Response

After inserting a new record with the POST request body's retrieved request attribute values, the database is queried with the returned ID value of the inserted record, to retrieve the created record from the database. If the record failed to be recovered from the database, or an error occurred whilst attempting to execute the query, a HTTP 400 status code is returned, alongside the JSON-encoded error message, as shown in Figure 5.43. In the case of the new record being recovered successfully, a HTTP 201 'Created' status code is returned, informing the client that the request was successful and a new record has been added, alongside the JSON-encoded recovered object.

```

let isSuccess = false;

let message = '';
let result = null;

try {
    const status = await database.query(sql);
    if (status[0].affectedRows === 0) message = `Failed to update record
${id}`;

    const table = 'Modules LEFT JOIN Users ON
Modules.ModuleLeaderID=Users.UserID';

    const whereField = 'ModuleID';

    const fields =
['ModuleID', 'ModuleCode', 'ModuleName', 'ModuleImageURI', 'ModuleLevel', 'ModuleDes
cription', 'ModuleLeaderID', 'CONCAT(Users.UserTitle, " ", Users.UserFirstname, "
", Users.UserLastname) AS ModuleLeaderName', 'Users.UserEmail AS
ModuleLeaderEmail'];

    const extendedTable = `${table}`;
    const extendedFields = `${fields}`;
    let recoverRecord = `SELECT ${extendedFields} FROM ${extendedTable}`;
    recoverRecord += ` WHERE ${whereField}=${id}`;
    [result] = await database.query(recoverRecord);
    if (result.length === 0) message = 'Failed to recover updated record';
    else {
        isSuccess = true;
        message = 'Record successfully recovered';
    }
}

catch (error) {
    message = `Failed to execute query: ${error.message}`;
}

// Response
isSuccess ? res.status(200).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});

```

Figure 5.44 PUT Endpoint Response

Upon updating an existing record with the retrieved request body attribute values from a PUT request, if the number of affected rows is equal to zero, meaning no database records were modified, or an error occurred whilst attempting to execute the query, a HTTP status code of 400 is returned, alongside the JSON-encoded error message, as shown in Figure 5.44. If the record was successfully updated, the database is queried with the provided ID value of the record to update, to retrieve the updated record from the database, with a HTTP status code of 200 being returned, informing the client that the request was successful and the record has been updated, alongside the JSON-encoded recovered object.

```

let isSuccess = false;

let message = '';
let result = null;

try {
    const status = await database.query(sql);
    if (status[0].affectedRows === 0) message = `Failed to delete record
${id}`;
    else {
        isSuccess = true;
        message = 'Record successfully deleted';
    }
}

catch (error) {
    message = `Failed to execute query: ${error.message}`;
}

// Response

isSuccess ? res.status(200).json({message}) :
res.status(400).json({message});

```

Figure 5.45 DELETE Endpoint Response

After deleting an existing record from a DELETE request, if the number of affected rows is equal to zero, meaning no database records were deleted, or an error occurred whilst attempting to execute the query, a HTTP status code of 400 is returned, alongside the JSON-encoded error message. If the record was successfully deleted, a HTTP status code of 200 is returned, informing the client that the request was successful, alongside a JSON-encoded message detailing that the record has been deleted.

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
<meta charset="utf-8">
<title>Error</title>
</head>
<body>
<pre>Cannot GET /api/usertypes</pre>
</body>
</html>

```

Figure 5.46 Undefined Endpoint HTML Response

Figure 5.47 Undefined Endpoint Status Code and Rendered HTML Response

If an endpoint has not been defined and created within the backend, and a request is made to the unimplemented endpoint, a HTTP status code of 404 'Not Found' is returned, alongside a HTML webpage informing the user that the endpoint they have requested does not exist, as shown in Figure 5.46 and Figure 5.47.

The returned HTTP status codes and JSON-encoded objects and messages are crucial to informing the client of the status of their request, and any specific errors within the request or its execution. This enables users to better diagnose causes of failure within their use of the application, aids in developers troubleshooting bugs or errors, and enhances security of the API, through informing users of inappropriate requests. By adhering to HTTP and RESTful API conventions and best practices, the backend API has increased code maintainability, and may be easily utilised and called by third-party frontends, who will receive expected API behaviour.

5.7.7 Database Connection

The backend API currently utilises an SQL-based relational database, MySQL, as a persistent data storage medium. The Express backend API must interact with the database, to retrieve, create, update and delete data records, based on incoming client requests made to its endpoints. The Express connection to the MySQL database may be implemented manually, although this would require extensive knowledge of both JavaScript web connections and the remote access to manage MySQL databases.

As such, it was decided that a third-party library, mysql2 with the provided promise wrapper, would be used (Sidorov, 2023). This allows MySQL database connections to be easily created and managed, whilst using JavaScript promises to offer asynchronous database connections, thus increasing performance, available request throughput and scalability.

Figure 5.48 Database Connection Directory Structure

To reduce coupling to a MySQL database, the backend API was structured with the database connection and configuration files remaining separate from the application logic, as shown in Figure 5.48. As such, if the persistent storage medium were to be migrated to a different technology, only the connection and storage interaction methods would require modification.

```
// Imports -----
import mysql from 'mysql2/promise';
import { dbConfig } from './databaseConfig.js';
// Database Connection -----
let database = null;
try {
  database = await mysql.createConnection(dbConfig);
}
catch (error) {
  console.log(`Error creating database connection: ${error.message}`);
  process.exit();
}
export default database;
```

Figure 5.49 Database Connection Using MySQL2 with Promise Wrapper

The database object variable is initialised, and a database connection is attempted with the defined database configuration object, containing the database access credentials, as shown in Figure 5.49. If a database connection cannot be established, the error is displayed within the API console, and the application stops running, to increase power efficiency, as it cannot provide any useful purpose without accessing the persistent data storage. The database object is exported, to allow it to be connected to and utilised by other files, to run their necessary queries.

```
export const dbConfig = {
  database: process.env.DB_NAME || 'collabase',
  port: process.env.DB_PORT || 3306,
  host: process.env.DB_HOST || 'localhost',
  user: process.env.DB_USER || 'root',
  password: process.env.DB_PSWD || '',
  namedPlaceholders: true
};
```

Figure 5.50 Database Configuration Object

The database config file contains the database configuration and access credentials, including its name, port number, user and password, enabling the database to be located and a connection to be made, as shown in Figure 5.50. Through including database configuration settings in a separate file, these may be modified to allow the application to use a different SQL-based database, without requiring any other application code to be altered, improving maintainability.

All database config attributes first check if the associated operating system environment variable is defined, else the default configuration values are used. Environment variables were used with a view to backend API deployment, in which the application would first attempt to utilise the defined database configuration settings, before using the default credentials in the case such settings were not present. Upon deployment, the database configuration could then be easily modified, through changing the associated environment variable values, without requiring modification to any backend API code.

```
const [result] = await database.query(selectSql);
```

Figure 5.51 MySQL2 Database Query Execution

As shown in Figure 5.51, SQL queries may be run on the database through using the query() method and passing the SQL statement to be executed.

5.7.8 Backend Structure

Initially, much of the backend API code was contained within the main application starting file, app.js. Within the app.js file, the Express app and associated middleware were configured, the Express server was started, and the endpoint routing was defined. This file also contained the controllers to validate requests, build SQL statements, execute queries, and return responses for each endpoint.

Until further HTTP request types, such as POST, PUT and DELETE requests, were implemented, the code was not able to be definitively refactored, as any such refactoring could have hindered the creation of future endpoints to handle these requests.

```
// Configure express app -----
const app = new express();
// Configure middleware -----
app.use(function (req, res, next) {
    res.header("Access-Control-Allow-Origin", "*");
    res.header("Access-Control-Allow-Headers", "Origin, X-Requested-With, Content-Type, Accept");
    next();
});
app.disable('x-powered-by');
app.use(cors({ origin: '*' }));
app.use(express.json());
```

Figure 5.52 Express Application and Middleware Initialisation

After initialising the app variable, to contain a new Express object, the app.use() function is used to provide the Express application with the middleware and configuration settings required to perform its desired operations, as shown in Figure 5.52. By default, Express does not allow Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS), meaning requests originating from the same machine as the Express server is running on, are blocked.

During development, all requests originate from the same machine as the Express server, meaning CORS must be enabled, as previously discussed. As the endpoint will receive and return JSON-encoded objects, the `express.json()` middleware must be included, to encode and decode the required request and response bodies.

```
// Start server -----  
const PORT = process.env.PORT || 5000;  
app.listen(PORT, () => console.log(`Server started on port ${PORT}`));
```

Figure 5.53 Express Application Starting Code

The backend server must then be started, to listen for incoming requests on the defined or default port, with a callback function informing the developer of the server starting via the console, as shown in Figure 5.53.

```
app.get('/api/groups', (req, res) =>  
  getGroupsController(req, res, 'groups', 'GroupID'));  
app.post('/api/groups', postGroupsController);  
app.put('/api/groups/:id', putGroupsController);  
app.delete('/api/groups/:id', deleteGroupsController);
```

Figure 5.54 GET, POST, PUT and DELETE Endpoint Definitions

For each required endpoint, the HTTP method must be defined, using the associated `app` function, such as `get()` or `post()`, as shown in Figure 5.54. The function must receive the resource location URL, with any ID values being represented by a colon, followed by the chosen name of the ID value, for retrieval in the controller function. A callback function with request and response parameters to the associated controller function must be provided, to handle the received request.

Each controller contains validation of the received body or parameter data, where appropriate, performs any necessary conformance, and executes the prepared SQL data access method. The results are retrieved from the database and an appropriate HTTP status code and body is returned to the client, in the associated HTTP response.

Figure 5.55 Backend API Directory and File Structure

All conformance, validation object schemas, and the `reportError()` and `reportErrors()` functions, are contained within separate files, located within their associated directory, as shown in Figure 5.55. This enables conformance and validation rulesets to be easily located and modified, without affecting the underlying backend API logic.

5.7.9 Conclusion

This subsection evaluated the different backend platforms available, identifying Express as providing the most benefit to the project. The implementation of the backend API, used for interacting with the database, was examined throughout the implementation of its necessary components. Request validation was explored, identifying the necessity to ensure stored data is valid, providing security and data integrity.

The data access methods between the backend API and database were examined, alongside the creation of data conformance functions, to translate data between suitable database and request body formats. Consideration was taken to ensure the backend API returned appropriate responses, providing security and suitable client feedback. The connection to the database, to provide the persistent data storage functionality, was explored, as was the structure of the backend API, to promote maintainability.

5.8 Frontend Implementation

5.8.1 Introduction

Following the implementation of the backend API, to facilitate secure interaction with the persistent database storage medium, the frontend application was developed, to provide the application's users with the tool's desired functionality. The implementation of the backend API, in addition to copious wireframing at varying degrees of fidelity, aided in the frontend implementation, from both design and required component creation perspectives.

This subsection will evaluate the different frontend platforms available, before detailing the creation of the frontend web application, including the construction of reusable and bespoke components, use of existing components. The handling of the corresponding component state with hooks will be discussed, alongside form input validation, including data conformance, required to communicate with the backend API. The frontend application's page navigation, configuration, and styling will be examined, alongside the frontend structure and refactoring undertaken.

5.8.2 Frontend Platform Implementation

After reviewing the created wireframes, and analysing the available technologies for the production of websites, React remained the most suitable frontend technology for frontend implementation. As the backend API returns JSON objects, these may be appropriately converted and handled by the majority of frontend application technologies, due to its common support.

Furthermore, all web-compatible technologies must ultimately return a series of HTML-encoded data, likely combined with JavaScript and CSS, as these are the only languages universally supported by web browsers. The selection of a suitable frontend technology is therefore crucial to the success of the application, with traditional PHP, modern JavaScript-based frameworks, such as React, Vue or Angular, or general-purpose programming languages, including Java or Python's PyScript library, being available.

React was used to produce the frontend web application, due to its component-based approach to web development, minimising code duplication and increasing potential application development time (Boduch, 2017). Through creating reusable components, which may be passed props to modify their behaviour and increase reusability, the frontend application's development may be accelerated (Boduch, 2017). Upon all required reusable components being produced, components only require placing in the appropriate location on new pages, to quickly develop a series of new application webpages, offering the desired functionality.

React utilises a JSX-based JavaScript framework, for the creation of scalable and maintainable single-page applications, which run within the Node.js environment (Danielsson, no date). A significant factor in the use of React was its increasing presence in industry, with many websites opting for a React-based approach. As with Express, React runs within Node.js, which supports a plethora of free libraries, including those providing existing components, data or component handler functionality, and styling.

As previously described, the imposed project time constraints require the application's development to be expedited, to produce a fully functional application, therefore the use of existing libraries is necessary to support the implementation. With varying browser support for 'experimental' HTML elements and JavaScript features, including datetime pickers, it is often necessary to import components which are guaranteed compatible with all web browsers.

As one of the project's non-functional requirements highlights the importance of application compatibility, the creation of such components would require significant amounts of time to implement a suitable workaround to particular browsers lacking support for HTML elements, thus detracting from the functionality available to be implemented in the project's short duration. Consequently, the ability to import existing, cross-browser compatible components became an essential requirement for the frontend application, as unlike the backend API, which offers guaranteed support across all browsers, due to the JSON-encoded data it returns, the frontend application may present browser compatibility concerns. As the development team is unable to manage the type of device the user accesses the frontend from, the available imported React components provide the most feasible solution.

As outlined previously, the advantages offered by utilising the same technology for both the frontend and backend application creation is significant, with developers gaining a better understanding and familiarity with the language, and there being the potential for increased application maintainability.

All user interactions with the created tool occur within the frontend React application, therefore input forms, to create and edit stored system objects, output reports, to view lists of objects, and object details reports, to provide an expanded view of an object's information, were created. The frontend handled all user story functionality, providing an easy to use, user-friendly graphical interface for users to manage and view the contained database data. It serves to send GET requests to the backend API, to retrieve object information to display on-screen, POST and PUT requests, to create and edit objects based on the user's inputted form data respectively, and DELETE requests to delete existing objects. It was subsequently decided that React provided the most appropriate frontend application solution.

5.8.3 Reusable React Components Creation

One of the foundational principles of React is its facilitation of the creation of reusable components. Reusable components are user-creatable React elements, typically formed of a viewable user interface widget, with its own integrated behaviour and styling. In recent best practice, React reusable components are declared as functions, previously having been declared as classes, accepting props, which allow any necessary data or behaviour to be passed to the component, thus providing its reusability.

Reusable components allow the same user interface element to be used throughout a React application, without repeating the code definition for each use, thus increasing code maintainability and updatability. Rather than having to modify multiple instances of the same code, across different pages of the application, changes need only be made to the global reusable component, and will automatically traverse to all its implementations and uses.

The creation of reusable components significantly increases the speed at which a consistent user interface, formed of multiple of the same types of components, may be constructed, benefitting this project with a limited timescale. Upon definition of a reusable component, all further uses only require the importation and passing of any necessary props, to reuse the component across multiple locations, thus reducing development time.

React supports the wrapping of components within other components, known as component nesting, to provide increases in component reusability. With this method, a very genericised component may be produced, with subsequent entity-specific components being created formed of the child genericised component with an entity-specific parent wrapper component, all exported as a new, singular component.

In such cases, the generic component may be used to extract core behaviour across all entities and instantiations of the component, with each entity-specific component being implemented across multiple locations throughout the application. Rather than repeat the generic component's behaviour and implementation across all entity-specific components, extracting this code into a genericised component further increases maintainability, as changes need only be made to the singular genericised component.

```
export default function Button({ children, onClick, hasTitle, title }) {  
  return (  
    <button className='button is-light is-responsive' onClick={onClick}>  
      {children}  
      {  
        hasTitle  
        && <p className='Title'>  
          {title}  
        </p>  
      }  
    </button>  
  );  
};
```

Figure 5.56 Creation of Button Reusable Component

A Button reusable component was created, as it was identified that many instances of the same button were required across the application, as shown in Figure 5.56. After evaluating all uses of buttons throughout the application, similarities were noted across the button's styling and use of titles. Consequently, these elements were extracted to produce a generic Button component, which may be passed an icon to render, through the children prop, have an onClick event, and an optional title.

```
function AddNew({ onClick, hasTitle=false, title }) {
  return (
    <Button onClick={onClick} hasTitle={hasTitle} title={title}>
      <Icon.Add />
    </Button>
  );
};

function Cancel({ onClick, hasTitle=false, title='Cancel' }) {
  return (
    <Button onClick={onClick} hasTitle={hasTitle} title={title}>
      <Icon.Cancel />
    </Button>
  );
};
```

Figure 5.57 Creation of AddNew and Cancel Button Components

The Button reusable component was wrapped within further, specific button components, each passing the relevant onClick() function, inherited from their parent, and a hasTitle prop defaulting to false, meaning the title will not be displayed, as shown in Figure 5.57. Where appropriate, the button title is passed to the Button component, alongside an appropriate button icon child.

```
Button.AddNew = AddNew;
Button.Cancel = Cancel;
```

Figure 5.58 Exporting of AddNew and Cancel Button Components

The button components were exported, for use within other files, as shown in Figure 5.58. One of the main uses for the produced button components was in the ButtonBar component. A ButtonBar is a wrapper component containing one or more buttons, flexed in the centre of the container, allowing buttons to be appropriately styled within a parent component.

After importing the Button component, containing the required button implementations, a generic ButtonBar component is created, to provide the appropriate ButtonBar SCSS flexbox styling, as shown in Figure 5.59. Specific ButtonBar components, such as CancelConfirm and EditDeleteToggleFavourite components, are produced. A CancelConfirm ButtonBar contains Cancel and Confirm buttons, passed the appropriate onClick and title functions from their parent implementation.

This is commonly used during the creation of forms. In contrast, the EditDeleteToggleFavourite component contains Edit and Delete buttons, alongside a togglable RemoveFavourite and Favourite button, depending on the status of the parent object. This is used for cards displaying objects within lists, with the favourite toggle changing the button, depending on the favourites status of the object.

```

import Button from './Buttons';

function ButtonBar({ className, children }) {
  return ( <div className={'ButtonBar ' + className}>{children}</div> );
};

function CancelConfirm({ className, onClickCancel, onClickConfirm, cancelTitle,
confirmTitle }) {
  return (
    <ButtonBar className={className}>
      <Button.Cancel onClick={onClickCancel} hasTitle title={cancelTitle} />
      <Button.Confirm onClick={onClickConfirm} hasTitle
title={confirmTitle} />
    </ButtonBar>
  );
};

function EditDeleteToggleFavourite({ className, onClickEdit, onClickDelete,
onClickToggleFavourite, favourite }) {
  return (
    <ButtonBar className={className}>
      <Button.Edit onClick={onClickEdit} />
      <Button.Delete onClick={onClickDelete} />
      {
        favourite ? <Button.RemoveFavourite
onClick={onClickToggleFavourite} /> : <Button.Favourite
onClick={onClickToggleFavourite} />
      }
    </ButtonBar>
  );
};

```

Figure 5.59 Creation of ButtonBar, CancelConfirm and EditDeleteToggleFavourite Components

The ButtonBar.scss file defines the styling rules required within the ButtonBar component, as shown in Figure 5.60. In the case of a standard ButtonBar, the Button components are flexed in the centre of the container in the row direction, with a gap of 25 pixels between the centre of the buttons, to prevent user mis-clicks when utilising button functionality. In the event of the ButtonBar being used within a form, the FormButtonBar class is passed to the ButtonBar component as a prop, and appended to the className attribute. ButtonBars used on forms must fill the form width and have a bottom margin of 20 pixels, to increase the aesthetics of the from.

```

@import '../../../variables';
@import "../../../mixins";
div.ButtonBar {
  @include flexCenter(row);
  gap: 25px;
}
.FormButtonBar {
  width: 100%;
  margin-bottom: 20px;
}

```

Figure 5.60 ButtonBar and FormButtonBar Component Custom SCSS Rulesets

```

ButtonBar.CancelConfirm = CancelConfirm;
ButtonBar.EditDeleteToggleFavourite = EditDeleteToggleFavourite;
export default ButtonBar;

```

Figure 5.61 Exporting of CancelConfirm and EditDeleteToggleFavourite ButtonBar Components

The ButtonBar implementations were exported, to be used in other files, as shown in Figure 5.61.

As previously discussed, one of the main uses of ButtonBar components is within forms, as shown in Figure 5.62. In the generic Form component, contained within the Form.js file, a CancelConfirm ButtonBar is defined to handle form cancel and confirm functionality. The 'FormButtonBar' class is passed as a prop, to ensure the form-specific CSS rulesets are applied to the component. The appropriate onClick functions and titles are passed as props, with the confirmTitle being constructed based on the usage of the form. In the case of the form being used for login, the button must display 'Login', with edit and create forms containing their respective functionality and object name.

The Form.js file also contains an Item component, used to wrap a form input component and provide it with a label, advice and error message, where appropriate, as defined by the passed props, as shown in Figure 5.63. The reusable generic Item component is used within FormInput components, to create a consistent form input element with suitable user feedback, regardless of the form field component used.

Within the FormField.js file, a FormField object is declared, allowing the appropriate functions to be exported using the JavaScript dot syntax, for easier import and use in other files, as shown in Figure 5.64. A Text component is declared, to facilitate the creation of a text input field, with the relevant name, placeholder, value, onChange, disabled and hidden props. The inputType defaults to 'text', meaning the rendered element will contain a textbox, although this may be defined in the prop, enhancing component reusability.

```

import ButtonBar from '../button/ButtonBar';

function Form({ children, onSubmit, onCancel, cancelTitle='Cancel',
confirmTitle='', editForm, login }) {

  const handleSubmit = () => onSubmit();

  const handleCancel = () => onCancel();

  return (

    <div className='BorderedForm'>

      <div className='FormTray'>

        {

          children

        }

      </div>

      <ButtonBar.CancelConfirm

        className='FormButtonBar'

        onClickCancel={handleCancel}

        onClickConfirm={handleSubmit}

        cancelTitle={cancelTitle}

        confirmTitle={login ? 'Login' : editForm ? 'Edit ' +
confirmTitle : 'Create ' + confirmTitle}

      />

    </div>

  );

};

```

Figure 5.62 Implementation of CancelConfirm ButtonBar Component Within Form Component

An APISelect component was created, accepting props including the list of items to render in the dropdown list, a loading message to display if the list of items is not yet populated, the itemType of the given items, and the previously discussed name, value, onChange, disabled and hidden props, as shown in Figure 5.65. If no items are provided, the loading message is displayed, informing users that the items are loading.

In the case of items being passed to the component, the select component appends a disabled 'Please select' option to the start of the list, informing the user of the input's use, followed by the list of items. Should no items be present, the select component will inform the user of no items being found. To produce a reusable select component, each rendered item object must be modified to contain an ItemID and ItemText attribute, before being passed to the APISelect component, ensuring the component's generalisation. All FormField components are exported, for use within other files.

```

function Item({ children, label, htmlFor, advice, error, hidden }) {
  return (
    <div className='field' hidden={hidden}>
      <label className='label' htmlFor={htmlFor}>{label}</label>
      { advice && <p className='help'>{advice}</p> }
      { children }
      { error && <p className='help is-danger'>{error}</p> }
    </div>
  );
};
Form.Item = Item;
export default Form;

```

Figure 5.63 Creation of Item Component

```

const FormField = {};
function Text({ name, inputType='text', placeholder, value, onChange, disabled,
hidden, children, className }) {
  return (
    <div className={children ? 'control has-icons-left' : 'control'}>
      <input
        className={`input ${className}`}
        inputType={inputType}
        name={name}
        placeholder={placeholder}
        value={value}
        onChange={onChange}
        disabled={disabled}
        hidden={hidden}
      /> { children }
    </div>
  );
};

```

Figure 5.64 Creation of Text FormField Component

In the case children are passed to the input field, the 'control has-icons-left' Bulma CSS class is applied to the field's container, else only the 'control' field is applied. The 'has-icons-left' Bulma CSS class allows Font Awesome icons to be overlaid on the left area inside the input field, used when defining the icons used in the login fields. The children are subsequently rendered after the input field.

```

function APISelect({ items, loadingMessage, itemType, name, value, onChange,
disabled, hidden, className }) {
  return (
    !items
    ? <div className='control'><p
className={className}>{loadingMessage}</p></div>
    : <div className='control'>
      <div className={`select ${className}`}>
        <select
          name={name}
          value={value}
          onChange={onChange}
          disabled={disabled}
          hidden={hidden}
        >
          {(items.length === 0 || items.message)
            ? <option value='0' disabled>{`No ${itemType}
found`}</option>
            : <option value='0' disabled>Please select</option>}
          {
            items.length !== 0 && !items.message &&
            items.map((item) =>
              <option key={item.ItemID} value={item.ItemID}>
                {item.ItemText}
              </option>
            )
          }
        </select>
      </div>
    </div>
  );
};

FormField.Text = Text;
FormField.APISelect = APISelect;
export default FormField;

```

Figure 5.65 Creation and Export of APISelect FormField Component and Export of Text Component

```

import Form from './Form';
import FormField from './FormField';
const FormInput = {};
function NameInput({ dataType, inputType='Name', name, error, placeholder,
value, onChange, disabled, hidden, children='' }) {
    return (
        <Form.Item
            label={`${dataType} ${inputType}`}
            htmlFor={name}
            advice={`Please enter the ${inputType.toLowerCase()} of the
${dataType.toLowerCase()}`}
            error={error}
            hidden={hidden}
        >
            <FormField.Text
                name={name}
                inputType={inputType}
                placeholder={placeholder}
                value={value}
                onChange={onChange}
                disabled={disabled}
                hidden={hidden}
                className={error && 'is-danger'}
                children={children}
            />
        </Form.Item>
    );
};
FormInput.NameInput = NameInput;
export default FormInput;

```

Figure 5.66 Creation and Export of NameInput FormInput Component

Within the FormInput.js file, a FormInput object is declared for easier component import, as shown in Figure 5.66. After importing both the Form and FormField components, to provide the necessary Item and Field components, a NameInput component is declared. This accepts the dataType prop containing the type of object requiring input, in addition to the inputType, or type of data requiring input. The name, error, placeholder, value, onChange, disabled and hidden props are passed to the component from its parent, to provide reusability within the Input components. By default, children is set to an empty String, although any child components passed will be rendered as normal.

The NameInput component utilises a combination of an Item component, to wrap the FormField component and provide an input field with associated user feedback, to be contained within a form. All props are passed to the Item and FormField components where necessary, to ensure appropriate functionality, with labels and advice messages being formed based on the concatenation of the provided values. This ensures consistency across all text used in the form input components, enhancing the application's usability. As before, all FormInput components are exported, for use within other files.

```
import Form from '../..//form/Form';
import FormInput from '../..//form/FormInput';

<Form onSubmit={handleSubmit} onCancel={onCancel} confirmTitle='Alert'
editForm={editForm}>

    <FormInput.NameInput
        dataType='Alert'
        inputType='Title'
        name='AlertTitle'
        error={errors.AlertTitle}
        placeholder='Reminder - Submit Pitch Presentation'
        value={alert.AlertTitle}
        onChange={handleChange}
    />

    ...
<FormInput.APISelectInput
    dataType='User Group'
    name='AlertUsertypeID'
    error={errors.AlertUsertypeID}
    items={usertypes}
    loadingMessage={loadingUsertypesMessage}
    value={alert.AlertUsertypeID}
    onChange={handleChange}
/>

</Form>
```

Figure 5.67 AlertForm Component Implementing NameInput and APISelectInput Components

Forms, such as the AlertForm contained within AlertForm.js, utilise FormInput components, as shown in Figure 5.67. After importing the Form and associated FormInput components, the Form component is declared, being passed the necessary onSubmit, onCancel, confirmTitle and editForm props, to provide the ButtonBar functionality. A NameInput component is declared, being passed the relevant 'Alert' and 'Title' props, placeholder text, value, error and onChange function. Similarly, an APISelectInput component is passed the input's dataType, name, error, list of render items, loading message, value and onChange function.

As previously identified within the requirements elicitation, and proposed within the system designs, a draggable and droppable component was required, to facilitate the input and selection of multiple items within a form. Whilst dropdown lists serve to offer a suitable mechanism for selecting single items, they are often impractical when selecting multiple items, and the repetition of multiple dropdown lists to select items of the same type within a form, is tedious and unintuitive for users.

To mitigate against such issues, a DragAndDrop form field was created, to facilitate the dragging and dropping of elements. DragAndDrop form fields comprise two separate components, namely Draggable and Droppable area components, used for managing the selected and available options.

```
function Draggable({ id, className, onDoubleClick, children }) {  
  const handleDrag = event => event.dataTransfer.setData('text',  
event.target.id);  
  
  const handleDoubleClick = event => onDoubleClick(event.target.id);  
  
  return (  
    <div  
      key={id}  
      id={id}  
      draggable='true'  
      onDragStart={handleDrag}  
      className={`draggable ${className}`}  
      onDoubleClick={handleDoubleClick}  
    >  
      {children}  
    </div>  
  );  
};
```

Figure 5.68 Draggable Component

Within the draggable component, as shown in Figure 5.68, a `handleDrag()` function is used to facilitate the transfer of data between div elements upon a div element being dragged. The `handleDoubleClick()` function is used to retrieve the ID value of the div element, upon it being double-clicked. A div, with appropriate key and id values for unique identification of the draggable element, is declared with its 'draggable' prop enabled, allowing the div to be dragged across the webpage.

```

function Droppable({ id, children }) {
  const handleDrop = event => {
    event.preventDefault();

    const draggable =
document.getElementById(event.dataTransfer.getData('text'));

    const droppable = document.getElementById(id);
    if (droppable.contains(draggable)) return;
    droppable.appendChild(draggable);
    console.log(draggable);
  };

  const allowDrop = event => event.preventDefault();

  return (
    <div
      id={id}
      onDrop={handleDrop}
      onDragOver={allowDrop}
      className='droppable'
    >
      {children}
    </div>
  );
};

```

Figure 5.69 Droppable Component

Within the droppable component, as shown in Figure 5.69, a `handleDrop()` function is used to retrieve the draggable div element's data, and append it to the droppable div region it has been dropped over, as a child of the droppable div. If the draggable element is attempted to be dropped on another draggable element, no action is taken, to prevent draggables being added to any elements other than droppables. The `allowDrop()` function is used to prevent the form from being submitted upon the draggable item being placed above the droppable region.

```

if (document.getElementById(name)) {
    const observer = new MutationObserver((mutations) => {
        let selectedItems = [];
        mutations.forEach((mutation) => {
            if (mutation.type === 'childList') {
                selectedItems =
Array.from(document.getElementById(name).querySelectorAll('*')).map(child =>
child.id);
            }
        });
        onChange(selectedItems ? selectedItems : []);
    });
    observer.observe(document.getElementById(name), { childList: true });
};

const existingItems = items.filter((item) => value.indexOf(item.ItemID) !==
-1);
const newItems = items.filter((item) => value.indexOf(item.ItemID) === -1);
const handleDoubleClick = leader => {
    setLeader(leader);
    const draggableItems = document.querySelectorAll('.draggable');
    draggableItems.forEach((item) => item.classList.remove('selected'));
    const clickedItem = document.getElementById(leader);
    if (clickedItem) clickedItem.classList.add('selected');
};

```

Figure 5.70 DragAndDrop Component Logic

The Draggable and Droppable components are utilised together within the DragAndDrop form field component, as shown in Figure 5.70 and Figure 5.71. Upon the droppable area being instantiated, an observer is created to return all draggable child elements contained within the droppable area, upon a new draggable child element being added or removed from the droppable region. These contained draggable elements are subsequently returned from the form field, via the onChange() function, with the observer being set to observe the selection droppable area.

Depending on the items passed to the form field, if the draggable element has been selected previously, based on the form being used for editing an existing value, the item is added to the existingItems array, which is displayed within the droppable selection region. In the case of the item not already being selected, it is added to the newItems array, for display in the droppable choices region.

Upon double-clicking an element, the selected element is returned. All elements are set to normal font weight, and the selected element is set to use a bold font weight, identifying it has been selected. This behaviour facilitates the selection of a group or panel leader from a selection of draggable elements. In the case of items being present to populate the droppable regions using, the selected droppable region is set to contain the existing selected draggable elements.

```

<Droppable id={name}>
  <div className='draggableItems'>
    {
      existingItems.length !== 0 && existingItems.map((item) =>
        <Draggable id={item.ItemID}
onDoubleClick={handleDoubleClick} className={({item.ItemID === leader) ?
'selected' : ''}>
          {item.ItemText}
        </Draggable>
      )}
    </div>
  </Droppable>
<Droppable id='choices'>
  <div className='draggableItems'>
    {
      newItems.length !== 0 && !items.message &&
      newItems.map((item) =>
        <Draggable id={item.ItemID}
onDoubleClick={handleDoubleClick} className={({item.ItemID
=== leader) ? 'selected' : ''}>
          {item.ItemText}
        </Draggable>
      )}
    </div>
  </Droppable>

```

Figure 5.71 DragAndDrop Component View Utilising Draggable and Droppable Components

Any remaining draggable elements are contained within the choices droppable region, to be added to the selected droppable region, as necessary. The existing selected group or panel leader draggable element is displayed in bold. The choices region uses a droppable area, to allow draggable elements to be dragged from the selected droppable region back into the choices area, to de-select options.

```
div.draggable {
  display: inline-block;
  font-size: 90%;
  margin: 2px;
  padding: 2px 5px;
  border: 1px solid DarkGrey;
  border-radius: 2px;
  background: White;
  cursor: pointer;
}
div.droppable {
  margin: 0 0 1rem 0;
  padding: 1rem;
  border: 2px dashed lighten(#230c33, 64%);
  border-radius: 7px;
  min-height: 100px;
}
.selected {
  font-weight: bold;
}
```

Figure 5.72 Draggable, Droppable and DragAndDrop Component Styling

SCSS rulesets were declared, to facilitate the draggable and droppable component styling and display the selected draggable element with bold text.

As with previous components, the DragAndDrop and form field component is wrapped within a Form.Item component, to facilitate the appropriate labelling of the component for use in form implementations, including displaying advice and error messages.

5.8.4 Existing React Component Use

While bespoke and reusable react components offer added flexibility and customisation, being able to be modified as needed to fit the desired purpose, functionality and styling, they require significant time to implement. It is also likely that, due to the nature of the available HTML elements, and their cross-browser support, some features may not be available across all browsers. Consequently, in projects with a limited timeframe, and requirement for creation of a fully cross-browser compatible application, the use of existing components can mitigate against such application development issues.

As explained previously, React utilises JavaScript and the Node.js runtime environment, and is supported by a wealth of freely importable libraries and components, available via npm (npm, no date). These packages often provide cross-browser support, varying degrees of customisation, and seek to increase application development speed, using trusted, maintained and well-developed components. Where bespoke components would require too much time to implement, thus preventing core application functionality from being implemented, or experimental HTML elements lacked support across browsers, existing components were imported and used as an alternative.

A rich text editor input field was implemented, to allow assessment and module descriptions to be added, with HTML-based input. It was identified that the majority of assessments and module descriptions will likely require links to other files, briefs or websites, and emphasis on certain included text, through the use of bold characters. Such functionality cannot be achieved using a standard text input, therefore a new rich text input was created.

After researching the most suitable rich text editor libraries for React, the ReactQuill library was recognised as providing all desired HTML markup features, including bold text and link insertion, whilst offering a customisable toolbar, to increase control over the available text editor functionality (zeno, 2023). Its simple React integration and support for SCSS ensured its use within the frontend would be fast to implement, and could be styled to match the existing webpage styles.

```
import ReactQuill from 'react-quill';
```

Figure 5.73 Importing of ReactQuill Third-Party Rich Text Editor Component

As the ReactQuill component is provided by an external library, it must be imported within the application, as shown in Figure 5.73.

A new ReactQuill component may be instantiated through passing the necessary props, as shown in Figure 5.74. It must be noted that while most props are identical to standard JSX components, such as placeholder, value, onChange, disabled and hidden, the ReactQuill component does not support the name prop. Instead, the name must be passed using the id prop, with each ID being required to be unique, to identify the ReactQuill component instance. It should be noted that the desired text editor theme, and any additional styling, are passed to the ReactQuill component via their associated props.

Due to the nature of the implementation of the ReactQuill component, a standard event.target object is not returned from the ReactQuill, upon changes being made to the contents within the rich text input, as shown in Figure 5.75. Consequently, an alternative approach, involving retrieving the content and name of the ReactQuill component within the onChange() function, is required.

This modification was made within the useForm custom hook, through the creation of a handleRichTextChange() method, which is able to extract the required information from a ReactQuill component, and append it to the record and errors objects.

```
function RichText({ name, placeholder, value, onChange, disabled, hidden }){
  return (
    <div className='control'>
      <ReactQuill
        id={name}
        placeholder={placeholder}
        value={value}
        onChange={onChange}
        disabled={disabled}
        hidden={hidden}
        theme='snow'
        className='reactquill'
      />
    </div>
  );
};
```

Figure 5.74 Creation of RichText Reusable Component

```
const handleRichTextChange = (content, delta, source, editor, name) => {
  setRecord({ ...record, [name]: content });
  setErrors({ ...errors, [name]: isValid[name](content) ? null :
  errorMessage[name]});
};
```

Figure 5.75 Creation of handleRichTextChange() Rich Text onChange() Handler Function

```
return [record, errors, handleChange, handleDateChange, handleRichTextChange,
handleSubmit];
```

Figure 5.76 Returned Values and Functions within useForm Custom Hook

This new function was exported as part of the useForm custom hook, to allow the method to be used when handling the output from a ReactQuill component within a form, as shown in Figure 5.76.

```
const [module, errors, handleChange, , handleRichTextChange, handleSubmit] =
Form.useForm(initialModule, conformance, moduleValidation, onCancel, onSubmit);
```

Figure 5.77 Implementation of useForm Custom Hook within Modules Form

As a result of exporting a new function within the useForm custom hook, all existing instances of the useForm hook required modification, either to use the new exported handleRichTextChange() function, or due to the exporting of an additional function now changing the exported location of the handleSubmit() function within the useForm hook, as shown in Figure 5.77.

```

function RichTextInput({ dataType, name, an, error, placeholder, value,
onChange, disabled, hidden }) {
  return (
    <Form.Item
      label={`${dataType} Description`}
      htmlFor={name}
      advice={`Please enter ${an ? 'an' : 'a'} ${dataType.toLowerCase()}
description`}
      error={error}
      hidden={hidden}
    >
      <FormField.RichText
        name={name}
        placeholder={placeholder}
        value={value}
        onChange={onChange}
        disabled={disabled}
        hidden={hidden}
        className={error && 'is-danger'}
      />
    </Form.Item>
  );
};

```

Figure 5.78 Creation of RichTextInput FormInput Component

The RichText component was wrapped in an associated RichTextInput wrapper component, allowing additional information to be displayed around the input component, including an input field name, advice and error message, where applicable, as shown in Figure 5.78.

```

<FormInput.RichTextInput
  dataType='Module'
  name='ModuleDescription'
  error={errors.ModuleDescription}
  placeholder='This module focusses on the fundamental concepts
of building websites using React...'
  value={module.ModuleDescription}
  onChange={(content, delta, source, editor) =>
handleRichTextChange(content, delta, source, editor, 'ModuleDescription')}/>

```

Figure 5.79 Implementation of RichTextInput Component within Module Form

The RichTextInput component may be implemented within a form, such as for the module description input within the module form, as shown in Figure 5.79.

During the creation of the form item components, the need for obtaining dates of user input was identified. The start and end date inputs are of a date time format required the importing of a third-party library, react-flatpickr, to handle the user input of this data (Hao, 2023). As HTML input elements do not have a consistent datetime input which is compatible with all browsers or browser versions, the Flatpickr was the most suitable alternative, to ensure the date and time may be entered on all user platforms, meeting the compatibility non-functional requirements. Furthermore, the Flatpickr component is very user-friendly and aesthetically pleasing, allowing users to easily select dates and input times, improving usability and associated non-functional requirements.

```
import Flatpickr from 'react-flatpickr';
import 'flatpickr/dist/themes/material_green.css';
```

Figure 5.80 Import of react-flatpickr Component and Associated CSS Theme

As the react-flatpickr component is contained within a third-party library, it must first be installed via npm, before being imported for use within the application, as shown in Figure 5.80. If desired, a pre-built CSS theme may also be imported, to style the Flatpickr component against a defined colour scheme. In this case, the material_green theme styles the date time picker with a green and grey theme, chosen to match the grey colour scheme used throughout the frontend user interface.

```
function DateTimePicker({ name, value, onChange, disabled, hidden }) {
  return (
    <div className='control'>
      <Flatpickr
        data-enable-time
        name={name}
        placeholder='Click to open datetime picker'
        value={value}
        onChange={onChange}
        disabled={disabled}
        hidden={hidden}
      /></div>
  );
};
FormField.DateTimePicker = DateTimePicker;
```

Figure 5.81 Creation and Export of DateTimePicker FormField Component

As the date time picker form input component was required across multiple forms throughout the application, it was decided that a DateTimePicker reusable component would be created, implementing the Flatpickr component and providing it with default values, for consistency across forms, as shown in Figure 5.81. This includes the div wrapper, containing the 'control' class, used by Bulma CSS to style the input component.

The Flatpickr's data-enable-time prop ensures the component displays both a calendar, to input the desired date, and time input field within the same component. A placeholder message is passed to the Flatpickr, ensuring consistency across messaging for all Flatpickr components, with the name, value, onChange, disabled and hidden props being passed via the parent component, as with all other FormField components. Similarly, the DateTimePicker is exported, for use within other files.

```
function DateInput({ dataType, dateType, name, error, value, onChange,
disabled, hidden }) {
  return (
    <Form.Item
      label={` ${dataType} ${dateType} Date`}
      htmlFor={name}
      advice={`Please enter the ${dateType.toLowerCase()} date and time
of the ${dataType.toLowerCase()}`}
      error={error}
      hidden={hidden}
    >
      <FormField.DateTimePicker
        name={name}
        value={value}
        onChange={onChange}
        disabled={disabled}
        hidden={hidden}
      />
    </Form.Item>
  );
}
FormInput.DateInput = DateInput;
```

Figure 5.82 Creation of DateInput FormInput Component

As with the other FormField components, the DateTimeInput component was imported into the FormInput file, where it was wrapped within an Item component, to allow the appropriate labels, advice and error messages to be added, as shown in Figure 5.82. The relevant DateInput component props are passed to the DateTimePicker, to enable the desired functionality to be enacted upon the Flatpickr component. The DateInput component is then exported for use in forms.

One use of the DateInput component was within the AssessmentForm, as shown in Figure 5.83. When creating a new assessment, it is vital that the assessment leader is able to input the starting and ending date and time for an assessment event, to inform students of the date they are required to attend. Similar to other Input components, the dataType prop is passed, whilst the dateType prop allows the advice text to be configured for either start or ending dates, improving component reusability.

```

<FormInput.DateInput
    dataType='Assessment'
    dateType='Start'
    name='AssessmentStartdate'
    error={errors.AssessmentStartdate}
    value={assessment.AssessmentStartdate}
    onChange={(dateStr) =>
handleDateChange('AssessmentStartdate',dateStr)}
/>

```

Figure 5.83 Implementation of DateInput FormInput Component within Assessment Form

After passing in the field name, error and value props, the onChange function is passed an anonymous function to update the AssessmentStartdate value, when required. Upon changes being made to the selected date or time within the Flatpickr component, the onChange method runs, returning a string containing the selected date and time values. This is passed to the handleDateChange() function, used to update the assessment object's AssessmentStartdate value. The structure and functionality of the handleDateChange() function is discussed in detail within subsection 5.8.7 – Data Conformance.

During the project, all application icons were migrated to use the react-fontawesome icon library (FontAwesome, no date), instead of the icons8 web-based icons previously used (icons8, no date). Whilst icons8 provided a wide variety of icons, as the icons used within the application were descended from different icons8 libraries, there was inconsistency between icon design and size.

```

function Image({ type, src, alt }) {
  return (
    <div className={'Image ' && type}>
      <img src={src} alt={alt} />
    </div>
  );
};
export default Image;
function Group() {
  return (
    <Icon className='Icon IconGroup'>
      <Image type='Icon' src='https://img.icons8.com/ios-filled/50/undefined/conference-call.png' alt='Group icon' />
    </Icon>
  );
};

```

Figure 5.84 Creation and Export of Image Component and Creation of Group Icon Component

Icons8 icons required fetch requests to be made to the icons8 web server, for icon retrieval, using the specified icon PNG image URL, handling the icon as an image, as shown in Figure 5.84. A generic Image component was created, to handle the icon images returned from the icons8 web server.

However, the icons8 server occasionally suffered downtime, meaning the icons used throughout the application could not be retrieved and displayed. As such, users accessing the website during this period were greeted with alt text in place of the desired icons, severely impacting usability. After researching suitable icon library React imports, Font Awesome notably offered a range of standardised importable icons, fulfilling the application's requirement.

```
import { faStar as faSolidStar, faUserGroup, faPlus, faXmark, faCheck, faPen,
faTrash, faPercent, faLock, faEnvelope, faUser } from '@fortawesome/free-solid-
svg-icons';

import { faStar as faRegularStar } from '@fortawesome/free-regular-svg-icons';

import { FontAwesomeIcon } from '@fortawesome/react-fontawesome';

export default function Icon({children}) {

  return (

    <div className='Icon'>

      {children}

    </div>

  );

};

function Group() {

  return (

    <Icon className='Icon IconGroup'>

      <FontAwesomeIcon className='fa-2xl' icon={faUserGroup} />

    </Icon>

  );

};
```

Figure 5.85 Creation of Icon and Group Icon Components

Consequently, Font Awesome was imported using npm, and all icon elements were refactored to use the Font Awesome-equivalent icon, as shown in Figure 5.85. Font Awesome offers a range of icon weightings, including 'solid' and 'regular'. Solid icons contain coloured infill, whilst regular icons contain only icon outlines, with most icons being solid, with the exception of the star icon used when displaying an assessment that has not been added to favourites.

The FontAwesomeIcon component is imported to provide a wrapper element to display the required icon, and any icon size styling that may be required. The application icons use an 'fa-2xl' styling, meaning they are of size XXL, being of a visible and user-friendly size on the webpage. Due to the nature of the imported Font Awesome icons, all icons remain consistent in their styling and size, as governed by the applied size class ruleset.

Figure 5.86 Network Analysis of Loading Assessments Webpage Browser Requests

It must also be noted that the icons displayed within the webpage are all retrieved from the local web server hosting the application, not from further external connections to remote image servers, to retrieve the necessary icons, as shown in Figure 5.86. Additionally, as the icons are added to the webpage within the FontAwesomelcon wrapper component, no further requests are made from the browser to the frontend web server to retrieve the icons, as they are not treated as image elements.

This significantly reduces the overhead on both the browser, web server, and associated network connection, as fewer content item requests are made upon loading the webpage, with all icons being bundled with the initial webpage content data. This also seeks to improve reliability and user experience, as the webpage icons will always be displayed, due to being returned alongside the other page content, and mitigates the issue of downtime of a separate image server hindering the web application.

The bundling of icons within the page content provides the additional benefit of all page content loading and being displayed at the same time, rather than some icons being loaded significantly after the other page content has been rendered, thus increasing the user experience.

A core concept of the creation and management of React components is the use of state, which reflects a component's behaviour and stored value. The management of component state allows React to only re-render page components that have been modified, through examining changes in component state, thus only re-rendering such objects within the page.

Where traditional web applications request a new webpage upon changing one element on the page, React state allows only changed components to be updated and re-rendered, thus preventing page refresh and increasing webpage performance.

5.8.5 Component State and Hooks

React component state is managed using a `useState` hook, imported from the React library (React, no date a), which accepts an initial state value, and returns an array containing an accessible value and state modifier function. In order for React to be notified of state changes, all modifications to the state value must be made through calling the state setter function.

State may be combined with the React library's `useEffect` hook, which allows a callback function to be run, upon changes to any value within the `useEffect`'s dependencies array. This allows a function to execute once, and subsequently only when changes occur which require the re-running of the method.

```
import { useState } from 'react';  
  
const [records, setRecords] = useState(null);  
  
const [loadingMessage, setLoadingMessage] = useState('Loading records ...');
```

Figure 5.87 Importation of useState Hook and Creation of Records and LoadingMessage State

During reviewing the frontend React implementation, it was identified that there was significant repetition within the code to 'GET' objects from the API, as shown in Figure 5.87. To retrieve objects from the API, `useState` is required to contain the returned objects, and to contain the appropriate loading message, whilst the user is waiting for the objects to be fetched.

```
import { useEffect } from 'react';  
  
useEffect(() => { loadRecords(endpoint) }, [endpoint]);
```

Figure 5.88 Importation and Implementation of useEffect Hook

An asynchronous method is used to fetch the objects from the API GET method, setting the objects state to the returned value, or loading message to the appropriate error message, as appropriate, as shown in Figure 5.88. This is called within a `useEffect` hook, preventing the unnecessary re-running and rendering of the page when the objects are returned from the API.

This same code was repeated across the Homepage, to retrieve the assessments from the API, and within the AssessmentForm component, to retrieve both the assessment leaders and modules from the API, to populate the relevant form input components. `from` and clearing the loading message. This repeated code was difficult to maintain, as modification to the code would require all of these methods to be manually updated, whilst their duplication makes the code significantly more difficult to read.

Consequently, to rectify this repeated code, the repeated method was abstracted, to remove any references to any particular objects, such as assessments or modules, and a new custom hook was created. The hook features all of the repeated code, with the data logic occurring within the hook, and the records, `setRecords` method, `loadingMessage` and `loadRecords` method all being returned, for use in place of the original code in the implementation of the hook.

The custom useLoad hook was created within its own file, being imported and implemented in place of each of the repeated code blocks. This has increased maintainability, as code is being reused, making it easier to modify and improving code readability. A detailed explanation of the useLoad hook may be found in subsection 5.8.8 – Backend API Data Fetch.

During frontend code inspection, it was also identified that there was significant repetition within the code used to handle Form components, including setting and updating the initial record based on inputted data, validating input, and identifying input field errors. To reduce code duplication, and therefore increase maintainability, a custom useForm hook was created, allowing such repeated functions to be declared once, and efficiently utilised throughout the application.

```
import { useState } from 'react';

function useForm(initialRecord, { integer }, { isValid, errorMessage },
onCancel, onSubmit) {

  const [record, setRecord] = useState(initialRecord);

  const [errors, setErrors] = useState(
    Object.keys(initialRecord).reduce((accum, key) => ({ ...accum, [key]:
null}), {})
  );

};
```

Figure 5.89 Importation of useState Hook and Creation of useForm Custom Hook

After importing useState, the useForm hook is declared, accepting an initialRecord parameter, destructured integer, isValid and errorMessage values, and onCancel and onSubmit functions, as shown in Figure 5.89. A useState hook is used for storing both the record, initialised with the passed initialRecord object, and errors, with the errors value originally being set to a new object containing all the initialRecord attributes, but with null values.

Three handleChange() functions are declared, used for receiving the appropriate input fields' current value, when the relevant onChange() function is called, as shown in Figure 5.90. Whilst all vanilla JSX components are managed via their event prop, custom third-party components, including the date and rich text components, do not make use of the event prop, thus require custom handlers to extract their values.

In the case of the handleChange() function, the name and value of the input field is retrieved from the event.target attribute. If the passed integer conformance object contains the specified input field name, the retrieved value is converted into an integer, with the record object being updated with the relevant attribute's new value. The isValid function is passed the name and value, to preform validation on the input, against the specified validation rule. Should errors be detected, these are reported and added to the corresponding attribute in the errors object.

In the case of the handleDateChange() function, the name and value are passed to the function as props, with the value array's zero index containing the selected date and time as a JavaScript Date object. This is parsed to an ISO string, required for transmission to the backend API, before the previously outlined process occurs. In the case of the handleRichTextChange() function, although the react-quill editor returns many props, only the content and name are required, being utilised in the same manner as the other handleChange() functions.

```

const handleChange = (event) => {
    const { name, value} = event.target;
    const newValue = integer.includes(name) ? parseInt(value) : value;
    setRecord({ ...record, [name]: newValue });
    setErrors({ ...errors, [name]: isValid[name](newValue) ? null :
errorMessage[name]});
};

const handleDateChange = (name, value) => {
    const newValue = value[0].toISOString();
    setRecord({ ...record, [name]: newValue });
    setErrors({ ...errors, [name]: isValid[name](newValue) ? null :
errorMessage[name]});
};

const handleRichTextChange = (content, delta, source, editor, name) => {
    setRecord({ ...record, [name]: content });
    setErrors({ ...errors, [name]: isValid[name](content) ? null :
errorMessage[name]});
};

```

Figure 5.90 Creation of `handleChange()`, `handleDateChange()` and `handleRichTextChange()` Functions

```

const isValidRecord = (record) => {
    let isRecordValid = true;
    Object.keys(record).forEach((key) => {
        if (isValid[key](record[key])) {
            errors[key] = null;
        }
        else {
            errors[key] = errorMessage[key];
            isRecordValid = false;
        }
    });
    return isRecordValid;
};

```

Figure 5.91 Creation of `isValidRecord()` Function

The `isValidRecord()` function is declared, accepting a record for validation, and initialising its validity to true, as shown in Figure 5.91. For each attribute within the record, if the value is valid, the corresponding errors object's attribute is set to null, removing the attribute from the errors object, else the errors object's attribute value is set to the appropriate error message for the input field data, and the `isRecordValid` flag is set to false, indicating the record is not valid. This flag is subsequently returned.

```
const handleSubmit = () => {  
    isValidRecord(record) && onSubmit(record);  
    setErrors({ ...errors });  
};  
return [record, errors, handleChange, handleDateChange,  
handleRichTextChange, handleSubmit];  
};
```

Figure 5.92 Creation of `handleSubmit()` Function

The `handleSubmit()` function is declared, calling the `isValidRecord()` function with the record object, to verify the validity of the object, as shown in Figure 5.92. Should the record be valid, and no errors are present after validation has been performed, the `onSubmit()` function is called and passed the record, allowing the record to be submitted to the backend API for persistent storage. The errors value is set to the errors object, clearing the errors object. The necessary values and functions are exported from the hook, for use within the application.

5.8.6 Form Input Validation

When accepting user input via a frontend application form, input field validation must be considered, as only valid data should be sent to the backend API, based on the acceptable value range of values for the data object. While validation on the frontend does not explicitly prevent errors or malicious attacks from occurring during the ultimate persistent storage of the data, due to such validation occurring on the backend API, it provides valuable and immediate user feedback.

With validation rulesets being integrated within frontend input fields, form input data may be validated in real time as the user completes each field, with corresponding error messages being displayed alongside the form input. This allows users to be aware of any errors within their input data prior to the form data being sent to the backend API, and potentially being rejected for not meeting validation criteria. This increases the usability of the application, with the system providing immediate user feedback, to allow the user to determine their subsequent actions.

Additionally, this seeks to enhance the application's usability, through increasing the probability of the user's input being accepted by the endpoint. Upon the request being sent, should the endpoint reject the request data as being invalid, the user would be required to re-complete the input form, thus hindering the user experience, therefore form validation seeks to mitigate against this issue.

All frontend input field validation was performed using custom JavaScript validation functions, to ensure the validation was lightweight, adding minimal overhead to the frontend application and increasing performance, especially on older or slower devices. Whilst robust validation ensures validation accuracy and reliability, such as that provided by the joi validation framework, it adds unnecessary overhead to the client browser and request times, and is unnecessary where more obscure invalid values will be handled by the backend.

Furthermore, validation may be performed by sending input field data to a backend API validation method, with it subsequently checking and returning the validity of the data, and the results being displayed within the form. Such approaches lead to reduced browser overhead and may lead to more accurate form validation, but lead to significant request overhead, potentially impacting performance on slower network connections.

```
import { assessmentValidation } from '../../../../../schemas/Validation';
const [assessment, errors, handleChange, handleDateChange,
handleRichTextChange, handleSubmit] = Form.useForm(initialAssessment,
conformance, assessmentValidation, onCancel, onSubmit);
```

Figure 5.93 Importation of assessmentValidation and Implementation of useForm Custom Hook

After importing the appropriate validation object, this must be passed to the useForm custom hook, to perform validation on the inputted values, against the defined schema, as shown in Figure 5.93. All form input fields contain validation, with their entered data being passed to a handleChange() function upon each change made to an input field, such as the input of a character. Here, the inputted data is converted into the required data type, where necessary, before being passed to the relevant validation method, depending on the input form element.

```
const validateString = (string, minLength, maxLength) => string.length >=
minLength && string.length <= maxLength;
const validateDate = date => /^(?:\d{4})-(?:\d{2})-
(?:\d{2})T(?:\d{2}):(?:\d{2}):(?:\d{2})(?:\.\d*)?Z$/.test(date);
```

Figure 5.94 Creation of validateString() and validateDate() Functions

Within the Validation.js file, a series of validate() functions are defined, to validate inputted data based on their datatypes, including Strings and dates, as shown in Figure 5.94. Strings may be between a defined minimum and maximum number of characters, due to the size of the acceptable value range, managed by the database.

```
const stringErrorMessage = (fieldName, minLength, maxLength) => `${fieldName}
length is invalid (must be between ${minLength} and ${maxLength} characters)`;
const dateErrorMessage = fieldName => `${fieldName} date is not in a valid
format`;
```

Figure 5.95 Creation of stringErrorMessage() and dateErrorMessage() Functions

A corresponding set of validation error message functions are created, to return the desired String error message, depending on the datatype, as shown in Figure 5.95.

Validation objects are created for each entity, containing an isValid object, with appropriate validation() function calls, depending on the attribute's datatype, and corresponding errorMessage() function calls, to construct a suitable error message, if necessary, as shown in Figure 5.96.

The assessment name is checked to ensure it is between 8 and 75 characters long, the start and end dates and times are checked against the correct regex ISO 8601 date format string, the image URL is checked against the correct regex URL format, and the leader and module IDs are checked to ensure they are not equal to 0.

```

const assessmentValidation = {
  isValid: {
    AssessmentName: (name) => validateString(name, 8, 75),
    AssessmentStartdate: (date) => validateDate(date),
    AssessmentEnddate: (date) => validateDate(date),
    AssessmentImageURI: (url) => validateURL(url),
    AssessmentLeaderID: (id) => validateID(id),
    AssessmentModuleID: (id) => validateID(id),
    AssessmentDescription: (description) => validateString(description, 0,
5000)
  },
  errorMessage: {
    AssessmentName: stringErrorMessage('Assessment name', 8, 75),
    AssessmentStartdate: dateErrorMessage('Assessment start'),
    AssessmentEnddate: dateErrorMessage('Assessment end'),
    AssessmentImageURI: urlErrorMessage('Assessment image'),
    AssessmentLeaderID: idErrorMessage('assessment leader'),
    AssessmentModuleID: idErrorMessage('module'),
    AssessmentDescription: stringErrorMessage('Assessment description', 0,
5000)
  }
};
export { assessmentValidation };

```

Figure 5.96 Creation and Export of assessmentValidation Object

Upon one of the user input fields containing invalid data, the validation test will fail, and an error message will be displayed against the appropriate field. This informs the user of the errors before they submit the form, encouraging them to correct any errors immediately. When the user input field passes the validation check, the error message will be immediately cleared. Before the submission of the form, all input fields are validated simultaneously, to ensure users cannot accidentally submit an empty form.

The user must select an assessment leader and module to associate the new assessment with, so to ensure a user can only link the assessment with an existing assessment leader and module, a dropdown list was implemented. The select component only provides the user with options retrieved from a HTTP GET request, meaning the user is presented with usable information relating to existing items, such as a module or assessment leader name, whilst enforcing valid data input, through ultimately submitting the associated ID value of the selected option from the database.

A detailed explanation of data validation is contained within the useLoad custom hook explanation in subsection 5.8.5 – Component State and Hooks.

5.8.7 Data Conformance

Data conformance involves manipulating input form data into a suitable best-practice JSON format to be sent to the backend API, and converting returned backend API data into a valid format to be displayed or handled within the frontend application. Due to the adherence of best practice within the backend API, data entered into the frontend application's form must be converted into a format that may be accepted and understood by the backend. Although most input field values may be successfully converted to JSON object values, including string and integer values, more complex data types such as dates, require conversion to be suitably understood by the backend API.

The data from the input fields of the assessment leader and module is returned as a String, although these ID values should be of type Integer. These values were converted using the JavaScript `parseInt()` function, to ensure they were stored in the appropriate data type in the database. The date returned from the Flatpickr component is in a JavaScript date format, whereas the HTTP POST endpoint requires dates in the ISO 8601 date format.

All dates retrieved from the Flatpickr were converted into an ISO string using the JavaScript `toISOString()` function, to ensure they were stored in the appropriate data type for the endpoint. Due to the nature of retrieving values from the third-party Flatpickr component, in comparison to the traditional HTML input elements, a different function, `handleDateChange()` required creation, as Flatpickr components return data in a `dateStr`, rather than using event objects.

```
const conformance = {
  integer: ['AssessmentLeaderID', 'AssessmentModuleID'],
  date: ['AssessmentStartdate', 'AssessmentEnddate']
};

const [assessment, errors, handleChange, handleDateChange,
handleRichTextChange, handleSubmit] = Form.useForm(initialAssessment,
conformance, assessmentValidation, onCancel, onSubmit);
```

Figure 5.97 Creation of conformance Object and Implementation of useForm Custom Hook

After declaring a conformance object, containing conformance datatype attributes and arrays containing their corresponding input field names, this must be passed to the `useForm` custom hook, as shown in Figure 5.97. A detailed explanation of data conformance is contained within the `handleChange()` function explanations in subsection 5.8.5 – Component State and Hooks.

5.8.8 Backend API Data Fetch

Due to the application's architecture utilising a separate frontend and backend, with both being separate and self-contained, the frontend is required to be connected to the backend, to facilitate the transfer of the application's persistent data. With the backend being exposed via a series of URL-accessible endpoints, the frontend may utilise the JavaScript Fetch API to make backend requests to retrieve data to be shown on the frontend, and create, update and delete stored backend data, upon the relevant functionality being utilised by the frontend's user. Should the frontend lack access to the backend, data will not be displayed on the frontend, and create, update and delete operations will fail to enact changes on the stored data.

```

import useLoad from '../../../../../api/useLoad';

import { ASSESSMENTLEADERS, MODULES } from '../../../../../api/apiURL';

const [assessmentLeaders, , loadingAssessmentLeadersMessage, ] =
useLoad(ASSESSMENTLEADERS);

```

Figure 5.98 Importation and Implementation of useLoad Custom Hook and Importation of API URLs

The backend API data fetch process is utilised extensively throughout the application, to provide the necessary functionality, including in the assessment form, as shown in Figure 5.98. One example is the use of a HTTP GET request, sent to the '/api/assessmentleaders' endpoint to retrieve the users of type assessment leader.

After importing useLoad, to fetch the data from the backend API, and the appropriate apiURL, the useLoad hook is used to retrieve the assessment leader objects from the associated ASSESSMENTLEADERS endpoint. The useLoad hook returns an array containing two key aspects – the assessmentLeaders array of assessment leader objects retrieved, and the loadingAssessmentLeadersMessage, used for displaying the loading message in place of the input field.

```

<FormInput.APISelectInput
    dataType='Assessment Leader'
    an name='AssessmentLeaderID'
    error={errors.AssessmentLeaderID}
    items={assessmentLeaders}
    loadingMessage={loadingAssessmentLeadersMessage}
    value={assessment.AssessmentLeaderID}
    onChange={handleChange}
/>

```

Figure 5.99 Implementation of APISelectInput Component within Assessment Form

The returned data or error message, where appropriate, from both GET requests is used to populate the associated assessment form input field, as shown in Figure 5.99. The '/api/assessmentleaders' GET request data is used to populate the Assessment Leader dropdown list, allowing the user to select the option of the assessment leader they wish to lead the assessment they are creating.

Due to the nature of asynchronous method calls, a loading message is displayed within the dropdown list, until such time the data has been returned from the endpoint, at which point the dropdown list is re-rendered with the appropriate options. The dropdown list contains the assessment leader or assessment name, although the list item value uses the associated ID, to allow the new assessment to be associated with the appropriate record in the database.

To increase maintainability and facilitate code reuse, the backend API data fetch method has been implemented in an entity-independent function within a separate file, allowing the function to be called with the necessary endpoint and data, reducing unnecessary code duplication across all pages. The data fetch process utilises an asynchronous function to ensure other frontend processes may continue to execute whilst the backend data fetch request is performed. As such, uses of the backend API fetch method must use the associated await reserved word, to indicate the backend data fetch returns a promise, in this case to perform the backend API call.

```
const handleAddSubmit = async (assessment) => {  
    const response = await API.post(ASSESSMENTS, assessment);  
    return response.isSuccess  
        ? loadAssessments(assessmentsEndpoint) || true  
        : false;  
};
```

Figure 5.100 Creation of handleAddSubmit() Function

Upon completion of the form, with the data being successfully validated, the assessment form sends a HTTP POST request to the '/api/assessments' endpoint, to create a new assessment, as shown in Figure 5.100. The new assessment should be inserted and returned, although if unsuccessful, a status message will be returned. After receiving the status message or assessment record, the frontend sends a HTTP GET request to the '/api/users/:uid/assessments' endpoint, to retrieve the assessments the user, in this case of type assessor, has to assess. This is updated to include the newly created assessment, where applicable.

```
import { useState, useEffect } from 'react';  
import API from './API';  
function useLoad(endpoint) {  
    const [records, setRecords] = useState(null);  
    const [loadingMessage, setLoadingMessage] = useState('Loading records ...');  
    const loadRecords = async endpoint => {  
        const response = await API.get(endpoint);  
        response.isSuccess  
            ? setRecords(response.result)  
            : setLoadingMessage(response.message)  
    };  
    useEffect(() => { loadRecords(endpoint) }, [endpoint]);  
    return [records, setRecords, loadingMessage, loadRecords];  
};  
export default useLoad;
```

Figure 5.101 Implementation of useLoad Custom Hook

The useLoad hook accepts a backend API endpoint, used to make the request to, as a prop, as shown in Figure 5.101. It declares two useState hooks, with state being used to store the returned records from the backend API, and set a loading message to display to the user, whilst records are being retrieved. An asynchronous loadRecords method is declared, calling the fetch API's get method with the provided endpoint.

If the response is successful, the returned records are stored within the records state, else the loading message is updated with the returned error message. The loadRecords method is contained within a useEffect hook, with endpoint dependency, to prevent it from infinitely looping when fetching records, otherwise the record state would update, and force the method to rerun. The required state is returned from the hook, and exported for use in other files.

```
const API_URL = 'http://localhost:5000/api';
export const API = {};
API.get = (endpoint) => callFetch(endpoint, 'GET', null);
API.post = (endpoint, data) => callFetch(endpoint, 'POST', data);
API.put = (endpoint, data) => callFetch(endpoint, 'PUT', data);
API.delete = (endpoint) => callFetch(endpoint, 'DELETE', null);
```

Figure 5.102 Declaration of API Base URL and Creation of API get(), post(), put() and delete() Functions

The API.js file contains the Fetch API logic, required to connect the frontend to the backend API, as shown in Figure 5.102. After importing the base URL from the apiURL.js file, an API object is declared, allowing the appropriate functions to be exported using the JavaScript dot syntax, for easier import and use in other files.

The necessary get, post, put and delete functions are declared, used for calling the callFetch() function with the appropriate endpoint, HTTP method, and data, where applicable, to perform the desired CRUD operation on the backend API. Whilst HTTP GET and DELETE methods require no request body, the POST and PUT method bodies must contain the new or updated data object to be created or updated, respectively.

```
export const callFetch = async (endpoint, method, dataObj) => {
  let requestObj = { method: method }; // GET, POST, PUT, DELETE
  if (dataObj) requestObj = {
    ...requestObj,
    headers: { 'Content-type': 'application/json' },
    body: JSON.stringify(dataObj)
  }
}
```

Figure 5.103 Creation of callFetch() Function

After declaring the `callFetch()` function, accepting endpoint URL, HTTP request method, and data object parameters, the request object method is defined, based on the passed HTTP method, as shown in Figure 5.103. If a data object has been provided as a request body, Content-type headers, required by the endpoint for verifying the type of data received, and a JSON-encoded version of the data object body, to be transmitted to the endpoint for creating or updating a record using, are appended to the request object.

```
try {
  let result = null;
  const endpointAddress = API_URL + endpoint;
  const response = await fetch(endpointAddress, requestObj);
  if (response.status !== 204) result = await response.json();
  return (response.status >= 200) && (response.status < 3000)
    ? { isSuccess: true, result: result }
    : { isSuccess: false, message: `Error recovering records: status
code ${response.status}` }
}
catch (error) {
  return { isSuccess: false, message: error.message };
}
}
export default API;
```

Figure 5.104 Creation and Export of Backend API Data Fetch Connection

Using the base URL and desired endpoint, the JavaScript Fetch API is used to create a HTTP request, with the created request object body, with the response being stored, as shown in Figure 5.104. If the response object's HTTP status is not equal to 204, meaning no content is to be received alongside the request, the response's JSON object body is waited upon.

In the case of the response object's HTTP status being valid, the `isSuccess` attribute is set to true and the result is returned, however an exceptional HTTP status results in the `isSuccess` attribute being set to false, and the construction of an error message, based on the response status. Should any errors be present when calling the endpoint using the JavaScript Fetch API, the returned object's `isSuccess` attribute is set to false, and the `message` attribute contains the identified error, which may be identified and reported to the user via a frontend message.

5.8.9 Page Navigation

A foundation of web applications is the ability to view and navigate to different webpages, each containing differing application functionality. Webpage navigation provides the user with the ability to access numerous webpages within the application, each containing their own data objects or offering associated create, edit or delete functions. Whilst typical websites require a complete page refresh for each webpage navigated to, identified by the webpage URL, React mitigates against page reloads by only requesting the necessary components required to be shown or updated within the new webpage.

This navigational behaviour is achieved through the use of the react-router-dom library, which offers routing via individual URLs using its associated BrowserRouter, Routes, Route and NavLink components. Through extracting the entered URL, the BrowserRouter fetches the associated React page component to display, with the underlying React library monitoring changes between the fetched page component and the existing webpage displayed. Any changes result in the appropriate components being fetched from the frontend server, whilst unchanged elements are not re-rendered.

```
import { BrowserRouter, Routes, Route } from 'react-router-dom';
```

Figure 5.105 Importation of BrowserRouter, Routes and Route Components

After installing the react-router-dom library from npm, the BrowserRouter, Routes and Route components must be imported, for use within the App.js file, as shown in Figure 5.105.

```
function App() {  
  return (  
    <UserProvider>  
      <BrowserRouter>  
        <Layout>  
          <Routes>  
            <Route exact path="/" element={<Home />}/>  
            <Route path="/assessments" element={<Assessments />}/>  
            <Route path="/panels" element={<Panels />}/>  
            <Route path="/groups" element={<Groups />}/>  
            <Route path="/modules" element={<Modules />}/>  
            <Route path="/rubrics" element={<Rubrics />}/>  
            <Route path="/comments" element={<Comments />}/>  
            <Route path="/alerts" element={<Alerts />}/>  
            <Route path="/login" element={<Login />}/>  
            <Route path="/" element={<Login />}/>  
            <Route path="*" element={<PageNotFound/>}/>  
          </Routes>  
        </Layout>  
      </BrowserRouter>  
    </UserProvider>  
  );  
};
```

Figure 5.106 Implementation of BrowserRouter, Routes and Route Components within App

Within the App.js file, the frontend application's starting point containing the main component management, the BrowserRouter component is contained, as shown in Figure 5.106. The BrowserRouter is used to store the browser's currently navigated URL, and provide navigation using the browser's navigation history stack. It wraps all defined routes within the application, facilitating navigation of defined pages within the Route paths.

The Routes wrapper component is used to define all child route paths and their corresponding elements, accessible within the application. Each Route component defines a specific URL route and its corresponding element, in this case page components, to be displayed upon the user navigating to the appropriate URL in the browser. These components facilitate the navigation between different page components, based on the URL entered within the browser.

```
import { NavLink } from 'react-router-dom';
function Navbar () {
  const getLinkStyle = ({ isActive }) => (isActive ? 'Selected' : null);
  return (
    <div className='navbar-menu'>
      <div className='navbar-start'>
        <NavLink to='/assessments' className={`navbar-item
${getLinkStyle}`} >Assessments</NavLink>
        <NavLink to='/panels' className={`navbar-item
${getLinkStyle}`} >Panels</NavLink>
        <NavLink to='/groups' className={`navbar-item
${getLinkStyle}`} >Groups</NavLink>
        <NavLink to='/modules' className={`navbar-item
${getLinkStyle}`} >Modules</NavLink>
        <NavLink to='/rubrics' className={`navbar-item
${getLinkStyle}`} >Rubrics</NavLink>
        <NavLink to='/comments' className={`navbar-item
${getLinkStyle}`} >Comments</NavLink>
        <NavLink to='/alerts' className={`navbar-item
${getLinkStyle}`} >Alerts</NavLink>
        <NavLink to='/login' className={`navbar-item
${getLinkStyle}`} >Login</NavLink>
      </div>
    </div>
  );
};
```

Figure 5.107 Importation of NavLink Component and Implementation within Navbar Component

Within the `Navbar.js` file, containing the navigation menu comprising user interface navigation links to relevant pages within the application, the `NavLink` component is imported from the `react-router-dom` library, as shown in Figure 5.107. Each `NavLink` component defines a URL route to navigate to within the browser, relative to the application's base URL, in the `'to'` prop, followed by a CSS class for styling the navigation link item. By default, all `NavLink` items use the `'navbar-item'` class provided by Bulma CSS, with the `getLinkStyle()` function being called to style the selected page in the `Navbar`.

If the current browser URL matches that of one of the `NavLink` `'to'` props, the link is identified as being active, therefore the destructured `'isActive'` prop is true. If `isActive` is truthy, the `'Selected'` CSS class is applied to the `NavLink`, in addition to the Bulma CSS `'navbar-item'` class, else no additional class is added to the `NavLink`. Within the `NavLink` component, the name of the link to be displayed on-screen is passed as a child.

```
.Selected { color: $navbarSelectedColour; }
```

Figure 5.108 Creation of Selected Class SCSS Rulesets

The `'Selected'` class is defined in the `Navbar.scss` file, and contains reference to the `$navbarSelectedColour`, setting the currently selected navigation bar link item to black, as shown in Figure 5.108.

5.8.10 Frontend Styling

SCSS was used to style all created React components within the frontend application. SCSS is a CSS pre-processor, which provides added flexibility and functionality for styling using CSS, as CSS rulesets may be produced in a more concise manner, and translated into CSS at runtime, to be rendered by the browser. All React pages and components were styled using SCSS, to provide consistency and flexibility, whilst also improving the default HTML styling of elements, otherwise provided by browsers.

A significant reason for the use of SCSS was its support for the creation of mixins, which are defined 'functions' containing executable CSS rulesets. These created mixins may be called and 'inserted' into different SCSS files, to provide a series of common styling, with only the mixin requiring importation and definition in the relevant location. Mixins also support parameters, allowing the output of the mixin's CSS styling to be modified, based on the desired inputs.

The use of mixins allows common CSS styles to be declared once and reused throughout the application, rather than requiring all rulesets to be declared across all styling elements or classes. Similarly to the creation reusable React components, mixins improve efficiency and maintainability, as statements can be modified in a centralised location, with these changes being reflected across all instances of the mixin throughout the whole application.

```

@mixin flexCenter($flexDirection) {
    display: flex;
    justify-content: center;
    align-items: center;
    flex-direction: $flexDirection;
}

@mixin defaultShadow() {
    box-shadow: 5px 0px 15px 5px rgba(0.0,0.0,0.0,0.3);
    filter: brightness(95%);
}

```

Figure 5.109 Creation of flexCentre() and defaultShadow() SCSS Mixins

Mixins are declared using the `@mixin` rule, with a suitable name, and relevant parameters being contained within the parentheses, prefixed with dollar signs, as shown in Figure 5.109. Standard CSS rulesets are contained inside the braces, and may include any passed parameters, using the associated dollar sign prefix. The `flexCentre` mixin was created to allow a `div` element to be flexed, with the items being aligned in the centre of the container. The use of the `$flexDirection` parameter allows the flex direction to be set dynamically in the mixin call, facilitating the selection of row or column flex directions.

```

@import "../..../mixins";

div.List {
    @include flexCenter(row);
    flex-wrap: wrap;
    gap: 20px;
}

```

Figure 5.110 Importation of Mixins and Creation of div Element List Class SCSS Rulesets

After importing the mixin, the `@include` rule, followed by the mixin name and parentheses containing the required parameter values, may be used to apply the defined mixin styling to the associated container, as shown in Figure 5.110. Within the list component, the `flexCentre(row)` mixin was used to set the list items within the container to be flexed from the centre of the container, in the row direction.

SCSS also supports the declaration of variables, which allow styling values to be defined in one location, and subsequently imported and applied to multiple locations or CSS rules, further improving CSS maintainability. Instead of the traditional CSS approach of hard-coding CSS rule values, including those used for font size or colour schemes, SCSS variables may be utilised, meaning all variables of the same type may utilise a variable containing the common value.

As such, should the colour or size value require modification, all instances may be updated simultaneously, via changing the variable value, which would be reflected upon all uses of the variable across the application. The use of variables significantly increases the maintainability and updatability of the application, with consistent styling changes being able to be applied quickly and easily from one location.

```
$formInputLabelTextSize: 15px;
$formInputTextSize: 12px;
$formBackgroundColour: White;
$formErrorTextColour: darken(#edafb8, 20%);
$formAdviceColour: darken(#29e7cd, 10%);
$formBorderColour: LightGrey;
$formInputDisabledColour: Grey;
```

Figure 5.111 Creation of SCSS Variables

SCSS variables are declared using the dollar sign, followed by the variable name, a colon, and the variable value, as shown in Figure 5.111. Variables are commonly used to contain font size and colour values, although they may contain CSS functions, such as the `darken()` function used to make a given colour darker, based on the provided value.

```
@import "../../variables";
select, input, textarea {
  width: 100%;
  padding: 3px;
  margin: 1px 0;
  font-size: 100%;
  border-radius: 0px;
  border: 1px solid $formBorderColour;
  background: $formBackgroundColour;
}
```

Figure 5.112 Importation of Variables and Creation of select, input and textarea SCSS Rulesets

After importing the necessary variables, these may be inserted in CSS rulesets in place of a constant value, instead offering the ruleset the value defined in the variable, as shown in Figure 5.112. Upon the SCSS compilation into CSS, all variables will be replaced with their corresponding value, meaning the `$formBorderColour` will be substituted for the constant `LightGrey`. This step is necessary, as browsers are unable to render SCSS, with it instead requiring pre-processing into CSS before being provided to the browser.

```
function Footer() {
  return (
    <footer className='Footer'>
      <p>&copy; 2022 MarkIt</p>
      <h6>All icons courtesy of <a
href='https://img.icons8.com/'>icons8.com</a></h6>
    </footer>
  );
};
```

Figure 5.113 Creation of Footer Component

```
footer.Footer {
  height: 75px;
  margin-top: 50px;
  display: grid;
  place-items: center;
  border-top: 1px solid black;
  background-color: rebeccapurple;
  & a {
    color: black;
    text-decoration: none;
  }
}
```

Figure 5.114 Creation of footer Element Footer Class SCSS Rulesets

Initially, the application was developed using wholly custom SCSS rulesets, with all styling being implemented by the development team, as shown in Figure 5.113 and Figure 5.114. The footer element used the Footer CSS class to set the display size and colour scheme, with the background having a colour of rebeccapurple, and link text being black with no underline.

Following the first sprint, the user interface, although not unusable, was identified by the client as being relatively unattractive. The created icons did not change colour, and the produced webpage consisted of a relatively basic design and colour choice, thus lacking user-friendliness and appeal to most users. It was subsequently identified that styling modifications were required, to ensure users' use of the application's functionality was not hindered by a difficult to use user interface.

Consequently, research was conducted into possible UI design frameworks, which would rectify all existing styling issues within the application, with styling better than that achievable by the development team, without requiring excessive time. Based on research of UI design frameworks, it was realised that Bulma CSS was the most suitable framework to adopt for the frontend user interface design (Bulma, no date). When investigating the strengths and pitfalls of the Material UI design framework (Material UI, no date), it was decided that this would require too much modification of the existing frontend code.

As Material UI provides its own components, all existing frontend reusable components would require substitution for the equivalent Material UI component, thus rendering all of the existing frontend implementation redundant. Due to time constraints imposed on the project, there would likely not be enough time to migrate the frontend to use Material UI.

It must also be noted that where Material UI fails to offer a suitable reusable component, this would require the unique creation of a Material UI-style equivalent, which may appear visibly different, reducing the user experience of the website.

It was therefore realised a different framework approach would be required, notably one which would integrate with the existing React components created within the frontend, and seek to only provide styling to components. Bulma CSS offers a modern, flexbox-based approach to component styling, through providing a pure CSS-only framework. It is available in a SCSS format, meaning it may integrate with the existing SCSS stylesheets used throughout the frontend, and may utilise mixins and variables.

Bulma also allows additional SCSS styling to override the default styling options, meaning component or webpage-specific styling may be applied, where necessary. As Bulma does not provide integrated React components, HTML or JavaScript, it will provide less overhead and potential interactions with the existing frontend implementation, only affecting the styling of the webpage components. Such interactivity is already provided by the existing JavaScript functionality contained within the webpages, therefore it is not required to be provided by the framework.

The Bulma SCSS styling rulesets may be applied to the relevant user interface components, without requiring modification to the frontend, to produce a more consistent, aesthetically pleasing, and usable website. Bulma will not be used to provide component layout within the webpage, with this being controlled manually via the existing SCSS rulesets, offering greater webpage layout flexibility.

Upon installing the Bulma SCSS framework, using npm, all core elements were re-styled using the defined Bulma CSS rulesets. Bulma offers a range of pre-built style classes for all component types, including navigation bars, footers, cards, forms and form input fields, ensuring consistency across the while website component appearance.

Whilst Bulma significantly reduces the development time required to produce a visually-appealing frontend, through its use of pre-built styling rulesets, it is excellent for creating modern, aesthetically pleasing websites, in turn contributing to an increase in usability. For developers with a distinct lack of artistic quality, Bulma can enhance otherwise feature-rich and design-poor websites, elevating them to appear user-friendly, therefore the development team identified the benefits it could offer to the project.

```
@charset "utf-8";  
  
@import "../..../node_modules/bulma/bulma.sass";
```

Figure 5.115 Definition of Charset and Importation of Bulma CSS' SCSS Framework

As defined by Bulma CSS best-practice, a 'mystyles.scss' SCSS file was created, containing the import of the Bulma SCSS framework, alongside any re-definitions of Bulma SCSS variables, such as colour schemes, as shown in Figure 5.115. After evaluating the default Bulma SCSS colour theme, it was decided that this best fit the original colours used during the created medium fidelity wireframes, therefore there was no requirement to override any of the existing SCSS styles.

```
import '../..../sass/mystyles.scss';

function Footer() {
  return (
    <footer className='footer'>
      <div className='content has-text-centered'>
        <div className='content-container'>
          <div className='content-column'>
            <NavLink to='/help' className='navbar-item
link'>Help</NavLink>
            <NavLink to='/terms' className='navbar-item link'>Terms
of Service</NavLink>
            <NavLink to='/contact' className='navbar-item
link'>Contact Us</NavLink>
          </div>
          <div className='content-column'>
            <NavLink to='/cookie-policy' className='navbar-item
link'>Cookie Policy</NavLink>
            <NavLink to='/privacy-policy' className='navbar-item
link'>Privacy Policy</NavLink>
          </div>
        </div>
        <p className='copyright-notice'>&copy; 2023 MarkIt Limited</p>
        <p className='courtesy-message'>All icons courtesy of Font
Awesome; CSS styling courtesy of Bulma</p>
      </div>
    </footer>
  );
};
```

Figure 5.116 Importation of Bulma SCSS and Creation of Footer Component utilising Bulma SCSS

Upon importing the Bulma SCSS stylesheet within the 'mystyles.scss' file, this file may be imported within any necessary component files, where Bulma SCSS is required, as shown in Figure 5.116. The associated Bulma CSS classes may be applied to components, via the standard 'className' prop, in order to apply the Bulma stylesheet to the component. Bulma SCSS rulesets may be applied in conjunction with existing application-specific SCSS rules, such as the 'copyright-notice' and 'courtesy-message' classes imported from the custom './Footer.scss' file.

To successfully utilise Bulma styling, the Bulma SCSS documentation must be heavily consulted. Bulma lists comprehensive documentation, including example implementations and included SCSS classes. Such classes may be applied, where appropriate, to relevant components within the user interface. Often, Bulma requires nested SCSS components to provide appropriate styling, which may be achieved through the creation of additional 'div' wrapper components, utilising the necessary SCSS class rules.

The 'footer' class defines the top-tier footer component styling. Within the footer, the associated footer content must be contained within a div with the 'content' class applied, meaning the child rulesets applied relate to the components contained within the footer. The 'has-text-centered' class ensures that the text contained within the content parent element in the footer will be centred within the footer.

Two div components with the 'content-column' class are contained within a 'content-container' div, to wrap the main links and create two flexbox-based column wrappers, to contain the associated links. All links utilise the 'navbar-item' and 'link' classes, to ensure appropriate styling and consistency across both the footer and navbar.

```
// Imports -----
@import "../mixins";
// Styling -----
.content-container {
  @include flexCenter(row);
  column-gap: 20%;
  align-items: flex-start;
}
.link {
  font-size: 15px;
  font-weight: bold;
}
.copyright-notice {
  font-size: 13px;
}
.courtesy-message {
  font-size: 10px;
}
```

Figure 5.117 Footer Component Custom SCSS Rulesets Following Bulma SCSS Use

As styling is managed by Bulma CSS, the custom SCSS rulesets are only used for setting the layout of items within the footer, using the flexCentre(row) mixin to set all items to be centred within the div element with the content-container class, and font sizes of footer content, as shown in Figure 5.117.

```

import '../..//sass/mystyles.scss';

function Header() {
  const { userFirstName } = useContext(UserContext);
  return (
    <header className='Header'>
      <nav className='navbar is-fixed-top is-light'>
        <div className='navbar-brand'>
          <div className='navbar-item'><Link to='/'><img
className='logo' src='/logo.png'/></Link></div>
        </div>
        <Navbar />
        <div className='navbar-end'>
          <div className='navbar-item has-dropdown is-hoverable'>
            <a className='navbar-link'>
              <div className='user-container'>
                <Icon.User />
                <p>`Welcome ${userFirstName}!`</p>
              </div>
            </a>
            <div className='navbar-dropdown'>
              <NavLink to='/profile' className='navbar-item'
onClick={ (event) => { event.target.blur(); } }>Profile</NavLink>
              <NavLink to='/alerts' className='navbar-item'
onClick={ (event) => { event.target.blur(); } }>Alerts</NavLink>
              <hr className='navbar-divider' />
              <NavLink to='/logout' className='navbar-item'
onClick={ (event) => { event.target.blur(); } }>Log Out</NavLink>
            </div>
          </div>
        </div>
      </nav>
    </header>
  );
};

```

Figure 5.118 Importation of Bulma SCSS and Creation of Header Component utilising Bulma SCSS

Similarly, the 'navbar' class is attached to the navbar, to apply defined Bulma navbar styling to the nav component, as shown in Figure 5.118. The 'is-fixed-top' modifier class ensures the navbar is sticky, and always displayed at the top of the webpage, regardless of user scrolling within the page, whilst the 'is-light' class defines the light colour scheme to use for the navigation bar. The 'navbar-brand' class is used to define leftmost navbar styling, such as for the website logo, whilst the 'navbar-end' class is used for rightmost navbar styling elements.

The 'navbar-item has-dropdown is-hoverable' ruleset creates a navigation bar item with an associated hoverable dropdown list, used for defining the functionality associated with the user's account. Such functionality is defined within the 'navbar-dropdown' class, with the hr element containing the 'navbar-divider' class, used for separating the login option from the remaining dropdown list items.

Due to the nature of the React SPA frontend application, the navbar dropdown menu usually remains open upon the user selecting an option, and only clears upon the new linked webpage being downloaded and rendered within the browser. As no page refresh cycles occur with React, the dropdown menu would continue to stay open, even upon the page content updating. As such, the use of the `onClick event.target.blur()` anonymous function ensures that the dropdown list is hidden, upon clicking on a list item.

Consequently, Bulma CSS was used to provide the application styling, although custom SCSS rulesets were still applied to configure page layout. Whilst Bulma offers an excellent UI framework, it is unable to provide the desired webpage layout and component positioning, to ensure the application's frontend usability and adherence to the created wireframes, is suitably fulfilled. It is therefore necessary to add custom SCSS classes to components, in addition to their Bulma CSS styling classes, for the management of layout.

The developed user interface is only suitable for viewing on a desktop browser with a large viewable area. Based on client and prospective user interviews, it was decided that there was only a current requirement for the user interface to have a desktop layout, as the overwhelming majority of users do not access university-related tools from their mobile devices. This led to the creation of the application's desktop layout, with there being no current intentions of producing a tablet or mobile device layout, unless all user stories were to be fulfilled in the current desktop view implementation. Due to project time constraints, it was not feasible to implement both core functionality and the mobile webpage styling.

5.8.11 Frontend Structure

The use of a suitable frontend application directory and file structure provides significant benefit to the maintainability of the web application. Whilst poor structures and naming conventions can increase the difficulty for which necessary files and code may be found, separating logic into files and directories with appropriate names can both increase maintainability, as code requiring maintenance may be easily identified, and increase updatability, as developers working in a team are able to work on different elements of the application simultaneously, without posing risk to their co-workers' code.

- > public
- ▼ src
 - > api
 - ▼ components
 - > layouts
 - > pages
 - ▼ ui
 - > button
 - > card
 - ▼ entities
 - > alerts
 - > assessments
 - > comments
 - > groups
 - > login
 - ▼ modules
 - JS ModuleForm.js
 - JS ModuleItem.js
 - JS ModuleList.js
 - > panels
 - > rubrics
 - ▼ form
 - JS Form.js
 - 🔗 Form.scss
 - JS FormField.js
 - 🔗 FormField.scss
 - JS FormInput.js
 - > icon
 - > image
 - > item
 - ▼ list
 - JS List.js
 - 🔗 List.scss
 - > contexts
 - > helpers
 - > sass
 - > schemas
 - 🔗 _mixins.scss
 - 🔗 _variables.scss
 - JS App.js
 - 🔗 App.scss
 - JS index.js
 - 🔒 .gitignore
 - { } package-lock.json
 - { } package.json
 - 📘 README.md

Figure 5.119 Frontend Directory and File Structure

Consequently, all frontend application code is structured using a suitable file and directory structure, with conventions being outlined and strictly followed from the beginning of the project, as shown in Figure 5.119. Files use a clear file name, typically the same as their exported function or component, and generally only contain one exported function or component, to make file identification easier, and reduce the potential for multiple developers to cause risk to created components.

In the case of buttons and icons, a singular file contains all button and icon components, due to this simplifying imports of groups of similar components, rather than having to import them individually. This improves code maintainability, as changes to the directory structure or component names will not require updates to be performed in each file using the component.

All code is contained within a directory named after the type of components contained within the directory. For example, buttons are contained within the button directory, within the ui directory, contained in the components directory. This structure allows component files to be easily located, whilst offering a clear file structure traversal when importing components to be reused in other components. An entities directory is used to store directories containing specific components associated with a contextual aspect of the application, such as an assessment or module. These typically implement reusable components, with them then applying context-specific functionality, such as an assessment form or assessment list.

The main app logic, including webpage routing, is contained within `app.js`, with all subsidiary components contained within the appropriate directories. An `api` directory with an `API.js` and `apiConfig.js` file is present, to handle all API calls separately from the main frontend logic. This increases maintainability, as the API could theoretically be changed, without requiring modification of the frontend components. All directory names utilise lowercase, while file names typically use sentence case. This allows for easy identification and differentiation between files and directories, improving maintainability.

Within the webpage structure, all pages follow the layout defined in the `Layout` component within the `Layout.js` file, as shown in Figure 5.120. Pages contain a `Header` component, which in turn comprises a `Navbar` component, followed by content, passed in the `children` prop, and a `Footer` component, containing less important links, unsuitable for the `Navbar`. When navigating between pages, the header and footer remain consistent, although the content changes, due to the necessary page data component being passed to the `Layout` component as a prop, within the element defined in the `Route` component in `App.js`.

```

import Header from './Header';
import Footer from './Footer';
import './Layout.scss';
function Layout({ children }) {
  return (
    <div className='Layout'>
      <div className='Header'>
        <Header />
      </div>
      <main className='Content'>
        { children }
      </main>
      <div className='Footer'>
        <Footer />
      </div>
    </div>
  );
};
export default Layout;

```

Figure 5.120 Creation of Layout Component

5.8.12 Implementation of Key Features

During the implementation of the system, a range of must have requirements were implemented, as identified and agreed with the client during the commencement of each sprint. This subsection will examine the implemented core system functionality from the client's perspective, as interacted through the application's frontend user interface.

The application's homepage, as shown in Figure 5.121, displays the user's enrolled assessments and, in the case of an assessment leader, the assessments they are responsible for managing. If the user is an assessment leader, they may create a new assessment using the 'New Assessment' button, although such functionality is not accessible by other user account types. Assessment leaders may edit and delete assessments they are tasked with overseeing, whilst all user types may favourite an assessment, for ease of future location.

Figure 5.121 Home page displaying assessments

Figure 5.122 Create new assessment

The assessment form, as displayed in Figure 5.122, facilitates the input of assessment details including the assessment's name, start and end date, image URL, leader, module and description. The assessment start and end date are inputted using a datetime picker, ensuring the input of such values is intuitive and user-friendly, whilst dropdown lists containing the available assessment leaders and modules, offer fast assessment creation. A rich text editor accepts assessment description input, providing enhanced flexibility in the display of assessment content to students.

Figure 5.123 View assessment details

All user types may view the details for the assessments they are enrolled on or manage, as shown in Figure 5.123. In the case of students, the assessment details and description provide invaluable information into the assessment format, submission details or structure of the presentation event. Within an assessment, a user may view the groups, panels and rubrics related to the assessment, offering insight into the assessment marking scheme and assessors.

Figure 5.124 View assessment groups

The groups contained within an assessment may be viewed by all user types, as shown within Figure 5.124, with assessment leaders being able to create new groups, and both assessment leaders and assessors provided with the ability to edit and delete groups. Through assessment leaders and assessors being able to edit groups, this allows for the immediate moderation and removal of inappropriate group names or biographies, as input by student groups.

Figure 5.125 Create new assessment group

An assessment leader may create a new group through using the group form, as shown in Figure 5.125. The group form offers an efficient and intuitive mechanism for creating new groups, through its use of a drag and drop input. The assessment leader may simply drag the students they wish to add to the group from the available list of students enrolled within the assessment, before dropping their selected students within the droppable area.

The group leader, responsible for managing the group, facilitating contact between the panel or assessment leader, and submitting the group's work, may be selected through double-clicking on a chosen student. To re-assign the role of group leader to a different group member, double-clicking on another student will automatically re-assign the role to the last selected student.

Figure 5.126 View assessment group details

All user types may view a group's profile to gain further information regarding a group, as shown in Figure 5.126. Through viewing group profiles, assessors may gain an insight into the groups they are to assess, thus increasing their understanding of the group's interests and hobbies.

In the case of assessors, the ability to grade an assessment is displayed, whilst assessment leaders are able to publish or unpublish provided assessment feedback. This allows for feedback to be created, to disseminate to students, being hidden until such time as feedback has been moderated or provided for all groups. Errors within feedback may be corrected whilst the feedback is unpublished, prior to being re-published. Group members may view the assessment feedback for their own groups, to gain knowledge into their presentation's strengths and weaknesses.

Figure 5.127 View assessment panels

The panels contained within an assessment may be viewed by all user types, as shown within Figure 5.127, with assessment leaders being able to create new panels, and both assessment leaders and assessors provided with the ability to edit and delete panels. Through assessors being able to edit their panel profile, this allows them to include information surrounding their career journey, interests and experience, allowing students to gain a greater understanding into their assessors.

Figure 5.128 View assessment panel details

All user types may view a panel's profile to gain further information regarding a panel, as shown in Figure 5.128. Through viewing panel profiles, students may gain an insight into the panels they are to be assessed by, thus increasing their understanding into their interests, hobbies, experience and potential career paths, aiding in the teaching of employability.

Figure 5.129 View assessment rubrics

The rubrics contained within an assessment may be viewed by all user types, as shown within Figure 5.129, with assessment leaders being able to create, edit and delete assessment rubrics. Through users being able to view assessment rubrics, assessors can gain a greater understanding into the criteria they are to mark against, and students are offered insight into the work expected of them.

Figure 5.130 View assessment rubric comments

The pre-configured rubric comments contained within an assessment’s rubric may be viewed by all user types, as shown within Figure 5.130, with assessment leaders being able to create, edit and delete assessment rubric comments. Through users being able to view assessment rubric comments, assessors can gain a greater understanding into the criteria they are to mark against, and students are offered insight into the work expected of them.

Figure 5.131 Mark group’s assessment

A group’s assessment may be marked by an assessor or assessment leader, providing the group with feedback and grades for all rubrics, as shown in Figure 5.131. This facilitates fast and efficient marking, collation and dissemination of feedback to students, thus reducing the administration time required during and after panel-based assessment.

Figure 5.132 Login screen

The system contains a login screen, facilitating access to different users, each with their own accounts. Access is granted upon a user correctly entering a matching account email and password, providing the user with access to their personal enrolled assessments, groups and panels within the system.

This subsection discussed the implemented core system functionality, as intended to be used by the client, as interacted through the application's frontend user interface. Such functionality fulfils many of the must have requirements, as previously elicited from the client, and adheres to the system designs produced earlier.

5.8.13 Conclusion

This subsection evaluated the different frontend platforms available, identifying React as offering the most suitable platform for the project. The implementation of the frontend, used for providing a user-friendly mechanism for users to interact with the application, was discussed, including the creation of custom reusable components, for maintainability. The use of existing third-party components was explored, examining their cross-platform and reduced development time benefits.

The creation and management of component state was examined, ensuring re-rendering only occurs on modified components, thus enhancing application performance, with custom hooks being created for enhanced maintainability. Form input validation and data conformance was discussed, highlighting the necessity for ensuring transmitted data is in a suitable format to be received by the backend API. The use of the JavaScript Fetch API, to connect the frontend to the backend API for data communication, was explored. Page navigation was detailed, with the importance of producing navigable pages containing separated content, to increase application usability. The frontend application styling, and use of Bulma CSS to enhance frontend aesthetics, was highlighted, before the use of file and directory structure to enhance maintainability was discussed.

5.9 Refactoring

Refactoring is the process whereby existing developed code is improved, to mitigate against identified code smells and revise its structure and design, without affecting the code's behaviour. The refactoring process is integral to benefitting the system's maintainability and future updatability, due to offering increased readability, code reuse and a reduction in code duplication. As such, the risks of inconsistency across future application updates is reduced, leading to potentially increased system reliability and reduced potential of bugs. This subsection will explore the refactoring undertaken throughout the system, detailing the opportunities identified and resulting code enhancements made.

5.9.1 Backend Refactoring

During the development of the backend API, refactoring was performed following the implementation of each sprint, based on identified code smells. As previously discussed, refactoring provides numerous benefits to the developed system, reducing repeated code and improving system maintainability. This subsection will detail the refactoring enacted on the opportunities identified within the developed backend API.

During refactoring, it was noted that the `getController()` functions used to validate ID fields, build the necessary resource selection SQL statements, to retrieve the appropriate data from the database, and return the relevant HTTP status code and JSON data object contained significant repeated code, as shown in Figure 5.133. It could be observed that all controllers contain the same logic, with the only differences being the ID validation schema used, and the SQL statement builder function used to generate the required SQL.

Consequently, to increase code reuse, and improve maintainability, these `getController()` functions were extracted into a `get()` function, which may be called with the appropriate `createQuery()` function to build the necessary SQL to retrieve the data, as shown in Figure 5.134. The `validateID` parameter was used as a substitute for comparing the variant against the controller variant, benefitting code readability.

The associated `read()` function is used to execute the provided query and return the desired response which, when combined with the `get()` function, replicates all provided `getController()` functionality, with no code duplication, as shown in Figure 5.135.

Similarly, it was noted that the `postController()`, `putController()` and `deleteController()` functions used to validate request bodies, perform conformance on the retrieved object, build the necessary resource insertion, updating and deletion SQL statements, to perform the necessary action, subsequently retrieve the appropriate data from the database, and return the relevant HTTP status code and JSON data object, contained significant repeated code. Such functions were refactored in the same manner as the `getController()`, utilising `create()`, `update()` and `delete()` functions respectively.

```

const getUsersController = async (req, res, variant, whereField) => {

  const id = req.params.pid;

  if (id) {

    const { error } = userIdSchema.validate(id);

    if (error) return res.status(400).json({message: reportIdError(error)});

  }

  const sql = buildUsersSelectSql(id, variant, whereField);

  const { isSuccess, result, message } = await read(sql);

  isSuccess ? res.status(200).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});

};

const getModulesController = async (req, res, variant, whereField) => {

  const id = req.params.pid;

  if (id) {

    const { error } = assessmentIdSchema.validate(id);

    if (error) return res.status(400).json({message: reportIdError(error)});

  }

  const sql = buildModulesSelectSql(id, variant, whereField);

  const { isSuccess, result, message } = await read(sql);

  isSuccess ? res.status(200).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});

};

```

Figure 5.133 Prior to refactoring – repetition of getController() functions for each type of resource

It was also noted that there was significant repetition in the statements required to append WHERE clauses and their associated fields and values to the created SQL SELECT statement, based on the ID values provided, as shown in Figure 5.136. Across each buildSelectSql() function, the same code block of 'if' statements ensured 'WHERE' and/or 'AND' fields were added to the created SQL statement, depending on if an ID value and associated where field attribute was provided. As such, to reduce repeated code, increasing code readability, the WHERE field functionality was extracted into a 'where' method, called within each buildSelectSql() function, as shown in Figure 5.137.

```

sqlldb.get = async (req, res, createQuery, validateId, variant,
primaryWhereField, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryWhereField) => {

    let primaryId = req.params.pid;

    let secondaryId = req.params.sid;

    let tertiaryId = req.params.tid;

    if (validateId || primaryId) {

        const { error } = Validation.idSchema(true).validate(primaryId);

        if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});

    }

    if (secondaryWhereField) {

        const { error } = Validation.idSchema(true).validate(secondaryId);

        if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});

    }

    if (tertiaryWhereField) {

        const { error } = Validation.idSchema(true).validate(tertiaryId);

        if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});

    }

    const sql = createQuery(primaryId, secondaryId, tertiaryId, variant,
primaryWhereField, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryWhereField);

    const { isSuccess, result, message } = await sqlldbController.read(sql);

    isSuccess ? res.status(200).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});

};

```

Figure 5.134 After refactoring – creation of single get() function

```

sqlldbController.read = async (selectSql) => {
  try {
    const [result] = await database.query(selectSql);
    return (result.length === 0)
      ? { isSuccess: false, result: null, message: 'No record(s) found' }
      : { isSuccess: true, result, message: 'Record(s) successfully
recovered' };
  }
  catch (error) {
    return { isSuccess: false, result: null, message: `Failed to execute
query: ${error.message}` };
  }
};

```

Figure 5.135 After refactoring – creation of single read() function

```

const buildUsersSelectSql = (id, variant, whereField) => {
  let sql = '';
  const table = 'Users LEFT JOIN Usertypes ON
Users.UserUsertypeID=Usertypes.UsertypeID';
  const fields =
['UserID', 'UserTitle', 'UserFirstname', 'UserMiddlename', 'UserLastname',
'UserEmail', 'UserUsertypeID', 'UsertypeName', 'UsertypeDescription'];
  sql = `SELECT ${fields} FROM ${table}`;
  if (id) sql += ` WHERE ${whereField}=${id}`;
  return sql;
};

const buildModulesSelectSql = (id, variant, whereField) => {
  let sql = '';
  const table = 'Modules LEFT JOIN Users ON
Modules.ModuleLeaderID=Users.UserID LEFT JOIN Usertypes ON Users.UserUsertypeID
=Usertypes.UsertypeID';
  const fields = ['ModuleID', 'ModuleCode', 'ModuleName', 'ModuleLevel',
'ModuleDescription', 'ModuleLeaderID', 'UserTitle', 'UserFirstname',
'UserMiddlename', 'UserLastname', 'UserEmail', 'UserUsertypeID',
'UsertypeName', 'UsertypeDescription'];
  sql = `SELECT ${fields} FROM ${table}`;
  if (id) sql += ` WHERE ${whereField}=${id}`;
  return sql;
};

```

Figure 5.136 Prior to refactoring – repetition of appending WHERE clause fields to SQL statement

```

const buildSelectStatement = (table, fields, includeWhere, primaryId,
primaryWhereField, secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId,
tertiaryWhereField, whereField) => {
    let sql = '';
    sql = `SELECT ${fields} FROM ${table}`;
    sql += sqlDb.where(whereField, includeWhere, primaryId, primaryWhereField,
secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId, tertiaryWhereField);
    return sql;
};

sqlDb.where = (whereField, whereRequired, primaryId, primaryWhereField,
secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId, tertiaryWhereField) => {
    let sql = '';
    if (whereRequired && ((primaryId && primaryWhereField) || (secondaryId &&
secondaryWhereField) || (tertiaryId && tertiaryWhereField))) sql += ` WHERE`;
    if (whereField) sql += whereField;
    if (!whereRequired && (primaryId && primaryWhereField)) sql+= ` AND`;
    if (primaryId) sql += ` ${primaryWhereField}=${primaryId}`;
    if (secondaryId) sql += ` AND ${secondaryWhereField}=${secondaryId}`;
    if (tertiaryId) sql += ` AND ${tertiaryWhereField}=${tertiaryId}`;
    return sql;
};

```

Figure 5.137 After refactoring – creation of where() function for constructing SQL SELECT statement

```

const table = 'Panels';
const fields =
['PanelName', 'PanelImageURI', 'PanelBiography', 'PanelAssessmentID', 'PanelLeaderID'];
let sql = `INSERT INTO ${table} SET
    ${fields[0]}="${conformanceObject['PanelName']}",
    ${fields[1]}="${conformanceObject['PanelImageURI']}",
    ${fields[2]}="${conformanceObject['PanelBiography']}",
    ${fields[3]}="${conformanceObject['PanelAssessmentID']}",
    ${fields[4]}=${conformanceObject['PanelLeaderID']}`;

```

Figure 5.138 Prior to refactoring – repetition of attributes in SQL statement 'SET' clauses

Within each putController() and postController() function, it was noted that there was repetition of the declaration and appending of the associated value within the creation of the INSERT or UPDATE SQL statement, as shown in Figure 5.138. Whilst reducing code readability, such repetition also hindered the maintainability of the statement, as the hard-coded object value definitions cannot be easily substituted or modified, should the schema of the object be changed.

As such, a `buildSetRecord()` function was created, which iterates over the provided record's keys, creating a template string for inserting the object within the SQL database, as shown in Figure 5.139. This may be passed alongside the data object, to be executed on the database, ensuring SQL prepared statements are used to prevent the risks of SQL injection attacks, whilst increasing code maintainability, through not using hard-coded value definitions. This method was called within both the post and put methods, whilst constructing the necessary data access SQL statement.

```
const buildSetTemplate = record => {
  const arrayOfKeys = Object.keys(record);
  return arrayOfKeys.reduce((prev, curr, index) => prev + `${curr}=${curr}`
+ (index === (arrayOfKeys.length-1) ? ' ' : ', '), 'SET ');
};
```

Figure 5.139 After refactoring – creation of `buildSetTemplate()` function for creating SQL 'SET' values

It was noted that all endpoint resource location URL paths began with the same global base URL of `/api`, as shown in Figure 5.140. The base URL both contributes to code duplication, whilst also significantly hindering code maintainability. Currently, with the base URL being hard-coded, should any changes be required to the base URL value, these would have to be manually updated across all defined endpoints.

This could lead to some endpoint URLs not being updated, leading to severe inconsistency across the application. To mitigate this issue, a router, `appRouter`, was created, which allows the base URL to be set, and corresponding further resource locator values will be passed to the appropriate endpoint, as shown in Figure 5.141.

Any changes to the base URL are only required to be updated at the base `appRouter`, and will automatically update all attached URLs. This may be used in the future, should a v2 of the endpoints be created, in which case a further router and endpoint may be created, adopting the v2 base URL.

```
app.get('/api/users', (req, res) =>
getUsersController(req, res, 'users', 'UserID'));

app.get('/api/users/:pid', (req, res) =>
getUsersController(req, res, 'users', 'UserID'));
```

Figure 5.140 Prior to refactoring – repetition of resource location base URL in endpoint definitions

```
const appRouter = express.Router();

app.use('/api', appRouter);

appRouter.get('/users', (req, res) =>
sqlDb.get(req, res, retrieve.users, false, 'users'));

appRouter.get('/users/:pid', (req, res) =>
sqlDb.get(req, res, retrieve.users, true, 'users', 'UserID'));
```

Figure 5.141 After refactoring – extraction of resource location base URL into global router

```

const buildAssessmentLeadersSelectSql = (id, variant, whereField) => {
    let sql = '';
    const table = 'Users';
    const fields = ['UserID AS AssessmentLeaderID', 'UserTitle AS
AssessmentLeaderTitle', 'UserFirstname AS
AssessmentLeaderFirstname', 'UserMiddlename AS
AssessmentLeaderMiddlename', 'UserLastname AS AssessmentLeaderLastname',
'UserEmail AS AssessmentLeaderEmail'];
    sql = `SELECT ${fields} FROM ${table}`;
    sql += ` WHERE ${whereField}=2`;
    if (id) sql += ` AND ${whereField}=${id}`;
    return sql;
};

const buildAssessorsSelectSql = (id, variant, whereField) => {
    let sql = '';
    const table = 'Users';
    const fields = ['UserID AS AssessorID', 'UserTitle AS
AssessorTitle', 'UserFirstname AS AssessorFirstname', 'UserMiddlename AS
AssessorMiddlename', 'UserLastname AS AssessorLastname', 'UserEmail AS
AssessorEmail'];
    sql = `SELECT ${fields} FROM ${table}`;
    sql += ` WHERE ${whereField}=3`;
    if (id) sql += ` AND ${whereField}=${id}`;
    return sql;
};

```

Figure 5.142 Prior to refactoring – repetition of field names in build[UsersOfType]SelectSql() functions

It was identified that there was significant repetition across all buildSelectSql() statements used to create SQL statements for retrieving users of different usertypes, such as assessment leaders, assessors, students and administrators, as shown in Figure 5.142. With the exception of the field aliasing used to return the attribute names with respect to the usertype requested, and the userUsertypeID used to select appropriate records, all other field and table names remained consistent.

As such, it was identified that a getUserType() function should be created, to return an array of the usertypeID and associated aliasing name, based on the provided variant, as shown in Figure 5.143. This ensures a single function may be used to return all users of a required type, with full aliasing functionality, increasing code reuse and maintainability.

```

const getUserType = variant => {
  switch(variant) {
    case 'students':
      return ['1','Student'];
    case 'assessmentleaders':
      return ['2','AssessmentLeader'];
    case 'assessors':
      return ['3','Assessor'];
    case 'administrators':
      return ['4','Administrator'];
    default:
      return ['(1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4)','User'];
  }
};

retrieve.usertypeusers = (primaryId, secondaryId, tertiaryId, variant,
primaryWhereField, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryWhereField) => {
  const table = 'Users';
  const userType = getUserType(variant)

  const fields = [`UserID AS ${userType[1]}ID`,`UserTitle AS
${userType[1]}Title`,`UserFirstname AS ${userType[1]}Firstname`,`UserMiddlename
AS ${userType[1]}Middlename`,`UserLastname AS
${userType[1]}Lastname`,`UserEmail AS ${userType[1]}Email`];

  return buildSelectStatement(table, fields, false, primaryId,
primaryWhereField, secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId,
tertiaryWhereField, ` WHERE UserUsertypeID=${userType[0]}`);
};

```

Figure 5.143 After refactoring – creation of getUserType() and usertypeusers() functions

```

const buildSelectStatement = (table, fields, includeWhere, primaryId,
primaryWhereField, secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId,
tertiaryWhereField, whereField) => {

    let sql = '';

    sql = `SELECT ${fields} FROM ${table}`;

    sql += sqldb.where(whereField, includeWhere, primaryId, primaryWhereField,
secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId, tertiaryWhereField);

    return sql;
};

retrieve.assessments = (primaryId, secondaryId, tertiaryId, variant,
primaryWhereField, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryWhereField) => {

    const table = 'Assessments LEFT JOIN Users ON
Assessments.AssessmentLeaderID=Users.UserID LEFT JOIN Modules ON
Assessments.AssessmentModuleID=Modules.ModuleID';

    const fields =
['AssessmentID', 'AssessmentName', 'AssessmentStartdate', 'AssessmentEnddate', 'Ass
essmentImageURI', 'AssessmentLeaderID', 'AssessmentModuleID', 'ModuleCode AS
AssessmentModuleCode', 'ModuleName AS AssessmentModuleName', 'CONCAT(UserTitle, "
",UserFirstname, " ",UserLastname) AS AssessmentLeaderName'];

    const extendedTable = `Userassessments INNER JOIN ${table} ON
Userassessments.UserassessmentAssessmentID = Assessments.AssessmentID`;

    const extendedFields = `${fields}, UserassessmentID AS
AssessmentEnrollmentID, UserassessmentsAssessmentfavourite AS
AssessmentFavourite`;

    return (variant === 'users')

    ? buildSelectStatement(extendedTable, extendedFields, true, primaryId,
primaryWhereField, secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId,
tertiaryWhereField)

    : buildSelectStatement(table, fields, true, primaryId, primaryWhereField,
secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId, tertiaryWhereField);
};

```

Figure 5.144 After refactoring – creation of unified buildSelectStatement() function

Additionally, a retrieve method was created to build the necessary SQL SELECT statement to retrieve the desired records. Each retrieve function defined the table and fields required, and called the buildSelectStatement() function, to create a SELECT statement with the required field names. This reduced the code duplication across the multitude of buildSelectSql() functions previously used, with all SELECT functionality being handled by one function, passed the appropriate parameter values.

```

appRouter.get('/users', (req, res) =>
sqldb.get(req, res, retrieve.users, false, 'users'));

appRouter.get('/users/:pid', (req, res) =>
sqldb.get(req, res, retrieve.users, true, 'users', 'UserID'));

```

Figure 5.145 Prior to refactoring – all endpoint handlers defined in app.js

```

appRouter.use('/modules', modulesRouter);

appRouter.use('/assessments', assessmentsRouter);

const assessmentsRouter = Router({ mergeParams: true });

assessmentsRouter.get('/:pid', (req, res) => sqlDb.get({req, res, createQuery:
retrieve.assessments, queryWhereField: 'AssessmentName', variant:
'assessments', whereFields: ['AssessmentID']}));

assessmentsRouter.get('/:pid/users', userAssessmentsRouter);

```

Figure 5.146 After refactoring – creation of routers for each endpoint resource type

During refactoring, it was noted that the app.js main Express application file contained definitions for all endpoint routes and their associated endpoint handlers, used for executing the relevant logic and providing a suitable response upon requests being received by the specified URL, as shown in Figure 5.145. Consequently, to increase code reuse and improve maintainability, these routes were extracted into different Express Routers, used for sending received requests to their base URLs to their appropriate endpoint or Router handler functions, as shown in Figure 5.146. This improves code readability within the app.js file, and ensures similar logic, used within collections of endpoints associated with the same entity, is easily accessible.

By default, Express Routers do not facilitate merged parameters, meaning all received parameters and handled within the Express Router associated with the base URL. As such, child Routers are unable to access the URL parameters used by the parent Routers to define the appropriate child router to send the request to, thus preventing the request from being fulfilled. To rectify this issue, the Routers used the 'mergeParams: true' prop to ensure all parent routers passed request parameters to child Routers, ensuring child routers could extract the necessary request parameters to execute the query.

Figure 5.147 Prior to refactoring – sqlController.js contained within model > sqlDatabase directory

Figure 5.148 After refactoring – creation of controller > sqlDatabase directory for sqlController.js

During refactoring it was noted that the `sqlController.js` file was incorrectly located within the model parent directory, as shown in Figure 5.147. With respect to the Model View Controller (MVC) code design pattern, the controller should be contained within a separate directory to the model code. As such, a new directory, `model`, was created, alongside an `sqlDatabase` sub-directory, to contain the `sqlController.js` file, as shown in Figure 5.148. This ensures code compliance with best practice, and maintainability, improving the structure of the application.

```
app.get('/api/users', (req, res) =>
getUsersController(req, res, 'users', 'UserID'));

sqlldb.get = async (req, res, createQuery, validateId, variant,
primaryWhereField, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryWhereField) => {

    let primaryId = req.params.pid;

    let secondaryId = req.params.sid;

    let tertiaryId = req.params.tid;

    if (validateId || primaryId) {

        const { error } = Validation.idSchema(true).validate(primaryId);

        if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});

    }

    if (secondaryWhereField) {

        const { error } = Validation.idSchema(true).validate(secondaryId);

        if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});

    }

    if (tertiaryWhereField) {

        const { error } = Validation.idSchema(true).validate(tertiaryId);

        if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});

    }

    const sql = createQuery(primaryId, secondaryId, tertiaryId, variant,
primaryWhereField, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryWhereField);

    const { isSuccess, result, message } = await sqlldbController.read(sql);

    isSuccess ? res.status(200).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});

};
```

Figure 5.149 Prior to refactoring – use of multiple id and whereField parameters passed to functions

```

const buildSelectStatement = (table, fields, includeWhere, primaryId,
primaryWhereField, secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId,
tertiaryWhereField, whereField) => {

    let sql = '';

    sql = `SELECT ${fields} FROM ${table}`;

    sql += sqldb.where(whereField, includeWhere, primaryId, primaryWhereField,
secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId, tertiaryWhereField);

    return sql;
};

retrieve.assessments = (primaryId, secondaryId, tertiaryId, variant,
primaryWhereField, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryWhereField) => {

    const table = 'Assessments LEFT JOIN Users ON
Assessments.AssessmentLeaderID=Users.UserID LEFT JOIN Modules ON
Assessments.AssessmentModuleID=Modules.ModuleID';

    const fields =
['AssessmentID', 'AssessmentName', 'AssessmentStartdate', 'AssessmentEnddate', 'Ass
essmentImageURI', 'AssessmentLeaderID', 'AssessmentModuleID', 'ModuleCode AS
AssessmentModuleCode', 'ModuleName AS AssessmentModuleName', 'CONCAT(UserTitle, "
",UserFirstname, " ",UserLastname) AS AssessmentLeaderName'];

    const extendedTable = `Userassessments INNER JOIN ${table} ON
Userassessments.UserassessmentAssessmentID = Assessments.AssessmentID`;

    const extendedFields = `${fields}, UserassessmentID AS
AssessmentEnrollmentID, UserassessmentsAssessmentfavourite AS
AssessmentFavourite`;

    return (variant === 'users')

    ? buildSelectStatement(extendedTable, extendedFields, true, primaryId,
primaryWhereField, secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId,
tertiaryWhereField)

    : buildSelectStatement(table, fields, true, primaryId, primaryWhereField,
secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId, tertiaryWhereField);
};

```

Figure 5.150 Prior to refactoring – use of multiple id and whereField parameters passed to functions

```

sqlDb.where = (whereField, whereRequired, primaryId, primaryWhereField,
secondaryId, secondaryWhereField, tertiaryId, tertiaryWhereField) => {

  let sql = '';

  if (whereRequired && ((primaryId && primaryWhereField) || (secondaryId &&
secondaryWhereField) || (tertiaryId && tertiaryWhereField))) sql += ` WHERE`;

  if (whereField) sql += whereField;

  if (!whereRequired && (primaryId && primaryWhereField)) sql+= ` AND`;

  if (primaryId) sql += ` ${primaryWhereField}=${primaryId}`;

  if (secondaryId) sql += ` AND ${secondaryWhereField}=${secondaryId}`;

  if (tertiaryId) sql += ` AND ${tertiaryWhereField}=${tertiaryId}`;

  return sql;

};

```

Figure 5.151 Prior to refactoring – use of multiple id and whereField parameters passed to functions

```

userAssessmentsRouter.get('/:pid/users', (req, res) => sqlDb.get({req, res,
createQuery: retrieve.userassessments, queryWhereField:
'UserTitle,UserFirstname,UserMiddlename,UserLastname,UserEmail', variant:
'users', whereFields: ['Userassessments.UserassessmentAssessmentID']}));

retrieve.userassessments = ({whereIds, variant, whereFields, queryWhereField,
query}) => {

  const table = 'Userassessments LEFT JOIN Users ON
Userassessments.UserassessmentUserID=Users.UserID';

  const fields =
['UserID','UserTitle','UserFirstname','UserMiddlename','UserLastname'];

  return buildSelectStatement({table, fields, whereIds, whereFields,
queryWhereField, query});

};

const buildSelectStatement = ({table, fields, excludeWhere=false, whereIds,
whereFields, queryWhereField, query, whereField, distinct=false, variant=null,
orField=null}) => {

  let sql = '';

  sql = `SELECT ${distinct ? 'DISTINCT ' : ''}${fields} FROM ${table}`;

  sql += sqlDb.where({whereField, excludeWhere, whereIds, whereFields,
queryWhereField, query, variant, orField});

  console.log(sql);

  return sql;

};

```

Figure 5.152 After refactoring – use of array for id and whereField and orField parameters

```

sqlDb.where = ({whereField, excludeWhere, whereIds, whereFields,
queryWhereField, query, variant, orField}) => {

  let sql = '';

  if (whereField) sql += whereField;

  if ((!excludeWhere && (whereIds && whereFields) || query)) sql += ` WHERE `;

  if (excludeWhere && (whereIds && whereFields && (whereIds[0] &&
whereFields[0]))) sql+= ` AND `;

  if (whereIds && whereFields && (whereIds[0] && whereFields[0])) sql += `
${whereFields[0]}=${whereIds[0]}`;

  if (variant === 'users' && orField && whereIds[0]) sql+= ` OR
${orField}=${whereIds[0]}`;

  if (whereIds && whereFields && (whereIds.length > 1 && whereFields.length >
1)) {

    for (let i = 1; i < (whereIds.length); i++) {

      if (whereIds[i]) sql += ` AND ${whereFields[i]}=${whereIds[i]}`;

    };

  };

  if (query) sql += `${whereIds[0] ? ' AND' : ''} CONCAT_WS(' ',
${queryWhereField}) LIKE '%${query}%'`;

  return sql;
};

```

Figure 5.153 After refactoring – use of array for id and whereField and orField parameters

During refactoring, it was noted that multiple id and whereField parameters were passed between functions, to build the SQL WHERE clause, as shown in Figure 5.149, Figure 5.150 and Figure 5.151. Consequently, to reduce the number of passed parameters, and increase code maintainability, through supporting any number of WHERE clause conditions, the primaryId, secondaryId and tertiaryId parameters were instead passed using a whereIds array, as shown in Figure 5.152, 5.153 and Figure 5.154.

Similarly, the primaryWhereField, secondaryWhereField and tertiaryWhereField parameters were passed using a whereFields array. The sqlDb.where() function was modified to iterate through the passed arrays and append the conditions to the created WHERE clause. This allows any number of WHERE conditions to be appended to the generated SQL statement, whilst improving code maintainability.

```

sqlldb.get = async ({req, res, createQuery, queryWhereField, validateId=true,
variant, whereFields, orField}) => {

    const { query } = req.query;

    const { pid, sid, tid } = req.params;

    const whereIds = [pid, sid, tid];

    if (validateId || pid) {

        const { error } = Validation.idSchema(true).validate(pid);

        if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});

    }

    if (whereFields && whereFields[1]) {

        const { error } = Validation.idSchema(true).validate(sid);

        if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});

    }

    if (whereFields && whereFields[2]) {

        const { error } = Validation.idSchema(true).validate(tid);

        if (error) return res.status(400).json({message:
reportIdError(error)});

    }

    const sql = createQuery({whereIds, variant, whereFields, queryWhereField,
query, orField});

    const { isSuccess, result, message } = await sqlldbController.read({sql});

    isSuccess ? res.status(200).json(result) : res.status(400).json({message});
};

```

Figure 5.154 After refactoring – use of array for id and whereField and orField parameters

During this time, the includeWhere parameter was modified to an excludeWhere parameter, as it was noted that the majority of endpoint handler functions required a 'WHERE' operator to be appended to the SQL statement. To facilitate this modification, the sqlldb.where() function's use of the includeWhere parameter value was inverted, and all references to 'includeWhere' were modified to 'excludeWhere', with the default value being set to 'false' in the buildSelectStatementSql() function. Consequently, sqlldb.get() function calls utilising a 'WHERE' operator within a WHERE clause did not require a 'true' value to be passed.

It was identified that all functions accepted standard object parameters, meaning the order in which parameters were passed to the functions was integral to their appropriate behaviour. As a result, for function calls not utilising particular functionality, such as a conformance object, null or Boolean values were required in place of object values, reducing the maintainability and reliability of the application. Consequently, all functions and associated function calls were modified to accept destructured parameters, to ensure only the required parameters needed to be provided to the function call.

Additionally, it was identified that there was no mechanism for handling conditional searching of records using the OR operator, thus certain SQL statements resulted in the return of incomplete data. In the case of an assessment leader, it is paramount that they may view both the assessments they are enrolled in, and those they are the manager of, else management of such assessments becomes impossible.

Consequently, the backend API was modified to support an orField, passed in a similar manner to the previously-defined whereFields, handled within the sqlDb.where() function, as shown in Figure 5.152, 5.153 and Figure 5.154. Such field appends an OR operator to the SQL statement, utilising the relevant ID value, thus ensuring the appropriate records are returned from the database.

5.9.2 Data Model Refactoring

During the development of the database, refactoring was performed following the implementation of each sprint, based on identified code smells. As previously discussed, refactoring provides numerous benefits to the developed system, reducing repeated code and improving system maintainability. This subsection will detail the refactoring enacted on the opportunities identified within the developed database.

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Comments	Extra
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 AssessmentfeedbackitemID 🗝️	int(5)			No	None		AUTO_INCREMENT
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 AssessmentfeedbackitemAssessmentfeedbackID 🔑	int(5)			Yes	NULL		
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 AssessmentfeedbackitemAssessmentrubricID 🔑	int(5)			Yes	NULL		
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 AssessmentfeedbackitemAssessmentrubriccommentID 🔑	int(5)			No	None		
<input type="checkbox"/>	5 AssessmentfeedbackitemAdditionalcomments	varchar(500)	utf8mb4_general_ci		Yes	NULL		
<input type="checkbox"/>	6 AssessmentfeedbackitemGrade	int(2)			Yes	NULL		
<input type="checkbox"/>	7 AssessmentfeedbackitemCreateddate	datetime			Yes	current_timestamp()		

Figure 5.155 After refactoring – AssessmentfeedbackitemAssessmentrubriccommentID field

It was identified that assessments should utilise a singular pre-defined rubric comment, due to the nature of the rubric comments being specific to the particular standard of presentation. It is not intended that multiple rubric comments be able to be applied to the same rubric, as they should represent different standards and levels of ability.

It was therefore decided that the AssessmentfeedbackitemAssessmentrubriccommentID attribute be added within the Assessmentfeedbackitem table, to mitigate against the requirement for a separate Assessmentfeedbackitemcomments table which, requiring joins and further API calls to populate, would reduce the database’s performance and thus scalability, as shown in Figure 5.155. Through incorporating the field within the Assessmentfeedbackitem table, no functionality is lost, although the database overhead is reduced.

5.9.3 Frontend Refactoring

During the development of the frontend, refactoring was performed following the implementation of each sprint, based on identified code smells. As previously discussed, refactoring provides numerous benefits to the developed system, reducing repeated code and improving system maintainability. This subsection will detail the refactoring enacted on the opportunities identified within the developed frontend.

```
function Tabbar ({ assessmentID=0 }) {
  return (
    <div className='tabs'>
      <ul>
        <li
          className='tab'><NavLink
to={` /assessments/${assessmentID}`}
className={` tabbar-item`}
end>Details</NavLink></li>
        <li><NavLink
          to={` /assessments/${assessmentID}/groups`}
className={` tabbar-item`}>Groups</NavLink></li>
        <li><NavLink
          to={` /assessments/${assessmentID}/panels`}
className={` tabbar-item`}>Panels</NavLink></li>
        <li><NavLink
          to={` /assessments/${assessmentID}/rubrics`}
className={` tabbar-item`}>Rubrics</NavLink></li>
      </ul>
    </div>
  );
}
export default Tabbar;
```

Figure 5.156 After refactoring – creation of Tabbar to facilitate access to assessment subitems

It was identified that the majority of users, including assessment leaders, typically prefer to access assessment subitems through the assessment itself, rather than the top-tier navigation menu, as shown in Figure 5.156. As groups, panels and rubrics are related to an assessment, assessment leaders often find it easier to locate such items from within the assessment itself, rather than searching through all records.

To support the location of records within an element, a Tabbar component was produced, facilitating the navigation to the appropriate assessment subitem pages. This aims to mitigate against the requirement to access all assessment subitems from their respective item lists using the navigation bar, increasing usability.

```

    {
        (userContextValue.userPrivileges=== 'manager' ||
userContextValue.userPrivileges=== 'admin') &&

        <ButtonBar className='ButtonBar'>

            <Button.AddNew onClick={toggleAddForm} hasTitle title='New
Assessment' />

        </ButtonBar>

    }

showAddAssessmentForm && <Modal title='Create New Assessment'><AssessmentForm
onCancel={cancelAddForm} onSubmit={handleAddSubmit} /></Modal>

export default function Modal({ title, children }) {

    return (

        <div className='modaloverlay'>

            <main className='modalpane'>

                <Card>

                    <header>

                        <p>{title}</p>

                    </header>

                    <main className='modaldescription'>

                        {children}

                    </main>

                </Card>

            </main>

        </div>

    );

}

```

Figure 5.157 New item button contained at top of page and use of Modal component

A range of issues were identified with the user interface design, based on the usability testing previously performed. One such issue related to the use of the 'New' item buttons being placed at the bottom of the page, thus navigating to the button within the page was difficult with long lists of data, as shown in Figure 5.157.

Furthermore, the form would open inside the page, making its visibility poor and increasing the page length. As such, a modal was produced, with associated styling, to contain the item form, ensuring the form is displayed prominently within the middle of the page, improving the user interface. Additionally, the new item button was migrated to the top of the page, improving its accessibility.

5.10 Coding Principles

Coding principles define standards and agreed best practices, which developers should adhere to, in order to produce maintainable code. Whilst some coding principles may be language-specific, principles are typically practices that may apply to all development, being language agnostic, and focussing on concepts, rather than specific implementation. Through following best practices, developed code has increased readability, maintainability, testability, and is thus less likely to contain bugs.

During the application's development, coding principles were heavily considered, to ensure the maintainability of the produced application. Key principles adhered to included the use of a sprint-based development approach, and performing intensive refactoring, upon the completion of each sprint, seeking to reducing the likelihood of the development of unmaintainable code.

5.10.1 Sprint-Based Implementation

The application's implementation was performed using a series of seven sprints, to increase the likelihood of implementation success. As sprints must be performed over a fixed time period, but may implement varying numbers of features, this was best suited to this project, with there being a fixed deadline. Through utilising sprints, the application's features were able to modified to fit the time available, with some sprints implementing fewer user stories than expected, due to challenges faced during the development cycle.

The user stories to be implemented within each sprint were identified at sprint commencement, providing the development team with suitable time to evaluate the most important user stories to implement. This process ensured sprint time was only spent implementing necessary features, meaning development time was better managed, and a minimum viable product could be produced. Had sprints not been used during the application's development, it is likely that unnecessary features would have been implemented, and there would have been a lack of motivation for the development team to implement the features they had identified as being created during the set time period.

A sprint duration of four weeks was identified as providing the most benefit to the project, matching the implementation tasks required for an application utilising a separate frontend and backend architecture. Consequently, the development team achieved the conduction of a total of seven sprints in the available development time.

Within the first week of each sprint, the user stories to implement were selected, with their workflows captured using activity and sequence diagrams, where appropriate. The associated user types, assumptions and constraints for each user story were also defined, to give the development team a clear understanding of the functionality required to be implemented within the application.

During the sprint's second week, the database relations were updated, where necessary, to handle the new user stories for the sprint, with SQL statements being created and tested, to retrieve the user story data. The corresponding endpoint syntax was identified, and the backend API was implemented and tested, to provide the necessary persistent storage for the user story data.

Within the third week each sprint, the user story's associated user interface was designed, with the React components required for the implementation being identified, alongside any contextual information necessary to provide the desired functionality. From these designs, the frontend React application was developed, offering a suitable user interface to allow users to access the application's functionality.

The final week of each sprint involved identifying code smells within the developed code, and using appropriate refactoring techniques, to mitigate against these issues, and improve code maintainability. An individual 'sprint retrospective' was conducted by the development team, to identify the sprint's success stories, improvement opportunities, and learning to try in the following sprint. This ensured increased success within future sprints, as shown by the increase in number and complexity of user stories, as more sprints had been performed.

5.10.2 Refactoring Sprint Implementation

Following the implementation of each sprint's desired user story functionality, refactoring was performed to improve code maintainability. Refactoring is the process of modifying system architecture and created code, to minimise code duplication and thus increase maintainability, readability, and efficiency, without impacting or changing the developed functionality.

Refactoring is crucial to increasing code reuse, which is a fundamental principle of React, highlighted in its facilitation of the creation of reusable components (Boduch, 2017). Refactoring was required to be performed after implementation of each sprint's functionality, due to code smells becoming prominent, and refactoring opportunities arising to mitigate against such issues. Often, upon implementing a set of functionality, it is not clear where similar future functionality will require the repetition of significant portions of existing code. However, adhering to the DRY ("Don't Repeat Yourself") coding principle, code should not be repeated multiple times, instead being abstracted or normalised (Hunt and Thomas, 1999).

During user story implementation, a WET ("Write Everything Twice") approach was followed (.NET Design Patterns, no date), with code often being repeated multiple times with minimal changes, due to the development team not fully being aware of the changes within the repeated code. This led to significant code duplication, hindering maintainability and readability. Repeated code was addressed through the code review and subsequent refactoring performed, to migrate WET code into DRY code, using abstraction into functions and, in the case of the React frontend, components and custom hooks.

After refactoring code, a further benefit of reduced future feature implementation is realised, with reusable components and functions only requiring a different value to be passed within a function parameter, as opposed to copying and modifying vast amounts of code. It must be noted that, although future features are faster to implement, the process of refactoring is lengthy, with refactoring typically the same or greater time to complete, as the original feature implementation.

5.11 Security

When developing a web application, security is a key consideration, as the application is publicly accessible, increasing its vulnerability to malicious attacks. Security mechanisms must be implemented to protect and mitigate against attacks by unauthorised third parties, which can lead to system downtime, reduced reliability, data theft, or data integrity problems. Whilst attacks are damaging to the application's credibility, they may cause disruption or potential harm to its users, therefore potential threats must be minimised.

Within an application utilising a separate frontend and backend, there are increased security challenges and importance. As attacks may be performed on both the frontend and backend API, a potential vulnerability in either aspect of the application can lead to significant dangers, compromising the whole system and its contained data. Consequently, it is crucial that all aspects of the application are secured, in an attempt to reduce the risk of threats.

5.11.1 Database Security Mechanisms

Database security mechanisms were strongly considered, as the database is arguably the most important element within the application to malicious attackers, due to it persistently storing all application data. In the case of an attack on the database, data loss may occur, either jeopardising the integrity of the stored data, or resulting in data theft, both significantly impacting the reputation of the application, and potentially catalysing Information Commissioner’s Office GDPR investigations, or other such legal issues.

Figure 5.158 Creation of New Secure Database User Account within phpMyAdmin

To mitigate against unauthorised data access, a secure user account was created within the database, as shown in Figure 5.158. It is widely regarded that the root user account, provided by default within MySQL, should be deleted or secured with a suitable strong password, due to it providing unrestricted access to all database management functionality (IBM, no date). As such, a ‘markitapplication’ user account was created, with access only to the collabase database running on localhost, with a secure password.

This account was further restricted to only being able to perform SQL data operations defined by the associated API endpoints, thus mitigating against database structure or administration operations being performed, in the case of the user account being compromised. Consequently, this sought to protect the database against unauthorised access, compromising the database or its contained data.

5.11.2 Backend Security Mechanisms

Backend API security mechanisms were evaluated, as the backend poses a potential vulnerability, due to its direct access to the database. In the event of the attacker unable to directly access the database, they may exploit weaknesses in the endpoint to gain access to the database. Alternatively, attempts may be made to perform a denial-of-service attack on the backend API, to compromise system availability.

```
app.disable('x-powered-by');
```

Figure 5.159 Disabling of ‘X-Powered-By: Express’ Backend API Response Header

Within the `app.js` file, in the Express app's middleware, the `disable()` function was used to remove the 'X-Powered-By' header in the API's responses, as shown in Figure 5.159. When a new Express app is configured, it returns 'X-Powered-By: Express' within the header of any responses returned by the endpoint by default. This provides casual malicious attackers with an immediate method of determining the type of software used to run the backend API, potentially increasing the risk of known Express endpoint exploits being performed.

Although advanced methods may be used to determine the backend API application platform, removing the 'X-Powered-By' header reduces the server software fingerprinting, thus aiding in securing the endpoints (Express, no date).

As discussed in subsection 5.7.4 – Data Access, SQL prepared statements are used when querying the database. SQL prepared statements are valid SQL statements, containing placeholders represented by the required conformance object attributes, with which the values are added to the query upon execution, and treated literally, not as part of the SQL statement for execution itself. This ensures any SQL commands received by the endpoint would not be executed directly on the database, thus protecting against SQL injection attacks.

The joi validation framework was used to validate all received request data, as discussed in subsection 5.7.3 – Request Validation. Upon requests being received by the backend API, their request parameter ID values and request bodies are validated against defined rulesets. By confirming all received data is valid, prior to storage, this affirms that the database only contains valid data, ensuring data integrity.

The joi validator also escapes any received HTML. Through escaping HTML received by the endpoint, this safeguards against cross-site scripting (XSS) attacks, where malicious JavaScript elements are received within an object's attribute value, within associated HTML `<script></script>` tags.

Should the database persistently store JavaScript values, when such data is returned and rendered within a frontend webpage in the browser, the associated script will run, potentially displaying harmful content, or redirecting the user to an unwanted or malicious webpage.

Appropriate HTTP status codes and messages were returned in the backend API responses, as previously discussed in subsection 5.2.2 – Representational State Transfer (REST) API and subsection 5.7.6 – Returned Responses. Through the endpoint returning the appropriate HTTP status code and resource object, according to best practice, this significantly enhances endpoint security. With clients being aware of the status of their request, errors can be identified, whilst the API's implementation may be abstracted.

5.12 Conclusion

This phase of the project sought to develop the produced designs into a working application, suitable of fulfilling the necessary captured user stories. Extensive consideration was taken to ensure the system architecture, technologies and tools used facilitated maintainability, with a particular focus on the ensuring the technologies used facilitated efficient development, due to the project's time constraints. After research, it was determined that a separate frontend and backend architecture utilising React, SCSS, Express and MySQL, offered maintainability, fast development time, and scalability, all of which were mandatory characteristics of the project's implementation.

Development tools were evaluated, with the application implementation utilising tools containing features to reduce development time and fully support the chosen technologies. After researching potential libraries and frameworks to implement, in order to increase application compatibility, mitigate against potential software bugs, and reduce development time, a range of frontend and backend packages were identified as providing benefit during application implementation.

A MySQL database was successfully created, to provide a mechanism for persistent application storage, and subsequently populated with realistic generated data, to aid in the application's testing and demonstration. A range of necessary SQL queries were written, to facilitate database access, offering the ability to create, retrieve, update and delete stored data.

The backend API was subsequently developed, utilising request validation, to ensure the validity of received data prior to database storage, thus enhancing security and protecting data integrity. The database utilised SQL statements and the mysql2 package, to asynchronously connect to the created MySQL database, for data access. Data conformance ensured that data exchanged between the API and database was in a suitable format to be understood by both components.

The backend API's returned responses were heavily considered, ensuring correct responses were returned, as per best practice, to enhance security and provide appropriate client feedback. The backend API was structured such that maintainability and updatability was enhanced, with appropriate files, directories and exported functions.

Following backend API development, the frontend implementation offered users with a user-friendly mechanism to access the application. The frontend utilised both custom reusable components, for increased maintainability, minimised code duplication, and reduced development time, and existing third-party components, for both efficiency and compatibility. Component state was used to increase frontend application performance and efficiency, with only modified components being re-rendered within the browser. The creation of custom hooks increased maintainability, with core functionality being exported for reuse across frontend components.

Form input validation was used to immediately alert users to errors within their input data, prior to transmission to the backend API, with data conformance translating input data into a valid format to be accepted by the API. The JavaScript Fetch API was used to connect to the backend API, for the purposes of creating, retrieving, updating and deleting stored objects.

Page navigation was crucial in ensuring users may view all application functionality in a clear and user-friendly manner, with data being separated across different pages, accessible using page navigation. The frontend styling was heavily considered, providing users with a user-friendly, accessible and aesthetically pleasing application experience, therefore the Bulma CSS framework was used. The frontend was structured to enhance maintainability, with respect to file and directory structures and naming conventions.

The necessity of coding principles, including the use of a sprint-based approach to implementation, and refactoring being performed during each sprint, was identified, safeguarding against the successful implementation of all necessary features, and aiding in the creation of maintainable code, with a reduced development time.

Security mechanisms within the frontend and backend were significantly reviewed, protecting the application from potential unauthorised access, data leaks, denial of service, SQL injection and cross-site scripting attacks. Due to the vulnerabilities within applications utilising separate frontend and backend architectures, further exacerbated by the risks imposed by being publicly accessible via the internet, security methods required detailed evaluation. As such, processes were undertaken to mitigate against such threats, ensuring data integrity, system availability, and only authorised access of data.

The implementation chapter offers vast importance to the development system, providing the final product to be delivered to the client thus, if successfully implementing the necessary client requirements, ensuring the client's original needs are fulfilled. Arguably, a failed project implementation provides little benefit to the client, who expects a suitable tool to be produced, to achieve their original use case and purpose of the project.

6 Validation

6.1 Introduction

The validation chapter will focus on checking the developed system meets the client's requirements, provides accurate and reliable functionality, and offers a user interface that may be easily understood and used by the target userbase. The produced testing strategy will be explored, examining the importance of the creation of a testing strategy, and the proposed validation and verification methods.

The expected goals and purpose of each testing mechanism performed will be discussed, offering insight into the value the test method will provide. The design and procedure of test conduction will be detailed, exploring the manner in which the results were obtained. The results of the test method will be presented, before a thorough analysis is provided, examining identified trends and proposing reasons for such outcomes. An extensive evaluation will discuss the accuracy and reliability of both the tests conducted and their results, with a tabular recommendations proposing the changes to be made to the application, based on the obtained outcomes.

6.2 Testing Strategy

6.2.1 Introduction

When developing a system, it is vital that testing is performed, to ensure both functionality is present and correctly implemented, and that the system is navigable and usable by its target audience, even under load (Jamil *et al.*, 2016). To facilitate these testing requirements, black box, white box and unit testing may be employed, each encompassing different testing methods and techniques (Jamil *et al.*, 2016).

Prior to system validation and verification, the development of a testing strategy seeks to ensure all aspects of the system are appropriately tested, with sufficient test coverage and testing mechanisms to validate application accuracy, usability and client suitability (Woodward and Hennell, 2005). Preceding the performance of application testing, a test strategy was produced, detailing the types of tests to be conducted, their benefits and an outline method of their implementation within the project.

6.2.2 Testing Strategy Creation

During the creation of the testing strategy, possible test methods to be conducted were analysed, with the most suitable test mechanisms being selected to be performed. Following extensive research into the typical conduction of testing methods and their proposed project benefits, it was decided that a combination of integration, performance and load testing would seek to provide adequate validation of the working functionality system's implemented features. Furthermore, functionality and usability testing would affirm that the system met all identified requirements and was operable by all target user groups.

The produced testing strategy outlined the types of testing to be conducted and their benefits to the application and client, enabling the client to gain an increased understanding into the accuracy and suitability of the system. After receiving client approval for the proposed validation methods, the project-specific implementation of such testing mechanisms was thoroughly researched, with a test plan being produced for each testing type to provide the validation team with a detailed guide to how to accurately complete each test.

A template of a test table to be completed for each form of testing conducted was constructed, providing a structure to the recording of results, and ensuring all necessary information was captured at the time of completing the test, for the benefit of results analysis. Test tables were to be completed for all requirements or necessary aspects of the system under the defined testing method, to gauge the system’s suitability against the specified requirements.

Performance Test ID	Performance Test Description	Performance Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Performance Test Passed?
1	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a specified single Module record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/modules/:id HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 150 Duration: 10 seconds Request Frequency: 15 requests per second	Highest Response Time: 15ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 1ms Highest Response Time: 14ms Average Response Time: 8ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Figure 6.1 Testing Strategy Test Table for Performance Testing

Figure 6.1 shows an example test table produced for recording the results of performance testing, developed within the testing strategy. The testing strategy produced for each form of testing is located within the Introduction and Goals subsections of each testing method performed, with the associated completed test table being located within the Data Gathering subsection.

6.2.3 Conclusion

It was hoped that by creating a testing strategy utilising different testing methods, test coverage was high, and the development team could have increased confidence that the developed system meets all client requirements, from usability, performance, scalability and functionality aspects. Through performing tests with most benefit to the system, and detailing the steps required to conduct such tests, test relevancy and accuracy is increased, without adversely impacting the project’s schedule. The creation of test tables ensured all necessary test results were recorded, for appropriate system suitability analysis.

It must be noted that whilst test passes show the system is fit for purpose in the test area, it is not unexpected that the system may fail occasional tests, due to it being a prototype and potentially containing unforeseen bugs. Any errors identified as a result of failed tests would be sought to be resolved before deployment and handover to the client. Although this testing strategy developed was thorough, there was a high probability of bugs still being present within the system, which were not identified during the execution of the limited range of testing methods.

6.3 Integration Testing

6.3.1 Introduction

Integration testing is a method of testing that different components or systems within an application are communicating and interacting with each other correctly, and producing the appropriate behaviour, when used together (Jamil *et al.*, 2016). Whilst it is necessary to run unit tests to ensure functionality within both systems is correct, integration tests are crucial to verifying that the different elements of the system provide the expected behaviour when combined, as would occur within the final product (Jamil *et al.*, 2016).

There are a range of approaches to integration testing, including big-bang, bottom-up, top-down and mixed integration testing (Leung and White, 1990). Big-bang testing involves merging all elements within the system, and checking the functionality matches that intended of the system, and is a form of black box testing. In contrast, bottom-up testing involves testing the smallest components within a system first, and testing increasingly larger subsystems, with top-down testing providing the reverse form of testing, by testing larger subsystems first. Mixed testing involves using a combination of bottom-up and top-down testing used together when testing different components.

6.3.2 Integration Testing Goals

Integration testing validates that the component and interacting system behaviour is appropriate. It was used to check that both the Express backend components were fully functional, and the database and its connection to the backend, was also working correctly. Integration testing is integral to ensuring all components and systems provide correct outcomes when run, validating the behaviour of the system's constituent elements is appropriate.

Integration testing was performed, as it allows the location of faults within the system to be more easily identified. One such case is validating the backend API is fully functional prior to its connection to the frontend, thus highlighting any errors present within the backend, before unnecessary time is spent debugging the fully working frontend implementation.

Upon the database and backend being complete, integration testing was performed, to ensure both components were fully operational when combined. Upon the completion of the corresponding frontend component, whole application integration testing was used to verify that the frontend, backend and database were all communicating properly and providing the required functionality.

6.3.3 Integration Testing Design

The approach used for the conduction of integration testing is key in the accuracy and relevancy of the obtained test results. For this project, big-bang integration testing was identified as providing the most benefit, being simple to use, thus meaning little prior research was required to perform the testing. Due to it being fast to conduct, it ensured the project meet the imposed deadlines, whilst being suited to small systems with little interdependence between elements, much like the produced application.

Integration testing involved validating all backend API HTTP request methods using Postman, a tool used for sending HTTP requests and inspecting the output, as previously described. Postman was used to sending requests to the backend API endpoints with the necessary parameters and bodies, and checking the returned body and status code was as expected. Due to the nature of this testing process, requests were sent automatically using the JavaScript testing feature in Postman, with the tests passing or failing depending on the returned response HTTP status code and body type. Analysis of the shortest and longest response times is not supported in Postman, therefore such results required manual recording.

All implemented endpoint URLs, associated HTTP methods and body data, where appropriate, where saved into Postman folders, allowing groups of tests to be run on endpoints whenever changes were made to the backend API, to verify desired behaviour was not affected, therefore increasing testing process efficiency. In the case of testing the whole application using the frontend, all create, read, update and delete (CRUD) operations were invoked within the frontend application, with the necessary results and data being manually inspected within both the database and frontend, to ensure the frontend was enacting appropriate behaviour.

6.3.4 Integration Testing Data Gathering

Following the design of the design of the integration testing strategy, integration tests were conducted. Integration tests centred around testing all produced backend API endpoint functionality, in addition to system functionality accessible from the frontend application, to ensure consistency and accuracy of component and system behaviour, and identify likely issues. Integration tests were formed of view, create, edit and delete operations, to recognise system performance across all operation types, with the task description and expected output being recorded for each task. During any modifications to the system functionality, and following refactoring, all integration tests were re-run, to ensure no system behaviour had been modified.

During the conduction of the integration test, the system’s output was recorded, including the HTTP status code and response body returned from the backend API, or items displayed on-screen from whole system testing. Such data was gathered through observing the results in the Postman application, or displayed outputs rendered within the browser, with the outputs being manually recorded by the testing team.

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
1	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of User records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: <code>http://localhost:5000/api/users</code> HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON User objects, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: { { "UserID": 1, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Cherianne", "UserMiddlename": "Mella", "UserLastname": "Girvan", "UserEmail": "" }, { "UserID": 2, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Olivette", "UserMiddlename": "Galen", "UserLastname": "Temprell", "UserEmail": "" } }...	Pass
62	Test frontend homepage successfully displays assessment items retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: <code>http://localhost:3000/</code>	Assessment records "Bright Ideas Competition", "Commercial Awareness Pitch" are displayed on homepage	Assessment records "Bright Ideas Competition", "Commercial Awareness Pitch" are displayed on homepage	Pass

Table 6.2 Excerpt of Integration Testing for Backend API and Complete System

Table 6.2 details a subset of the backend API and complete system integration testing results. The description of the purpose of the test can be observed, alongside the type of component the integration test is being verifying. The input data used during the testing process is detailed, with the expected output from the test being recorded.

In the case of testing the backend API, input data includes the endpoint resource, listed in the form of a URL, HTTP method, and any request parameters or body. The complete system is tested using the frontend application, therefore details the URL of the associated frontend application page, where the tested functionality is located. The actual output from the completion of the test is documented, with the actual output's status code and body values being compared to the expected output, to determine whether the integration test had passed.

A comprehensive set of integration test tables are contained within Appendix U.

6.3.5 Integration Testing Analysis

After conducting all integration tests, the collected results were thoroughly analysed, to obtain valuable insight into the accuracy of the application's behaviour. The data obtained from the performance of integration testing both informed the overall system behaviour, and noted reasons for failed tests, therefore allowing a greater understanding to be obtained into the system's failings.

It was identified that thirty-one out of a total of sixty-one backend API integration tests passed, meaning the backend API had an overall test pass rate of just fifty-one percent. The vast number of failed tests indicates major problems with the backend API implementation, showing measures must be taken to rectify errors, and ensure appropriate data is returned.

Of the thirty-two failed tests, twenty such tests failed as a result of no records being found matching the endpoint resource requested. This test result may be easily rectified through ensuring the database contains mock data in every table, or modifying the resource requested to a select a resource that exists in the database. As such, these failed tests may be discounted, as they are not necessarily a reflection on errors within the backend API or database implementation.

Seven of the failed tests were as a result of missing returned attributes or returned objects containing attributes not expected by the original return JSON object designs. This test result indicates errors within the backend API's SELECT statement code, with missing or additional column fields being executed within the SELECT statement, thus being returned by the endpoint. These missing or additional columns must be rectified, as they pose potential risks in the displayed data used by the frontend application, whilst additional returned fields impose additional performance overheads on the database, and potential security risks. It must be noted that such modifications to the backend API would not be expected to be overly complex or time consuming.

Three of the thirty-one failed tests were noted as failing due to an error within the SQL syntax executed within the database. This SQL syntax error must be resolved, as it causes the endpoint to fail to return the requested resource. Additionally, as such error is reported to the client, this exposes the underlying persistent database storage mechanism used, risking the security of the application. This may be resolved through correcting the SQL syntax used during the request, although it may be time consuming to debug the location of the error.

Two of the failed tests were as a result of a fatal server-side error, with the application crashing and unable to provide the client with a response. This error must be resolved, as it causes the endpoint to fail to return the requested resource, both to the requesting client, and all other client machines, reducing the application's reliability. This error may be resolved through correcting the faulty code used during the request, although it may be time consuming to debug the location of the error.

It was identified that twenty-six out of a total of forty whole system integration tests passed, meaning the system had an overall test pass rate of sixty-five percent. The vast number of failed tests indicates major problems with the whole system implementation, showing measures must be taken to rectify errors, and ensure appropriate data is returned.

Nine of the twenty-six failed tests were caused by the database not containing any mock data, therefore the frontend application received no results to populate its list using. This test result may be easily rectified through ensuring the database contains mock data in every table. As such, these failed tests may be discounted, as they are not necessarily a reflection on errors within the frontend, backend API or database implementation.

Three failed tests were caused by errors within the frontend or backend implementation, meaning error messages were displayed on pages attempting to use such data. This error must be resolved, as it causes the application to fail to display the requested resource, preventing the system from functioning as desired by the user. This error may be resolved through correcting the faulty code used during the request, although it may be time consuming to debug the location of the error.

A further nine failed tests were caused by testing features or pages that had not yet been implemented. This test result is crucial to the user's experience of the application, thus meaning it must be rectified quickly. This test result may be rectified through ensuring the remaining features are implemented, or removing unimplemented features from the application, to prevent users from unknowingly attempting to use them.

Five of the twenty-six failed tests were caused by the user attempting to view an item they had created but were not enrolled in. This is a major usability concern, as it prevents users from being able to manage or view their created assessments. Such an issue can be resolved by enrolling the user on the object upon its creation, which would be a relatively simple function to implement.

6.3.6 Integration Testing Evaluation

Although the integration testing conducted provided the development team with valuable insight into the accuracy of the system behaviour within the application, the integration testing approach itself had shortcomings.

One such problem with the backend API integration testing performed was that the results of such tests required manual recording into the test tables. As transcription was performed by the testing team, there is the potential for results to be incorrectly recorded, thus causing recorded false positive or negative test results. Additionally, due to the lengthy time required to record data, integration testing required a significant amount of project time.

A further problem related to the lack of test data contained within the system, to test all functionality was appropriately working. When certain tests were performed, the database lacked records matching the endpoint's resource type, therefore no such records were returned. In this case, this caused the test to fail, with no data being returned and a HTTP 400 status code being returned instead. Such testing would have benefitted from a full complement of persistently stored test data, to ensure all functionality and endpoints could be tested.

Although tests were conducted automatically, with the status code and body value type being checked by Postman, the expected output was produced manually, through inspecting the contained database records and recording the expected results to be returned. It also required the testing team to manually cross-reference the actual request body with the expected request body. This problem of manual expected results population and cross-referencing of the actual output and expected output was also present within the whole system integration testing. These processes may have led to incorrect expected outputs being recorded, and both required significant time.

6.3.7 Conclusion

This subsection identified the benefits and necessity of conducting integration testing on the created system. It detailed the goals hoped to be achieved through the performing of such testing, and proposed a suitable approach to the conduction of the integration test, and subsequent recording and analysis of the results obtained. The process of recording the data obtained from the integration testing was documented, examining the potential data obtainable from such a test, and its relevancy in relation to analysis and decision making from the perspective of verifying the application’s suitability to the elicited requirements.

The results of data analysis on the acquired results were presented, alongside potential modifications required, to resolve current system behaviour concerns. A thorough review of the integration testing process was detailed, exploring the potential shortcomings in the integration testing conducted, and how such issues may hinder the accuracy or relevancy of the results.

6.3.8 Conclusive Recommendations

Identified Problem	Potential Solution	Importance
No records found matching the endpoint resource requested	Ensuring database contains mock data in every table, or modify the resource requested to a select a resource that exists in the database	Low
Missing returned attributes or returned objects containing attributes not expected	Add missing attributes and remove additional attributes in SELECT statement in backend API	High
Error within the SQL syntax executed within the database	Modify SQL syntax error within backend API	High
Fatal server-side error	Investigate backend API for error and resolve issue	High
Errors within the frontend and backend implementation	Investigate frontend and backend API for error and resolve issue	Medium
Features and pages have not yet been implemented	Ensure the remaining features are implemented, or remove unimplemented features from the application	Medium
User attempted to view an item they had created but were not enrolled in	Enrol the user on the object upon its creation	High

Table 6.3 Integration Testing Conclusive Recommendations and Potential Solutions

Following the performance of integration testing, the identified problems were listed, alongside potential solutions to resolve such issues, as shown in Table 6.3. The level of importance, to designate how urgently the fault must be fixed, is also detailed.

6.4 Performance Testing

6.4.1 Introduction

Performance testing is a method of testing the typical response time, scalability, stability and reliability of an application under “normal” use, which often encompasses a range of loads (Weyuker and Vokolos, 2000). It is used to evaluate the expected system performance, and thus user experience, the system is likely to deliver to its users when deployed, checking the system will meet the non-functional requirements outlined.

6.4.2 Performance Testing Goals

Performance testing is crucial to ensuring the system will meet the day-to-day needs of its users, and may be suitably scaled to meet potential future demands (Weyuker and Vokolos, 2000). Prior to releasing the system for real-world use, it is important to develop a critical understanding of the application’s typical performance under normal working conditions.

As the non-functional system requirements state that all pages must load within five seconds, it is important that performance testing is conducted, to ensure the developed application is fit for purpose, and meets the client’s needs. Performance testing was conducted to verify that the application offers suitable performance as specified within the non-functional requirements, identify any components causing bottlenecks or limiting factors within the system’s loading times, and provide the client with commonly expected performance guidelines.

6.4.3 Performance Testing Design

Performance testing was conducted on the frontend React application using Lighthouse, a Google Chrome Developers inspection tool for webpages which, amongst other aspects, reports website performance. Lighthouse offers a simple, efficient method to determine webpage performance, with measurements being agnostic of the underlying webpage development platform, such as React or PHP, therefore ensuring the webpage performance is measured fairly against other webpages users are likely to visit. The extension generates automated webpage performance report generation with a single-click, making it highly suitable for testing with the limited project timescales provided. After navigating to an appropriate page within the frontend web application, the Lighthouse browser extension was clicked, to generate a page performance report. Such report was manually analysed, with results being recorded in the test table.

Performance was also measured using the React Developer Tools browser extension’s Profiler to view both the components rendered within each webpage, and their render time. React Developer Tools is a browser extension used to view both component hierarchies, using the Components tab, and page rendering, through the Profiler tab.

Whilst running the Profile tool, Apache JMeter was run, sending multiple backend and frontend server requests, to simulate real-world concurrent usage. Apache JMeter is an application that allows a tester to send a specified number and frequency of HTTP requests to a URL, such as a frontend or backend web server, to replicate a number of simultaneous users accessing the web server. The combination of Apache JMeter and React Developer Tools was straightforward, but provided valuable insights into the performance of the application when under typical usage.

6.4.4 Performance Testing Data Gathering

Following the design of the design of the performance testing strategy, performance tests were conducted. Performance tests centred around testing all produced backend API endpoint functionality, and the whole system, formed as a result of frontend and backend coupling, to ensure the system processed requests and returned responses in a timely manner, as per the non-functional requirements. Performance tests were formed of view, create, edit and delete operations, to recognise system performance across all operation types, with the task description and expected output being recorded for each task. During any modifications to the system functionality, and following refactoring, all performance tests were re-run, to ensure system performance had not been adversely affected.

During the conduction of the performance test, the system's output was recorded, including the lowest, highest and average response times, and number of internal server errors, with HTTP status codes between 500 and 511, returned from the backend API. When testing the whole system, the overall system performance was recorded, as per the results from Lighthouse, in addition to any internal server errors. Such data was gathered through observing the results from the running of Postman application tests, or the report generated by Lighthouse, with the outputs being manually recorded by the testing team.

Performance Test ID	Performance Test Description	Performance Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Performance Test Passed?
1	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a specified single User record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users/:id HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 52ms Average Response Time: 6ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Table 6.4 Excerpt of Performance Testing for Backend API

Table 6.4 details a subset of the backend API performance testing, with Table 6.5 containing the performance testing results obtained from the whole system. The description of the purpose of the test can be observed, alongside the type of component the performance test is being verifying. The input data used during the testing process is detailed, with the expected output from the test being recorded.

In the case of testing the backend API, input data includes the endpoint resource, listed in the form of a URL, HTTP method, and any request parameters or body. The complete system is tested using the frontend application, therefore details the URL of the associated frontend application page, where the performance test is to be run. The actual output from the completion of the test is documented, with the actual output's response times and number of 500-511 HTTP status codes being compared to the expected output, to determine whether the performance test had passed.

A comprehensive set of performance test tables are contained within Appendix V.

Performance Test ID	Performance Test Description	Performance Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Performance Test Passed?
21	Test frontend homepage loading performance	Frontend	URL: localhost:3000	5 browser tabs open of home page	Performance, Accessibility, Best Practices, SEO Metrics > 75 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Performance: 53 Accessibility: 56 Best Practices: 92 SEO: 73	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Fail – Website performance, accessibility and SEO requires significant improvement
22	Test frontend homepage render performance	Frontend	URL: localhost:3000	5 browser tabs open of home page	Render: < 50ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Render: 10ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Table 6.5 Performance Testing for Frontend-Backend Coupling

6.4.5 Performance Testing Analysis

After conducting all performance tests, the collected results were thoroughly analysed, to obtain valuable insight into the performance of the system under typical usage. The data obtained from the conduction of performance testing both informed the overall system performance, and noted reasons for failed tests, therefore allowing a greater understanding to be obtained into the system's failings.

It was identified that all performed twenty backend API performance tests passed, meaning the backend API had an overall test pass rate of one hundred percent. This shows the backend API offers suitable performance, and fully complies with the defined five second page load speeds outlined in the non-functional requirements. During testing, no HTTP 500-511 status codes were returned, with the typical average response time being four milliseconds. The highest response time was 52 milliseconds, significantly under the five thousand millisecond limit, demonstrating the suitability of the backend API performance.

Following the integration testing of the whole system, it was noted that one of the two tests failed, offering a success rate of fifty percent. The failed test was noted as being caused by the website performance, accessibility and search engine optimisation (SEO) requiring significant performance increases, with scores of 53, 56 and 73 respectively.

To rectify such issues, the frontend React implementation may be refactored, with increased component reuse, to mitigate against the performance overhead. The frontend user interface design may utilise higher contrast between text and the background, with suitable adjustments made for screen readers. SEO may be optimised through using appropriate HTML meta tags, to provide increased knowledge surrounding the contents of the webpage. Whilst performance and accessibility must be addressed, to ensure all users have a positive user experience with the application, SEO would only be applicable to increase search rankings following deployment, therefore less emphasis may be placed on improving such score, with the process of rectifying these issues likely being time consuming.

6.4.6 Performance Testing Evaluation

Although the performance testing conducted provided the development team with valuable insight into the typical system performance, the performance testing approach itself had shortcomings.

One such problem with the backend API performance testing performed was that the results of such tests required manual recording into the test tables. As transcription was performed by the testing team, there is the potential for results to be incorrectly recorded, thus causing recorded false positive or negative test results. Additionally, due to the lengthy time required to record data, performance testing required a significant amount of project time. Furthermore, Postman does not display the highest and lowest response times or success rates for a test run, therefore such data had to be manually extracted through viewing all endpoint responses.

It could be argued that the number and frequency of requests sent to the backend API was not representative of real-world typical system usage, with twenty-five requests being sent with a one second delay between each request. In a deployed system with many thousand registered users, it may be that significantly greater numbers of requests would be sent, over a shorter time period, therefore rendering the results obtained inaccurate.

The whole system performance testing may arguably lack credibility, as the use of opening additional tabs on the frontend seeks only to hinder the performance of the overall system, thus also reducing server-side performance. As such, the use of additional client overheads may be seen to invalidate the overall results of the performance testing.

The Lighthouse browser extension used only provides the testing team with an overall performance metric for the website, in relation to typical website performance measured across existing sites. Consequently, as it does not return a comparable figure, such as a performance time in milliseconds, it may be seen to offer limited value to the testing process, as the actual application performance cannot be analysed.

The React Developer Tools' Profiler must be set to record, and the results analysed, manually, thus leading to potential inconsistencies in results. Should the recording of results be captured after the webpage has rendered for the first time, the render time for subsequent pages will appear significantly reduced, as only new or modified components will be required to be re-rendered. Furthermore, the render time is dependent on the performance of the frontend browser and machine the testing is performed on, thus results may not be representative of what all users may experience. For these reasons, this may lead to the results being argued as invalid.

The relevancy of conducting backend API and whole system performance testing on a production build system, running on a development machine, should not be overlooked. The results obtained could be seen to be inaccurate and irrelevant, as the real-world deployed system, running on significantly more powerful hardware, and with factors including internet connectivity and client latency, may result in vastly different performance outcomes. As such, whilst the system's performance may be measured to indicate there are no bottlenecks within the application, it may not truly reflect the expected performance of the system, thus reducing the validity of the performance testing.

Furthermore, it could be argued that testing the application using a client running on the same machine as the server would invalidate the results, as the running of the client application, or other processes or applications open on the machine, would add significant overhead to the server processes, thus negatively impacting the performance outcomes, and potentially leading to inaccuracies in results.

6.4.7 Conclusion

This subsection identified the benefits and necessity of conducting performance testing on the created system. It detailed the goals hoped to be achieved through the performing of such testing, and proposed a suitable approach to the conduction of the performance test, and subsequent recording and analysis of the results obtained. The process of recording the data obtained from the performance testing was documented, examining the potential data obtainable from such a test, and its relevancy in relation to analysis and decision making from the perspective of verifying the application's suitability to the non-functional requirements.

The results of data analysis on the acquired results were presented, alongside potential modifications required, to resolve current system performance concerns. A thorough review of the performance testing process was detailed, exploring the potential shortcomings in the performance testing conducted, and how such issues may hinder the accuracy or relevancy of the results.

6.4.8 Conclusive Recommendations

Identified Problem	Potential Solution	Importance
Website performance, accessibility and search engine optimisation (SEO) requires significant performance increases	Refactor frontend React implementation, use higher contrast between page text and background, make suitable adjustments for screen readers, use appropriate HTML meta tags	Medium

Table 6.6 Performance Testing Conclusive Recommendations and Potential Solutions

Following the conduction of performance testing, the identified problems were listed, alongside potential solutions to resolve such issues, as shown in Table 6.6. The level of importance, to designate how urgently the fault must be fixed, is also detailed.

6.5 Load Testing

6.5.1 Introduction

Load testing is a method of testing the system under extreme load, at the highest peaks in real-world usage and above (Draheim *et al.*, 2006). It is used to test the theoretical maximum number of simultaneous users the system can serve, identify any memory leaks within aspects of the application, and detect any limiting aspects or factors within the system, such as a database which cannot handle the demands of the front and backends.

6.5.2 Load Testing Goals

Load testing is important to ensuring the client is aware of the theoretical maximum number of users, allowing them to plan to mitigate against peak usage or seek to scale the system, as necessary (Draheim *et al.*, 2006). Load testing is critical to ensuring the system will meet the peak demands of its users, and may continue to be both reliable and usable, even with extreme usage. Prior to releasing the system for real-world use, it is important to develop a critical understanding of the application's maximum theoretical performance under extreme working conditions, to determine its behaviour and reliability and mitigate against potential risks associated with high system demand.

As the non-functional system requirements state the system must function under exceptional traffic loads or usage spikes, support a minimum of 150 concurrent users and sustain 99% yearly uptime, it is important that load testing is conducted, to ensure the developed application is fit for purpose, and meets the client's needs. Load testing was conducted to verify that the application offers support for usage spikes and a minimum of 150 concurrent transactions and page requests, with no downtime, and offers acceptable performance to large numbers of requests. It also allows for the identification of any components preventing the system from meeting the non-functional requirements and provides the client with expected maximum concurrent user guidelines.

6.5.3 Load Testing Design

Load testing was conducted on the frontend React application using the Lighthouse browser extension to determine webpage performance, via the single-click generated automated webpage performance report, making it highly suitable for testing with the limited project timescales provided. After navigating to an appropriate page within the frontend web application, the Lighthouse browser extension was clicked, to generate a page performance report. Such report was manually analysed, with results being recorded in the test table. Performance was also measured using the React Developer Tools browser extension's Profiler to view both the components rendered within each webpage, and their render time.

Whilst running the Profile tool, Apache JMeter was run to perform load testing on the backend and frontend, through sending a number of backend requests and measuring both the response times and status codes, to test the theoretical maximum number of simultaneous requests the server can handle. Apache JMeter is an application that allows a tester to send a specified number and frequency of HTTP requests to a URL, such as a frontend or backend web server, to replicate a number of simultaneous users accessing the web server.

Apache JMeter allows the tester to view the response times in both a tabular format, and plotted graphically within a line graph, showing the performance over time, and as more requests are handled. The combination of Apache JMeter and React Developer Tools was straightforward, but provided valuable insights into the performance of the application when under extreme load.

Attention was paid to the typically increasing response times, to calculate expected performance and scalability under load. Further consideration was given to the returned HTTP status codes, with status codes within the 500-599 range indicating a server error, likely due to the server being overloaded with requests, thus indicating that the server had reached its maximum number of simultaneous clients. Apache JMeter offers a simple and fast process to load testing, with its interface being similar to Postman.

6.5.4 Load Testing Data Gathering

Following the design of the design of the load testing strategy, load tests were conducted. Load tests centred around testing all produced backend API endpoint functionality, and the whole system, formed as a result of frontend and backend coupling, to ensure the system was capable of processing a large number of requests and returned responses in a timely manner, thus supporting many concurrent users, as per the non-functional requirements. Load tests were formed of view, create, edit and delete operations, to recognise system performance across all operation types, with the task description and expected output being recorded for each task. During any modifications to the system functionality, and following refactoring, all load tests were re-run, to ensure system capacity had not been adversely affected.

During the conduction of the load test, the system’s output was recorded, including the lowest, highest and average response times, and number of internal server errors, with HTTP status codes between 500 and 511, returned from the backend API. When testing the whole system, the overall system performance was recorded, as per the results from Lighthouse, in addition to any internal server errors. Such data was gathered through observing the results from the running of Postman application tests, or the report generated by Lighthouse, with the outputs being manually recorded by the testing team.

Load Test ID	Load Test Description	Load Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Load Test Passed?
1	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a specified single User record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users/:id HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 426ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Table 6.7 Excerpt of Load Testing for Backend API

Load Test ID	Load Test Description	Load Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Load Test Passed?
21	Test frontend homepage loading performance	Frontend	URL: localhost:3000	5 browser tabs open of home page	Performance, Accessibility, Best Practices, SEO Metrics > 50 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Performance: 53 Accessibility: 56 Best Practices: 92 SEO: 73	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Fail – Website performance, accessibility and SEO requires significant improvement
22	Test frontend homepage render performance	Frontend	URL: localhost:3000	5 browser tabs open of home page	Render: < 500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Render: 25ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Table 6.8 Load Testing for Frontend-Backend Coupling

Table 6.7 details a subset of the backend API load testing, with Table 6.8 containing the load testing results obtained from the whole system. The description of the purpose of the test can be observed, alongside the type of component the performance test is being verifying. The input data used during the testing process is detailed, with the expected output from the test being recorded.

In the case of testing the backend API, input data includes the endpoint resource, listed in the form of a URL, HTTP method, and any request parameters or body. The complete system is tested using the frontend application, therefore details the URL of the associated frontend application page, where the load test is to be run. The actual output from the completion of the test is documented, with the actual output’s response times and number of 500-511 HTTP status codes being compared to the expected output, to determine whether the load test had passed.

A comprehensive set of load test tables are contained within Appendix W.

6.5.5 Load Testing Analysis

After conducting all load tests, the collected results were thoroughly analysed, to obtain valuable insight into the performance of the system under extreme usage. The data obtained from the conduction of load testing both informed the theoretical maximum system capacity, and noted reasons for failed tests, therefore allowing a greater understanding to be obtained into the system's failings.

It was identified that all performed twenty backend API load tests passed, meaning the backend API had an overall test pass rate of one hundred percent. This shows the backend API offers suitable capacity for supporting all concurrent users, and fully complies with the defined constraints outlined in the non-functional requirements. During testing, no HTTP 500-511 status codes were returned, with the typical average response time being nine hundred and twenty-nine milliseconds. The highest response time was one thousand, three hundred and seventy-six milliseconds, significantly under the two thousand, five hundred millisecond limit, demonstrating the suitability of the backend API capabilities.

Following the load testing of the whole system, it was noted that one of the two tests failed, offering a success rate of fifty percent. The failed test was noted as being caused by the website performance, accessibility and search engine optimisation (SEO) requiring significant load capacity increases, with scores of 53, 56 and 73 respectively.

To rectify such issues, the frontend React implementation may be refactored, with increased component reuse, to mitigate against the performance overhead. The frontend user interface design may utilise higher contrast between text and the background, with suitable adjustments made for screen readers. SEO may be optimised through using appropriate HTML meta tags, to provide increased knowledge surrounding the contents of the webpage. Whilst performance and accessibility must be addressed, to ensure all users have a positive user experience with the application, SEO would only be applicable to increase search rankings following deployment, therefore less emphasis may be placed on improving such score, with the process of rectifying these issues likely being time consuming.

It should be noted that the backend API had the most inconsistency with loading speeds, with the frontend appearing relatively consistent across load testing, although the backend suffering performance issues. It may be argued that a NoSQL document-oriented database would mitigate against such issues, due to the scalability and enhanced performance benefits it offers.

Resource requests involving queries with increased numbers of relational joins were noted as having an increased response time, therefore directly detailing the performance overhead caused by large numbers of joins. As such, joins were only made where necessary, to reduce the performance overhead on the database, thus increasing the potential performance, capacity and scalability of the application.

6.5.6 Load Testing Evaluation

Although the load testing conducted provided the development team with valuable insight into the theoretical maximum system capacity, the load testing approach itself had shortcomings.

One such problem with the backend API load testing performed was that the results of such tests required manual recording into the test tables. As transcription was performed by the testing team, there is the potential for results to be incorrectly recorded, thus causing recorded false positive or negative test results. Additionally, due to the lengthy time required to record data, load testing required a significant amount of project time. Furthermore, Postman does not display the highest and lowest response times or success rates for a test run, therefore such data had to be manually extracted through viewing all endpoint responses.

The whole system load testing may arguably lack credibility, as the use of opening additional tabs on the frontend seeks only to hinder the capacity of the overall system, thus also reducing server-side performance. As such, the use of additional client overheads may be seen to invalidate the overall results of the load testing.

The Lighthouse browser extension used only provides the testing team with an overall performance metric for the website, in relation to typical website performance measured across existing sites. Consequently, as it does not return a comparable figure, such as a performance time in milliseconds, it may be seen to offer limited value to the testing process, as the actual application capacity cannot be analysed.

The React Developer Tools' Profiler must be set to record, and the results analysed, manually, thus leading to potential inconsistencies in results. Should the recording of results be captured after the webpage has rendered for the first time, the render time for subsequent pages will appear significantly reduced, as only new or modified components will be required to be re-rendered. Furthermore, the render time is dependent on the performance of the frontend browser and machine the testing is performed on, thus results may not be representative of what all users may experience. For these reasons, this may lead to the results being argued as invalid.

The relevancy of conducting backend API and whole system load testing on a production build system, running on a development machine, should not be overlooked. The results obtained could be seen to be inaccurate and irrelevant, as the real-world deployed system, running on significantly more powerful hardware, and with factors including internet connectivity and client latency, may result in vastly different performance outcomes. As such, whilst the system's capacity may be measured to indicate there are no bottlenecks within the application, it may not truly reflect the expected capacity of the system, thus reducing the validity of the load testing.

Furthermore, it could be argued that testing the application using a client running on the same machine as the server would invalidate the results, as the running of the client application, or other processes or applications open on the machine, would add significant overhead to the server processes, thus negatively impacting the performance outcomes, and potentially leading to inaccuracies in results.

6.5.7 Conclusion

This subsection identified the benefits and necessity of conducting load testing on the created system. It detailed the goals hoped to be achieved through the performing of such testing, and proposed a suitable approach to the conduction of the load test, and subsequent recording and analysis of the results obtained. The process of recording the data obtained from the load testing was documented, examining the potential data obtainable from such a test, and its relevancy in relation to analysis and decision making from the perspective of verifying the application's suitability to the non-functional requirements.

The results of data analysis on the acquired results were presented, alongside potential modifications required, to resolve current system capacity concerns. A thorough review of the load testing process was detailed, exploring the potential shortcomings in the load testing conducted, and how such issues may hinder the accuracy or relevancy of the results.

6.5.8 Conclusive Recommendations

Identified Problem	Potential Solution	Importance
Website performance, accessibility and search engine optimisation (SEO) requires significant performance increases	Refactor frontend React implementation, use higher contrast between page text and background, make suitable adjustments for screen readers, use appropriate HTML meta tags	Medium

Table 6.9 Load Testing Conclusive Recommendations and Potential Solutions

Following the performance of load testing, the identified problems were listed, alongside potential solutions to resolve such issues, as shown in Table 6.9. The level of importance, to designate how urgently the fault must be fixed, is also detailed.

6.6 System Testing

6.6.1 Introduction

System testing is a method of testing that an application contains all its necessary requirements, and that the requirements are successfully met, achieving the desired outcome (Briand and Labiche, 2002). It involves testing the implemented functionality against the defined requirement, and testing the actual output matches that expected of the system. System testing is a form of black box testing, investigating the output of the system, independent of its implementation or underlying structure.

System testing involves testing each system requirement within the application, checking the output of completing the requirement in the system matches the expected output. For each requirement identified, a test case must be produced, with the developer specifying the necessary functionality, input data and system output. The testing is then enacted upon the system, with the actual and expected results being examined.

6.6.2 System Testing Goals

System testing is important to verifying that the developed system meets all defined requirements, as elicited from the client (Briand and Labiche, 2002). System testing is critical to ensuring the system will provide all necessary functionality and behaviour for its users and meet the desired non-functional requirements. Prior to releasing the system for real-world use, it is important to ensure all provided functionality is fully-functioning, and all implemented 'must have' requirements have been suitably developed, with appropriate behaviour.

As the system may be deployed following system testing, it is crucial to verify the functionality of all user stories and application features, to ensure they provide appropriate behaviour. Should any failed tests be present, the client must be aware of such issues, or associated functionality should be rectified or removed, to ensure the system is fit for purpose. System testing was used to ensure all necessary user stories had been successfully implemented, with appropriate behaviour, verifying the system was fit for purpose, with test results being able to be sent to the client. Test cases are paramount to ensuring the created system meets the needs of its users and client.

6.6.3 System Testing Design

Following the creation of use case descriptions, during the project's Requirements stage, functional test cases were produced, based on the identified use cases. Test cases record the results of testing against identified user stories, listing expected and actual results for all user stories, to demonstrate the system meets the system requirements identified. Test cases are used to test the system functionality against the identified user stories and requirements, ensuring the system is fit for purpose.

Each test case defines a series of pre-conditions and expected and actual output and performance. The process to be followed during testing, to perform the desired system operation, is listed, with the testing team following the documented steps on the developed system and recording the results. The overall actual output, performance and pass is determined from the sum of the results from each step undertaken to fulfil the test case.

6.6.4 System Testing Data Gathering

Following the design of the design of the system testing strategy, system tests were conducted. System tests centred around testing the whole system functionality, to ensure the system was capable of fulfilling the implemented functional requirements, adhering to non-functional requirements. System tests were formed of all implemented use case descriptions operations, to recognise system performance across all functionality, with the task description and expected output and performance being recorded for each task, alongside the stages required to accomplish the task. During any modifications to the system functionality, and following refactoring, all system tests were re-run, to ensure no system behaviour had been modified.

During the conduction of the performance test, the outlined test case processes were performed, with the system's output at each stage being recorded. Upon completion of all processes, the results obtained from the processes were combined to determine the overall system output and performance, determining whether the test case had passed. Such data was gathered through observing the results from the completion of processes, with the outputs being manually recorded by the testing team.

Table 6.10 details the results of a system test case for the view assessments use case. The description of the purpose of the test can be observed, alongside the goals and requirements being verified. Any required pre-conditions, prior to the start of the conduction of the processes, are listed, with the expected and actual performance and output being listed, for verification against defined functional and non-functional requirements. The test case is determined to have passed if all processes have passed, with each process having its own description, inputted data, and expected output. Upon completing each process, the output is recorded and compared to the expected output, to determine if the process has passed.

A comprehensive set of system test tables are contained within Appendix X.

Test Case Number:	1					
Test Case Name:	View Assessments					
Test Case Description:	Test that the system displays a list of the user's past, current and upcoming assessments on-screen					
Test Case Goals:	A list of the user's past, current and upcoming assessments are displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes assessment name, date, module information and assessment leader.					
Test Case Requirements:	R1, R2					
Pre-Conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User is logged in • User is a member of a module • Module contains assessments 					
Expected Output:	View Assessments screen should be displayed with a list user's past, current and upcoming assessments					
Actual Output:	View Assessments screen is displayed with a list user's assessments					
Expected Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of assessments should be displayed within 5 seconds 					
Actual Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of assessments is displayed within 5 seconds 					
Test Case Passed?	Passed (Passed Processes: 100% [2/2]) (Passed Performance: 100% [1/1])					
Process ID	Process	Process Description	Inputted Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Process Passed?
1	Homepage navigation	Navigate to homepage (localhost:3000/)	URL: localhost:3000 /	Homepage is displayed	Homepage is displayed	Pass
2	View webpage content	View assessment card information displayed on webpage	N/A	User's assessments are displayed on-screen	User's assessments are displayed on-screen	Fail – Not grouped by time

Table 6.10 System Test Case for View Assessments Use Case

6.6.5 System Testing Analysis

After conducting all system tests, the collected results were thoroughly analysed, to obtain valuable insight into the suitability of the system. The data obtained from the conduction of system testing both informed the appropriateness of the application, and noted reasons for failed tests, therefore allowing a greater understanding to be obtained into the system's failings.

It was identified that all performed five system tests passed, meaning the system had an overall test pass rate of one hundred percent. This shows the system offers suitable functionality and meets all use cases identified during the requirements elicitation process. During testing, only one minor issue was identified, with favourite assessments not being grouped into sections for favourites and unfavourite assessments. Such requirement was not listed in the test case requirements, although was noted in a previously elicited should have requirement. As such, the test was marked as passed, although should time become available, this feature would be implemented.

6.6.6 System Testing Evaluation

Although the system testing conducted provided the development team with valuable insight into the accuracy of system behaviour, the system testing approach itself had shortcomings.

One such problem with the system testing performed was that all system testing had pre-conditions, meaning such tasks had already been completed, prior to the test case being performed. As such, it could be argued that the test results may be invalid, as it cannot be verified that had the pre-conditions attempted to be performed during the test case, the system would still be fully functional and provide the appropriate behaviour, invalidating the results.

It could be argued that as the expected output of each process was based on the system designs and developed implementation, such output descriptions may be incorrect, as they may not be fit for the client’s purpose. Additionally, the workflow and order of processes is defined by the implemented system, and the system testing is unable to confirm whether the workflow used is the most effective.

As all performance metrics were manually timed by the testing team, there is the potential for there to be inaccuracies in the measurement of actual performance, meaning the results may be invalid.

The performing and recording of listed processes was completed manually. As transcription was completed by the testing team, there is the potential for results to be incorrectly recorded, thus causing recorded false positive or negative test results. Additionally, due to the lengthy time required to record data, system testing required a significant amount of project time.

The overall test case pass, passed processed and passed performance figures were extracted from the collation of all process pass results, therefore there may be inaccuracies in the calculation of the overall system test case results. Consequently, it could be argued that such results may lack validity, due to their potential to contain inaccuracies.

The system performance metric may arguably lack credibility, as the display time is dependent on the performance of the frontend browser and machine the testing is performed on, thus results may not be representative of what all users may experience. For these reasons, this may lead to the results being argued as invalid.

6.6.7 Conclusion

This subsection identified the benefits and necessity of conducting system testing on the created system. It detailed the goals hoped to be achieved through the performing of such testing, and proposed a suitable approach to the conduction of the system test, and subsequent recording and analysis of the results obtained. The process of recording the data obtained from the system testing was documented, examining the potential data obtainable from such a test, and its relevancy in relation to analysis and decision making from the perspective of verifying the application’s suitability to the elicited requirements and implemented user stories.

The results of data analysis on the acquired results were presented, alongside potential modifications required, to resolve current system behaviour and performance concerns. A thorough review of the system testing process was detailed, exploring the potential shortcomings in the system testing conducted, and how such issues may hinder the accuracy or relevancy of the results.

6.6.8 Conclusive Recommendations

Identified Problem	Potential Solution	Importance
Favourite assessments not being grouped into sections for favourites and unfavourite assessments	Separate list output of favourite and unfavourite assessments in frontend	Low

Table 6.11 System Testing Conclusive Recommendations and Potential Solutions

Following the performance of system testing, the identified problems were listed, alongside potential solutions to resolve such issues, as shown in Table 6.11. The level of importance, to designate how urgently the fault must be fixed, is also detailed.

6.7 Usability Testing

Usability testing is a method of testing that an application is able to be used successfully by its intended userbase (Wichansky, 2000). It involves testing the design is suitable for the target users, and that they can navigate and perform their required user stories within the system effectively, based on the workflows, visual cues and layout of items on-screen. Usability testing is crucial to checking the system's user interface is fit for purpose, as although the system may be functional from a technical perspective, if the target users are unable to properly utilise the system, it is not wholly appropriate.

6.7.1 Introduction

Usability testing is a mechanism for evaluating that a developed system meets the user interface design needs of its userbase, through observing and recording users completing a series of tasks within the system (Wichansky, 2000). Usability testing may be performed using methods including guerrilla testing, in which random users within a select location are asked to fulfil user stories within the system, a usability lab, where supervised sessions are held by a moderator to examine users' success with fulfilling user stories, or video and/or screen recording, in which participants and their actions are recorded, for their behaviour to be analysed.

Testing may be moderated, where the moderator prompts and assists the user throughout completing their user story, or unmoderated, where the participant is given a series of tasks to complete, with no guidance (Wichansky, 2000).

This subsection outlines the goals of the completion of utilising usability testing on the developed application, and benefits hoped to be obtained from the usability test results. The design of the usability testing strategy will be detailed, examining the mechanisms used to recruit usability test participants, conduct usability tests, and record results.

As human participants were recruited to participate in the usability testing process, to gain an accurate representation of the system's user interface suitability within different user types, consent is required to ensure participants are willing to participate in the study. The process of duly informing prospective participants and recording their consent is presented. The subsection presents the usability test results obtained from the conduction of usability tests on the recruited participants of all user types, followed by a detailed analysis of the obtained results, and evaluation of the usability testing strategy utilised.

6.7.2 Usability Testing Goals

Usability testing was used to identify any fundamental design issues within the frontend application, including navigational and workflow problems, visual cues and layout of items on-screen. It provides detail on any elements of confusion or barriers to preventing the user story being accomplished. Through monitoring the user's actions whilst performing the user story, and listening to user feedback, resolutions to design issues and prospective improvements become clearer.

The testing stage also seeks to gather further information and affirm decisions made surrounding the application's userbase, including their views, ideas, design requirements and competence in technology. The usability testing phase tests that the design is suitable for, and may be used successfully by, the target users. It is crucial to checking the system's user interface is fit for purpose, as although the system may be functional from a technical perspective, if the target users are unable to properly utilise the system, it is not wholly appropriate.

Usability testing seeks to collect both qualitative and quantitative data, with qualitative data, including numerical values, providing simple analysis and testing of defined non-functional requirements, and qualitative data seeking to ratify design decisions made and overall user interface opinions. Such tests were conducted on a range of test requirements, derived from the user stories captured for each user type. A minimum of one type of each user story operation was performed, such as a view, create, edit or delete procedure, with the results being able to be extrapolated to test the system's suitability across all provided functionality.

Quantitative data, although typically difficult to obtain, was gathered in the form of recording the expected completion time of a task, based on the associated non-functional requirement, and the average time recorded by the developer, performing the task as each of the user personas. During the usability test, the total time taken for the participant to achieve the user story was recorded, which was measured against the expected completion time, to calculate both the potential real-world user interface performance, and suitability with the non-functional requirements. User story completion time was collected by starting a stopwatch at the beginning of the user attempting to perform the user story, and recording the stopwatch value upon the completion of the user story.

The number of mis-clicks whilst performing the user story, or incorrect navigation or other such decisions, was monitored and recorded. This could be used to identify any issues with visual cues, insufficient or unhelpful accompanying textual descriptions, workflow or navigational problems within the user interface. Mis-clicks were visually monitored, both live and after watching a produced screen recording of the user accomplishing the user story, and tallied within the usability test report.

The number of pauses whilst performing the user story were recorded, as pauses can indicate clear problems with on-screen layout, visual cues and insufficient or unhelpful accompanying textual descriptions within the user interface. A pause can be identified as a significant time period, identified as greater than ten seconds, where the user is viewing the user interface but not performing any action. As with mis-clicks, pauses were visually monitored and tallied within the usability test report.

Qualitative metrics also provide a wealth of usability feedback, with the user's facial expressions during task completion having been visually monitored and recorded within the usability test report. Facial expressions can provide an accurate representation of a user's thoughts, emotions, problems or positive aspects whilst using the system. This provides a non-intrusive method of obtaining both user thoughts throughout their user story journey, and identifying changes of emotion over time, highlighting any issues or positive aspects of the user interface.

The user's speech during task completion was recorded within the usability test report. Speech can provide insight into a user's thoughts and identify issues within the user interface. Mumbling, use of words such as 'hmm' or long silent pauses may indicate struggles with the system's usability whilst using the system. This can provide a mechanism to better detect issues relating to the user interface, without risk of hindering the user's completion of their test task.

The usability test report notes any screen observations, such as mis-clicks, navigation issues or other usability problems, gathered during the task completion. These user mistakes highlight potential usability issues within the system. This seeks to record problems with the user interface, without impairing the user's task completion.

The user's overall opinions of the system was recorded in the usability test report. Upon completion of the user story, the participant was asked of their thoughts on the usability of the system and the ease of achieving the user story. Any comments gathered from the participant were documented, to obtain an insight into the usability and design of the user interface.

If the user successfully accomplished the task they were provided, this was recorded in the usability test report. This is crucial to calculating if the user interface is successful in allowing the user to fulfil their user story, thus identifying user interface issues if the task was unable to be completed. If the user's task had been completed successfully, and within the expected completion time, the usability test had been passed. This was documented within the usability report, to determine if the user interface is fit for purpose, and any changes required to be made, as detailed in Section 6.7.6 – Usability Testing Analysis.

6.7.3 Usability Testing Design

The design of usability testing is crucial to ensuring accurate usability testing, and a representative sample and sample size. Usability tests were conducted via individual interviews, as the testing team was unable to facilitate multiple usability tests occurring concurrently. To ensure users' unfamiliarity with the system, to provide more accurate results, interviews were conducted with participants in isolation, so participants were unable to be influenced or gain an understanding of system processes, through viewing other participants' completing tasks. It must be noted that for users lacking technological confidence or understanding, the presence of other participants may invoke worry or other negative emotions, thus affecting results.

Interviews with potential users from all identified user groups were performed, including students, assessors and assessment leaders, conducted using guerrilla testing, in which random users within a select location are asked to fulfil user stories within the system. Due to the nature of the project, paid participant usability lab sessions would be unsuitable, whereas guerrilla testing would allow a range of users to attempt the defined system tasks, efficiently and cost-effectively.

During interviews, users were asked to perform set tasks using the created system. The time taken to achieve the task, general observations and user feedback were recorded. The user was not provided guidance, hints or steps to accomplish their given task during the usability test, as the system must be navigable enough that untrained users may achieve user stories, without help. This also ensures consistency across test results, as different numbers or levels of hints provided to users across separate tests would make test results more difficult to compare against each other.

Usability testing was performed both using an unmoderated screen recording method, and reviewing the user's emotions and ideas as they complete the provided task, as this aids in identifying any issues with the navigability of the user interface. Once the application is deployed, it is unlikely users will receive any training on its use, therefore it is important that the system is intuitive enough for users to fulfil their user stories without assistance.

The use of screen recording and visual transcription assists with identifying any major issues with the usability of the frontend application and should not change user behaviour, as some users may be offput by being video recorded.

Upon completion of the usability test, the user was asked their overall opinions on the system, its usability, and their ease in accomplishing the task they were provided. This was recorded, to gain a better understanding of the system usability. If necessary, further test tasks were provided to the user, following the previously defined process.

The usability testing interviews were expected to take a relatively short time, with users having simple tasks to complete, analogous to the real-world user stories gathered. It is beneficial for tests to be conducted in a timely manner, as participants are often busy, would likely lack engagement or provide less accurate test results, if tests take too long to perform. As the system required setup, communication was required to arrange mutually convenient testing appointments with users, with subsequent writeup and meaningful analysis of the results being necessary, contained within Section 6.7.5 – Usability Testing Data Gathering and Section 6.7.6 – Usability Testing Analysis

6.7.4 Usability Testing Consent

To ensure participants were informed to consent in the study, a Participant Information Sheet (PIS) was constructed, outlining the project’s purpose and duration, expected participant commitment, potential risks involved in participating in the study, the required data that will be gathered, and how and by whom collected data will be used.

The PIS also detailed data retention, compliance with the Data Protection Act (2018) and GDPR, security mechanisms to protect collected data, data confidentiality, and the process for withdrawing from the study, including what happens to participants’ data if their consent is withdrawn.

The PIS was provided to prospective participants, in combination with a consent form, to brief them and gather their consent to take part in the study. Should participants have any questions prior to, during, or after conclusion of the study, they were able to contact the research team, to become better informed.

Prior to interviews, prospective participants were informed of the purpose of the study via the Participant Information Sheet (PIS), an excerpt of which is shown in Figure 12, and the testing team answered any participant questions, to ensure participants were duly informed of the study, collected data and potential risks. Should the informed participant wish to partake in the study, their consent was recorded on the provided consent form, an excerpt of which is shown in Figure 13. The user was be given instructions regarding the nature of the usability test, and the task they are expected to accomplish within the system.

What is the expected of you in the study?

You are expected to be available to provide feedback and answer questions, during regular intervals of the study’s duration. The study will operate using an iterative approach, therefore you will be contacted typically once every three weeks, to obtain feedback on the features implemented into a prototype application and gather information relating to the current issues and potential solutions surrounding group presentation assessment.

Contact may range from an email asking you if you could complete a survey, which should take no longer than ten minutes to complete, or a one-to-one interview, which should last no more than fifteen minutes. Your commitment is highly appreciated, although if you are unavailable to participate in the study for a short duration, this is perfectly acceptable, and you are under no obligation to be involved in the study each time you receive contact from us.

Figure 6.12 Subset of Usability Test Participant Information Sheet (PIS)

Please tick the appropriate boxes	Ye s	No
1. Taking part in the study		
I have read and understood the study information dated 12/11/2022, or it has been read to me. I have been able to ask questions about the study and my questions have been answered to my satisfaction.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study and understand that I can refuse to answer questions and I can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason, and without penalty.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 6.13 Subset of Usability Test Consent Form

The complete Participant Information Sheet (PIS) and consent form are contained within Appendix Y.

Individual interviews were conducted with individual participants, with structured and semi-structured interviews being used. Interviews following the completion of the usability test, to obtain further insight into the suitability of the system's design, collected data using transcription, with the interviewer manually recording response information in a Microsoft Word document.

No audio or video recording techniques were used, and interviewees were free to review or request copies, deletion, or modification of the transcribed document at any time. Response data was associated with participants through means of a provided ID, preventing responses from being directly linked to an individual, although facilitating the identification of responses, for deletion in the case of participant consent withdrawal.

6.7.5 Usability Testing Data Gathering

Following the design of the design of the usability testing strategy, and recruitment of consenting participants to contribute to the application's usability testing, usability tests were conducted. Three users of each user type, assessment leaders, assessors and students, were selected to partake in the usability test. Prior to the conduction of each usability test task, the user was informed of the activity to be performed within the system, and the results of their use of the system were subsequently recorded.

Usability tests centred around testing users on requirements representative of typical system activities of users of the defined user type, to better identify the application's real-world performance, and identify likely issues. Test requirements were formed of view, create, edit and delete operations, to recognise system performance across all operation types, with the task description and expected completion time being recorded for each task. For each user type, all participants within the user type completed the same tasks, to support analysis of system functionality.

During the user participating in the usability test, their performance, and thus the system usability, was recorded, including the time taken to complete the task, the number of times the user mis-clicked, navigated to an incorrect page or made an incorrect decision, and the number of pauses of greater than 10 seconds. Such data was gathered through later observing the screen recording of the user completing the task, as the testing team observed the user at the time of the test being conducted.

Through observing the user’s behaviour, facial expressions and participant speech were manually noted during the task completion, to gather further insight into the user’s emotions whilst using the system. Following the completion of the task, the user was questioned to obtain their overall opinions of the system and its usability, which were subsequently summarised and recorded. The user’s task achievement was noted, alongside if the usability test had passed, meaning the user had achieved the task within the expected completion time.

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
1	View Assessments	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	30 seconds	2	1	Initially happy, then became confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	None	User studied navbar and (currently displayed) homepage for a significant amount of time	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although was confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	Yes	Pass
3	Create Assessment	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page and create a new assessment	3 minutes	2 minutes	4	3	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User quickly located Create Assessment button and inputted appropriate assessment details	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the Create Assessment button should be positioned at the top of the page, as with many assessments displayed within the list, it would be difficult and time consuming to find, and the form should be displayed within a modal or a new page, for increased readability and to prevent distractions from the page content	Yes	Pass
5	Edit Assessment	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page and edit an existing assessment	3 minutes	1 minute 30 seconds	2	2	Happy	User mumbled "mm" to themselves multiple times throughout	User quickly located Edit button and inputted appropriate assessment details	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the form should be displayed within a modal, for increased readability and to prevent distractions from the page content	Yes	Pass
7	Delete Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and delete an existing rubric	2 minutes	30 seconds	1	1	Happy	None	User quickly located Delete button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were of a good size and easy to use	Yes	Pass

Table 6.14 Assessment Leader Participant’s Usability Test Results

Table 6.14 details a subset of an assessment leader participant’s usability test results, detailing tests conducted for each operation type. The usability test requirements can be observed, alongside a brief description of the stages required to complete the requirement. The expected completion time was generated based on the development team performing the task as each of the relevant user personas previously created, and calculating the average time taken. The usability test results recorded can be observed in the remaining columns.

A comprehensive set of usability test tables for all participants of all user types are contained within Appendix Z.

6.7.6 Usability Testing Analysis

After conducting all usability tests, the collected results were thoroughly analysed, to obtain valuable insight into the suitability of the application, including its user interface design, to the userbase. The data obtained from usability testing included both qualitative and quantitative data, allowing for more detailed and meaningful analysis to be conducted, to further improve the application’s user experience.

To better visualise the quantitative data obtained, a series of bar line graphs were produced for each participant user type and recorded metric, facilitating the comparison of different user types across each recorded measurement. Through grouping the data by task type, and plotting all participant results individually, anomalies or problems with particular functionality become clearer, through viewing them in comparison to the other tasks. Furthermore, the average trend line allows for the overall task performance to be compared across user and task types.

Figure 6.15 Assessment Leader Participant's Task Completion Times By Task Type

Figure 6.15 shows the task completion time taken for assessment leaders, outlining that no singular task of a particular type was abnormally difficult or longwinded to complete, in comparison to its counterpart, confirming all functionality is equally accessible and consistent. It can be observed that the greatest variance in completion times occurs in editing tasks, although this may be attributed to differences in typing speed when completing the form.

With the greatest overall completion time being three minutes, and shortest completion time being 30 seconds, the tasks are all able to be completed within a suitable time period for all assessment leaders. However, it must be noted that the times for viewing tasks would benefit from reductions, as for one user having a completion time of two minutes, this evidences a practical usability issue.

Figure 6.16 Assessor Participant’s Task Completion Times By Task Type

Figure 6.16 shows the task completion time taken for assessors, outlining that the editing tasks took significantly longer to complete than any other task type, potentially indicating a fundamental problem with such process. This could be attributed to the tasks themselves, with the assessors’ create operation not involving the completion of any forms, thus affecting the presented results.

It must be noted that assessor task completion times were significantly lower than those of assessment leaders, offering a strong indication that the system would be intuitive enough for external users to grasp with a lack of sufficient training. However, it must be noted that the edit task completion times must be reduced, as these are unsuitable for the vast data entry required when assessing students within a limited timeframe.

Figure 6.17 Student Participant's Task Completion Times By Task Type

Figure 6.17 shows the task completion time taken for students, outlining that the editing tasks similarly took significantly longer to complete than any other task type. In contrast, create and delete tasks were completed very quickly, indicating system uses an appropriate icon mapping to the real world and layout. It must be noted that the time taken to complete the view tasks was still disproportionately high, indicating a usability problem when attempting to find specific information on the website.

Figure 6.18 Assessment Leader Participant's Number of Mis-Clicks By Task Type

Figure 6.18 shows the number of mis-clicks, incorrect navigation, or wrong decisions made by assessment leaders, outlining that the all tasks invoked a similar number of mis-clicks or decisional problems. Input tasks, such as create and edit, typically involved more mis-clicks, identifying the requirement for improving the form visibility, to aid in its completion. In contrast, top-level layout must be improved, as poor navigation led to high numbers of incorrect decisions being made for view and delete tasks.

Figure 6.19 Assessor Participant’s Number of Mis-Clicks By Task Type

Figure 6.19 shows the number of mis-clicks, incorrect navigation, or wrong decisions made by assessors, outlining that edit tasks had a significantly higher number of mis-clicks. This may be attributed to the poor form readability, presenting a clear barrier that would hinder system efficiency, unless rectified. With all other task types averaging one mis-click or wrong decision, this is within tolerance, as the user is yet to familiarise themselves with the system.

Figure 6.20 Student Participant's Number of Mis-Clicks By Task Type

Figure 6.20 shows the number of mis-clicks, incorrect navigation, or wrong decisions made by students, outlining that edit tasks had a significantly higher number of mis-clicks than any other task type. This may be attributed to the poor form readability, highlighting that input forms must use larger text, to increase their legibility. All other task types can be noted as having an acceptable number of mis-clicks.

Figure 6.21 Assessment Leader Participant's Number of Pauses By Task Type

Figure 6.21 shows the number of pauses of greater than ten seconds made by assessment leaders, outlining that the create and edit forms significantly hinder user performance. This may be attributed to there being too much content within forms, and the font size making the content more difficult to read. In the case of the second view task, clear usability issues are present, due to the increased number of pauses in comparison to the first view task. This may be attributed to the card's title or image requiring clicking to navigate to the appropriate page, rather than the card background, thus confusing the user.

Figure 6.22 Assessor Participant's Number of Pauses By Task Type

Figure 6.22 shows the number of pauses of greater than ten seconds made by assessors, outlining that the edit form significantly hinders user performance. This may be attributed to the font size making the content more difficult to read. In the case of view and create operations, these may be higher, due to the users initially familiarising themselves with the system layout and functionality. After being aware of the location of the create task functionality, the delete task functionality becomes significantly quicker to locate, indicating a clear user experience journey, thus no pauses were recorded.

Figure 6.23 Student Participant's Number of Pauses By Task Type

Figure 6.23 shows the number of pauses of greater than ten seconds made by students, outlining that all task types had an equal number of pauses for some users. In the case of view operation, there may be more pauses, due to the users initially familiarising themselves with the system layout and functionality. After being aware of the location of the page layouts and task functionality, future tasks become significantly quicker to complete, indicating a clear user experience journey, thus no pauses were recorded.

After collation of the qualitative data, it was observed that most participants of any user type mumbled 'hmm' to themselves multiple times throughout the 'View Assessments' task, indicating that the method to perform such task was not clear within the system. During this time, users were observed studying the navigation bar and currently displayed homepage for a significant amount of time, indicating they were uncertain of the differences between the assessments they were seeing on the displayed homepage, compared to the assessments navigation link.

Following the completion of the task, users commonly expressed an opinion that they were confused about the differences between the homepage and Assessments page. The distinction between both pages must be rectified, to allow users to fully understand the differences between the assessments listed on both pages. Whilst the homepage contains assessments, these are the assessments the user is enrolled in. In contrast, the Assessments page is intended to display all available assessments. Through naming the Assessments page 'Assessments', this is presenting a significant usability issue, which may be resolved through renaming the page 'All Assessments', to provide additional contextual information.

It was identified that users of any user type completing the 'View Assessment Panel/Group Profile' task either mumbled 'hmm' to themselves multiple times throughout the task, or talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves, indicating they were struggling to complete the task. During later analysis of the screen recording, it was observed that the user was clicking the group or profile card background and not the text or image within the card itself.

Following the completion of the task, users commonly expressed an opinion that the clickable area of the card was too small, due to it only being present on the text or image. Instead, they noted that the background of the card should also be clickable, thus providing a greater clickable area. Through ensuring the entire card is clickable, this would seek to prevent navigability issues stemming from the user clicking the wrong element on the card. Users did note that the panel cards were of an appropriate size, utilised a good internal layout, and the journey to view a profile was clear and easy.

It was identified that assessment leaders completing the 'Create Assessment', 'Create Assessment Rubric', 'Edit Assessment' and 'Edit Assessment Rubric' tasks talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout attempting the task, indicating they were struggling to complete the requirement. After observing the screen recordings, assessment leaders frequently struggled to locate the 'Create Assessment' and 'Create Rubric' buttons and read the form field advice and error messages.

Following the completion of the task, assessment leaders commonly expressed an opinion that the 'Create Assessment' and 'Create Rubric' buttons should be positioned at the top of their respective pages, as with many assessments or rubrics displayed within the page's list, it would be difficult and time consuming to find the necessary button to create a new item. Additionally, some assessment leaders reported that form should be displayed within a modal or on a new page, for increased readability and to prevent distractions from the page content. As the form is currently displayed at the bottom of the page, some users may become overwhelmed with the content they are expected to view.

Assessment leaders also noted that the form advice and error messages should utilise a greater font size, as they were difficult to read, whilst the start and end time input fields needed to match the other textual input fields contained within the form, for increased readability. However, it was stated that the forms were intuitive, with useful error and help messages, and the date time selector and text editor were useful additions, for ease of input and description customisation.

The percentage input field was appreciated by assessment leaders, although they discussed that the percentage field should be less wide, to allow the percentage symbol to be more clearly marked. Through changing the position of the Create buttons, migrating the forms to a new page, increasing the form advice and error message font size, and narrowing the width of the percentage input field, this would vastly increase the usability of the form, ensuring the form could be completed within a shorter time period.

Assessment leaders were observed to quickly locate the Delete buttons for their delete tasks, commonly describing the icons as being of a suitable size and easy to use. This demonstrated that the use of representative icons was successful in enhancing the application's user experience, thus icons will likely be continued to be used throughout the application, to aid in displaying functionality in a system and language-independent manner.

It was identified that both assessors and students completing the 'Create Assessment Favourite' and 'Delete Assessment Favourite' tasks performed the requirement quickly and with no major struggles. Following the completion of the tasks, assessors and students commented that icons were easy to use and that the filled and unfilled star icon to show favourite assessments provided them with useful system feedback. This highlighted that the use of icons can significantly enhance the application's usability, and the importance of providing visual feedback to user actions throughout the system.

It was identified that both assessors and students completing the 'Edit Assessment Panel/Group Profile' task typically talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout performing the task, indicating confusion. After reviewing the screen recordings, user struggled to read the form field advice and error messages, with some zooming in to the webpage for increased readability.

Following the completion of the task, assessors and students reported that the form field advice messages should utilise a greater font size, to increase readability, whilst the form should be displayed in a modal, to reduce the amount of page content, and allow the form size to be increased, without hindering the page content or readability. Students noted that the icons were easy to use, due to their familiarity of the icons from existing applications they had used. This highlighted the necessary to increase the form advice and error message font sizes, place the form into a modal for increased readability, and retain the use icons throughout.

6.7.7 Usability Testing Evaluation

Although the usability testing conducted provided the development team with valuable insight into the suitability of the application for its target user groups, and any poor user experience problems that required resolution prior to deployment, the usability testing approach itself had shortcomings.

One such problem with the usability testing performed was that the sample size was very small, arguably not being great enough to provide meaningful or representative data across all potential users of the application. This problem is exacerbated in the assessors user type, where assessors' competency with technology can be hugely varied, with some assessors being well-exposed to technology, and others preferring more traditional approaches, namely recording information by hand. As such, should the application be deployed for real use, the issues highlighted in the usability testing may be proven to be insignificant or overshadowed by greater issues.

During the usability testing phase, no external assessors were available to test the application using, therefore all testing had to be completed by lecturers and other individuals posing as assessors. Consequently, their opinions and competency may not be fully representative of an actual assessor user type.

Due to the short attention spans of participants, and in light of their busy schedules, only a small subset of core functionality and requirements were usability tested during each conducted test. This may lead to the overall results being of less value, as untested features may have a poor user experience, which would not be highlighted during usability testing, or subsequently rectified prior to deployment.

For test repeatability and consistency, participants were given no prompts during the completion of their tasks. Whilst this ensures all tests were conducted using the same test conditions, with no training on the system, participants are likely to face an increased risk of struggling when completing tasks. In reality, the system would be deployed with full instructional guides and users would receive basic training on its use, arguably rendering the results of the usability test invalid.

It must also be noted that for create tests, in the case of assessment leader user types, and edit tests, in the case of all user types, the time taken to complete the task would be heavily dependent on the user's typing speed. As such tasks require the manual keyboard input of data into a form, such process would be governed by the user's typing speed, which would render the results of the test significantly less accurate, due to factoring in typing ability, not system usability.

It must also be noted that the participant was provided no time to familiarise themselves with the system prior to completing the first task of the usability test, therefore some participants may use the time in the first usability test to familiarise themselves with the basic layout and functionality of the system. As such, the completion time of the first task may be abnormally long to accommodate for this familiarisation process, therefore rendering the first task result less accurate. Furthermore, as additional tasks are completed and the participant gains an increased understanding of the system's layout, appearance and functionality, participant confidence and competence would increase during later tasks, therefore reducing their likelihood of mis-clicks or confusion.

It can be argued that there is a significant lack of consistency between tasks of different user types, with assessment leaders being required to complete forms for both creating and editing items, and all other user types only completing forms for editing an item. This would vastly change the time and complexity of the completion of such tasks, rendering comparison of task creation between user types difficult. Additionally, with assessor and student user types not completing two create, edit and delete tasks, this increases the risk of anomalies within the recorded results for each type of operation.

It must be stated that, due to the sprint-based approach and availability of participants, usability testing was conducted prior to the completion of all sprints. Consequently, participants were using a potentially unfinished system, with increased risk of bugs, lack of implementation of all functionality, and possibility for user interface design to be modified at a later date. This methodology prevented the usability testing from being performed upon project completion, meaning any results are arguably invalidated by the potential system changes made after the system had been usability tested.

6.7.8 Conclusion

This subsection identified the benefits and necessity of conducting usability testing on the created system. It detailed the goals hoped to be achieved through the performing of such testing, and proposed a suitable approach to participant recruitment, conduction of the usability test, and subsequent recording and analysis of the results obtained. The process used during the collection of participant consent was outlined, to ensure the project complies with ethical and legal considerations, including the Data Protection Act (2018).

The process of recording the data obtained from the usability testing was documented, examining the potential data obtainable from such a test, and its relevancy in relation to analysis and decision making from the perspective of improving the application's user interface design. The results of data analysis on the acquired results were presented, alongside potential user interface design choices to be implemented, to resolve current usability concerns, or enhance the user's experience. A thorough review of the usability testing process was detailed, exploring the potential shortcomings in the usability testing conducted, and how such issues may hinder the accuracy or relevancy of the results.

6.7.9 Conclusive Recommendations

Identified Problem	Potential Solution	Importance
Usability issues surrounding viewing items functionality	Ensure all navigation options are clear and make clear the distinction between the homepage and Assessments page	High
Create form button visibility is poor	Improve create form button visibility by placing button at top of page	Medium
Create and edit item forms are complex and difficult to read	Improve advice messages and increase form advice and error message font sizes, reduce form content, and place new forms on new page, and edit forms in a modal, start and end time input fields need to match other textual input form fields, percentage input field requires narrower width	High
Card navigation area is too small, making it difficult to click	Ensure the whole card area is clickable, including the card background area	High

Table 6.24 Usability Testing Conclusive Recommendations and Potential Solutions

Following the performance of usability testing, the identified problems were listed, alongside potential solutions to resolve such issues, as shown in Table 6.24. The level of importance, to designate how urgently the fault must be fixed, is also detailed.

6.8 Conclusive Recommendations

Identified Problem	Potential Solution	Importance
Create and edit item forms are complex and difficult to read	Improve advice messages and increase form advice and error message font sizes, reduce form content, and place new forms on new page, and edit forms in a modal, start and end time input fields need to match other textual input form fields, percentage input field requires narrower width	High
Card navigation area is too small, making it difficult to click	Ensure the whole card area is clickable, including the card background area	High
Missing returned attributes or returned objects containing attributes not expected	Add missing attributes and remove additional attributes in SELECT statement in backend API	High
Error within the SQL syntax executed within the database	Modify SQL syntax error within backend API	High
Fatal server-side error	Investigate backend API for error and resolve issue	High
Usability issues surrounding viewing items functionality	Ensure all navigation options are clear and make clear the distinction between the homepage and Assessments page	High
User attempted to view an item they had created but were not enrolled in	Enrol the user on the object upon its creation	High
Website performance, accessibility and search engine optimisation (SEO) requires significant performance increases	Refactor frontend React implementation, use higher contrast between page text and background, make suitable adjustments for screen readers, use appropriate HTML meta tags	Medium
Errors within the frontend and backend implementation	Investigate frontend and backend API for error and resolve issue	Medium
Features and pages have not yet been implemented	Ensure the remaining features are implemented, or remove unimplemented features from the application	Medium
Create form button visibility is poor	Improve create form button visibility by placing button at top of page	Medium
No records found matching the endpoint resource requested	Ensuring database contains mock data in every table, or modify the resource requested to a select a resource that exists in the database	Low
Favourite assessments not being grouped into sections for favourites and unfavourite assessments	Separate list output of favourite and unfavourite assessments in frontend	Low

Table 6.25 System Conclusive Recommendations and Potential Solutions

Following the performance of all testing mechanisms, the identified problems and solutions were prioritised according to their importance, as shown in Table 6.25. Based on the identified issues, problems with high importance must be fixed urgently, as they impact the system integrity, behaviour and usability, causing the system to be unsuitable for the client. In contrast, low importance issues may be resolved in the future, as although they present system usability concerns, such issues will not directly hinder system operation, usability or security.

6.9 Conclusion

This phase of the project sought to validate and verify the developed system's functionality, suitability to client requirements, typical performance and theoretical maximum capacity, and usability with the target userbase. After conducting extensive research into the available testing methods, the testing mechanisms most relevant to the project were selected and incorporated into a developed testing strategy. The produced testing strategy outlined the types of testing to be conducted and their benefits to the application and client, enabling the client to gain an increased understanding into the accuracy and suitability of the system, with test tables being created to record the results of conducting such tests.

It was decided that integration testing provided significant benefit in identifying the accuracy of system behaviour both at element level, such as testing the completed backend API, and system level, to ensure all functionality was correct. Performance and load testing were noted to confirm the system met all non-functional requirements, whilst identifying any major bottlenecks in code design, hindering the system's implementation. System testing was identified as auditing the system's functionality and behaviour was appropriate, meeting the elicited client requirements. The conduction of usability testing offered assurance that the user interface design was suitable for the userbase, thus meeting non-functional requirements.

Each test was thoroughly considered, to detail the proposed project benefits of completing the test. Following a systematic design of the process and technologies proposed to be used during each testing method, testing was conducted, with results being collected and recorded in the produced test tables. In the case of usability testing, as live participants were used to conduct the testing process, to increase results accuracy, informed consent was required, therefore study informational documentation was produced.

After the successful completion of all tests within a test method, the recorded data was thoroughly analysed to determine the overall system performance, according to the testing method used. Through the examination of low-performing results, system improvements could be produced, to be implemented and rectify existing system issues. High-performing results were equally considered, to evaluate the positive elements of the system, with a view to attempting to replicate any successful functionality across different system aspects, to improve the overall user experience. Furthermore, overall trends were scrutinised, to gain a better insight into the developed system, with a view to increasing global system performance.

Each testing method was extensively evaluated, to determine both the potential accuracy of results, and their relevancy to the project. Through gaining a detailed understanding into the likely validity of obtained results, a greater understanding into the required changes to the system may be obtained, with false or irrelevant readings likely to not invoke system modifications, due to potentially leading the project in the wrong direction. From the evaluation, better test methods, processes or technologies may be used in future tests, to increase the accuracy, reliability, repeatability and relevancy of test results.

7 Critical Review

7.1 Introduction

The critical review chapter will evaluate the completed project, to gain an extensive insight into its performance, shortcomings and successes, providing understanding of experiences which may be utilised to further the success of future endeavours. The project's aims and outcomes will be explored, examining the extent to which the project has successfully met its initial purpose and key output goals.

Significant project achievements will be detailed, offering insight into the knowledge obtained as a result of completing the project, whilst noting its successful elements, to further work in the collaborative marking solutions and SPA domains. Project shortcomings will be discussed, offering insight into the causes of such failings, and their impacts on the project's development, to ensure the causes of such issues may be addressed in future projects.

The future work required to be undertaken to ensure the success of the produced application in meeting all elicited requirements, significantly enhancing the work of existing systems and research performed in the collaborative marking and feedback tool domain, and producing a viable system for client use post deployment, will be examined. Such process will detail required system feature modifications or implementation, their purpose and benefit to the target userbase, and a potential method of employing such functionality.

7.2 Aims and Outcomes

Following the completion of the project, it is beneficial to review the project aims and outcomes, detailing the purpose and success criteria of the initial concept. Through examining the project's outcomes alongside its original aims and outcomes, project success, benefits and shortcomings may be realised. This section will examine the project's aims and objectives, evaluating each aim and objective and the extent to which it was achieved.

The primary aim of the project was to develop a university-oriented collaborative solution for the purposes of stimulating consistency and conforming to good practices within assessment panels partaking in collaborative marking. Upon completion of the project, it can be concluded that this aim was partially met. The solution is university-oriented, with a data model and page structure replicating a typical University course structure, with modules, assessments, groups, panels and students. Furthermore, it facilitates marking consistency and good practice, through the assessment leader disseminating the assessment information, rubric and comments to all assessors and students, to ensure adherence to defined assessment the criteria.

However, the project fails to deliver a fully collaborative solution, with all assessors marking assessments individually, with no contact with their co-panellists through the system itself, and no indication of their co-panellists' provided feedback, therefore determining that this aim was only partially met.

The secondary aim of the project was to reduce the time required for assessors to summarise and discuss assessment feedback after the conclusion of the assessment, increasing assessment throughput and minimising delays or inaccurate feedback given. This aim can be concluded as being partially met, with the nature of the displayed assessment rubrics and comments aiding in the marking summarisation and discussions process, through prompting panellists with generic 'best-fit' comments to reduce discussion time and the period of considering and typing a custom comment for each feedback report.

It must be noted that as the collaborative functionality is not implemented, discussions are still required following the completion of the group's assessment presentation, before completing the feedback report, therefore the time saved between presentations may be minimal. In the case of first-time users of the system, the application may reduce the speed at which they record their feedback initially than the method they have used previously, due to lacking full competency of its use, consequently rendering this aim to be partially met.

It can be concluded that both of the project's aims were partially met, therefore rendering the developed application somewhat fit for purpose in solving the original challenges of collaboratively marking group assessments.

The project's main objectives are detailed below, providing context during the evaluation process:

- Review current technologies and development platforms to identify the most suitable environment for a modern, cross-platform, scalable application
- Evaluate existing assessment and feedback platforms to determine their strengths and limitations
- Catalogue requirements elicited from meetings with the client, stakeholders and target demographic, to determine the necessary assessment marking features expected by users
- Produce clear and creative wireframes and prototypes to obtain both client and target audience feedback, assisting in refining the usability aspects of the frontend design
- Creating an ER diagram capable of accurately modelling the database, required to store necessary data including users, panels, groups, assessments and feedback
- Create a user-friendly frontend to allow students, assessors and the wider module team to view, record or export assessment feedback
- Create a suitably scalable backend API with a series of endpoints to facilitate frontend data retrieval for displaying data on-screen, with persistence to permanently save necessary data to the database for later retrieval
- Produce an authentication system to ensure the application is compliant with Data Protection Act (2018) regulations, facilitating secure and accurate data access and storage
- Ensure the backend API and database mitigates against common cyber security threats
- Perform extensive testing of the application to ensure it both fulfils all necessary client requirements and is fully functional
- Deploy the application to allow it to be accessed and used by the client and intended users

The first project objective sought to review current technologies and development platforms to identify the most suitable environment for a modern, cross-platform, scalable application. This objective was fully met, following the conduction of an extensive review of available frontend and backend technologies, which identified React, SCSS, Express and MySQL as being the most suitable technologies for this project.

The second project objective endeavoured to evaluate existing assessment and feedback platforms to determine their strengths and limitations. This objective was partially met, as the project team conducted research into the existing feedback platforms, including obtaining their strengths and weaknesses from interviews with users of these platforms. However, due to the sensitive data contained within such platforms, and the limited access available to create new learning management systems (LMS) such as Canvas for research purposes, the project team were unable to use any existing assessment and feedback platforms, to obtain first-hand insight into their functionality, strengths and limitations. It can therefore be determined that although research was conducted, the lack of first-hand experience in using these platforms undermines the full completion of this project objective.

The third project objective involved the catalogue of requirements elicited from meetings with the client and target demographic, to determine the necessary assessment marking features expected by users. This objective was partially met, with client and target user interviews being transcribed and their associated requirements being elicited, to form a MoSCoW-prioritised list of requirements, user stories and use case descriptions. It must be noted that the lack of client and target user availability throughout the project, due to their demanding schedules, meant that requirements could not be continually gathered and evaluated throughout the project, as expected in the project methodology's sprints. As clients were not consulted and interviewed as frequently as was defined in the methodology, although the requirements eliciting and cataloguing process was suitably followed, this project objective was only partially met.

The fourth project objective sought to produce clear and creative wireframes and prototypes to obtain both client and target audience feedback, assisting in refining the usability aspects of the frontend design. This objective was partially met, with a series of low and medium wireframes being created and presented to the client and target audience, with feedback being collected and used to improve the frontend design, prior to implementation. It was decided that there was not suitable time to produce a working prototype prior to implementation, therefore this prevented the project objective from being fully met.

The fifth project objective involved creating an ER diagram capable of accurately modelling the database, required to store necessary data including users, assessment events and feedback. This objective was fully met, with an ER diagram being produced prior to database implementation, to provide suitable designs for the data model to subsequently be realised in MySQL.

The sixth project objective involved the creation of a user-friendly frontend to allow students, (external) assessors and the wider module team to view or record assessment feedback. This objective was partially met, with an application frontend being produced using React and SCSS, to handle all user types. The created frontend received generally positive feedback during the usability testing stage, with some usability issues being identified, therefore preventing the project objective of a 'user-friendly' frontend from being fully met.

The seventh project objective aimed to create a suitably scalable backend API with a series of endpoints to facilitate frontend data retrieval for displaying data on-screen, with persistence to permanently save necessary data to the database for later retrieval. This objective was fully met, with the implementation of an Express backend API, containing all required endpoints for frontend data retrieval, connected to a MySQL database, facilitating persistent storage for later retrieval. Such technology provides suitable scalability for the implemented system, although had the system handled big data, arguably the MySQL database would cause the objective to not be fully met, with a document-oriented NoSQL database, such as MongoDB, being more suitable.

The eighth project objective sought to produce an authentication system to ensure the application is compliant with GDPR regulations, with data being held securely and accurately. This objective failed to be met, with the application not implementing an authentication system, due to time constraints and the complexity of producing such system using RESTful APIs and React, although the use of JSON Web Tokens (JWT), for authenticating user frontend and backend requests, and Bcrypt, for secure password hashing and storage in the database, was researched.

The ninth project objective involved ensuring the backend API and database mitigates common cyber security threats. This objective was fully met, with the backend API utilising SQL prepared statements, HTML-escaping of received body data, frontend and backend data validation and conformance, creation of a restricted database user, and return of appropriate HTTP status codes and messages. Further security mechanisms were implemented, including the disabling of the 'x-powered-by' header from the Express backend API responses, and use of environment variables to store credential data, with a view to deployment.

The tenth project objective endeavoured to perform extensive testing of the application to ensure it both fulfils all necessary client requirements and is fully functional. This objective was fully met, with system, integration, load, performance, and usability testing all performed on the frontend and backend components, to ensure system stability, reliability, and expected behaviour. Following extensive testing, the application was determined to meet all client requirements, through the performed system testing, with reliability and expected behaviour being determined by integration, load, and performance testing.

The final project objective sought to deploy the application to allow it to be accessed and used by the client. This objective failed to be met, due to the cost implications involved in hosting the developed application. As the project received no funding, and following extensive research for free Node.js hosting environments yielding no successful results, the development team were unable to deploy the application, thus leading to the objective failing to be met.

7.3 Summary of Achievements

Whilst the project led to the creation of a scalable web application for the purposes of marking group presentations, valuable lessons and skills were learnt and developed throughout all phases of the project. Experience was gained in transferrable skills, technical knowledge, effective project management and communication. This subsection will detail the achievements obtained from the project and their significance.

During the project, it was vital that a suitable project management approach was developed and adhered to, ensuring the project's successful time, quality and feature management, and suitable client and stakeholder communication. Valuable lessons were learnt concerning time management through the implementation of sprints, delivering varying features of a high quality over a fixed time period, contributing to the project's achievement in ensuring deadlines did not overrun.

The importance of successful communication with both clients and stakeholders was realised, ensuring features were fulfilled in order of their importance to the client, and validating system designs and implementation, seeking to mitigate against changing client requirements and incorrectly interpreted requirements.

The necessity of the order of activities within sprints was highlighted, with sprints following the format of defining the workflow, to ensure the client's most important requirements are implemented first, followed by appropriate backend implementation, to provide data for the frontend to consume. The frontend implementation then provides the application with a suitable user interface, before refactoring ensures clean code, with minimal duplication and removal of code smells, aiding in the implementation of the next sprint.

The analysis phase of the project sought to teach the successful implementation of previously theoretical requirements elicitation methods, stressing the importance of effective communication, regular client meetings, and the benefits and limitations of different elicitation techniques.

Survey technique was developed, with initially produced surveys being overly complex and time-consuming, reducing user participation, before questions were condensed into a short, readable format, to increase response numbers. Requirements elicitation was improved by utilising a combination of surveys and interviews, with interview conducting skills being developed, to better obtain relevant responses, prevent topic changes where necessary, and ensure results were suitably recorded for subsequent requirements analysis.

The extraction of requirements from survey and interview responses into a MoSCoW-prioritised list, and subsequently user stories and use case descriptions, demonstrated the importance of fully understanding requirements and formatting them in a suitable manner for effective realisation in the design stage. Further lessons were learnt through the creation of accurate and realistic user personas, to aid in the thought process of designing and developing systems for their target user groups.

The design phase taught the importance of the production of increasingly higher fidelities of wireframes. It was learnt that initial wireframes should be of minimal detail, so as not to waste time or inhibit change based on the client's preliminary feedback, and become increasingly detailed, to provide a more easily changeable solution than the final implementation prior to development, and aid in the frontend creation.

The role of detailed designs and plans for all implementation stages, including ER diagrams, returned endpoint objects and syntaxes, and reusable components, to reduce development time and increase consistency across all aspects within the application, was learnt. Implementation significantly benefitted from adequate design, with design stages being fast to change, and implementation being significantly more complex and long-winded to have to modify to meet client requirements.

Valuable lessons regarding development using ES6 JavaScript syntax were learnt, including arrow functions, array functions, ternary and logical operators. Whilst traditional JavaScript syntax provides sufficient functionality, ES6 syntax allows the application to utilise modern programming techniques, and increase code maintainability, readability, and underlying performance. Furthermore, JavaScript Promises were learnt, including their importance and successful management, to provide appropriate application behaviour, based on the successful completion of threads.

The implementation of React components, and subsequent creation of reusable components, was learnt, improving the maintainability of the application's code, reducing repeated code and increasing updatability. React knowledge was underpinned by the development of lessons from using `useState` and `useEffect` React hooks, and creation of custom hooks. With understanding of the `useState` and `useEffect` hooks, the application's frontend could have increased efficiency, with component re-rendering occurring only where necessary. The use of custom hooks facilitated extracting repeated behaviour into a single location, to be accessed where necessary, increasing maintainability and code reuse.

Styling practices were vastly improved through the developed understanding of SCSS, including its use of variables and mixins, to facilitate fast styling changes and reduce repeated rulesets. Through supporting nested styling statement declarations, ruleset readability was increased, therefore aiding the application's maintainability.

The definition of endpoints was learnt, with the roles of each form of HTTP request type being fully understood. The associated validation and conformance required to ensure received request body data is suitable, and convert necessary data into a format for interaction with the database or frontend, was discovered. The importance of security mechanisms to protect backend API endpoints and databases was improved by significant research and implementation of discovered protection methods.

The importance of stored database data and generation of accurate mock data was realised, with mock data providing clients with the ability to easily visualise the system's functionality, during client meetings. Furthermore, it allows for appropriate validation, with the application being able to be tested continually during development, via inspecting the results of the mock data.

External libraries, including date time picker and rich text editor components used within the frontend, and `joi` validation used within the backend API, available from npm were a significant achievement within the project. Developing skills of successfully utilising existing code within an application significantly aids in development time, alongside having the potential to increase application reliability.

During the development of the application, a range of valuable lessons were learned regarding coding best practices, including variable, function and file naming conventions, indentation and core principles, including Don't Repeat Yourself (DRY). The completed application achieved adherence to best practice, identifying the importance of coding practices in increasing maintainability.

Code practices were improved by the successful identification of code smells, with refactoring being performed during the final week of each sprint, to rectify located issues, thus increasing code maintainability, and inhibiting future feature implementation. Such process required lessons learnt through utilising effective debugging tools, including Postman to send HTTP requests to the backend API and validate the implemented behaviour, and using `console.log()` statements to view the values of variables or running of functions.

The importance of testing applications, to validate the system behaviour is appropriate, ensure the system meets all client requirements, check the intended user groups can successfully utilise the application, and ensure its scalability and performance, was learnt. Successful validation was achieved, with the system behaviour being suitable, and usability test results being positive. Valuable lessons were learnt through the involvement of clients and users of the target user groups during the validation stage. Whilst white box testing was performed by the development team, black box testing involved the client and target user groups, to ensure the system's suitability.

Key transferrable skills were learnt, with the achievement of the creation of a Participant Information Sheet (PIS) and consent form providing insight into the ethics behind the conduction of project, and its potential impact on participants who may be consulted on their views on the application. The PIS and consent form also improved legal knowledge of the Data Protection Act (2018), required to ensure all data was securely handled, stored and used within the project. The importance of the collection and recording of participant consent was highlighted, with the project successfully meeting all legislation and ethical codes of conduct in its practices.

Research skills were improved by the necessity to full examine existing competitor solutions, the available technologies to use for producing the application, and troubleshooting coding issues within the development process. Knowledge relating to the understanding of technology and library documentation, including that of Express and React, was developed by utilising such information to aid in successfully resolving problems within the developed application.

7.4 Reflections

Upon completing the project, it is advantageous to reflect on the challenges faced, which contributed to a lack of achievement of elements of the project, and evaluate the factors responsible for causing such issues. Through reflecting on the functionality not implemented during the system's development, and examining the reasons for such failings, future projects may result in greater success, should they seek to mitigate against the encountered issues. This section will reflect upon the features lacking implementation within the system, and detail causes for each missing function.

One of the main features lacking achievement within the project was the implementation of a collaboration mode, enabling assessors to view their co-panellists' selected feedback and grades in real-time, via a tooltip. It could be argued that this was one of the core functions expected of the system, based on the requirements elicited from the client. Although the collaboration mode was heavily designed, being incorporated in the created wireframes, and its implementation researched, with the development team choosing to use the Socket.io JavaScript package to facilitate the underlying functionality, it failed to be implemented within the final application.

A main reason for the lack of collaborative functionality was due to overly ambitious goals, and underestimating the amount of knowledge and skills needed. Whilst a simple chat room application utilising Socket.io was produced, as a proof of concept, the development team did not possess the skills necessary to modify the application to pass secure object messages, to display in a tooltip. After producing the proof of concept application, it was expected that the modification to facilitate the desired collaborative functionality would be relatively trivial, although such task was complex and would require more time than was available for the project's deadline, therefore its implementation was abandoned.

A further feature lacking implementation was the ability for users to perform searching, refining and pagination within the application. Such tools are common across most webpages, with searching and refining being integral to facilitating the location of records from within the frontend application. Pagination ensures content is divided amongst separate pages, preventing pages from becoming cluttered or too long, thus increasing the difficulty at which items can be located, and increasing page load times, as all items must be retrieved and rendered upon page load.

Due to poor time management, through underestimating the time required to perform thorough validation across all elements within the application utilising different test methods, and upon any major changes being made to the system, such features were not implemented. It was decided that reliability was more important than functionality, as additional features may be implemented at a later date, potentially in a future update.

The implemented system lacked functionality to export data, including students' grades and feedback report, for upload into existing systems including Canvas. Commonly, student grades must be exported, to facilitate grade monitoring in existing learning management systems (LMS) or student information systems, such as SITS:Vision. Furthermore, students often wish to store copies of their feedback reports for future reference.

Data export functionality was not implemented, due to issues in mitigating against scope creep. During the early requirements elicitation, the client was very unsure of which features were necessary within the proposed system, as although they understood the overall functionality of the application, its specific features were less defined. As the project progressed, and the client became more informed about their needs, from viewing the produced wireframes, scope creep threatened the project's development. Although functionality including data export was originally proposed to be necessary, additional features elicited during the project's development were highlighted to be more important, and as such, disrupted the original planned functionality. As such, the initially proposed system data export functionality was unable to be implemented, due to other, more important requirements being elicited during the project.

The produced application lacked support for mobile devices, such as mobile phones or tablets, instead displaying a message to mobile users that the application is only available on screen sizes greater than 1100 pixels wide.

Although originally planned as a mobile and desktop-friendly app, due to the application's code frequently suffering from the reinvent the wheel code smell, through making custom components where possible, this severely delayed implementation. Had existing components and libraries been imported and used, many of which contained all the custom components produced, development time would have been reduced, offering the time necessary to implement support for mobile layouts, using SCSS. Due to the time required to produce the panels necessary to display content in a vertical orientation without using vast amounts of the available screen window, suitable for mobile layouts, the content could not be organised in a suitable manner thus mobile devices were not supported.

The developed application was originally planned to be deployed on a web server, facilitating system access to real-world users. As a result of limited resources, both including hardware and funding, deployment was unable to occur. Although the Kingston University-managed KUNET Webserver was originally intended to be used to deploy the application, later research determined it was unsuitable, due to not running the node.js runtime environment. As both the React and Express servers utilise the node.js runtime environment to serve their resources, the KUNET Webserver was unable to provide hosting for such application, with the development team having no control over the installed runtime environments on the web server.

After researching no-cost web hosting with the node.js runtime environment installed, it was determined there were no suitable web hosting services available to support the functionality required in deploying the created application. Due to the project's lack of funding, no paid-for web hosting services were suitable, as project financial issues preventing the paid subscription to such facilities.

The application was intended to support the creation of new assessor user accounts, to allow assessment leaders to provide their external assessors with a mechanism to access the system and provide feedback to group presentations.

Unfortunately, due to the code complexity required to facilitate the secure creation of new user accounts without a sign-up form, with the registered email address of the assessor receiving a link to create an account password, it was determined that such functionality was unrealistic. Consequently, the create new assessors functionality failed to be implemented, with assessment leaders instead having to manually create user accounts and provide external assessors with their associated account credentials.

During the project's requirements elicitation stage, many problems were encountered with contacting sample users to interview or complete surveys, to obtain information regarding their problems with the current systems used. Due to many assessment leaders and internal assessors having demanding schedules, it was difficult to obtain information from a wide userbase, meaning most of the requirements were elicited from the client. This hindered the initial project progress, as designs were unable to be produced until sufficient requirements analysis had been conducted, and additional user opinions would have ensured the developed system was more suitable.

This challenge was exacerbated by the, on reflection, poor choice of project methodology. As the methodology utilised sprints, of which requirements should be continually elicited and clients and users engaged throughout the project's lifecycle, interviews and feedback should have been gathered during all stages of the project. Unfortunately, due to the unavailability of clients and stakeholders, some sprints were not checked or signed-off by the client or stakeholder, potentially meaning any issues would not have been identified until later in the project, possibly preventing the developed application from being fit for purpose.

Further issues stemmed from the initial project concept, with the project's aim being overly complex and having potentially many complicated features requiring implementation. As the client was unsure of the system's functionality or requirements initially, often overestimating the importance of many of the requirements, initially too many requirements were listed as 'must haves'. This caused initial project derailment, with the development team being unsure of which core requirements were most important, therefore expected implementation first. The project was further hindered by scope creep, with later client requirements elicitation sessions highlighting additional features which they believed were also significant.

During the beginning of the development, the project was stalled by user interface design struggles, as the complexity and importance of the user interface design was not identified. As such, the first user interface design was poor, making it difficult for the client to picture the system's user interface, thus leading to them providing additional and conflicting requirements, leading to scope creep.

During the later stages of the application's development, it was realised that the database used, MySQL, did not support CHECK constraints, which were proposed to be used to validate the received data against a range of acceptable values in the produced data dictionary. CHECK constraints were intended to ensure a user's title and module's level, amongst other fields, contained valid data, as although data is validated via the backend API prior to transmission to the database, direct access to the database would allow validation checks to be bypassed, leading to potential data integrity problems. Consequently, the desired functionality could not be implemented, due to initial insufficient research into the supported SQL syntax and limitations of the chosen database platform.

It was originally proposed that unit testing would be conducted on both the React components and Express endpoint handler functions, although unlike languages such as Java's JUnit, it became apparent that there are severe limitations in the available unit testing frameworks. Although frameworks including React Testing Library and Jest are available, they are complex to learn and take significant amounts of time to implement. As a result, unit testing was not performed, therefore problems with the application's code could not be identified as quickly, meaning development took longer, with issues only being highlighted upon running associated integration testing, following the completed implementation of the functionality.

As all elements of the developed application adhered to best practice, this caused significant delays in the development of the backend API. As previously described, best practice API endpoint syntax list the resource to be returned at the end of the resource locator, which vastly increases the complexity of using Express Routers to route to the appropriate endpoint handler the backend application. Consequently, most refactoring was performed nearer to the project's completion, thus hindering the project's backend API development progress, due to having significantly duplicated code, whilst the process of identifying the most suitable method of refactoring was conducted.

7.5 Future Work

During the implementation of the project, a range of features were left unimplemented, commonly due to the short project duration and limited knowledge of external libraries required to implement advanced functionality. The implementation of such elements would seek to enhance the user's experience of the application, increase efficiency and benefit security. This section details a number of proposed features to be implemented in future updates to the system, alongside their benefits to the application's users, and a proposed method of implementation.

A collaboration mode, as previously detailed, would facilitate assessors in creating feedback reports for students, whilst viewing presentations. Due to the insufficient time between group presentations, with co-panellists often lacking appropriate discussion to produce agreed grades and feedback, if panellists were able to view their co-panellists' feedback, this would better promote consistency across provided feedback, seek to support inexperienced assessors, and mitigate against existing time constraints. Such system may be toggled by the assessment leader, due to some assessments being unsuited to this form of collaborative marking.

This feature may be implemented using the Socket.io JavaScript library, which allows messages and data objects to be transmitted to the web server from the client's browser, and sent to all registered subscribers (Socket.IO, no date). In this case, upon the user selecting a feedback option or grade, a request containing the selected option would be sent to an open socket on the web server, to be pushed to all open co-panellist client browsers, containing the selected feedback. This would be viewable through the user's mouse hovering over an icon located adjacent to the input form field's title, displaying the contents of the received data packet.

The ability to send direct messages between users, groups and panels would seek to further increase communication between panellists and students. During collaborative marking, it is often required for panel and group members to communicate, to coordinate introducing themselves and joining assessment meetings. Furthermore, users may be required to contact individual students, to aid them in joining assessment meetings, or assessment leaders, in the case of queries or problems occurring during assessments. Currently, such functionality is offered by applications including Microsoft Teams, although to unify the system, and prevent issues stemming from external assessors not having University-issued Microsoft Accounts and thus often being prevented from having access to all Teams functionality, a chat feature should be implemented.

This feature may be fulfilled using a combination of Socket.io, to push messages to users upon them receiving a message, and a 'Messages' database table, to contain the sent messages, for persistent storage and later retrieval (Socket.IO, no date). The chat feature would be accessible from the navigation bar, being contained within its own page, and contain a floating window on-screen in the bottom right-hand corner during live assessment events, facilitating easy access to communicate with co-panellists or group members.

Commonly, grades are required to be exported from the system, for upload and use within student information systems, such as SITS:Vision, or learning management systems (LMS) including Canvas. Furthermore, students often appreciate saving copies of their feedback reports, for later viewing, due to online systems potentially having risks of data loss, or being less efficient to access. It is therefore expected that grades should be able to be exported as a CSV file, due to its common support in many third-party applications, with feedback reports being exportable as PDF files, for compatibility and to prevent subsequent report modification.

The creation of a CSV file from the stored assessment grades may be accomplished using a blob JavaScript object to contain the download file, and constructing the file using returned grades data from the API, within the React frontend application. This may be implemented using a custom CSV creation function, alongside the JavaScript download functionality, to allow the created file to be downloaded. Similarly, a PDF report may be generated from the returned feedback data from the API using the html2canvas (html2canvas, no date) and jsPDF (jsPDF, no date) external JavaScript libraries. Upon creation of the PDF file, the JavaScript download functionality may be used to allow the created file to be downloaded.

Assessment leaders may have already created group and panel names and members, either using random group generator tools or from surveys used to allow students to choose their own groups. In this case, it is often laborious and time consuming for the assessment leader to be required to manually input all group and panel information, although it is already contained within an existing file. As such, the system should facilitate the upload and import of groups and panels from an existing CSV file.

This functionality may be accomplished through creating a file picker form input, allowing CSV files to be uploaded. Upon a file being uploaded, the csv-parse external JavaScript library would be used to convert the uploaded file into an array containing JSON objects of the imported data (CSV Parse, no date). This would be subsequently sent to the backend API, where database queries would run, to identify the ID number of each user in the proposed group or panel and, following the retrieval of such data, seek to create a new group or panel with the proposed name and members. The status of the request would be returned to the user, to be displayed on-screen.

Users often appreciate having alerts and feedback report publishing notifications emailed to them, allowing them to be notified at all times of changes to the system's status. Furthermore, password reset links may be emailed as a means to verify the user's identity, prior to the password being reset.

This functionality may be accomplished through creating a dedicated noreply email account, to send application email messages using, and utilising Nodemailer, an external JavaScript library (Nodemailer, no date), to facilitate the transmission of email messages, based on a defined format. Variables may be used to determine the specific content of the email, personalising messages to users and ensuring the relevancy of sent content.

Universities often utilise open-source learning management systems (LMS), such as Canvas, Blackboard and Moodle. Such systems facilitate the storage and management of all course and module-related content, student lists, assignments and grades, therefore providing an important resource for assessment information. As such, it is desirable that a collaborative assessment solution would integrate into Canvas via a plugin, to allow data to be transferred and managed through a Canvas module page, including exporting of grades and feedback directly into Canvas (Canvas, no date).

As the Canvas learning management system is open-source, the Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI) platform may be utilised to develop a suitable plugin to interact with the Canvas module, providing grade and feedback export functionality (IMS Global Learning Consortium, no date). The Canvas API documentation also provides detailed information into the mechanisms in which interaction with the backend Canvas API may be accomplished (*Canvas LMS REST API Documentation*, no date).

Universities commonly subscribe to Microsoft Office365, providing all students and staff members with University-registered Microsoft accounts. Educational platforms, including learning management systems such as Canvas, allow users to sign into their accounts using their organisation's Microsoft Account, facilitating easy and secure login. The system's login page could be upgraded to facilitate login functionality using Microsoft Account logins.

This feature could be implemented by using the Microsoft identity platform to request an authorisation code, upon the user logging in with their Microsoft Account. This would be validated in the collaborative marking application, to ensure the code was valid. Should the code be valid, a JWT will be provided to the user as before, facilitating the user's login to the system. The Microsoft identity platform supports the common OAuth2 standard, ensuring simpler integration (Microsoft, 2023).

7.6 Conclusion

This phase of the project sought to evaluate the project's successes, failures, and learnt lessons, to improve upon future projects. The project's initial aims and outcomes were revisited, with the completed project being evaluated against its original purpose and deliverables, to identify its overall success, and highlight the issues still requiring addressing following the close of the project. It was concluded that although the project successfully met a number of aims and objectives, a proportion of anticipated goals failed to be addressed, thus the project was unsuccessful in meeting its original purpose.

The project's achievements and successes were examined, highlighting the exceptional practices employed and resultant application functionality, utilised throughout the project's lifecycle. The positive outcomes obtained for the project team, including a wide range of transferrable skills, were discussed, detailing mechanisms in which the project benefitted both the collaborating marketing domain and its researchers.

A number of reflections were discussed, providing insight into the failings of the project, and investigating potential explanations for such shortcomings, to better mitigate against such issues in future work. Whilst a wide range of factors were identified as hindering the project's success, it must be noted that the project team's naivety, as demonstrated through poor time and complexity estimations, handling of scope creep and choice of project methodology had a significant negative affected on the number and complexity of features implemented during development.

Future work was proposed, identifying necessary functionality failing to be implemented as per the elicited requirements and produced user stories, before listing its significance and advantages to users. Each identified feature was supported by a potential mechanism for which the functionality may be implemented within the system, offering an insight into the time, complexity and method for which future developers may further the project through implementing such elements.

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Appendix

Appendix A – Project Schedule

Due Date	Sprint	Milestone	Phases	
				Documentation
Friday 30/09/2022		Project Specification		
Friday 07/10/2022	Sprint 1	First user story - design and document workflow	Literature Review	
Friday 14/10/2022		First user story - populate database and implement API		
Friday 21/10/2022		First user story - implement UI		
Friday 28/10/2022		First user story - refactor audit and user stories		
Friday 04/11/2022	Sprint 2	Second user story - design and document workflow		Requirements Analysis
Friday 11/11/2022		Second user story - populate database and implement API		
Friday 18/11/2022		Second user story - implement UI		
Friday 25/11/2022		Second user story - refactor audit and user stories		
Friday 02/12/2022	Sprint 3	Third user story - design and document workflow		UI and Data Model Design
Friday 09/12/2022		Third user story - populate database/implement API and UI		
Friday 16/12/2022		Third user story - refactor audit and user stories		
Friday 06/01/2023	Sprint 4	Fourth user story - design and document workflow		Implementation
Friday 13/01/2023		Fourth user story - populate database/implement API and UI		
Friday 20/01/2023		Fourth user story - refactor audit and user stories		
Friday 27/01/2023	Sprint 5	Fifth user story - design and document workflow		Validation

Friday 03/02/2023		Fifth user story - populate database/implement API and UI
Friday 10/02/2023		Fifth user story - refactor audit and user stories
Friday 17/02/2023	Sprint 6	Sixth user story - design and document workflow
Friday 24/02/2023		Sixth user story - populate database/implement API and UI
Friday 03/03/2023		Sixth user story - refactor audit and user stories
Friday 10/03/2023	Sprint 7	Seventh user story - design and document workflow
Friday 17/03/2023		Seventh user story - populate database/implement API and UI
Friday 24/03/2023		Seventh user story - refactor audit and user stories
Friday 31/03/2023		Draft Report
Friday 07/04/2023		Completed Report

Table A.1 Project Schedule Detailing Sprints, Milestones, Phases and Completion Dates

Appendix B – Sprint Breakdown

Task	Activity
1	Select a user story based on MoSCoW prioritized requirements list
2	Identify the system workflow and validate it with the client
3	Analyse the information required to be stored or displayed on frontend
4	Model the database relations and produce an ERD to show these
5	Formulate SQL statement(s) required to retrieve, add, edit or delete data from the database
6	Implement the relations in phpMyAdmin and test the previously formulated SQL statements
7	Implement backend API endpoints and test all functionality via mock Postman requests
8	Produce a user interface design and validate it with the client
9	Implement frontend user interface and test its suitability with the target user group
10	Refactor frontend and backend code

Table B.1 Sprint Task Breakdown

Appendix C – Weakness and Threat Mitigation

ID	Risk Description	Probability	Impact	Mitigation	Contingency
R1	Assessment leaders may not wish to adopt the tool	Low	Low	Explain strengths and benefits of tool	Offer to demonstrate tool in-person
R2	Stored assessment data may become corrupted	Low	High	Ensure database is backed up regularly to an external location to be restored in the event of corruption of data	Ensure assessment leaders export all important assessment data frequently
R3	Lack of time to fully implement all system requirements	High	High	Use MoSCoW prioritisation to ensure most important requirements are completed first	Discuss changing requirements prioritisation with client
R4	User is unable to assess students unless they have a suitable device	Low	High	Ensure users have the facilities to gain access to the service and provide them with suitable device, if necessary	Provide print or export function within tool, to print assessment form for paper-based marking
R5	System may suffer data loss or theft	Low	High	Ensure sensitive data is encrypted and passwords are hashed, database is secure, and system prevents SQL injection attacks	Monitor request traffic and alert users if this event occurs
R6	Records are manipulated by an unauthorised third party	Low	High	Ensure database and systems are secured from unauthorised access	Ensure all assessors and assessment leaders change their passwords immediately
R7	Advances in technology and existing software render the tool obsolete	Medium	Low	Ensure tool provides all necessary features and is user-friendly	Update tool's features and technological implementation as technology changes
R8	Risk of complete re-write of data model to facilitate use in other applications	Low	High	Ensure tool's functionality and naming is generic, where possible	Discontinue idea of using tool in different applications

R9	Client is unsure of features they require, thus leading to scope creep	High	High	Only implement features which have been prioritised using MoSCoW, in the appropriate order	Ensure client is briefed on the requirements and designs and involved in the project from an early stage
R10	Server is unable to handle request volume or tool does not meet performance non-functional requirements	Low	High	Seek to distribute services across different servers, introducing a microservice architecture, or use client-side processing, where possible	Upgrade server capacity or migrate server to a cloud hosting provider

Table C.1 Weakness and Threat Mitigation Table

Figure D.1 Adam Walker Student User Persona

James Evans

"The greatest gift in life is friendship."

Age: **20**
Work: **Full-Time Student**
Family: **In A Relationship, No Children**
Location: **Ashted, Surrey**
Character: **The Friend**

Personality

Confident Curious Thoughtful Resilient

Goals

- Would like to view present assessments, so he can prepare and ensure he attends at the correct time
- Wishes to see his grades for each assessment, so he can track his progress over time

Frustrations

- Assessment grades are spread across different locations, such as Canvas and email, making it difficult to keep track of
- Assessment dates are often hidden away within Canvas, meaning I can struggle to find the event I need to attend

Bio

James is a confident full-time student, who enjoys socialising with friends both online and in-person. He is curious and thoughtful, but can be forgetful, and becomes irritated when he cannot quickly access the information he requires. James likes to track his assessment progress over time, hoping to see improvements as he develops his understanding in the course he is taking.

Motivation

Brands & Influencers

Preferred Channels

Figure D.2 James Evans Student User Persona

Steven Smith

- Friendly
- Outgoing
- Clever
- Organised

Motivation

"There are no shortcuts to go to anywhere worth going to"

Age: **62**
Work: **University Lecturer**
Family: **Married, 2 Children**
Location: **Surbiton, London**
Character: **The Planner**

Frustrations

- Assessment feedback processes are lengthy
- Student feedback is often in different formats, so disseminating it is difficult
- Unfamiliar with mobile devices and don't like the idea

Brands & Influencers

Bio

Steven is a university lecturer who has to set assessments for students typically twice per academic year. Other assessors mark these assessments, but he must disseminate their feedback to his students. He is organised, and it irritates him that the process of gathering and sharing this feedback is lengthy and difficult. Steven wishes that this marking process could be as efficient as setting the work.

Preferred Channels

Personality

Goals

- Assess students in a timely, efficient manner
- Disseminate student feedback easily
- Easily manage and track assessment feedback created by other lecturers

Figure D.3 Steven Smith Assessment Leader User Persona

Olivia Johnson

Driven Decisive Passionate Astute

Goals

- Quickly set assessments that can be taken by vast numbers of students
- Provide pre-defined assessment rubric, to ensure markers give relevant and appropriate feedback

Frustrations

- Setting assessment activities and delivering them to students and panellists is demanding
- Panels often provide poor and inconsistent feedback for students, which negatively impacts the assessment

Bio

Olivia is a university lecturer. She is very career-oriented and focussed in achieving success. Her lecturers are motivational and aim to inspire future generations. She is responsible for setting assessments for students, but she is often unhappy with the quality of feedback she receives from her assessors. She is very technology-savvy and cannot understand why the process of setting and delivering assessment activities has not been made easier by a technological solution yet.

"Nothing is impossible, even the word itself says - I'm Possible"

Age: **32**
Work: **University Lecturer**
Family: **In A Relationship, No Children**
Location: **Epsom, Surrey**
Character: **The Motivational Speaker**

Personality

Motivation

Brands & Influencers

Preferred Channels

Figure D.4 Olivia Johnson Assessment Leader User Persona

Hannah Bansil

"In the middle of every difficulty lies opportunity"

Age: **38**
Work: **Software Developer**
Family: **Married, No Children**
Location: **Croydon, London**
Character: **The Carer**

Personality

Motivated Ambitious Kind Practical

Goals

- Wishes to positively give back to her old University through volunteering
- Help assess current students' work from an industry perspective

Frustrations

- Assessing work is difficult, as there is not enough support or training available
- Assessments are long and there is a lack of time to complete the huge workload required

Bio

Hannah is a software developer working for a large organisation, however she fondly remembers her experience of University, and wants to give back. She volunteers to assess current students' work, and completes the assessment sheets provided to her. As she is not a lecturer, she sometimes struggles with assessing work if there is a lack of support from the University team, and she cannot complete the assessments at a later date, as she has a large workload from her full-time job.

Motivation

Brands & Influencers

Preferred Channels

Figure D.5 Hannah Bansil External Assessor User Persona

Jane Edwards

"Never look down on anybody unless you are helping them up."

Age: **48**
Work: **University Lecturer**
Family: **Divorced, No Children**
Location: **Wembley, London**
Character: **The Kind Lecturer**

Personality

- Tactful
- Punctual
- Caring
- Helpful

Goals

- Accurately record student feedback and grades based on the presentations students have made
- Easily interact with co-assessors to ensure all feedback comments are reflected across the assessment panel

Frustrations

- Co-assessors from industry often struggle to produce feedback, increasing my workload
- Feedback comments from the panel can often be inconsistent, undermining the integrity of the panel

Bio

Jane is a university lecturer who specialises in teaching Java programming. She is highly knowledgeable in working with co-assessors to assess student presentations, often being recruited to do so. Her experience and kind-hearted personality helps to make both nervous panellists and students feel at ease.

Motivation

Brands & Influencers

Preferred Channels

Figure D.6 Jane Edwards External Assessor User Persona

Appendix E – User Stories

Students:

- “As a student, I want to view my upcoming assessments, so I can prepare for them in order to get a good grade.”
- “As a student, I want to view my past assessment feedback, so I can understand my strengths and weaknesses and rectify these in the future.”
- “As a student, I want to view my past assessment grade, so I can see if I am on-track to passing the module.”
- “As a student, I want to favourite important assessments events, so I can easily find them at a later date.”
- “As a student, I want to view my assessment event schedule, so I can see the dates and times I am expected to attend my assessments.”
- “As a student, I want to see my assessment setter’s profile, so I can contact them if I have any concerns regarding the feedback I have received.”
- “As a student, I want to see my group’s profiles, so I can contact them and arrange to meet to prepare for the assessment.”
- “As a student, I want to be able to create a user profile, so my fellow group members and panellists can get to know more about me.”

Figure E.1 User Stories for Students User Type

Assessment Leaders:

- “As an assessment leader, I want to create a new assessment event, so I can easily disseminate assessment information to students and assessors.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view assessment events I have created, so I can see the upcoming assessments I am managing.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to edit an assessment event, so I can change incorrect assessment information as necessary.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to delete an assessment event, so I can remove any accidentally-created or irrelevant assessments.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to create assessment groups of students, so I can share group feedback.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to create a new assessment rubric, so I can easily provide assessors with pre-configured feedback to improve consistency.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view assessment rubric I have created, so I can see the potential feedback comments I should expect from my assessment team.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to edit assessment rubric, so I can change incorrect assessment rubric as necessary.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to delete assessment rubric, so I can remove any accidentally-created or irrelevant pre-configurable feedback comments.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to create assessment groups of students, so I can share group feedback.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view assessment groups of students, so I can view students who worked together on a project.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to edit assessment groups of students, so I can add or remove students from groups when they change.”

- “As an assessment leader, I want to delete assessment groups of students, so I can remove any groups which do not exist anymore.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to create new external assessor accounts, so I can provide access to external panel members to assess work for my assessments.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view external assessor accounts for an assessment, so I can see the assessors who have been provided access to assess work for my assessments.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to edit external assessor accounts for an assessment, so I can correct account errors and provide access to external panel members to assess work for my assessments.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to delete external assessor accounts for an assessment, so I can revoke access to external panel members, where their accounts have been incorrectly created.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to create new assessment panels for an assessment, so I can determine which assessors will work together to produce feedback in an assessment event.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view assessment panels for an assessment, so I can see which assessors will work together to produce feedback in an assessment event.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to edit assessment panels for an assessment, so I can change which assessors will work together to produce feedback in an assessment event.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to delete assessment panels for an assessment, so I can remove collections of assessors who would have worked together to produce feedback in an assessment event.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to assign assessment panels to groups of students, so I can determine which assessors will assess which students.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view which assessment panels are assessing which groups of students, so I can ensure that all assessors have been assigned students to assess, and all students have been assigned an assessor.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to edit which assessment panels are assessing which groups of students, so I can rectify any errors made in assigning panels to groups.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to delete which assessment panels is assessing a group of students, so I can remove any accidental panel assignments.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view feedback and grades produced by panels, so I can determine if it is of a suitable quality and gauge the assessment’s participation.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to edit feedback and grades produced by panels, so I can rectify any errors in the provided feedback, before it is published to students.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to delete feedback and grades produced by panels, so I can remove any inappropriate or unsuitable feedback, before it is published to students.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to publish feedback and grades produced by panels to students, so they can view their results for their assessment.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to unpublish feedback and grades produced by panels to students, so I can rectify any errors with results away from the visibility of students.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to export grades in a suitable file type, so I can easily import them into a Learning Management System.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to be able to create alerts to be sent to all students participating in an assessment event, so I can quickly send messages to all students.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to be able to create alerts to be sent to all assessors participating in an assessment event, so I can quickly send messages to all assessors.”

- “As an assessment leader, I want to view the assessors’ profiles, so I can obtain a better understanding of the colleagues I am working with.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view the student groups’ profiles, so I can obtain a better understanding of their views and background.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to view the students’ profiles, so I can obtain a better understanding of their views and background.”
- “As an assessment leader, I want to be able to create a user profile, so my fellow assessors and students can get to know more about me.”

Figure E.2 User Stories for Assessment Leaders User Type

Assessors:

- “As an assessor, I want to view my upcoming assessments, so I can be aware of the events I need to attend to assess.”
- “As an assessor, I want to view the assessment feedback I have provided, so I can refer to this information for the future assessments I provide feedback for.”
- “As an assessor, I want to create assessment feedback for the groups I am required to assess, so I can report my feedback and grades to students.”
- “As an assessor, I want to view the assessment feedback I have provided, so I can refer to this information for the future assessments I provide feedback for.”
- “As an assessor, I want to edit the assessment feedback I have provided, so I can rectify any errors I have made in assessment feedback and grades.”
- “As an assessor, I want to view the profiles of my co-assessors, so I can obtain a better understanding of the colleagues I am working with.”
- “As an assessor, I want to view the profiles of the student group I am assessing, so I can obtain a better understanding of their views and background.”
- “As an assessor, I want to view the profiles of the students within the group I am assessing, so I can obtain a better understanding of their views and background.”
- “As an assessor, I want to be able to create a user profile, so my fellow assessors and students can get to know more about me.”
- “As a student, I want to see the assessment setter’s profile, so I can contact them if I have any concerns regarding the assessment event I am partaking in marking.”

Figure E.3 User Stories for Assessors User Type

Appendix F – Use Case Textual Descriptions

Use Case Number:	1
Name:	View Assessments
Description:	A list of the user's past, current and upcoming assessments are displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes assessment name, date, module and assessment leader.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to find a particular assessment
Frequency:	Varied depending on assessment schedule; typically once per week
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is a member of a module Module contains assessments
Post-Conditions:	A user's assessments are displayed on-screen to the user
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage User's assessments are displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	2a. If no assessments are available, appropriate message is displayed
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	User's list of assessments is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to view their list of assessments on-screen
Performance:	List of assessments should be displayed within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.1 Use Case Description for View Assessments User Story

Use Case Number:	2
Name:	View Assessment Feedback
Description:	The assessment feedback information from a past assessment is displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes assessment grade, mark breakdown and feedback comments.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to view an assessment's grade and feedback
Frequency:	Varied depending on assessment schedule; typically once per week
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is a member of a module Module contains assessments Assessment has been completed Assessment has been graded and had feedback published
Post-Conditions:	A user's assessment feedback is displayed on-screen to the user
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on a past (completed) assessment User's assessment feedback and grade is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	3a. If no assessments are available, appropriate message is displayed 3b. If assessment feedback is unpublished, 'unpublished' is displayed
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	User's assessment feedback is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to view their assessment feedback on-screen
Performance:	Assessment feedback should be displayed within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.2 Use Case Description for View Assessment Feedback User Story

Use Case Number:	3
Name:	Favourite Assessment
Description:	The assessment should be displayed as a favourite, signified by a yellow infilled star next to the card, and be easily accessible from the top of the homepage.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to easily find an assessment in the future
Frequency:	Typically once per month
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is a member of a module Module contains assessments
Post-Conditions:	A user's assessment has been highlighted by a yellow star and appears at the top of the user's assessment list on the homepage.
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on the 'favourite' button adjacent to an assessment Assessment displays at the top of the assessment list on homepage
Alternative Path:	3a. If no assessments are available, appropriate message is displayed
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessment displays yellow star and appears at top of homepage
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to favourite their assessment
Performance:	Assessment yellow star should be displayed within 2 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.3 Use Case Description for Favourite Assessment User Story

Use Case Number:	4
Name:	View User Profile
Description:	The profile information for a selected user is displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes the user's name, brief description, user role and profile picture.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to obtain more information about a user
Frequency:	Varied depending on assessment schedule; typically once per week
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in Existing users have created their own user profiles
Post-Conditions:	The other user's profile information is displayed on-screen to the user
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on the 'users' tab Click on a user's name User profile information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	4a. If no user profiles are available, appropriate message is displayed
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	User profile information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to view user profile information on-screen
Performance:	User profile information should be displayed within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.4 Use Case Description for View User Profile User Story

Use Case Number:	5
Name:	View Group Profile
Description:	The profile information for a selected group is displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes the names of all group members, brief description of their shared values, and profile picture.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to obtain more information about a group
Frequency:	Varied depending on assessment schedule; typically once per week
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in Existing groups have created their own group profiles
Post-Conditions:	The group profile information is displayed on-screen to the user
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on the 'groups' tab Click on a group's name Group profile information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	4a. If no group profiles are available, appropriate message is displayed
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Group profile information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to view group profile information on-screen
Performance:	Group profile information should be displayed within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.5 Use Case Description for View Group Profile User Story

Use Case Number:	6
Name:	Create User Profile
Description:	The user should be able to add relevant, descriptive information about themselves to their user profile. Information includes a customised profile picture and brief description about themselves and their background.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to inform others of their values and background
Frequency:	Once per user
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User has not previously created a profile
Post-Conditions:	The user's profile information is associated with their user account and displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on the user icon Input user profile information Click 'Save' button Created user profile information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	5a. If user profile has already been created, do not create a second profile
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Inputted user profile information is associated with user account and displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to save user profile information
Performance:	User profile information should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.6 Use Case Description for Create User Profile User Story

Use Case Number:	7
Name:	Create Group Profile
Description:	The group should be able to add relevant, descriptive information about themselves to their group profile. Information includes a customised profile picture and brief description about the group values and background.
Actor(s):	Student
Triggers:	Requirement to inform others of their values and background
Frequency:	Once per group
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is a member of the associated group Group has not previously created a profile
Post-Conditions:	The group's profile information is associated with their group and displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on 'assessments' Click on 'group' tab Click on 'profile' tab Input group profile information Click 'Save' button Created group profile information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	7a. If group profile has already been created, do not create a second profile
Extensions:	When a group profile has been created, all group members are alerted, informing them of this.
Success End Condition:	Inputted group profile information is associated with group and displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to save group profile information
Performance:	Group profile information should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.7 Use Case Description for Create Group Profile User Story

Use Case Number:	8
Name:	Create Assessment Event
Description:	The user should be able to add a new assessment event with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes an associated image, assessment name, duration, and module.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to create a new assessment to assess students
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per three weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event module has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment event information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on the 'add assessment event' icon Input assessment event information Click 'Save' button Created assessment event information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	5a. If assessment event cannot be created, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Inputted assessment event information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to create a new assessment event
Performance:	Assessment event information should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.8 Use Case Description for Create Assessment Event User Story

Use Case Number:	9
Name:	Create Assessment Group
Description:	The user should be able to create a new assessment group containing an appropriate number of users of type 'Student', associated with an assessment event. The assessment group should contain a name, for identification purposes.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to create a new group to assess students who have worked in teams
Frequency:	Varies; typically eighty times per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created Group member accounts have already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment group information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click 'Add Group' button Input group name Select group member accounts Click 'Save' button Created assessment group information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	7a. If assessment group cannot be created, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Inputted assessment group information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to create a new assessment group
Performance:	Assessment group information should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.9 Use Case Description for Create Assessment Group User Story

Use Case Number:	10
Name:	Create Assessment Rubric
Description:	The user should be able to add a new assessment event rubric with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes an associated assessment event, assessment criterion and pre-defined feedback comment.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to create an assessment's rubric
Frequency:	Varies; typically forty times per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment event rubric is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on 'Add Rubric' tab Input assessment event rubric Click 'Save' button Created assessment event rubric is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	6a. If assessment event rubric cannot be created, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Inputted assessment event rubric is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to create a new assessment event rubric
Performance:	Assessment event rubric should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.10 Use Case Description for Create Assessment Rubric User Story

Use Case Number:	11
Name:	Create Assessor Account
Description:	The user should be able to add a new external assessor account with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes an assessor's full name, email address and associated assessment event they are enrolled on.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to create a new external assessor account to assess students
Frequency:	Varies; typically sixteen times per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created Email address has not already been assigned to an account
Post-Conditions:	The assessor account information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on the 'Assessors' tab Click on 'Add New Assessor' Input assessor account information Click 'Save' button Created assessor account information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	7a. If assessor account information cannot be created, display appropriate error message 7b. If email is already assigned to an existing account, do not allow a duplicate account to be created
Extensions:	Once an assessor account has been created, send an email to the provided assessor email address to inform them of how to set up their account
Success End Condition:	Inputted assessor account information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to create a new assessor account
Performance:	Assessor account information should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.11 Use Case Description for Create Assessor Account User Story

Use Case Number:	12
Name:	Create Assessment Panel
Description:	The user should be able to create a new assessment panel containing an appropriate number of users of type 'Assessor, associated with an assessment event. The assessment panel should contain a name, for identification purposes.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to create a new panel to assess students
Frequency:	Varies; typically sixteen times per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created Assessor accounts have already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment panel information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click 'Add Assessment Panel' button Input panel name Select panel member accounts Click 'Save' button Created assessment panel information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	7a. If assessment panel cannot be created, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Inputted assessment panel information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to create a new assessment panel
Performance:	Assessment panel information should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.12 Use Case Description for Create Assessment Panel User Story

Use Case Number:	13
Name:	Edit Assessment Event
Description:	The user should be able to edit an existing assessment event with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes an associated image, assessment name, duration, and module.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to update a current assessment's information
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per month
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The updated assessment event information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on 'Edit Assessment' button Input updated assessment event information Click 'Save' button Updated assessment event information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	6a. If assessment event cannot be updated, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	All users enrolled in the assessment event should be notified of any changes made to the assessment event information
Success End Condition:	Updated assessment event information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to update an existing assessment event
Performance:	Assessment event information should be updated within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.13 Use Case Description for Edit Assessment Event User Story

Use Case Number:	14
Name:	Edit Assessment Group
Description:	The user should be able to edit an existing assessment group containing an appropriate number of users of type 'Student', associated with an assessment event. The assessment group should contain a name, for identification purposes.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to update an existing group's information, should group arrangements change
Frequency:	Varies; typically five times per month
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created Group member accounts have already been created Assessment group has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The updated assessment group information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click on 'Groups' tab Click on a group Click 'Edit Group' button Input new group information Click 'Save' button Updated assessment group information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	8a. If assessment group cannot be updated, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	Once assessment group has been updated, send an email to the group members to inform them of changes to their group
Success End Condition:	Updated assessment group information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to update an existing assessment group
Performance:	Assessment group information should be updated within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.14 Use Case Description for Edit Assessment Group User Story

Use Case Number:	15
Name:	Edit Assessment Rubric
Description:	The user should be able to update an existing assessment event rubric with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes an associated assessment event, assessment criterion and pre-defined feedback comment.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to update an existing assessment rubric, should assessment criterion change
Frequency:	Varies; typically forty times per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created Assessment rubric has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The updated assessment event rubric is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on 'Rubric' tab Click on 'Edit Rubric' button Input updated assessment event rubric Click 'Save' button Updated assessment event rubric is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	7a. If assessment event rubric cannot be updated, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Updated assessment event rubric is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to update an existing assessment event rubric
Performance:	Assessment event rubric should be updated within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.15 Use Case Description for Edit Assessment Rubric User Story

Use Case Number:	16
Name:	Edit Assessor Account
Description:	The user should be able to edit an existing external assessor account with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes an assessor's full name, email address and associated assessment event they are enrolled on.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to update an existing external assessor account, should assessor's information change
Frequency:	Varies; typically ten times per year
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created Assessor account has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The updated assessor account information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on the 'Assessors' tab Click on an assessor account Click on 'Edit Assessor Details' button Update assessor account information Click 'Save' button Updated assessor account information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	8a. If assessor account information cannot be updated, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	Once a assessor account has been updated, send an email to the provided assessor email address to inform them of changes to their account
Success End Condition:	Updated assessor account information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to update an existing assessor account
Performance:	Assessor account information should be updated within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.16 Use Case Description for Edit Assessor Account User Story

Use Case Number:	17
Name:	Edit Assessment Panel
Description:	The user should be able to edit an existing assessment panel containing an appropriate number of users of type 'Assessor', associated with an assessment event. The assessment panel should contain a name, for identification purposes.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to update an existing panel's information
Frequency:	Varies; typically twice per year
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created Assessor accounts have already been created Assessment panel has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The updated assessment panel information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click 'Assessment Panels' tab Click on an assessment panel Click on 'Edit Panel' button Update panel information Click 'Save' button Updated assessment panel information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	8a. If assessment panel cannot be updated, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	Once assessment panel has been updated, send an email to the panel members to inform them of changes to their panel
Success End Condition:	Updated assessment panel information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to update an existing assessment panel
Performance:	Assessment panel information should be updated within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.17 Use Case Description for Edit Assessment Panel User Story

Use Case Number:	18
Name:	Delete Assessment Event
Description:	The user should be able to delete an existing assessment event.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to delete an assessment event that is not required anymore
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment event information is removed from the assessment event list on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on 'Delete Assessment' button Assessment event is removed from assessment event list on-screen
Alternative Path:	4a. If assessment event cannot be deleted, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessment event is removed from assessment event list on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to delete an existing assessment event
Performance:	Assessment event should be deleted within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.18 Use Case Description for Delete Assessment Event User Story

Use Case Number:	19
Name:	Delete Assessment Rubric
Description:	The user should be able to delete an existing assessment rubric.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to delete an assessment rubric that is not required anymore
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment rubric has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment event rubric is removed from the assessment event on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on 'Assessment Rubric' tab Click on an assessment rubric Click on 'Delete Rubric' button Assessment event rubric is removed from assessment event on-screen
Alternative Path:	6a. If assessment event rubric cannot be deleted, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessment event rubric is removed from assessment event on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to delete an existing assessment event rubric
Performance:	Assessment event rubric should be deleted within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.19 Use Case Description for Delete Assessment Rubric User Story

Use Case Number:	20
Name:	Delete Assessment Group
Description:	The user should be able to delete an existing assessment group.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to delete an assessment group that is not required anymore
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment group has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment group is removed from the assessment event on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on 'Assessment Groups' tab Click on an assessment group Click on 'Delete Group' button Assessment group is removed from assessment event on-screen
Alternative Path:	6a. If assessment group cannot be deleted, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessment group is removed from assessment event on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to delete an existing assessment group
Performance:	Assessment group should be deleted within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.20 Use Case Description for Delete Assessment Group User Story

Use Case Number:	21
Name:	Create Assessment Feedback
Description:	The user should be able to create a new assessment feedback comment for a group's assessment, containing an appropriate grade, pre-configured rubric comment, and free-text comments.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to create a group's feedback comments for an assessment
Frequency:	Varies; typically forty times per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessor' Assessment event has already been created Assessment group has already been created Assessment panel has already been created Assessment rubric has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment feedback is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click on an existing group Click on 'Feedback' tab Click 'Record Feedback' button Input grade and feedback comments Click 'Save' button Created assessment feedback is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	8a. If assessment feedback cannot be created, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Inputted assessment feedback is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to create new assessment feedback
Performance:	Assessment feedback should be saved within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.21 Use Case Description for Create Assessment Feedback User Story

Use Case Number:	22
Name:	Edit Assessment Feedback
Description:	The user should be able to update existing assessment feedback comments for a group's assessment, containing an appropriate grade, pre-configured rubric comment, and free-text comments.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to update a group's feedback comments for an assessment
Frequency:	Varies; typically five times per week
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessor' Assessment event has already been created Assessment group has already been created Assessment panel has already been created Assessment rubric has already been created Assessment feedback has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The updated assessment feedback is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click on an existing group Click on 'Feedback' tab Click on an existing feedback comment Click on 'Edit Feedback' button Update grade and feedback comments Click 'Save' button Updated assessment feedback is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	9a. If assessment feedback cannot be updated, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Updated assessment feedback is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to update existing assessment feedback
Performance:	Assessment feedback should be updated within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.22 Use Case Description for Edit Assessment Feedback User Story

Use Case Number:	23
Name:	Delete Assessment Panel
Description:	The user should be able to delete an existing assessment panel.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to delete an assessment panel that is not required anymore
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment panel has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment panel is removed from the assessment event on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on 'Assessment Panels' tab Click on an assessment panel Click on 'Delete Panel' button Assessment panel is removed from assessment event on-screen
Alternative Path:	6a. If assessment panel cannot be deleted, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessment panel is removed from assessment event on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to delete an existing assessment panel
Performance:	Assessment panel should be deleted within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.23 Use Case Description for Delete Assessment Panel User Story

Use Case Number:	24
Name:	Delete Assessment Feedback
Description:	The user should be able to delete an existing assessment feedback comment.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to delete an assessment feedback comment that is not required anymore
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment feedback has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessment feedback comment is removed from the assessment group's assessment event feedback on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on 'Assessment Groups' tab Click on an assessment group Click on 'Assessment Feedback' tab Click on an assessment feedback comment Click on 'Delete Feedback Comment' button Feedback comment is removed from the assessment group's assessment event feedback on-screen
Alternative Path:	8a. If assessment feedback cannot be deleted, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessment feedback is removed from assessment group's assessment event feedback on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to delete an existing assessment feedback comment
Performance:	Assessment feedback comment should be deleted within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.24 Use Case Description for Delete Assessment Feedback User Story

Use Case Number:	25
Name:	Delete Assessor Account
Description:	The user should be able to remove an existing external assessor account.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to remove an existing external assessor account to revoke external access to an assessment
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessor account has already been created
Post-Conditions:	The assessor account is removed from assessment event on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on the 'Assessors' tab Click on an assessor Click on 'Delete Assessor' button Assessor account is removed from assessment event on-screen
Alternative Path:	6a. If assessor account cannot be deleted, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessor account is removed from assessment event on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to delete an existing assessor account
Performance:	Assessor account should be deleted within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.25 Use Case Description for Delete Assessor Account User Story

Use Case Number:	26
Name:	View Assessment Rubric
Description:	The assessment rubric information from an assessment event is displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes an associated assessment event, assessment criterion and pre-defined feedback comment.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to view an assessment's rubric, to be aware of marking criteria
Frequency:	Varied; typically once per three weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' or 'Assessor' Assessment event has already been created Assessment rubric has already been created
Post-Conditions:	An assessment event's assessment rubric is displayed on-screen to the user
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on 'Rubric' tab Assessment event rubric is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	4a. If no assessments are available, appropriate message is displayed 4b. If no assessment rubric is available, appropriate message is displayed
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessment event's assessment rubric is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to view assessment rubric on-screen
Performance:	Assessment rubric should be displayed within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.26 Use Case Description for View Assessment Rubric User Story

Use Case Number:	27
Name:	View Panel Profile
Description:	The profile information for a selected panel is displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes the names of all panel members and the name of the assessment panel.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to obtain more information about a panel
Frequency:	Varied depending on assessment schedule; typically once per week
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in Panels have been created for an assessment event
Post-Conditions:	The panel information is displayed on-screen to the user
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on the 'Assessor Panel' tab Assessment panel information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	3a. If no panels are available, appropriate message is displayed
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Panel information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to view panel information on-screen
Performance:	Panel information should be displayed within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.27 Use Case Description for View Panel Profile User Story

Use Case Number:	28
Name:	Assign Assessment Panel
Description:	A selected panel should be assignable to an assessment group for an assessment event, allowing the panel to assess a group of students.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to allow panels to assess groups partaking in an assessment event
Frequency:	Varied; typically forty times per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in Assessment event has been created External assessor accounts have been created Panels have been created for an assessment event
Post-Conditions:	The panel assignment information is displayed on-screen to the user
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an assessment event Click on the 'Assessor Panel' tab Assessment panel assignment information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	4a. If no panel assignments are available, appropriate message is displayed
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Panel assignment information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to view panel assignment information on-screen
Performance:	Panel assignment information should be displayed within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.28 Use Case Description for Assign Assessment Panel User Story

Use Case Number:	29
Name:	Publish Assessment Feedback
Description:	The user should be able to publish assessment feedback comments produced by an assessment panel for an assessment group at an assessment event.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to disseminate assessment feedback and grades to students
Frequency:	Varies; typically forty times per six weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessor' Assessment event has already been created Assessment group has already been created Assessment panel has already been created Assessment rubric has already been created Assessment feedback has already been created
Post-Conditions:	Assessment feedback is viewable from student view
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click on an existing group Click on 'Feedback' tab Click 'Publish Feedback' button Published assessment feedback is displayed on-screen in student view
Alternative Path:	6a. If assessment feedback cannot be published, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	Once assessment feedback has been published, send an email to the provided group member email addresses to inform them that their feedback is available to view
Success End Condition:	Published assessment feedback is displayed on-screen in student view
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to publish assessment feedback
Performance:	Assessment feedback should be published within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.29 Use Case Description for Publish Assessment Feedback User Story

Use Case Number:	30
Name:	Unpublish Assessment Feedback
Description:	The user should be able to unpublish assessment feedback comments produced by an assessment panel for an assessment group at an assessment event.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to hide unsuitable assessment feedback and grades from students
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per three weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessor' Assessment event has already been created Assessment group has already been created Assessment panel has already been created Assessment rubric has already been created Assessment feedback has already been created Assessment feedback has already been published
Post-Conditions:	Assessment feedback is hidden from student view
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click on an existing group Click on 'Feedback' tab Click 'Unpublish Feedback' button Unpublished assessment feedback is hidden on-screen in student view
Alternative Path:	6a. If assessment feedback cannot be unpublished, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessment feedback is hidden from student view
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to publish assessment feedback
Performance:	Assessment feedback should be unpublished within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.30 Use Case Description for Unpublish Assessment Feedback User Story

Use Case Number:	31
Name:	Export Assessment Grades
Description:	The user should be able to export assessment grades for all assessment groups for an assessment event.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to use assessment grades for official degree classification purposes
Frequency:	Varies; typically once per three weeks
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessor' Assessment event has already been created Assessment group has already been created Assessment panel has already been created Assessment rubric has already been created Assessment feedback has already been created
Post-Conditions:	Assessment grades are downloaded to the user's 'Downloads' directory on their device
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click on 'Export Grades' button Grades are downloaded to user's device
Alternative Path:	6a. If assessment grades cannot be downloaded, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Assessment grades downloaded file is stored locally on user's device
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to download assessment grades file
Performance:	Assessment grades download should be completed within 15 seconds
Priority:	Could

Figure F.31 Use Case Description for Export Assessment Grades User Story

Use Case Number:	32
Name:	Create Alert
Description:	The user should be able to create alerts directed at particular user types. Alerts should contain key information such as a title, description, assessment event, creation date and alert creator.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to inform users of key information regarding assessments
Frequency:	Typically once per week
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' Assessment event has already been created Assessment groups have already been created Assessment panels have already been created
Post-Conditions:	Selected user types receive a notification containing the alert
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on an existing assessment Click on 'Create Alert' button Input alert information Alerts are sent to all relevant users
Alternative Path:	5a. If alert cannot be sent, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	Once alert has been created, send an email to the appropriate user email addresses to inform them of the alert
Success End Condition:	Relevant users receive an alert message
Failure End Condition:	Alert message is not sent to users
Performance:	Alert messages should be sent within 15 seconds
Priority:	Could

Figure F.32 Use Case Description for Create Alert User Story

Use Case Number:	33
Name:	Edit Group Profile
Description:	The group should be able to modify their group profile information. Information includes a customised profile picture and brief description about the group values and background.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to update information on their values and background
Frequency:	Typically once per month
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is a member of the associated group Group has already created a profile
Post-Conditions:	The group's profile information is updated and displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on 'assessments' Click on 'group' tab Click on 'profile' tab Click on 'Update Profile' button Update group profile information Click 'Save' button Updated group profile information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	8a. If group profile information cannot be updated, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Inputted group profile information is associated with group and displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to update group profile information
Performance:	Group profile information should be updated within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.33 Use Case Description for Edit Group Profile User Story

Use Case Number:	34
Name:	Create Module
Description:	The user should be able to create a module. A module should contain key information such as a module code, title, description and module leader.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to relate an assessment event to a module
Frequency:	Typically four times per year
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is of user type 'Assessment Leader'
Post-Conditions:	The module's information is associated with a module leader and displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on 'Create Module' button Input module information New module information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	4a. If module cannot be created, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	New module is created and module information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to create a new module
Performance:	Module should be created within 5 seconds
Priority:	Must

Figure F.34 Use Case Description for Create Module User Story

Use Case Number:	35
Name:	View Module
Description:	The user should be able to view their modules. A module should contain key information such as a module code, title, description and module leader.
Actor(s):	Student, Assessment Leader, Assessor
Triggers:	Requirement to view modules a user is taking
Frequency:	Typically twice per week
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in User is enrolled in modules which contain assessment events
Post-Conditions:	The module's information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on 'Modules' tab Module information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	3a. If modules cannot be displayed, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Module information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to view their modules
Performance:	Modules should be displayed within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.35 Use Case Description for View Module User Story

Use Case Number:	36
Name:	Edit Module
Description:	The user should be able to edit their module information. A module should contain key information such as a module code, title, description and module leader.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to edit module information to ensure it is correct
Frequency:	Typically once per year
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in Module has already been created User is the module leader of the module
Post-Conditions:	The updated module's information is displayed on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on 'Modules' tab Click on a module Click on 'Edit Module' button Update module information Click 'Save' button Updated module information is displayed on-screen
Alternative Path:	7a. If module cannot be updated, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Updated module information is displayed on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to update their modules
Performance:	Modules should be updated within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.36 Use Case Description for Edit Module User Story

Use Case Number:	37
Name:	Delete Module
Description:	The user should be able to delete a module.
Actor(s):	Assessment Leader
Triggers:	Requirement to delete modules, should they become unnecessary
Frequency:	Typically once per year
Pre-Conditions:	User is logged in Module has already been created User is the module leader of the module
Post-Conditions:	The module information is removed from the module list on-screen
Basic Path:	Navigate to the website's homepage Click on 'Modules' tab Click on a module Click on 'Delete Module' button Module information is removed from module list on-screen
Alternative Path:	5a. If module cannot be deleted, display appropriate error message
Extensions:	None
Success End Condition:	Module information is removed from the module list on-screen
Failure End Condition:	User is unable to delete a module
Performance:	Modules should be deleted within 5 seconds
Priority:	Should

Figure F.2 Use Case Description for Delete Module User Story

Appendix G – Functional Requirements

ID	Functional Requirement Description	Owner
1	All users are able to view their enrolled assessments	All Users
2	All users are able to create their user profile	All Users
3	All users are able to receive direct messages from other users	All Users
4	All users are able to edit their user profile	All Users
5	All users are able to refine their displayed modules	All Users
6	All users are able to refine their displayed users	All Users
7	All users are able to unfavourite assessments	All Users
8	All users are able to send direct messages to other users	All Users
9	All users are able to search for a module	All Users
10	All users are able to search for an assessment	All Users
11	All users are able to view an enrolled assessment's details	All Users
12	All users are able to search for a user	All Users
13	All users are able to favourite assessments	All Users
14	All users are able to view other users' profiles	All Users
15	All users are able to refine their displayed assessments	All Users
16	All users are able to view their user profile	All Users
17	Students are able to view their assessment panel	Students
18	Students are able to view their assessment group's profile	Students
19	Students are able to edit their assessment group's profile	Students
20	Students are able to view their assessment panel's profile	Students
21	Students are able to view their modules	Students
22	Students are able to view their past assessment grade and feedback	Students
23	Students are able to view their assessment groups	Students
24	Assessors are able to view their assessment panel's profile	Assessors
25	Assessors are suggested feedback comments for an assessment based on AI predictions	Assessors
26	Assessors are able to edit their assessment panel's profile	Assessors
27	Assessors are able to view assessment group profiles for groups they are assessing	Assessors
28	Assessors are able to view rubric for an assessment	Assessors
29	Assessors are able to send assessment co-assessors direct messages	Assessors
30	Assessors are able to view feedback comments for an assessment	Assessors
31	Assessors are able to re-assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	Assessors
32	Assessors are able to view assessment co-assessors' direct messages	Assessors
33	Assessors are able to assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	Assessors
34	Assessors are able to create free-text feedback for an assessment	Assessors
35	Assessors are able to collaboratively view their co-assessors' feedback comments	Assessors
36	Assessors are able to edit free-text feedback for an assessment	Assessors
37	Assessors are able to view the assessment feedback they have provided	Assessors
38	Assessors are able to delete free-text feedback for an assessment	Assessors
39	Assessors are able to de-assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	Assessors

40	Assessment leaders are able to import assessment grades and feedback produced in other applications	Assessment Leaders
41	Assessment leaders are able to create new rubric for their assessment	Assessment Leaders
42	Assessment leaders are able to assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	Assessment Leaders
43	Assessment leaders are able to view their assessment panels' profiles	Assessment Leaders
44	Assessment leaders are able to re-assign an external assessor account to an assessment	Assessment Leaders
45	Assessment leaders are able to view their assessment panels	Assessment Leaders
46	Assessment leaders are able to edit their modules	Assessment Leaders
47	Assessment leaders are able to create new external assessor accounts	Assessment Leaders
48	Assessment leaders are able to toggle collaborative assessor feedback views on or off	Assessment Leaders
49	Assessment leaders are able to delete their assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
50	Assessment leaders are able to assign students to assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
51	Assessment leaders are able to create a new feedback comment for their assessment rubric	Assessment Leaders
52	Assessment leaders are able to import existing assessment groups from a file generated in an alternative application	Assessment Leaders
53	Assessment leaders are able to create new assessments	Assessment Leaders
54	Assessment leaders are able to re-assign assessors to assessment panels	Assessment Leaders
55	Assessment leaders are able to export feedback and grades in an LMS-readable format	Assessment Leaders
56	Assessment leaders are able to publish feedback and grades to students	Assessment Leaders
57	Assessment leaders are able to re-assign assessment panels to assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
58	Assessment leaders are able to create alerts to send to users	Assessment Leaders
59	Assessment leaders are able to edit their assessments	Assessment Leaders
60	Assessment leaders are able to view their assessment groups' profiles	Assessment Leaders
61	Assessment leaders are able to create assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
62	Assessment leaders are able to delete their assessment panels	Assessment Leaders
63	Assessment leaders are able to re-assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	Assessment Leaders
64	Assessment leaders are able to assign an external assessor account to an assessment	Assessment Leaders

65	Assessment leaders are able to de-assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	Assessment Leaders
66	Assessment leaders are able to edit free-text feedback for an assessment	Assessment Leaders
67	Assessment leaders are able to delete rubric for their assessment	Assessment Leaders
68	Assessment leaders are able to view external assessor accounts	Assessment Leaders
69	Assessment leaders are able to delete a feedback comment for their assessment rubric	Assessment Leaders
70	Assessment leaders are able to randomly generate assessment groups formed of similar students	Assessment Leaders
71	Assessment leaders are able to assign assessment panels to assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
72	Assessment leaders are able to de-assign assessment panels to assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
73	Assessment leaders are able to unpublish feedback and grades from students	Assessment Leaders
74	Assessment leaders are able to assign assessors to assessment panels	Assessment Leaders
75	Assessment leaders are able to view feedback comments for their assessment rubric	Assessment Leaders
76	Assessment leaders are able to edit rubric for their assessment	Assessment Leaders
77	Assessment leaders are able to de-assign assessors from assessment panels	Assessment Leaders
78	Assessment leaders are able to view the assessment feedback for an assessment	Assessment Leaders
79	Assessment leaders are able to create new modules	Assessment Leaders
80	Assessment leaders are able to view their assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
81	Assessment leaders are able to delete external assessor accounts	Assessment Leaders
82	Assessment leaders are able to de-assign students from assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
83	Assessment leaders are able to view rubric for their assessments	Assessment Leaders
84	Assessment leaders are able to delete free-text feedback for an assessment	Assessment Leaders
85	Assessment leaders are able to edit their assessment groups' profiles	Assessment Leaders
86	Assessment leaders are able to delete their assessments	Assessment Leaders
87	Assessment leaders are able to delete their modules	Assessment Leaders
88	Assessment leaders are able to associate an assessment with a module	Assessment Leaders
89	Assessment leaders are able to create assessment panels	Assessment Leaders

90	Assessment leaders are able to import existing assessment panels from a file generated in an alternative application	Assessment Leaders
91	Assessment leaders are able to edit their assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
92	Assessment leaders are able to view the external assessor account assignments to an assessment	Assessment Leaders
93	Assessment leaders are able to create free-text feedback for an assessment	Assessment Leaders
94	Assessment leaders are able to edit their assessment panels	Assessment Leaders
95	Assessment leaders are able to view assessment panel to assessment group assignments	Assessment Leaders
96	Assessment leaders are able to re-assign students to assessment groups	Assessment Leaders
97	Assessment leaders are able to edit a feedback comment for their assessment rubric	Assessment Leaders
98	Assessment leaders are able to edit external assessor accounts	Assessment Leaders
99	Assessment leaders are able to edit their assessment panels' profiles	Assessment Leaders
100	Assessment leaders are able to de-assign an external assessor account to an assessment	Assessment Leaders
101	Assessment leaders are able to access the feedback system through an inbuilt 'External Tool' option in Canvas LMS	Assessment Leaders

Table G.1 Elicited Functional Requirements

Appendix H – Non-Functional Requirements

ID	Category	Non-Functional Requirement Description
1	Performance	User interface must display requested page information within 5 seconds
2	Performance	System must send email messages within 10 seconds of the user enacting a task requiring user(s) to be notified via email
3	Compatibility	System must run on all major desktop and mobile platforms, including a minimum of Windows 10, macOS 11 (Big Sur), Linux (kernel version 3.10), Android 10, and iOS 15
4	Compatibility	System must run on the latest version of all popular web browsers, including Firefox, Chrome, Edge, and Safari
5	Compatibility	System must run on a minimum of a 1 GHz processor, 2 GB of RAM, 1 GB of available hard disk space, and 720p (1280 x 720) display resolution
6	Compatibility	User interface should be appropriately viewable and suitably interactable on mobile devices
7	Scalability	System must function under exceptional traffic loads or usage spikes
8	Scalability	System must support a minimum of 150 concurrent users
9	Scalability	Database must be able to store a minimum of 15,000 records
10	Reliability	System must sustain 99% yearly uptime
11	Reliability	In the event of system failure, system service must be resumed within 1 hour
12	Reliability	Database must utilise transaction management to only permit successful transactions to enact persistent changes to the database
13	Reliability	Database backups must be performed daily at midnight to allow the database to be restored in the event of failure or data loss
14	Reliability	System must avoid integration of third-party networked resources, where possible, to prevent system downtime should these resources become unavailable or modified
15	Maintainability	System must utilise an appropriate directory structure and naming conventions to improve code readability
16	Maintainability	System components must have high cohesion, low coupling and be reusable, where possible, to support efficient upgradability
17	Maintainability	System code must be readable to facilitate faster maintenance and allow new developers to understand the system's code
18	Maintainability	System must be appropriately documented to provide developers with suitable implementation information, for ease of maintenance
19	Maintainability	System frontend, backend, and database must be independent and have low coupling, allowing each aspect to be substituted for an alternative implementation, without affecting system functionality
20	Security	System must only be accessible to users with valid login credentials, with a reliable authentication mechanism implemented in the frontend, backend, and database
21	Security	A logged-in user must only be able to view data aligned with their system permission level, and not that of any other users, based on reliable authorisation mechanism
22	Security	System data must be appropriately stored based on sensitivity, with sensitive data including passwords being encrypted when stored in the database
23	Security	System data must be transmitted over a secure connection, HTTPS, between the frontend, backend, and database

24	Security	Backend API endpoints must not be accessible other than through the developed frontend, or authorised third-party services
25	Security	System must prevent against cross-site scripting (XSS) and SQL injection attacks
26	Usability	User interface must be clear, simple, navigable, and intelligible by all users, regardless of age, technological experience or neurodivergence
27	Usability	User interface colour scheme be accessible to all users, including those with visual impairments, such as colour blindness
28	Usability	User interface must be accessible to users interacting using alternative human interface devices, such as trackballs, Braille keyboards, or eye tracking systems, or using a screen reader
29	Usability	User interface must provide clear validation error messages to the user, in the case of inputting unsuitable data, based on the input mask format or data schema
30	Usability	User interface must use consistent colour schemes, styling, components, layout, navigation and textual identifiers across all webpages and device platforms
31	Usability	System must provide training to support first-time users in navigating and using the associated webpages
32	Localisation	System must abide by the appropriate legislation in the territory it is operating in, namely the Data Protection Act (2018) for use in the United Kingdom
33	Localisation	System must display information in a locality-specific format, including utilising suitable date formats, time zones and currencies

Table H.1 Elicited Non-Functional Requirements

Appendix I – MoSCoW Prioritisation

ID	Functional Requirement Description	Priority	Owner
1	All users must be able to view their enrolled assessments	MUST	All Users
2	All users must be able to view an enrolled assessment's details	MUST	All Users
3	Students must be able to view their past assessment grade and feedback	MUST	Students
4	Students must be able to view their assessment groups	MUST	Students
5	Students must be able to view their assessment panel	MUST	Students
6	Assessors must be able to view rubric for an assessment	MUST	Assessors
7	Assessors must be able to view feedback comments for an assessment	MUST	Assessors
8	Assessors must be able to assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	MUST	Assessors
9	Assessors must be able to de-assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	MUST	Assessors
10	Assessors must be able to create free-text feedback for an assessment	MUST	Assessors
11	Assessors must be able to view the assessment feedback they have provided	MUST	Assessors
12	Assessors must be able to edit free-text feedback for an assessment	MUST	Assessors
13	Assessors must be able to delete free-text feedback for an assessment	MUST	Assessors
14	Assessment leaders must be able to create new modules	MUST	Assessment Leaders
15	Assessment leaders must be able to delete their modules	MUST	Assessment Leaders
16	Assessment leaders must be able to create new assessments	MUST	Assessment Leaders
17	Assessment leaders must be able to delete their assessments	MUST	Assessment Leaders
18	Assessment leaders must be able to associate an assessment with a module	MUST	Assessment Leaders
19	Assessment leaders must be able to create assessment groups	MUST	Assessment Leaders
20	Assessment leaders must be able to view their assessment groups	MUST	Assessment Leaders
21	Assessment leaders must be able to delete their assessment groups	MUST	Assessment Leaders
22	Assessment leaders must be able to assign students to assessment groups	MUST	Assessment Leaders
23	Assessment leaders must be able to create assessment panels	MUST	Assessment Leaders
24	Assessment leaders must be able to view their assessment panels	MUST	Assessment Leaders
25	Assessment leaders must be able to delete their assessment panels	MUST	Assessment Leaders
26	Assessment leaders must be able to assign assessors to assessment panels	MUST	Assessment Leaders

27	Assessment leaders must be able to assign assessment panels to assessment groups	MUST	Assessment Leaders
28	Assessment leaders must be able to view assessment panel to assessment group assignments	MUST	Assessment Leaders
29	Assessment leaders must be able to create new rubric for their assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
30	Assessment leaders must be able to view rubric for their assessments	MUST	Assessment Leaders
31	Assessment leaders must be able to edit rubric for their assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
32	Assessment leaders must be able to delete rubric for their assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
33	Assessment leaders must be able to create a new feedback comment for their assessment rubric	MUST	Assessment Leaders
34	Assessment leaders must be able to view feedback comments for their assessment rubric	MUST	Assessment Leaders
35	Assessment leaders must be able to edit a feedback comment for their assessment rubric	MUST	Assessment Leaders
36	Assessment leaders must be able to delete a feedback comment for their assessment rubric	MUST	Assessment Leaders
37	Assessment leaders must be able to assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
38	Assessment leaders must be able to re-assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
39	Assessment leaders must be able to de-assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
40	Assessment leaders must be able to create free-text feedback for an assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
41	Assessment leaders must be able to view the assessment feedback for an assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
42	Assessment leaders must be able to edit free-text feedback for an assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
43	Assessment leaders must be able to delete free-text feedback for an assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
44	Assessment leaders must be able to create new external assessor accounts	MUST	Assessment Leaders
45	Assessment leaders must be able to view external assessor accounts	MUST	Assessment Leaders
46	Assessment leaders must be able to edit external assessor accounts	MUST	Assessment Leaders
47	Assessment leaders must be able to delete external assessor accounts	MUST	Assessment Leaders
48	Assessment leaders must be able to assign an external assessor account to an assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
49	Assessment leaders must be able to view the external assessor account assignments to an assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
50	Assessment leaders must be able to de-assign an external assessor account to an assessment	MUST	Assessment Leaders
51	Assessment leaders must be able to publish feedback and grades to students	MUST	Assessment Leaders

52	Assessment leaders must be able to unpublish feedback and grades from students	MUST	Assessment Leaders
53	Students must be able to view their assessment panel's profile	MUST	Students
54	Students should be able to view their assessment group's profile	SHOULD	Students
55	Students should be able to edit their assessment group's profile	SHOULD	Students
56	Students should be able to view their modules	SHOULD	Students
57	Assessors should be able to view assessment group profiles for groups they are assessing	SHOULD	Assessors
58	Assessors should be able to view their assessment panel's profile	SHOULD	Assessors
59	Assessors should be able to re-assign a feedback comment to an assessment group's assessment	SHOULD	Assessors
60	Assessors should be able to collaboratively view their co-assessors' feedback comments	SHOULD	Assessors
61	Assessors should be able to edit their assessment panel's profile	SHOULD	Assessors
62	Assessment leaders should be able to edit their modules	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
63	Assessment leaders should be able to edit their assessments	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
64	Assessment leaders should be able to edit their assessment groups	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
65	Assessment leaders should be able to view their assessment groups' profiles	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
66	Assessment leaders should be able to edit their assessment groups' profiles	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
67	Assessment leaders should be able to edit their assessment panels	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
68	Assessment leaders should be able to view their assessment panels' profiles	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
69	Assessment leaders should be able to edit their assessment panels' profiles	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
70	Assessment leaders should be able to re-assign assessors to assessment panels	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
71	Assessment leaders should be able to de-assign assessors from assessment panels	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
72	Assessment leaders should be able to re-assign students to assessment groups	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
73	Assessment leaders should be able to de-assign students from assessment groups	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
74	Assessment leaders should be able to re-assign assessment panels to assessment groups	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
75	Assessment leaders should be able to de-assign assessment panels to assessment groups	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
76	Assessment leaders should be able to re-assign an external assessor account to an assessment	SHOULD	Assessment Leaders
77	All users could be able to favourite assessments	COULD	All Users
78	All users could be able to unfavourite assessments	COULD	All Users
79	All users could be able to create their user profile	COULD	All Users
80	All users could be able to view their user profile	COULD	All Users

81	All users could be able to edit their user profile	COULD	All Users
82	All users could be able to view other users' profiles	COULD	All Users
83	All users could be able to refine their displayed modules	COULD	All Users
84	All users could be able to search for a module	COULD	All Users
85	All users could be able to refine their displayed assessments	COULD	All Users
86	All users could be able to search for an assessment	COULD	All Users
87	All users could be able to refine their displayed users	COULD	All Users
88	All users could be able to search for a user	COULD	All Users
89	Assessors could be able to send assessment co-assessors direct messages	COULD	Assessors
90	Assessors could be able to view assessment co-assessors' direct messages	COULD	Assessors
91	All users won't be able to send direct messages to other users	WON'T	All Users
92	All users won't be able to receive direct messages from other users	WON'T	All Users
93	Assessors won't be suggested feedback comments for an assessment based on AI predictions	WON'T	Assessors
94	Assessment leaders won't be able to export feedback and grades in an LMS-readable format	WON'T	Assessment Leaders
95	Assessment leaders won't be able to create alerts to send to users	WON'T	Assessment Leaders
96	Assessment leaders won't be able to import existing assessment panels from a file generated in an alternative application	WON'T	Assessment Leaders
97	Assessment leaders won't be able to import existing assessment groups from a file generated in an alternative application	WON'T	Assessment Leaders
98	Assessment leaders won't be able to access the feedback system through an inbuilt 'External Tool' option in Canvas LMS	WON'T	Assessment Leaders
99	Assessment leaders won't be able to randomly generate assessment groups formed of similar students	WON'T	Assessment Leaders
100	Assessment leaders won't be able to import assessment grades and feedback produced in other applications	WON'T	Assessment Leaders
101	Assessment leaders won't be able to toggle collaborative assessor feedback views on or off	WON'T	Assessment Leaders

Table 1.1 MoScow-Prioritised Functional Requirements

Appendix J – Initial Sketches

View Assessment Groups:

View Assessment Groups:
 Desktop/Laptop View:

Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool:
 Prototype idea → View assessment groups screen.
 "As an assessment leader/assessor, I would like to view assessment groups."

add in items as relevant → options not suitable for navbar.

Figure J.1 Initial Sketch for View Assessment Groups Webpage

View Assessment Panels:

View Assessment Panels:
Desktop/Laptop View:

Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool:
Prototype idea → view assessment panels screen
"As an assessment leader, I would like to view assessment panels."

Figure J.2 Initial Sketch for View Assessment Panels Webpage

View Assessment Rubric:

Figure J.3 Initial Sketch for View Assessment Rubric Webpage

Create/Edit Assessment Feedback:

Create /Edit Assessment Feedback:
Desktop /Laptop View.

Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool:
Prototype idea → Create /edit assessment feedback screen
"As an assessment leader /assessor, I would like to create /edit feedback."

Figure J.4 Initial Sketch for Create and Edit Assessment Feedback Webpage

Assign Groups to Panels:

Assign Groups to Panel:
Desktop/Laptop View:

Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool:
Prototype idea → assign groups to panel screen.
"As an assessment leader, I would like to assign/reassign groups to panels."

Figure J.5 Initial Sketch for Assign Groups to Panels Webpage

View Assessment Feedback:

Figure J.6 Initial Sketch for View Assessment Feedback Webpage

Create Alert:

Create Alert:

Desktop/Laptop View:

Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool:
 Prototype idea → create alert screen
 "As an assessment leader, I would like to create alerts."

Figure J.7 Initial Sketch for Create Alert Webpage

Create/Edit Assessment Rubric:

CREATE /Edit Assessment Rubric:
Desktop /Laptop view:

Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool:
Prototype idea → create /edit assessment rubric screen
"As an assessment leader, I would like to create/edit assessment rubric."

Figure J.8 Initial Sketch for Create and Edit Assessment Rubric Webpage

View User/Group Profile:

Figure J.9 Initial Sketch for View User and Group Profile Webpage

Create/Edit User/Group Profile:

Edit/Create (Assessment Leader):
Group/User Profile
 Desktop/Laptop View:

Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool:
 Prototype idea → edit/create user/profile screen
 'As an assessment leader, I would like to create/edit user/group profiles.'
 Group may be Student group or panel.

Figure J.10 Initial Sketch for Create and Edit User and Group Webpage

Create/Edit User Profile:

Figure J.11 Initial Sketch for Create and Edit User Profile Webpage

View Assessment Rubric Item:

View Assessment Rubric Item:
 Desktop / Laptop View:

Collaborative Marking And Feedback Tool:
 Prototype idea → view assessment rubric item screen
 "As an assessor / student / assessment leader I would like to view an assessment rubric item."

Figure J.12 Initial Sketch for View Assessment Rubric Item Webpage

View Assessment:

View Assessment:

Desktop/Laptop View:

Collaborative Making and Feedback Tool:

Prototype idea → View Assessment Screen

"As an assessment leader/assessor/student, I would like to view an assessment."

Figure J.13 Initial Sketch for View Assessment Webpage

View Assessment Students/Assessors:

View Assessment Students/Assessors:
Desktop/Laptop View:

Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool:
Prototype idea → view assessment students/assessors screen.
"As an assessment leader/assessor/student, I would like to view students/assessors."

Figure J.14 Initial Sketch for View Assessment Students and Assessors Webpage

View Assessments (Homepage):

View Assessments:
Desktop/Laptop View:

Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool:
Prototype idea → view assessments
"As an assessment leader/assessor/student, I would like to view my assessments."

login button → changes to user's pic when logged in.

Figure J.15 Initial Sketch for View Assessments (Homepage) Webpage

Create/Edit Assessment:

"As an assessment leader, I would like to be able to create a new assessment to be able to assess students on a particular topic."

Figure J.16 Initial Sketch for Create and Edit Assessment Webpage

Appendix K – Medium Fidelity Wireframes

Create Alert:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users' tabs, and a user profile 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Create New React Programming Assessment Alert'. It contains three sections: 'Alert Title' with a text input field containing 'Reminder - Upload Pitch Presentation to Canvas' and a note 'Alert title is less than 50 characters'; 'Alert Message' with a text area containing a reminder about submitting a PowerPoint presentation; and 'User Group' with a dropdown menu set to 'Students'. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Create Alert' buttons. A footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.1 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Alert Webpage

Create Assessment:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users' tabs, and a user profile 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Create New Assessment'. It contains five sections: 'Assessment Name' with a text input field containing 'Java EventManager Application Assessment' and a note 'Assessment name must be more than 10 characters'; 'Assessment Start Date' with a date-time picker set to '28/10/2022 | 09:00' and a note 'Assessment start date is in an incorrect format'; 'Assessment End Date' with a date-time picker set to '29/10/2022 | 17:00' and a note 'Assessment end date is in an incorrect format'; 'Assessment Image URL' with a text input field containing 'https://www.imagewebsite.com/assessment-image.png' and a note 'Assessment image URL is in an incorrect format'; and 'Assessment Leader' with a dropdown menu set to 'Professor Graeme Jones'. Below these are 'Assessment Module' with a dropdown menu set to 'CI4150 - Java Programming' and 'Assessment Description' with a text area containing a reminder about presenting the application. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Create Assessment' buttons. A footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.2 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Assessment Webpage

Create Assessment Feedback:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'Markit', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users' tabs, and a user profile 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Create New React Programming Assessment Feedback Report for Group 1 - The Wombats'.

Presentation Quality (Info icon)

Select Comments:
Please drag and drop appropriate comments for this assessment criterion

Search Comments...

Presentation was of an exceptional standard, with excellent use of Microsoft PowerPoint to fully explain the coding behind the website, and a professional and clear demonstration highlighting the successful fulfilling of all website requirements.

Presentation was of an excellent standard, with appropriate use of Microsoft PowerPoint, to explain the coding behind the website, and a professional demonstration, highlighting the successful fulfilling of all website requirements.

Additional Comments:
Please enter any additional comments for this assessment criterion

Your communication skills were great, and these presentation skills will really help you in the future!

Grade:
Please select the grade for this assessment criterion (1 lowest; 10 highest)

9

Selected Comments:

Presentation was of an exceptional standard, with excellent use of Microsoft PowerPoint to fully explain the coding behind the website, and a professional and clear demonstration highlighting the successful fulfilling of all website requirements.

Website UX Design (Info icon)

Select Comments:
Please drag and drop appropriate comments for this assessment criterion

Search Comments...

Website utilised an excellent, consistent UX design, fit for the target user group and strongly considering accessibility. The website workflow is logical and easy to follow, even for novices.

Website utilised a poor and inconsistent UX design, unfit for the target user group and lacking consideration for accessibility. The website workflow is illogical and difficult to follow.

Selected Comments:

Website utilised an excellent, consistent UX design, fit for the target user group and strongly considering accessibility. The website workflow is logical and easy to follow, even for novices.

Buttons: Cancel, Create Report

Footer: Help, Terms of Service, Contact Us, Cookie Policy, Privacy Policy, © 2022 Markit Limited

Figure K.3 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Assessment Feedback Webpage

Create Assessment Feedback (Help and Collaboration):

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'Markit', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users' tabs, and a user profile 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Create Assessment Feedback (Help and Collaboration)'.

Was the presentation of an acceptable quality, encompassing good use of presentation tools and technologies, such as Microsoft PowerPoint, to explain the website's development, and a suitable website demonstration, to show the key functionality has been successfully implemented and is fully functional?

Presentation Quality (Info icon)

Select Comments:
Please drag and drop appropriate comments for this assessment criterion

Search Comments...

Presentation was of an exceptional standard, with excellent use of Microsoft PowerPoint to fully explain the coding behind the website, and a professional and clear demonstration highlighting the successful fulfilling of all website requirements.

Presentation was of an excellent standard, with appropriate use of Microsoft PowerPoint, to explain the coding behind the website, and a professional demonstration, highlighting the successful fulfilling of all website requirements.

Additional Comments:
Please enter any additional comments for this assessment criterion

Panelist Feedback:

Selected Comments:
Professor Michael Smith: "Website utilised a poor and inconsistent UX design, unfit for the target user group and lacking consideration for accessibility. The website workflow is illogical and difficult to follow."
Mrs Julie Light: "Website utilised an excellent, consistent UX design, fit for the target user group and strongly considering accessibility. The website workflow is logical and easy to follow, even for novices."
Additional Comments:
Professor Michael Smith: "Unfortunately, your website lacks a consistent or suitable colour scheme, affecting its accessibility. The workflows seem quite long-winded for the average user to follow - could you not have simplified these?"
Mrs Julie Light: "Great use of fonts and font sizes. I love the way the user interface looks - it appears really stylish!"
Grading:
Professor Michael Smith: 3/10
Mrs Julie Light: 8/10

Selected Comments:

Presentation was of an exceptional standard, with excellent use of Microsoft PowerPoint to fully explain the coding behind the website, and a professional and clear demonstration highlighting the successful fulfilling of all website requirements.

Website UX Design (Info icon)

Select Comments:
Please drag and drop appropriate comments for this assessment criterion

Search Comments...

Website utilised an excellent, consistent UX design, fit for the target user group and strongly considering accessibility. The website workflow is logical and easy to follow, even for novices.

Website utilised a poor and inconsistent UX design, unfit for the target user group and lacking consideration for accessibility. The website workflow is illogical and difficult to follow.

Selected Comments:

Website utilised an excellent, consistent UX design, fit for the target user group and strongly considering accessibility. The website workflow is logical and easy to follow, even for novices.

Buttons: Cancel, Create Report

Footer: Help, Terms of Service, Contact Us, Cookie Policy, Privacy Policy, © 2022 Markit Limited

Figure K.4 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Assessment Feedback (Help and Collaboration) Webpage

Create Assessment Rubric:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and menu items 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A user profile icon and 'Welcome Tug!' are on the right. The main content area is titled 'Create New React Programming Assessment Rubric'. It contains three sections: 'Rubric Criterion' with a text input containing 'Presentation Quality' and a 50-character limit; 'Rubric Description' with a text area containing a sample description; and 'Rubric Weighting' with a text input containing '20%' and a note that weighting must be a whole number. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Create Rubric' buttons. A footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.5 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Assessment Rubric Webpage

Create Assessment Rubric Comment:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and menu items 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A user profile icon and 'Welcome Tug!' are on the right. The main content area is titled 'Create New React Programming Assessment Presentation Quality Rubric Comment'. It contains a 'Rubric Comment' section with a text area containing a sample comment. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Create Comment' buttons. A footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.6 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Assessment Rubric Comment Webpage

Create Assessor:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users' tabs, and a user profile 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Create New Assessor' and contains several form sections: 'Assessor's Name' with a dropdown for 'Professor' and a text input for 'Emily Donaldson'; 'Profile Image URL' with a text input for 'https://www.imagewebsite.com/emily-davidson.png' and an error message; 'Biography' with a text area containing a sample bio; 'Links' with a dropdown for 'LinkedIn' and a text input for 'https://www.linkedin.com/emily-donaldson'; 'Contact' with a dropdown for 'Email Address' and a text input for 'emily.donaldson@kingston.ac.uk'; and 'Password' with a text input and an error message. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Create Assessor' buttons. A footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.7 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Assessor Webpage

Create Group:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users' tabs, and a user profile 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Create New React Programming Assessment Group' and contains several form sections: 'Group Name' with a text input for 'The Wombats' and an error message; 'Profile Image URL' with a text input for 'https://www.imagewebsite.com/group-profile-picture.png' and an error message; 'Biography' with a text area containing a sample bio; and 'Group Members' with a search input 'Search Students...', a list of students including 'Mr Bob Smith', 'Mrs Jane Patel', 'Miss Anne Evans', 'Mr Paul Smith', 'Ms Jessica Jones', 'Mr Gobind Singh', and 'Mr Steve Chan', and a 'Selected Students' list containing 'Miss Kayleigh Smith', 'Mr Ahmed Patel', and 'Mr Bob Jones'. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Create Group' buttons. A footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.8 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Group Webpage

Create Module:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and 'Assessments' highlighted. The main content area is titled 'Create New Module' and contains three form sections: 'Module Code' (input: C15230), 'Module Name' (input: React Programming), and 'Module Leader' (dropdown: Professor Graeme Jones). Each section includes a placeholder text and a validation message. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Create Module' buttons. The footer contains links for Help, Terms of Service, Contact Us, Cookie Policy, and Privacy Policy, along with a copyright notice for 2022 MarkIt Limited.

Figure K.9 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Module Webpage

Create Panel:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and 'Assessments' highlighted. The main content area is titled 'Create New React Programming Assessment Panel' and contains three form sections: 'Panel Name' (input: Owls), 'Profile Image URL' (input: https://www.imagewebsite.com/panel-profile-pkture.png), and 'Biography' (text area). Below the biography is a 'Panel Members' section with a search bar and a list of assessors. The 'Selected Assessors' list includes Professor Jo Riley, Dr Majid Singh, and Mrs Alison Ahmed. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Create Panel' buttons. The footer contains links for Help, Terms of Service, Contact Us, Cookie Policy, and Privacy Policy, along with a copyright notice for 2022 MarkIt Limited.

Figure K.10 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Panel Webpage

Create Student:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and menu items 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', 'Users', and 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Create New Student' and contains several form sections:

- Student's Name:** A dropdown for 'Mr' and a text input for 'John Williams'. A message below states 'Student's name must be at least 10 characters'.
- Profile Image URL:** A text input with 'https://www.imagewebsite.com/johnwilliams.png'. A message below states 'Profile image URL is in an incorrect format'.
- Biography:** A text input with a sample biography: 'I am John and I am Interested in Computing, with my main focus being web development. I am a Second Year (Level 5) Student. Before studying at Kingston University, I went to Newton College, where I completed a Level 2 Diploma in Nursing.'
- Links:** A dropdown for 'Twitter' and a text input with 'https://www.twitter.com/johnwilliams'. A '+ New Link' button is below.
- Contact:** A dropdown for 'Email Address' and a text input with 'john.williams@kingston.ac.uk'. A '+ New Contact' button is below.
- Password:** A text input with '.....'. A message below states 'Password must be more than 8 characters'.

At the bottom of the form are 'Cancel' and 'Create Student' buttons. The footer contains 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.11 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Create Student Webpage

Edit Assessment:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and menu items 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', 'Users', and 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Edit React Programming Assessment' and contains several form sections:

- Assessment Name:** A text input with 'React Programming Assessment'. A message below states 'Assessment name is too short'.
- Assessment Start Date:** A date and time picker showing '23/09/2022 | 15:00'. A message below states 'Assessment start date is in an incorrect format'.
- Assessment End Date:** A date and time picker showing '24/09/2022 | 12:00'. A message below states 'Assessment end date is in an incorrect format'.
- Assessment Image URL:** A text input with 'https://www.imagewebsite.com/react-logo.png'. A message below states 'Assessment image URL is in an incorrect format'.
- Assessment Leader:** A dropdown menu with 'Professor Priti Singh' selected.
- Assessment Module:** A dropdown menu with 'CIS205 - Website Development' selected.
- Assessment Description:** A text input with a detailed description: 'For this assessment, your group is expected to present the website they have created over the past teaching block. The website must fulfil all of the specified requirements, and the presentation should demonstrate that the outlined functionality works successfully, and the associated code supporting the function. The presentation should have appropriate use of a visual aid, such as Microsoft PowerPoint, demonstrate the application and code through the web browser, and be professional.'

At the bottom of the form are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer contains 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.12 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Assessment Webpage

Edit Assessment Feedback:

The wireframe shows a user interface for editing assessment feedback. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and 'Assessments' highlighted, and a user profile 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Edit React Programming Assessment Feedback Report for Group 1 - The Wombats'. It features two assessment criteria: 'Presentation Quality' and 'Website UX Design'. Each criterion has a 'Select Comments' section with a search bar and a list of comments, and an 'Additional Comments' section with a text area. A 'Grade' dropdown is also present for each criterion. At the bottom of the form are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.13 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Assessment Feedback Webpage

Edit Assessment Rubric:

The wireframe shows a user interface for editing an assessment rubric. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and 'Assessments' highlighted, and a user profile 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Edit React Programming Assessment Presentation Quality Rubric'. It features three sections: 'Rubric Criterion' with a text input field containing 'Pitching Skills', 'Rubric Description' with a text area containing a detailed description, and 'Rubric Weighting' with a text input field containing '25%'. Below these sections are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.14 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Assessment Rubric Webpage

Edit Assessment Rubric Comment:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A user profile icon and 'Welcome Tug!' are on the right. The main content area is titled 'Edit React Programming Assessment Presentation Quality Rubric Comment'. It contains a 'Rubric Comment' section with a text input field containing the text: 'Presentation was of an excellent quality, with amazing use of Microsoft PowerPoint to fully explain the frontend and backend code behind the website. Great professional and clear demonstration highlighting the successful fulfilling of all website requirements.' Below the input are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.15 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Assessment Rubric Comment Webpage

Edit Group Profile (Assessment Leader):

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A user profile icon and 'Welcome Tug!' are on the right. The main content area is titled 'Edit Group Profile'. It contains several sections: 'Group Name' with a text input field containing 'The Wombats' and a note 'Group name must be more than 5 characters'; 'Profile Image URL' with a text input field containing 'https://www.imagewebsite.com/group-profile-picture.png' and a note 'Profile image URL is in an incorrect format'; 'Biography' with a text input field containing 'Our group believes in sustainability and accessibility - all things we do as people must be sustainable and inclusive of all. We enjoy playing games in our free time, with some of our favourite games being Minecraft and Fortnite. As a group, we hope to learn new things in React and wish to become full-stack web developers in the future.'; and 'Group Members' with a search input 'Search Students...', a list of members, and a 'Selected Students' list containing 'Miss Kayleigh Smith', 'Mr Ahmed Patel', and 'Mr Bob Jones'. Below the members list is a note 'Group must contain at least one member'. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.16 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Group Profile (Assessment Leader) Webpage

Edit Group Profile (Group Member):

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and menu items 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', 'Users', and 'Modules'. A user profile 'Welcome Tug!' is in the top right. The main content area is titled 'Edit Group Profile' and contains three form sections: 'Group Name' with a text input 'The Wombats' and a note 'Group name must be more than 5 characters'; 'Profile Image URL' with a text input 'https://www.imagewebsite.com/group-profile-picture.png' and a note 'Profile image URL is in an incorrect format'; and 'Biography' with a text area containing a paragraph about sustainability and React. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.17 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Group Profile (Group Member) Webpage

Edit Module:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and menu items 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', 'Users', and 'Modules'. A user profile 'Welcome Tug!' is in the top right. The main content area is titled 'Edit CIS230 - React Programming Module' and contains three form sections: 'Module Code' with a text input 'CIS230' and a note 'Module code must be in the correct format e.g. CI1234'; 'Module Name' with a text input 'React Web Development' and a note 'Module name must be more than 10 characters long'; and 'Module Leader' with a dropdown menu showing 'Dr Mick Evans'. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.18 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Module Webpage

Edit Panel Profile (Assessment Leader):

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and menu items 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A user profile icon shows 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Edit Panel Profile' and contains several sections: 'Panel Name' with a text input field containing 'Owls' and a validation message; 'Profile Image URL' with a text input field containing a URL and a validation message; 'Biography' with a text area containing a paragraph about Professor Graeme Jones and Mrs Janette Caci; and 'Panel Members' with a search input, a list of assessors, and a 'Selected Assessors' list containing 'Professor Jo Riley', 'Dr Majdi Singh', and 'Mrs Alison Ahmed'. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.19 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Panel Profile (Assessment Leader) Webpage

Edit Panel Profile (Panel Member):

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt' and menu items 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A user profile icon shows 'Welcome Tug!'. The main content area is titled 'Edit Panel Profile' and contains several sections: 'Panel Name' with a text input field containing 'Owls' and a validation message; 'Profile Image URL' with a text input field containing a URL and a validation message; 'Biography' with a text area containing a paragraph about Professor Graeme Jones and Mrs Janette Caci. At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.20 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit Panel Profile (Panel Member) Webpage

Edit User Profile:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A user profile is displayed with the following sections:

- Profile Image URL:** A text input field containing 'https://www.imagewebsite.com/user-profile-picture.png' with a message: 'Profile image URL is in an incorrect format'.
- Biography:** A text area containing: 'I am Mark and I am interested in Computer Science, with my main focus being programming. I am a Third Year (Level 6) Student and an academic mentor. Before studying at Kingston University, I went to Kingston College, where I completed a Level 3 Extended Diploma in ICT, specialising in Software Development. Here, I learnt C#.net, HTML, CSS, JavaScript and Visual Basic .net. Additionally, I learnt Cisco IOS for routers and other network devices.'
- Links:** A dropdown menu set to 'Twitter' with a text input 'https://www.twitter.com/twitter-user' and a trash icon. A '+ New Link' button is below.
- Contact:** A dropdown menu set to 'Telephone Number' with a text input '0121 123 4567' and a trash icon. A '+ New Contact' button is below.
- Change Password:** A text input field with a message: 'Password must be more than 8 characters'.
- Confirm Password:** A text input field with a message: 'Password doesn't match'.

At the bottom are 'Cancel' and 'Save Changes' buttons. The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.21 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Edit User Profile Webpage

Feedback Report:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A feedback report is displayed for 'React Programming Assessment Feedback Report for Group 1 - The Wombats'.

Buttons: Edit Feedback, Print

Grade Breakdown	Total Grade: 96%	
Presentation Quality Presentation was of an exceptional standard, with excellent use of Microsoft PowerPoint to fully explain the coding behind the website, and a professional and clear demonstration highlighting the successful fulfilling of all website requirements. Your communication skills were great, and these presentation skills will really help you in the future!	9/10	
Website UX Design User interface colour scheme, button and font size is all excellent, meeting the requirements of the target users. User journey is clear, consistent and simple, making the website easy to use. Great consideration of accessibility within your UX design, incorporating appropriate colour schemes and font styles. Well done!	10/10	
Research Performed Research has been performed to an excellent standard, with complex features being successfully implemented above the scope of the taught lecture content. Website's additional features are relevant to the user, making it easier for them to accomplish their goals. Great work!	10/10	
Best Practice/Code Quality Website successfully follows a suitable design pattern, such as MVC, and all best practices. Code is of an exceptional quality throughout, ensuring it is maintainable and highly readable. It clearly looks as if you have taken great care not only in the design and functionality, but in the code quality.	9/10	
Professionalism All group members remained professional throughout the demonstration, with appropriate visual media to accompany their demonstration. Attire was suitable for the nature of the pitch. Very smart clothes and professional language used throughout.	10/10	

The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.22 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Feedback Report Webpage

Group-Panel Assignments:

Figure K.23 Medium Fidelity Wireframe Group-Panel Assignments Webpage

Homepage:

Figure K.24 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Homepage Webpage

Login:

The wireframe shows a navigation menu at the top with items: MarkIt, Assessments, Groups, Panels, Users, and a user profile icon labeled 'Welcome Tug!'. Below the menu is a central 'Login' form. The form has a title 'Login' and two sections: 'Username:' with a text input field containing 'john.smith@kingston.ac.uk' and a note 'Username must be over 5 characters long'; and 'Password:' with a password input field containing '*****' and a note 'Password must be over 8 characters long'. At the bottom of the form are two buttons: 'Cancel' (with an 'X' icon) and 'Login' (with a checkmark icon). The footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.25 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for Login Webpage

View Assessment Details (Assessor/Student):

The wireframe shows a navigation menu at the top with items: MarkIt, Assessments, Groups, Panels, Users, and a user profile icon labeled 'Welcome Tug!'. Below the menu is the 'View Assessment Details' page for a 'React Programming Assessment'. The page has a breadcrumb trail: 'Details | Groups | Panels | Rubric | Students | Assessors'. The 'Assessment Information' section includes: 'Duration: Wednesday 21st December 2022 9:00am to Friday 23rd December 2022 3:00pm', 'Module: CIS100 - Website Development', and 'Assessment Leader: Professor Graeme Jones (graeme.jones@kingston.ac.uk)'. The 'Assessment Description' section contains two paragraphs of text. The 'Required Functionality' section lists four bullet points. A bolded statement reads: 'This assessment is worth 20% of your final module grade.' Below this is an 'Assessment Feedback' section with a 'View Feedback' button. The footer is identical to the previous wireframe, with links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', and the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.26 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Assessment Details (Assessor/Student) Webpage

View Assessment Details (Assessment Leader):

React Programming Assessment

Details | Groups | Panels | Rubric | Students | Assessors

Assessment Information

Duration: Wednesday 21st December 2022 9:00am to Friday 23rd December 2022 3:00pm
Module: CIS100 - Website Development
Assessment Leader: Professor Graeme Jones (graeme.jones@kingston.ac.uk)

Assessment Description

For this assessment, your group is expected to present the website they have created over the past teaching block. The website must fulfill all of the specified requirements, and the presentation should demonstrate that the outlined functionality works successfully, and the associated code supporting the function. The presentation should have appropriate use of a visual aid, such as Microsoft PowerPoint, demonstrate the application and code through the web browser, and be professional.

All group members must ensure professional attire is worn. Your group presentation will run for approximately 15 minutes, where you are expected to present for 10 minutes, with a further 5 minutes for answering questions from the panel. This presentation will be delivered online via Microsoft Teams. Please attend your timed assessment room via the provided link 15 minutes before your scheduled timeslot, in order to test your equipment (camera, microphone and internet connection) and have a quick rehearsal.

Required Functionality:
 * View, add, edit and delete tasks from task list
 * Assign, re-assign and delete task and user assignments
 * Export and import task lists
 * Login system to authenticate users - user may only see their tasks

This assessment is worth 20% of your final module grade.

Assessment Toolkit

Publish Feedback Export Grades Create Alert Enable Collaboration Edit Group-Panel Assignment

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Figure K.27 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Assessment Details (Assessment Leader) Webpage

View Assessors:

React Programming Assessment

Details | Groups | Panels | Rubric | Students | Assessors

Displaying 16 Assessors

	Mr James Albert jalbert@outlook.com	
	Mrs Amanda Chalke chalkeamanda@apple.com	
	Professor Beryl Daniels beryl.daniel@kingston.ac.uk	
	Dr Martin Goldman goldmanm@barclays.co.uk	
	Ms Julie Johnson jj89@gmail.com	

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Figure K.28 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Assessors Webpage

View Group Profile:

Figure K.29 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Group Profile Webpage

View Groups:

Figure K.30 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Groups Webpage

View Modules:

Figure K.31 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Modules Webpage

View Panel Profile:

Figure K.32 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Panel Profile Webpage

View Panels:

Figure K.33 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Panels Webpage

View Rubric:

Figure K.34 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Rubric Webpage

View Rubric Comments:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A user profile 'Welcome Tug!' is in the top right. The main content area is titled 'React Programming Assessment - Presentation Quality' and includes sub-navigation for 'Details', 'Groups', 'Panels', 'Rubric', 'Students', and 'Assessors'. A '+ New Comment' button is in the top right. The main content displays '5 Rubric Comments' in a list. Each comment row contains a text block and two icons: a pencil and a trash can. The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.35 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Rubric Comments Webpage

View Students:

The wireframe shows a navigation bar with 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users'. A user profile 'Welcome Tug!' is in the top right. The main content area is titled 'React Programming Assessment' and includes sub-navigation for 'Details', 'Groups', 'Panels', 'Rubric', 'Students', and 'Assessors'. A '+ New Student' button is in the top right. The main content displays '247 Students' in a list. Each student row contains a placeholder image, a name, an email address, and a trash can icon. The footer includes 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', 'Privacy Policy', and '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

Figure K.36 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View Students Webpage

View User Profile:

The wireframe shows a user profile page for 'Mr Mark Evans'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with tabs for 'MarkIt', 'Assessments', 'Groups', 'Panels', and 'Users', and a user greeting 'Welcome Tug!'. The profile header includes the name 'Mr Mark Evans' and an 'Edit Profile' button. The main content area is divided into sections: 'Biography' with a paragraph about the user's background in computer science and education; 'Links' with social media and website URLs; 'Contact Me' with email and phone information; and 'Enrollments' listing various modules and groups. A large, light gray placeholder image is on the right side. The footer contains links for 'Help', 'Terms of Service', 'Contact Us', 'Cookie Policy', and 'Privacy Policy', along with the copyright notice '© 2022 MarkIt Limited'.

MarkIt Assessments Groups Panels Users Welcome Tug!

Mr Mark Evans Edit Profile

Biography
I am Mark and I am interested in Computer Science, with my main focus being programming. I am a Third Year (Level 6) Student and an academic mentor. Before studying at Kingston University, I went to Kingston College, where I completed a Level 3 Extended Diploma in ICT, specialising in Software Development. Here, I learnt C#.net, HTML, CSS, JavaScript and Visual Basic .net. Additionally, I learnt Cisco IOS for routers and other network devices.

I have always been enthusiastic about technology, studying GCSE ICT at secondary school, in addition to aiding the mass deployment and technical support of iPads at the school, learning about MDM (mobile device management) amongst other skills. My hobbies include listening to music, attending concerts and playing guitar. I am particularly interested in different, obscure music formats from the past.

Links
Twitter: www.twitter.com/markevans123
Facebook: www.facebook.com/markevans123
Instagram: www.instagram.com/markevans123
Portfolio: www.pebblepad.com/markevans123/portfolio
Website: www.markevans.com

Contact Me
Email: mark.evans@kingston.ac.uk
Phone: 0121 123 4567

Enrollments
Member of Modules: CI4260 - Games Programming, CI5290 - Quantum Computing, CI6340 - Computer Vision
Member of Groups: Group 1 - The Wombats, Group 4 - The Beavers, Group 7 - The Eco-Gamers
Member of Panels: None

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Figure K.37 Medium Fidelity Wireframe for View User Profile Webpage

Wireflow:

Figure K.38 Wireflow for System

Appendix L – Navigation Diagrams

Assessment Leader:

Figure L.1 Navigation Diagram for Assessment Leader

Assessor/Student:

Figure L.2 Navigation Diagram for Assessor and Student

Admin:

Figure L.3 Navigation Diagram for Administrator

Appendix M – Reusable Component and Container Sketches

Reusable Component Sketches:

Layout Container, Tab Container, Tab Item and, Horizontal Card and Horizontal Card Container:

Figure M.1 Reusable Component and Container Sketch for Layout Container, Tab Container, Tab Item and, Horizontal Card and Horizontal Card Container

Button Container, Button, Dual-Panel Structural Container and Section Container:

Figure M.2 Reusable Component and Container Sketch for Button Container, Button, Dual-Panel Structural Container and Section Container

Form Item, Form, Select Form Item Input, Text Input Form Item and Multiline Text Input Form Item:

Figure M.3 Reusable Component and Container Sketch for Form Item, Form, Select Form Item Input, Text Input Form Item and Multiline Text Input Form Item

Draggable Input Form Item Container, Draggable Input Form Item, Droppable Input Form Item Container and Drag/Drop Input Container:

Draggable Input Form Item Container:

Draggable Input Form Item:

Droppable Input Form Item Container:

Drag/Drop Input Container:

Figure M.4 Reusable Component and Container Sketch for Draggable Input Form Item Container, Draggable Input Form Item, Droppable Input Form Item Container and Drag/Drop Input Container

Reports:

Modules Report:

Modules Report :

Figure M.5 Reusable Component and Container Sketch for Modules Report

Assessments Report:

Assessments Report :

Figure M.6 Reusable Component and Container Sketch for Assessments Report

Forms:

Module Form:

Module Form:

Figure M.7 Reusable Component and Container Sketch for Module Form

User Form:

User Form:

Figure M.8 Reusable Component and Container Sketch for User Form

Appendix N – Endpoint Syntax Designs

Alerts:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/alerts – lists all alerts
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/alerts/:aid – return an alert
GET	POST			api/modules/:mid/alerts – list a module’s alerts
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/modules/:mid/alerts/:aid – return a module’s alert
GET				api/users/:uid/alerts – list a user’s alerts
GET				api/users/:uid/alerts/:aid – return a user’s alert
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/alerts – list an assessment’s alerts
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/alerts/:aid – return an assessment’s alert
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/alerts – list an assessment leader’s alerts
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/alerts/:aid – return an assessment leader’s alert
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/alerts – list a user’s assessment’s alerts
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/alerts/:aid – return a user’s assessment’s alert
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/alerts – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s alerts
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/alerts/:aid – return an assessment leader’s assessment’s alert

Table N.1 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Alerts Endpoint

User Types:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/usertypes – lists all user types
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/usertypes/:uid – returns a user type
GET				api/assessments/:aid/usertypes – lists all enrolled user types within an assessment
GET				api/assessments/:aid/usertypes/:uid – return an enrolled user types within an assessment

Table N.2 Endpoint Syntax Designs for User Types Endpoint

Assessments:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/assessments – list all assessments
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid – return an assessment
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments – list a user’s assessments
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid – return a user’s assessment
GET	POST			api/modules/:mid/assessments – list a module’s assessments
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/modules/:mid/assessments/:aid – return a module’s assessment
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/assessments – list an assessment leader’s assessments
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid – return an assessment leader’s assessment

Table N.3 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Assessments Endpoint

Modules:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/modules – list all modules
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/modules/:mid – return a module
GET				api/users/:uid/modules – list a user’s modules
GET				api/users/:uid/modules/:mid – return a user’s module
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/modules – list an assessment leader’s modules
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/modules/:mid – return an assessment leader’s module
GET	POST			api/moduleleader/:lid/modules – list a module leader’s modules
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/moduleleader/:lid/modules/:mid – return a module leader’s module

Table N.4 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Modules Endpoint

Users:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/users – list all users
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/users/:uid – return a user
GET	POST			api/modules/:mid/users – list a module’s users
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/modules/:mid/users/:uid – return a module’s user
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/users – list an assessment’s users
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/users/:uid – return an assessment’s user

Table N.5 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Users Endpoint

Panels:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/panels – list all panels
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/panels/:pid – return a panel
GET	POST			api/modules/:mid/assessments/:aid/panels – list a module’s assessment’s panels
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/modules/:mid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid – return a module’s assessment’s panel
GET				api/users/:uid/panels – list a user’s panels
GET				api/users/:uid/panels/:pid – return a user’s panel
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/panels – list an assessment’s panels
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid – return an assessment’s panel
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/panels – list a user’s assessment’s panels
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid – return a user’s assessment’s panel
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/panels – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s panels
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid – return an assessment leader’s assessment’s panel

Table N.6 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Panels Endpoint

Groups:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/groups – list all groups
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/groups/:gid – return a group
GET	POST			api/modules/:mid/assessments/:aid/groups – list a module’s assessment’s groups
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/modules/:mid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid – return a module’s assessment’s group
GET				api/users/:uid/groups – list a user’s groups
GET				api/users/:uid/groups/:gid – return a user’s group
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/groups – list an assessment’s groups
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid – return an assessment’s group
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/groups – list a user’s assessment’s groups
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid – return a user’s assessment’s group
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/groups – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s groups
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid – return an assessment leader’s assessment’s group

Table N.7 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Groups Endpoint

Panel-Group Assignments:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET				api/panelgroupassignments/:pid – return a panel-group assignment
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/panelgroupassignments – list an assessment’s panel-group assignments
GET		PUR	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/panelgroupassignments/:pid – return an assessment’s panel-group assignment
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/panelgroupassignments – list an assessment’s panel’s group assignments
GET		PUR	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/panelgroupassignments/:pgid – return an assessment’s panel’s group assignment
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/panelgroupassignments – list an assessment’s group’s panel assignments
GET		PUR	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/panelgroupassignments/:pid – return an assessment’s group’s panel assignment
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/panelgroupassignments – list a user’s group’s panel-group assignments
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/panelgroupassignments – list a user’s panel’s panel-group assignments
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/panelgroupassignments – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s panel-group assignments
GET		PUR	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/panelgroupassignments/:pid – return an assessment leader’s assessment’s panel-group assignment

Table N.8 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Panel-Group Assignments Endpoint

Rubrics:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/rubrics – list all assessment’s rubrics
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid – return an assessment’s rubric
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/rubrics – list a user’s assessment’s rubrics
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid – return a user’s assessment’s rubric
GET	POST			api/modules/:mid/assessments/:aid/rubrics – list a module’s assessment’s rubrics
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/modules/:mid/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid – return a module’s assessment’s rubric
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/rubrics – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s rubrics
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid – return an assessment leader’s assessment’s rubric

Table N.9 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Rubrics Endpoint

Rubric Comments:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid/comments – list an assessment’s rubric item’s comments
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid/comments/:cid – return an assessment’s rubric item’s comment
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid/comments – list a user’s assessment’s rubric item’s comments
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid/comments/:cid – return a user’s assessment’s rubric item’s comment
GET	POST			api/modules/:mid/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid/comments – list a module’s assessment’s rubric item’s comments
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/modules/:mid/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid/comments/:cid – return a module’s assessment’s rubric item’s comment
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid/comments – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s rubric item’s comments
GET		PUT	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/rubrics/:rid/comments/:cid – return an assessment leader’s assessment’s rubric item’s comment

Table N.10 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Rubric Comments Endpoint

Feedback:

Endpoint Methods				Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data
GET	POST			api/groups/:gid/feedback – list a group’s feedback
GET		PULL	DELETE	api/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid – return a group’s feedback
GET	POST			api/modules/:mid/groups/:gid/feedback – list a module’s group’s feedback
GET		PULL	DELETE	api/modules/:mid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid – return a module’s group’s feedback
GET				api/users/:uid/groups/:gid/feedback – list a user’s group’s feedback
GET				api/users/:uid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid – return a user’s group’s feedback
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback – list an assessment’s group’s feedback
GET		PULL	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid – return an assessment’s group’s feedback
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback – list a user’s assessment’s group’s
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid – return a user’s assessment’s group’s feedback
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s group’s feedback
GET		PULL	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid – return an assessment leader’s assessment’s group’s feedback
GET	POST			api/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback – list an assessment’s panel’s feedback
GET		PULL	DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid – return an assessment’s panel’s feedback
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback – list a user’s assessment’s panel’s feedback
GET				api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid – return a user’s assessment’s panel’s feedback
GET	POST			api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s panel’s feedback
GET		PULL	DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid – return an assessment leader’s assessment’s panel’s feedback

Table N.11 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Feedback Endpoint

Feedback Comments:

Endpoint Methods		Endpoint Syntax – GET Request Method Return Data	
G ET	PO ST		api/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments – list a group’s feedback comments
G ET		P U DELETE	api/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – return a group’s feedback comment
G ET	PO ST		api/modules/:mid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments – list a module’s group’s feedback comments
G ET		P U DELETE	api/modules/:mid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – return a module’s group’s feedback comment
G ET			api/users/:uid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments – list a user’s group’s feedback comments
G ET			api/users/:uid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – return a user’s group’s feedback comment
G ET	PO ST		api/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments – list an assessment’s group’s feedback comments
G ET		P U DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – return an assessment’s group’s feedback comment
G ET			api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments – list a user’s assessment’s group’s feedback comments
G ET			api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – return a user’s assessment’s group’s feedback comment
G ET	PO ST		api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s group’s feedback comments
G ET		P U DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/groups/:gid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – return an assessment leader’s assessment’s group’s feedback comment
G ET	PO ST		api/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid/comments – list an assessment’s panel’s feedback comments
G ET		P U DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – return an assessment’s panel’s feedback comment
G ET	PO ST		api/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid/comments – list an assessment’s panel’s feedback comments
G ET		P U DELETE	api/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – return an assessment’s panel’s feedback comment
G ET			api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid/comments – list a user’s assessment’s panel’s feedback comments
G ET			api/users/:uid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – return a user’s assessment’s panel’s feedback comment

G ET	PO ST		api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid/comments – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s panel’s feedback comments
G ET		P U T DELETE	api/leader/:lid/assessments/:aid/panels/:pid/feedback/:fid/comments/:cid – list an assessment leader’s assessment’s panel’s feedback comment

Table N.12 Endpoint Syntax Designs for Feedback Comments Endpoint

Appendix O – Initial Request/Response Body Objects

Alert Object:

```
Alert {
  "AlertID": "AlertID",
  "AlertTitle": "AlertTitle",
  "AlertMessage": "AlertMessage",
  "AlertUsergroupID": "AlertUsergroupID",
  "AlertUsergroupName": "AlertUsergroupName",
  "AlertUsergroupDescription": "AlertUsergroupDescription",
  "AlertAssessmentID": "AlertAssessmentID",
  "AlertAssessmentName": "AlertAssessmentName",
  "AlertAssessmentStartdate": "AlertAssessmentStartdate",
  "AlertAssessmentEnddate": "AlertAssessmentEnddate",
  "AlertAssessmentImageURI": "AlertAssessmentImageURI",
  "AlertAssessmentLeaderID": "AlertAssessmentLeaderID",
  "AlertAssessmentLeaderName": "AlertAssessmentLeaderName",
  "AlertAssessmentLeaderEmail": "AlertAssessmentLeaderEmail",
  "AlertAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID":
"AlertAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID",
  "AlertAssessmentModuleID": "AlertAssessmentModuleID",
  "AlertAssessmentModuleCode": "AlertAssessmentModuleCode",
  "AlertAssessmentModuleName": "AlertAssessmentModuleName",
  "AlertAssessmentCreatedDate": "AlertAssessmentCreatedDate",
  "AlertCreatedDate": "AlertCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure O.1 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for Alert Object

UserType Object:

```
UserType {
  "UsertypeID": "UsertypeID",
  "UsertypeName": "UsertypeName",
  "UsertypeDescription": "UsertypeDescription"
}
```

Figure O.2 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for UserType Object

Assessment Object:

```
Assessment {
  "AssessmentID": "AssessmentID",
  "AssessmentName": "AssessmentName",
  "AssessmentStartdate": "AssessmentStartdate",
  "AssessmentEnddate": "AssessmentEnddate",
  "AssessmentImageURI": "AssessmentImageURI",
  "AssessmentLeaderID": "AssessmentLeaderID",
  "AssessmentLeaderName": "AssessmentLeaderName",
  "AssessmentLeaderEmail": "AssessmentLeaderEmail",
  "AssessmentLeaderUsertypeID": "AssessmentLeaderUsertypeID",
  "AssessmentModuleID": "AssessmentModuleID",
  "AssessmentModuleCode": "AssessmentModuleCode",
  "AssessmentModuleName": "AssessmentModuleName",
  "AssessmentCreatedDate": "AssessmentCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure O.3 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for Assessment Object

Module Object:

```
Module {
  "ModuleID": "ModuleID",
  "ModuleCode": "ModuleCode",
  "ModuleName": "ModuleName",
  "ModuleLevel": "ModuleLevel",
  "ModuleDescription": "ModuleDescription",
  "ModuleLeaderID": "ModuleLeaderID",
  "ModuleLeaderTitle": "ModuleLeaderTitle",
  "ModuleLeaderFirstname": "ModuleLeaderFirstname",
  "ModuleLeaderMiddlename": "ModuleLeaderMiddlename",
  "ModuleLeaderLastname": "ModuleLeaderLastname",
  "ModuleLeaderEmail": "ModuleLeaderEmail",
  "ModuleLeaderUsertypeID": "ModuleLeaderUsertypeID",
  "ModuleLeaderUsertypeName": "ModuleLeaderUsertypeName",
  "ModuleLeaderUsertypeDescription":
  "ModuleLeaderUsertypeDescription",
  "ModuleCreatedDate": "ModuleCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure O.4 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for Module Object

User Object:

```
User {
  "UserID": "UserID",
  "UserTitle": "UserTitle",
  "UserFirstname": "UserFirstname",
  "UserMiddlename": "UserMiddlename",
  "UserLastname": "UserLastname",
  "UserBiography": "UserBiography",
  "UserLinks": [
    {
      "UserlinkID": "UserlinkID",
      "UserlinkLinkID": "UserlinkLinkID",
      "UserlinkLinkType": "UserlinkLinkType",
      "UserlinkLinkAddress": "UserlinkLinkAddress",
      "UserlinkCreatedDate": "UserlinkCreatedDate"
    }
  ],
  "UserContacts": [
    {
      "UsercontactID": "UsercontactID",
      "UsercontactContactID": "UsercontactContactID",
      "UsercontactContactType": "UsercontactContactType",
      "UsercontactContactAddress":
"UsercontactContactAddress",
      "UsercontactCreatedDate": "UsercontactCreatedDate"
    }
  ],
  "UserUsertypeID": "UserUsertypeID",
  "UserUsertypeName": "UserUsertypeName",
  "UserUsertypeDescription": "UserUsertypeDescription",
  "UserCreatedDate": "UserCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure O.5 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for User Object

Panel Object:

```
Panel {
  "PanelID": "PanelID",
  "PanelName": "PanelName",
  "PanelImageURI": "PanelImageURI",
  "PanelBiography": "PanelBiography",
  "PanelAssessmentID": "PanelAssessmentID",
  "PanelAssessmentName": "PanelAssessmentName",
  "PanelAssessmentStartdate": "PanelAssessmentStartdate",
  "PanelAssessmentEnddate": "PanelAssessmentEnddate",
  "PanelAssessmentImageURI": "PanelAssessmentImageURI",
  "PanelAssessmentLeaderID": "PanelAssessmentLeaderID",
  "PanelAssessmentLeaderName": "PanelAssessmentLeaderName",
  "PanelAssessmentLeaderEmail": "PanelAssessmentLeaderEmail",
  "PanelAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID":
"PanelAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID",
  "PanelAssessmentModuleID": "PanelAssessmentModuleID",
  "PanelAssessmentModuleCode": "PanelAssessmentModuleCode",
  "PanelAssessmentModuleName": "PanelAssessmentModuleName",
  "PanelAssessmentCreatedDate": "PanelAssessmentCreatedDate",
  "PanelLeaderID": "PanelAssessmentLeaderID",
  "PanelLeaderName": "PanelLeaderName",
  "PanelLeaderEmail": "PanelLeaderEmail",
  "PanelLeaderUsertypeID": "PanelLeaderUsertypeID",
  "PanelMembers": [
    {
      "PanelMemberID": "PanelMemberID",
      "PanelMemberUserID": "PanelMemberUserID",
      "PanelMemberUserName": "PanelMemberUserName",
      "PanelMemberUserEmail": "PanelMemberUserEmail",
      "PanelMemberUsertypeID": "PanelMemberUsertypeID",
      "PanelMemberEnrolledDate": "PanelMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
  ],
  "PanelCreatedDate": "PanelCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure O.6 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for Panel Object

Group Object:

```
Group {
  "GroupID": "GroupID",
  "GroupName": "GroupName",
  "GroupImageURI": "GroupImageURI",
  "GroupBiography": "GroupBiography",
  "GroupAssessmentID": "GroupAssessmentID",
  "GroupAssessmentName": "GroupAssessmentName",
  "GroupAssessmentStartdate": "GroupAssessmentStartdate",
  "GroupAssessmentEnddate": "GroupAssessmentEnddate",
  "GroupAssessmentImageURI": "GroupAssessmentImageURI",
  "GroupAssessmentLeaderID": "GroupAssessmentLeaderID",
  "GroupAssessmentLeaderName": "GroupAssessmentLeaderName",
  "GroupAssessmentLeaderEmail": "GroupAssessmentLeaderEmail",
  "GroupAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID":
"GroupAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID",
  "GroupAssessmentModuleID": "GroupAssessmentModuleID",
  "GroupAssessmentModuleCode": "GroupAssessmentModuleCode",
  "GroupAssessmentModuleName": "GroupAssessmentModuleName",
  "GroupAssessmentCreatedDate": "GroupAssessmentCreatedDate",
  "GroupLeaderID": "GroupLeaderID",
  "GroupLeaderName": "GroupLeaderName",
  "GroupLeaderEmail": "GroupLeaderEmail",
  "GroupLeaderUsertypeID": "GroupLeaderUsertypeID",
  "GroupMembers": [
    {
      "GroupMemberID": "GroupMemberID",
      "GroupMemberUserID": "GroupMemberUserID",
      "GroupMemberUserName": "GroupMemberUserName",
      "GroupMemberUserEmail": "GroupMemberUserEmail",
      "GroupMemberUsertypeID": "GroupMemberUsertypeID",
      "GroupMemberEnrolledDate": "GroupMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
  ],
  "GroupCreatedDate": "GroupCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure O.7 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for Group Object

PanelGroupAssignment Object:

```
PanelGroupAssignment {
  "PanelGroupAssignmentID": "PanelGroupAssignmentID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentStartDate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentStartDate",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentEndDate": "PanelGroupAssignmentEndDate",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelID": "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelName",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelImageURI":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelImageURI",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelBiography":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelBiography",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelAssessmentLeaderID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderName",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderEmail":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderEmail",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderUserTypeID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderUserTypeID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMembers": [
    {
      "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberID",
      "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberUserID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberUserID",
      "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberUserName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberUserName",
      "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberUserEmail":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberUserEmail",
      "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberUserTypeID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberUserTypeID",
      "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberEnrolledDate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
  ],
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelCreatedDate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelCreatedDate",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupID": "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupName",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupImageURI":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupImageURI",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupBiography":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupBiography",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderName",

```

```

    "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderEmail":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderEmail",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderUsertypeID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderUsertypeID",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMembers": [
        {
            "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberID",
            "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberUserID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberUserID",
            "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberUserName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberUserName",
            "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberUserEmail":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberUserEmail",
            "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberUsertypeID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberUsertypeID",
            "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberEnrolledDate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupMemberEnrolledDate"
        }
    ],
    "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupCreatedDate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupCreatedDate",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentID",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentName",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentStartdate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentStartdate",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentEnddate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentEnddate",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentImageURI":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentImageURI",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentLeaderID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentLeaderID",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentLeaderName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentLeaderName",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentLeaderEmail":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentLeaderEmail",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentModuleID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentModuleID",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentModuleCode":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentModuleCode",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentModuleName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentModuleName",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentCreatedDate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentCreatedDate",
    "PanelGroupAssignmentCreatedDate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentCreatedDate"
}

```

Figure O.8 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for PanelGroupAssignment Object

Rubric Object:

```
Rubric {
  "RubricID": "RubricID",
  "RubricCriterion": "RubricCriterion",
  "RubricDescription": "RubricDescription",
  "RubricWeighting": "RubricWeighting",
  "RubricAssessmentID": "RubricAssessmentID",
  "RubricAssessmentName": "RubricAssessmentName",
  "RubricAssessmentStartdate": "RubricAssessmentStartdate",
  "RubricAssessmentEnddate": "RubricAssessmentEnddate",
  "RubricAssessmentImageURI": "RubricAssessmentImageURI",
  "RubricAssessmentLeaderID": "RubricAssessmentLeaderID",
  "RubricAssessmentLeaderName": "RubricAssessmentLeaderName",
  "RubricAssessmentLeaderEmail": "RubricAssessmentLeaderEmail",
  "RubricAssessmentLeaderUserTypeID":
"RubricAssessmentLeaderUserTypeID",
  "RubricAssessmentModuleID": "RubricAssessmentModuleID",
  "RubricAssessmentModuleCode": "RubricAssessmentModuleCode",
  "RubricAssessmentModuleName": "RubricAssessmentModuleName",
  "RubricAssessmentCreatedDate": "RubricAssessmentCreatedDate",
  "RubricCreatedDate": "RubricCreatedDate"
}
```

```
RubricComment {
  "RubricCommentID": "RubricCommentID",
  "RubricCommentDescription": "RubricCommentDescription",
  "RubricCommentRubricID": "RubricCommentRubricID",
  "RubricCommentRubricCriterion":
"RubricCommentRubricCriterion",
  "RubricCommentRubricDescription":
"RubricCommentRubricDescription",
  "RubricCommentRubricWeighting":
"RubricCommentRubricWeighting",
  "RubricCommentRubricCreatedDate":
"RubricCommentRubricCreatedDate",
  "RubricCommentAssessmentID": "RubricCommentAssessmentID",
  "RubricCommentAssessmentName": "RubricCommentAssessmentName",
  "RubricCommentAssessmentStartdate":
"RubricCommentAssessmentStartdate",
  "RubricCommentAssessmentEnddate":
"RubricCommentAssessmentEnddate",
  "RubricCommentAssessmentImageURI":
"RubricCommentAssessmentImageURI",
  "RubricCommentAssessmentLeaderID":
"RubricCommentAssessmentLeaderID",
  "RubricCommentAssessmentLeaderName":
"RubricCommentAssessmentLeaderName",
  "RubricCommentAssessmentLeaderEmail":
"RubricCommentAssessmentLeaderEmail",
}
```

```

    "RubricCommentAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID":
"RubricCommentAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID",
    "RubricCommentAssessmentModuleID":
"RubricCommentAssessmentModuleID",
    "RubricCommentAssessmentModuleCode":
"RubricCommentAssessmentModuleCode",
    "RubricCommentAssessmentModuleName":
"RubricCommentAssessmentModuleName",
    "RubricCommentAssessmentCreatedDate":
"RubricCommentAssessmentCreatedDate",
    "RubricCommentCreatedDate": "RubricCommentCreatedDate"
}

```

Figure O.9 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for Rubric Object

Feedback Object:

```

Feedback {
    "FeedbackID": "FeedbackID",
    "FeedbackGrade": "FeedbackGrade",
    "FeedbackAssessmentID": "FeedbackAssessmentID",
    "FeedbackAssessmentName": "FeedbackAssessmentName",
    "FeedbackAssessmentStartdate": "FeedbackAssessmentStartdate",
    "FeedbackAssessmentEnddate": "FeedbackAssessmentEnddate",
    "FeedbackAssessmentImageURI": "FeedbackAssessmentImageURI",
    "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderID": "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderID",
    "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderName":
"FeedbackAssessmentLeaderName",
    "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderEmail":
"FeedbackAssessmentLeaderEmail",
    "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID":
"FeedbackAssessmentLeaderUsertypeID",
    "FeedbackAssessmentModuleID": "FeedbackAssessmentModuleID",
    "FeedbackAssessmentModuleCode":
"FeedbackAssessmentModuleCode",
    "FeedbackAssessmentModuleName":
"FeedbackAssessmentModuleName",
    "FeedbackAssessmentCreatedDate":
"FeedbackAssessmentCreatedDate",
    "FeedbackGroupID": "FeedbackGroupID",
    "FeedbackGroupName": "FeedbackGroupName",
    "FeedbackGroupImageURI": "FeedbackGroupImageURI",
    "FeedbackGroupLeaderID": "FeedbackGroupLeaderID",
    "FeedbackGroupLeaderName": "FeedbackGroupLeaderName",
    "FeedbackGroupLeaderEmail": "FeedbackGroupLeaderEmail",
    "FeedbackGroupLeaderUsertypeID":
"FeedbackGroupLeaderUsertypeID",
    "FeedbackGroupMembers": [
        {
            "FeedbackGroupMemberID": "FeedbackGroupMemberID",
            "FeedbackGroupMemberUserID":
"FeedbackGroupMemberUserID",

```

```

        "FeedbackGroupMemberUserName":
"FeedbackGroupMemberUserName",
        "FeedbackGroupMemberUserEmail":
"FeedbackGroupMemberUserEmail",
        "FeedbackGroupMemberUsertypeID":
"FeedbackGroupMemberUsertypeID",
        "FeedbackGroupMemberEnrolledDate":
"FeedbackGroupMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
],
    "FeedbackGroupCreatedDate": "FeedbackGroupCreatedDate",
    "FeedbackPanelID": "FeedbackPanelID",
    "FeedbackPanelName": "FeedbackPanelName",
    "FeedbackPanelImageURI": "FeedbackPanelImageURI",
    "FeedbackPanelLeaderID": "FeedbackPanelLeaderID",
    "FeedbackPanelLeaderName": "FeedbackPanelLeaderName",
    "FeedbackPanelLeaderEmail": "FeedbackPanelLeaderEmail",
    "FeedbackPanelLeaderUsertypeID":
"FeedbackPanelLeaderUsertypeID",
    "FeedbackPanelMembers": [
        {
            "FeedbackPanelMemberID": "FeedbackPanelMemberID",
            "FeedbackPanelMemberUserID":
"FeedbackPanelMemberUserID",
            "FeedbackPanelMemberUserName":
"FeedbackPanelMemberUserName",
            "FeedbackPanelMemberUserEmail":
"FeedbackPanelMemberUserEmail",
            "FeedbackPanelMemberUsertypeID":
"FeedbackPanelMemberUsertypeID",
            "FeedbackPanelMemberEnrolledDate":
"FeedbackPanelMemberEnrolledDate"
        }
    ],
    "FeedbackPanelCreatedDate": "FeedbackPanelCreatedDate",
    "FeedbackCreatedDate": "FeedbackCreatedDate"
}

```

Figure O.10 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for Feedback Object

FeedbackComment Object:

```
FeedbackComment {
  "FeedbackCommentID": "FeedbackCommentID",
  "FeedbackCommentAdditionalComments":
"FeedbackCommentAdditionalComments",
  "FeedbackCommentGrade": "FeedbackCommentGrade",
  "FeedbackCommentRubricComments": [
    {
      "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentID":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentID",
      "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentDescription":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentDescription",
      "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentCreatedDate":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentCreatedDate"
    }
  ],
  "FeedbackCommentFeedbackID": "FeedbackCommentFeedbackID",
  "FeedbackCommentFeedbackGrade":
"FeedbackCommentFeedbackGrade",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentID": "FeedbackCommentAssessmentID",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentName":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentName",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentStartdate":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentStartdate",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentEnddate":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentEnddate",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentImageURI":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentImageURI",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentLeaderID":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentLeaderID",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentLeaderName":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentLeaderName",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentLeaderEmail":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentLeaderEmail",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentLeaderUserTypeID":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentLeaderUserTypeID",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentModuleID":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentModuleID",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentModuleCode":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentModuleCode",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentModuleName":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentModuleName",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentCreatedDate":
"FeedbackCommentAssessmentCreatedDate",
  "FeedbackCommentGroupID": "FeedbackCommentGroupID",
  "FeedbackCommentGroupName": "FeedbackCommentGroupName",
  "FeedbackCommentGroupImageURI":
"FeedbackCommentGroupImageURI",
  "FeedbackCommentGroupLeaderID":
"FeedbackCommentGroupLeaderID",
```

```

    "FeedbackCommentGroupLeaderName":
"FeedbackCommentGroupLeaderName",
    "FeedbackCommentGroupLeaderEmail":
"FeedbackCommentGroupLeaderEmail",
    "FeedbackCommentGroupLeaderUsertypeID":
"FeedbackCommentGroupLeaderUsertypeID",
    "FeedbackCommentGroupMembers": [
        {
            "FeedbackCommentGroupMemberID":
"FeedbackCommentGroupMemberID",
            "FeedbackCommentGroupMemberUserID":
"FeedbackCommentGroupMemberUserID",
            "FeedbackCommentGroupMemberUserName":
"FeedbackCommentGroupMemberUserName",
            "FeedbackCommentGroupMemberUserEmail":
"FeedbackCommentGroupMemberUserEmail",
            "FeedbackCommentGroupMemberUsertypeID":
"FeedbackCommentGroupMemberUsertypeID",
            "FeedbackCommentGroupMemberEnrolledDate":
"FeedbackCommentGroupMemberEnrolledDate"
        }
    ],
    "FeedbackCommentGroupCreatedDate":
"FeedbackCommentGroupCreatedDate",
    "FeedbackCommentPanelID": "FeedbackCommentPanelID",
    "FeedbackCommentPanelName": "FeedbackCommentPanelName",
    "FeedbackCommentPanelImageURI":
"FeedbackCommentPanelImageURI",
    "FeedbackCommentPanelLeaderID":
"FeedbackCommentPanelAssessmentLeaderID",
    "FeedbackCommentPanelLeaderName":
"FeedbackCommentPanelLeaderName",
    "FeedbackCommentPanelLeaderEmail":
"FeedbackCommentPanelLeaderEmail",
    "FeedbackCommentPanelLeaderUsertypeID":
"FeedbackCommentPanelLeaderUsertypeID",
    "FeedbackCommentPanelMembers": [
        {
            "FeedbackCommentPanelMemberID":
"FeedbackCommentPanelMemberID",
            "FeedbackCommentPanelMemberUserID":
"FeedbackCommentPanelMemberUserID",
            "FeedbackCommentPanelMemberUserName":
"FeedbackCommentPanelMemberUserName",
            "FeedbackCommentPanelMemberUserEmail":
"FeedbackCommentPanelMemberUserEmail",
            "FeedbackCommentPanelMemberUsertypeID":
"FeedbackCommentPanelMemberUsertypeID",
            "FeedbackCommentPanelMemberEnrolledDate":
"FeedbackCommentPanelMemberEnrolledDate"
        }
    ]

```

```

    ],
    "FeedbackCommentPanelCreatedDate":
"FeedbackCommentPanelCreatedDate",
    "FeedbackCommentFeedbackCreatedDate": "FeedbackCommentFeedbackC
reatedDate",
    "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricID":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricID",
    "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricCriterion":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricCriterion",
    "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricDescription":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricDescription",
    "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricWeighting":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricWeighting",
    "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricCreatedDate":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricCreatedDate",
    "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentCreatedDate":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentCreatedDate"
}

```

Figure O.11 Initial Request/Response Body Object Design for FeedbackComment Object

Appendix P – Final Request/Response Body Objects

Alert Object:

```
Alert {
  "AlertID": "AlertID",
  "AlertTitle": "AlertTitle",
  "AlertMessage": "AlertMessage",
  "AlertUsergroupID": "AlertUsergroupID",
  "AlertUsergroupName": "AlertUsergroupName",
  "AlertUsergroupDescription": "AlertUsergroupDescription",
  "AlertCreatedDate": "AlertCreatedDate",
  "AlertAssessmentID": "AlertAssessmentID"
}
```

Figure P.1 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for Alert Object

UserType Object:

```
UserType {
  "UserTypeID": "UserTypeID",
  "UserTypeName": "UserTypeName",
  "UserTypeDescription": "UserTypeDescription"
}
```

Figure P.2 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for UserType Object

Assessment Object:

```
Assessment {
  "AssessmentID": "AssessmentID",
  "AssessmentName": "AssessmentName",
  "AssessmentStartdate": "AssessmentStartdate",
  "AssessmentEnddate": "AssessmentEnddate",
  "AssessmentImageURI": "AssessmentImageURI",
  "AssessmentLeaderID": "AssessmentLeaderID",
  "AssessmentLeaderName": "AssessmentLeaderName",
  "AssessmentLeaderEmail": "AssessmentLeaderEmail",
  "AssessmentLeaderUserTypeID": "AssessmentLeaderUserTypeID",
  "AssessmentModuleID": "AssessmentModuleID",
  "AssessmentModuleCode": "AssessmentModuleCode",
  "AssessmentModuleName": "AssessmentModuleName",
  "AssessmentCreatedDate": "AssessmentCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure P.3 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for Assessment Object

Module Object:

```
Module {
  "ModuleID": "ModuleID",
  "ModuleCode": "ModuleCode",
  "ModuleName": "ModuleName",
  "ModuleLevel": "ModuleLevel",
  "ModuleDescription": "ModuleDescription",
  "ModuleLeaderID": "ModuleLeaderID",
  "ModuleLeaderTitle": "ModuleLeaderTitle",
  "ModuleLeaderFirstname": "ModuleLeaderFirstname",
  "ModuleLeaderMiddlename": "ModuleLeaderMiddlename",
  "ModuleLeaderLastname": "ModuleLeaderLastname",
  "ModuleLeaderEmail": "ModuleLeaderEmail",
  "ModuleLeaderUsertypeID": "ModuleLeaderUsertypeID",
  "ModuleLeaderUsertypeName": "ModuleLeaderUsertypeName",
  "ModuleLeaderUsertypeDescription":
"ModuleLeaderUsertypeDescription",
  "ModuleCreatedDate": "ModuleCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure P.4 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for Module Object

Panel Object:

```
Panel {
  "PanelID": "PanelID",
  "PanelName": "PanelName",
  "PanelImageURI": "PanelImageURI",
  "PanelBiography": "PanelBiography",
  "PanelAssessmentID": "PanelAssessmentID",
  "PanelLeaderID": "PanelAssessmentLeaderID",
  "PanelLeaderName": "PanelLeaderName",
  "PanelLeaderEmail": "PanelLeaderEmail",
  "PanelLeaderUsertypeID": "PanelLeaderUsertypeID",
  "PanelMembers": [
    {
      "PanelMemberID": "PanelMemberID",
      "PanelMemberUserID": "PanelMemberUserID",
      "PanelMemberUserName": "PanelMemberUserName",
      "PanelMemberUserEmail": "PanelMemberUserEmail",
      "PanelMemberUsertypeID": "PanelMemberUsertypeID",
      "PanelMemberEnrolledDate": "PanelMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
  ],
  "PanelCreatedDate": "PanelCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure P.5 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for Panel Object

User Object:

```
User {
  "UserID": "UserID",
  "UserTitle": "UserTitle",
  "UserFirstname": "UserFirstname",
  "UserMiddlename": "UserMiddlename",
  "UserLastname": "UserLastname",
  "UserBiography": "UserBiography",
  "UserLinks": [
    {
      "UserlinkID": "UserlinkID",
      "UserlinkLinkID": "UserlinkLinkID",
      "UserlinkLinkType": "UserlinkLinkType",
      "UserlinkLinkAddress": "UserlinkLinkAddress",
      "UserlinkCreatedDate": "UserlinkCreatedDate"
    }
  ],
  "UserContacts": [
    {
      "UsercontactID": "UsercontactID",
      "UsercontactContactID": "UsercontactContactID",
      "UsercontactContactType": "UsercontactContactType",
      "UsercontactContactAddress":
"UsercontactContactAddress",
      "UsercontactCreatedDate": "UsercontactCreatedDate"
    }
  ],
  "UserUsertypeID": "UserUsertypeID",
  "UserCreatedDate": "UserCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure P.6 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for User Object

Group Object:

```
Group {
  "GroupID": "GroupID",
  "GroupName": "GroupName",
  "GroupImageURI": "GroupImageURI",
  "GroupBiography": "GroupBiography",
  "GroupAssessmentID": "GroupAssessmentID",
  "GroupLeaderID": "GroupLeaderID",
  "GroupLeaderName": "GroupLeaderName",
  "GroupLeaderEmail": "GroupLeaderEmail",
  "GroupLeaderUsertypeID": "GroupLeaderUsertypeID",
  "GroupMembers": [
    {
      "GroupMemberID": "GroupMemberID",
      "GroupMemberUserID": "GroupMemberUserID",
      "GroupMemberUserName": "GroupMemberUserName",
      "GroupMemberUserEmail": "GroupMemberUserEmail",
      "GroupMemberUsertypeID": "GroupMemberUsertypeID",
      "GroupMemberEnrolledDate": "GroupMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
  ],
  "GroupCreatedDate": "GroupCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure P.7 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for Group Object

PanelGroupAssignment Object:

```
PanelGroupAssignment {
  "PanelGroupAssignmentID": "PanelGroupAssignmentID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentStartDate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentStartDate",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentEndDate": "PanelGroupAssignmentEndDate",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelID": "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelName",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelImageURI":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelImageURI",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelAssessmentLeaderID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderName",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderEmail":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderEmail",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderUserTypeID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentPanelLeaderUserTypeID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupID": "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupName",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupImageURI":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupImageURI",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderName":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderName",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderEmail":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderEmail",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderUserTypeID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentGroupLeaderUserTypeID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentID":
"PanelGroupAssignmentAssessmentID",
  "PanelGroupAssignmentCreatedDate":
"PanelGroupAssignmentCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure P.8 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for PanelGroupAssignment Object

Rubric Object:

```
Rubric {
  "RubricID": "RubricID",
  "RubricCriterion": "RubricCriterion",
  "RubricDescription": "RubricDescription",
  "RubricWeighting": "RubricWeighting",
  "RubricAssessmentID": "RubricAssessmentID",
  "RubricCreatedDate": "RubricCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure P.9 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for Rubric Object

RubricComment Object:

```
RubricComment {
  "RubricCommentID": "RubricCommentID",
  "RubricCommentDescription": "RubricCommentDescription",
  "RubricCommentRubricID": "RubricCommentRubricID",
  "RubricCommentAssessmentID": "RubricCommentAssessmentID",
  "RubricCommentCreatedDate": "RubricCommentCreatedDate"
}
```

Figure P.10 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for RubricComment Object

FeedbackComment Object:

```
FeedbackComment {
  "FeedbackCommentID": "FeedbackCommentID",
  "FeedbackCommentAdditionalComments":
"FeedbackCommentAdditionalComments",
  "FeedbackCommentGrade": "FeedbackCommentGrade",
  "FeedbackCommentRubricComments": [
    {
      "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentID":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentID",
      "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentDescription":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentDescription",
      "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentCreatedDate":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentCreatedDate"
    }
  ],
  "FeedbackCommentFeedbackID": "FeedbackCommentFeedbackID",
  "FeedbackCommentAssessmentID": "FeedbackCommentAssessmentID",
  "FeedbackCommentGroupID": "FeedbackCommentGroupID",
  "FeedbackCommentPanelID": "FeedbackCommentPanelID",
  "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentID":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentID",
  "FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricID":
"FeedbackCommentRubricCommentRubricID",
  "FeedbackCommentFeedbackCreatedDate": "FeedbackCommentFeedbackC
reatedDate"
}
```

Figure P.11 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for FeedbackComment Object

Feedback Object:

```
Feedback {
  "FeedbackID": "FeedbackID",
  "FeedbackGrade": "FeedbackGrade",
  "FeedbackAssessmentID": "FeedbackAssessmentID",
  "FeedbackAssessmentName": "FeedbackAssessmentName",
  "FeedbackAssessmentStartdate": "FeedbackAssessmentStartdate",
  "FeedbackAssessmentEnddate": "FeedbackAssessmentEnddate",
  "FeedbackAssessmentImageURI": "FeedbackAssessmentImageURI",
  "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderID": "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderID",
  "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderName":
"FeedbackAssessmentLeaderName",
  "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderEmail":
"FeedbackAssessmentLeaderEmail",
  "FeedbackAssessmentLeaderUserTypeID":
"FeedbackAssessmentLeaderUserTypeID",
  "FeedbackAssessmentModuleID": "FeedbackAssessmentModuleID",
  "FeedbackAssessmentModuleCode":
"FeedbackAssessmentModuleCode",
  "FeedbackAssessmentModuleName":
"FeedbackAssessmentModuleName",
  "FeedbackGroupID": "FeedbackGroupID",
  "FeedbackGroupName": "FeedbackGroupName",
  "FeedbackGroupLeaderID": "FeedbackGroupLeaderID",
  "FeedbackGroupLeaderName": "FeedbackGroupLeaderName",
  "FeedbackGroupLeaderEmail": "FeedbackGroupLeaderEmail",
  "FeedbackGroupLeaderUserTypeID":
"FeedbackGroupLeaderUserTypeID",
  "FeedbackGroupMembers": [
    {
      "FeedbackGroupMemberID": "FeedbackGroupMemberID",
      "FeedbackGroupMemberUserID":
"FeedbackGroupMemberUserID",
      "FeedbackGroupMemberUserName":
"FeedbackGroupMemberUserName",
      "FeedbackGroupMemberUserEmail":
"FeedbackGroupMemberUserEmail",
      "FeedbackGroupMemberUserTypeID":
"FeedbackGroupMemberUserTypeID",
      "FeedbackGroupMemberEnrolledDate":
"FeedbackGroupMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
  ],
  "FeedbackPanelID": "FeedbackPanelID",
  "FeedbackPanelName": "FeedbackPanelName",
  "FeedbackPanelLeaderID": "FeedbackPanelLeaderID",
  "FeedbackPanelLeaderName": "FeedbackPanelLeaderName",
  "FeedbackPanelLeaderEmail": "FeedbackPanelLeaderEmail",
  "FeedbackPanelLeaderUserTypeID":
"FeedbackPanelLeaderUserTypeID",
  "FeedbackPanelMembers": [
```

```

    {
        "FeedbackPanelMemberID": "FeedbackPanelMemberID",
        "FeedbackPanelMemberUserID":
"FeedbackPanelMemberUserID",
        "FeedbackPanelMemberUserName":
"FeedbackPanelMemberUserName",
        "FeedbackPanelMemberUserEmail":
"FeedbackPanelMemberUserEmail",
        "FeedbackPanelMemberUsertypeID":
"FeedbackPanelMemberUsertypeID",
        "FeedbackPanelMemberEnrolledDate":
"FeedbackPanelMemberEnrolledDate"
    }
],
"FeedbackCreatedDate": "FeedbackCreatedDate"
}

```

Figure P.12 Final Request/Response Body Object Design for Feedback Object

Appendix Q – Entity Relationship Diagrams (ERD)

Initial Entity Relationship Diagrams (ERD):

Create/Edit/View/Delete Alerts:

Figure Q.1 Entity Relationship Diagram for Create/Edit/View/Delete Alerts

Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessment Rubric:

Figure Q.2 Entity Relationship Diagram for Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessment Rubric

Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessment Rubric Comments:

Figure Q.3 Entity Relationship Diagram for Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessment Rubric Comments

Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessments:

Figure Q.4 Entity Relationship Diagram for Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessments

Create/Edit/View Panel-Group Assignments:

Figure Q.5 Entity Relationship Diagram for Create/Edit/View Panel-Group Assignments

Create/Edit/View/Delete Modules:

Figure Q.6 Entity Relationship Diagram for Create/Edit/View/Delete Modules

Create/Edit/View/Delete Student/Assessor (User):

Figure Q.7 Entity Relationship Diagram for Create/Edit/View/Delete Student/Assessor (User)

Appendix R – Data Dictionaries

Initial Data Dictionaries:

Create/Edit/View/Delete Alerts:

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Assessments	AssessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentName	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	AssessmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	AssessmentLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Userassessments	UserassessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserassessmentUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Users	UserID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserTitle	VARCHAR	9	CHECK('Professor','Dr','Mr','Mrs','Miss','Ms')
	UserFirstname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserMiddlename	VARCHAR	35	
	UserLastname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserEmail	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	UserUsertypeID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Usertypes	UsertypeID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsertypeName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	UsertypeDescription	VARCHAR	150	
Alerts	AlertID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY

AlertTitle	VARCHAR	100	NOT NULL
AlertMessage	VARCHAR	500	
AlertUsergroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY

Table R.1 Initial Data Dictionary for Create/Edit/View/Delete Alerts

Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessment Rubric:

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Modules	ModuleID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	ModuleCode	VARCHAR	6	UNIQUE
	ModuleName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	ModuleLevel	INT	1	NOT NULL
	ModuleDescription	VARCHAR	250	
	ModuleLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Assessments	AssessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentName	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	AssessmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	AssessmentLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentTimeslotduration	INT	3	DEFAULT(15)
Userassessments	AssessmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
	UserassessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserassessmentUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Users	UserassessmentEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
	UserID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserTitle	VARCHAR	9	CHECK('Professor','Dr','Mr','Mrs','Miss','Ms')
	UserFirstname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL

	UserMiddlename	VARCHAR	35	
	UserLastname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserEmail	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	UserUsertypeID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Usermodules	UsermodulesID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsermodulesUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Usertypes	UsertypeID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsertypeName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	UsertypeDescription	VARCHAR	150	
Groups	GroupID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	GroupName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	GroupImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	GroupBiography	VARCHAR	500	
	GroupAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Groupmembers	GroupmemberID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	GroupmemberUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupmemberGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupmemberEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Panels	PanelID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	PanelImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	PanelBiography	VARCHAR	500	
	PanelAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())

Panelmembers	PanelmemberID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelmemberUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelmemberGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelmemberEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Panelgroupassignment s	PanelgroupassignmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentPanelID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	PanelgroupassignmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	PanelgroupassignmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Assessmentrubrics	AssessmentrubricID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentrubricCriterion	VARCHAR	100	NOT NULL
	AssessmentrubricDescription	VARCHAR	500	
	AssessmentrubricWeighting	INT	3	CHECK(AssessmentrubricWeighting<=100)
	AssessmentrubricAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentrubricCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())

Table R.2 Initial Data Dictionary for Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessment Rubric

Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessment Rubric Comments:

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Modules	ModuleID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	ModuleCode	VARCHAR	6	UNIQUE
	ModuleName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	ModuleLevel	INT	1	NOT NULL
	ModuleDescription	VARCHAR	250	
	ModuleLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Assessments	AssessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentName	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	AssessmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	AssessmentLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentTimeslotduration	INT	3	DEFAULT(15)
AssessmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())	
Userassessments	UserassessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserassessmentUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Users	UserID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserTitle	VARCHAR	9	CHECK('Professor','Dr','Mr','Mrs','Miss','Ms')
	UserFirstname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserMiddlename	VARCHAR	35	
	UserLastname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserEmail	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	UserUsertypeID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Usermodules	UsermodulesID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsermodulesUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY

	UsermodulesModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Usertypes	UsertypeID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsertypeName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	UsertypeDescription	VARCHAR	150	
Userlinks	UserlinkID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserlinkUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserlinkLinkID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserlinkLinkaddress	VARCHAR	250	NOT NULL
	UserlinkCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Links	LinkID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	LinkType	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
Usercontacts	UsercontactID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsercontactUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsercontactContactID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsercontactContactaddress	VARCHAR	250	NOT NULL
	UsercontactCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Groups	GroupID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	GroupName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	GroupImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	GroupBiography	VARCHAR	500	
	GroupAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Groupmembers	GroupmemberID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	GroupmemberUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupmemberGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupmemberEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Panels	PanelID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	PanelImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)

	PanelBiography	VARCHAR	500	
	PanelAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Panelmembers	PanelmemberID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelmemberUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelmemberGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelmemberEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Panelgroupassignments	PanelgroupassignmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentPanelID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	PanelgroupassignmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	PanelgroupassignmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Assessmentrubrics	AssessmentrubricID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentrubricCriterion	VARCHAR	100	NOT NULL
	AssessmentrubricDescription	VARCHAR	500	
	AssessmentrubricWeighting	INT	3	CHECK(AssessmentrubricWeighting<=100)
	AssessmentrubricAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentrubricCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Assessmentrubriccomments	AssessmentrubriccommentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentrubriccommentComment	VARCHAR	500	
	AssessmentrubriccommentAssessmentrubricID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentrubriccommentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())

Table R.3 Initial Data Dictionary for Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessment Rubric Comments

Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessments:

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Modules	ModuleID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	ModuleCode	VARCHAR	6	UNIQUE
	ModuleName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	ModuleLevel	INT	1	NOT NULL
	ModuleDescription	VARCHAR	250	
	ModuleLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Assessments	AssessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentName	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	AssessmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	AssessmentLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentDescription	VARCHAR	500	
	AssessmentFeedbackvisibility	BOOLEAN	-	NOT NULL
AssessmentCollaborationmode	BOOLEAN	-	NOT NULL	
AssessmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())	
Userassessments	UserassessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserassessmentUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentAssessmentfavourite	BOOLEAN	-	NOT NULL
	UserassessmentEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Users	UserID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserTitle	VARCHAR	9	CHECK('Professor','Dr','Mr','Mrs','Miss','Ms')
	UserFirstname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserMiddlename	VARCHAR	35	

	UserLastname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserEmail	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	UserUsertypeID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Usermodules	UsermodulesID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsermodulesUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Usertypes	UsertypeID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsertypeName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	UsertypeDescription	VARCHAR	150	

Table R.4 Initial Data Dictionary for Create/Edit/View/Delete Assessments

Create/Edit/View Panel-Group Assignments:

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Modules	ModuleID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	ModuleCode	VARCHAR	6	UNIQUE
	ModuleName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	ModuleLevel	INT	1	NOT NULL
	ModuleDescription	VARCHAR	250	
	ModuleLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Assessments	AssessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentName	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	AssessmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	AssessmentLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentTimeslotduration	INT	3	DEFAULT(15)

	AssessmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Userassessments	UserassessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserassessmentUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Users	UserID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserTitle	VARCHAR	9	CHECK('Professor','Dr','Mr','Mrs','Miss','Ms')
	UserFirstname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserMiddlename	VARCHAR	35	
	UserLastname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserEmail	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	UserUsertypeID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Usermodules	UsermodulesID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsermodulesUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Usertypes	UsertypeID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsertypeName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	UsertypeDescription	VARCHAR	150	
Userlinks	UserlinkID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserlinkUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserlinkLinkID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserlinkLinkaddress	VARCHAR	250	NOT NULL
	UserlinkCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Links	LinkID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	LinkType	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
Usercontacts	UsercontactID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsercontactUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsercontactContactID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsercontactContactaddress	VARCHAR	250	NOT NULL
	UsercontactCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())

Groups	GroupID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	GroupName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	GroupImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	GroupBiography	VARCHAR	500	
	GroupAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Groupmembers	GroupmemberID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	GroupmemberUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupmemberGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupmemberEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Panels	PanelID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	PanelImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	PanelBiography	VARCHAR	500	
	PanelAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Panelpmembers	PanelpmemberID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelpmemberUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelpmemberGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelpmemberEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Panelgroupassignment s	PanelgroupassignmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentPanelID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	PanelgroupassignmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL

PanelgroupassignmentCreateddate DATETIME - DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())

Table R.5 Initial Data Dictionary for Create/Edit/View Panel-Group Assignments

Create/Edit/View/Delete Modules:

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Modules	ModuleID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	ModuleCode	VARCHAR	6	UNIQUE
	ModuleName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	ModuleLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Assessments	AssessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentName	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	AssessmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	AssessmentLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Userassessments	UserassessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserassessmentUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Users	UserID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserTitle	VARCHAR	9	CHECK('Professor','Dr','Mr','Mrs','Miss','Ms')
	UserFirstname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserMiddlename	VARCHAR	35	
	UserLastname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserEmail	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	UserUserypeID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY

Usermodules	UsermodulesID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsermodulesUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Usertypes	UsertypeID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsertypeName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	UsertypeDescription	VARCHAR	150	

Table R.6 Initial Data Dictionary for Create/Edit/View/Delete Modules

Create/Edit/View/Delete Student/Assessor (User):

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Modules	ModuleID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	ModuleCode	VARCHAR	6	UNIQUE
	ModuleName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	ModuleLevel	INT	1	NOT NULL
	ModuleDescription	VARCHAR	250	
	ModuleLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Assessments	AssessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentName	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	AssessmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	AssessmentLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Userassessments	UserassessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserassessmentUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY

	UserassessmentEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Users	UserID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserTitle	VARCHAR	9	CHECK('Professor','Dr','Mr','Mrs','Miss','Ms')
	UserFirstname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserLastname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	UserBiography	VARCHAR	500	
	UserPassword	VARCHAR	25	NOT NULL
	UserUsertypeID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Usermodules	UsermodulesID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsermodulesUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Usertypes	UsertypeID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsertypeName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	UsertypeDescription	VARCHAR	150	
Userlinks	UserlinkID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserlinkUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserlinkLinkID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserlinkLinkaddress	VARCHAR	250	NOT NULL
	UserlinkCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Links	LinkID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	LinkType	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
Usercontacts	UsercontactID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsercontactUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsercontactContactID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsercontactContactaddress	VARCHAR	250	NOT NULL
	UsercontactCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Contacts	ContactID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY

ContactType	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
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Table R.7 Initial Data Dictionary for Create/Edit/View/Delete Student/Assessor (User)

Final Data Dictionary:

Table	Column	Data Type	Length	Constraints
Modules	ModuleID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	ModuleCode	VARCHAR	6	UNIQUE
	ModuleName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	ModuleImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	ModuleLevel	INT	1	NOT NULL
	ModuleDescription	VARCHAR	250	
	ModuleLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Assessments	AssessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentName	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	AssessmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	AssessmentImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	AssessmentLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentDescription	VARCHAR	500	
	AssessmentTimeslotduration	INT	3	DEFAULT(15)
	AssessmentCollaborationEnabled	TINYINT	1	NOT NULL DEFAULT(1)
AssessmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())	
Userassessments	UserassessmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserassessmentUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserassessmentsAssessmentfavourite	TINYINT	1	DEFAULT(0)

	UserassessmentEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Users	UserID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserTitle	VARCHAR	9	CHECK('Professor','Dr','Mr','Mrs','Miss','Ms')
	UserFirstname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserMiddlename	VARCHAR	35	
	UserLastname	VARCHAR	35	NOT NULL
	UserEmail	VARCHAR	75	NOT NULL
	UserPassword	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	UserImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	UserBiography	VARHCAR	500	
	UserUserTypeID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserLastaccesseddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
	UserCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Usermodules	UsermodulesID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsermodulesUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesModuleID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsermodulesEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Usertypes	UsertypeID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsertypeName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	UsertypeDescription	VARCHAR	150	
Groups	GroupID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	GroupName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	GroupImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	GroupBiography	VARCHAR	500	
	GroupAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Groupmembers	GroupmemberID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY

	GroupmemberUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupmemberGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	GroupmemberEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Panels	PanelID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	PanelName	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
	PanelImageURI	VARCHAR	500	DEFAULT(https://images.pexels.com/photos/414102/pexels-photo-414102.jpeg)
	PanelBiography	VARCHAR	500	
	PanelAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelLeaderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
	PanelmemberID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
Panelmembers	PanelmemberUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelmemberGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelmemberEnrolleddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
	PanelgroupassignmentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
Panelgroupassignments	PanelgroupassignmentPanelID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	PanelgroupassignmentStartdate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	PanelgroupassignmentEnddate	DATETIME	-	NOT NULL
	PanelgroupassignmentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
	AssessmenttrubicID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
Assessmenttrubrics	AssessmenttrubicCriterion	VARCHAR	100	NOT NULL
	AssessmenttrubicDescription	VARCHAR	500	
	AssessmenttrubicWeighting	INT	3	CHECK(AssessmenttrubicWeighting<=100)
	AssessmenttrubicAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmenttrubicCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Assessmentfeedbacks	AssessmentfeedbackID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY

	AssessmentfeedbackAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackGroupID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackPanelID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackGrade	INT	2	CHECK(AssessmentfeedbackGrade<=10)
	AssessmentfeedbackPublished	TINYINT	1	NOT NULL DEFAULT(0)
	AssessmentfeedbackCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Assessmentrubriccomments	AssessmentrubriccommentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentrubriccommentComment	VARCHAR	500	
	AssessmentrubriccommentAssessmentrubricID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentrubriccommentCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Assessmentfeedbackitemcomments	AssessmentfeedbackitemcommentID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackitemcommentAssessmentrubriccommentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackitemcommentAssessmentfeedbackitemID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
Assessmentfeedbackitems	AssessmentfeedbackitemID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackitemAssessmentfeedbackID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackitemAssessmentrubricID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackitemAssessmentrubriccommentID	INT	5	NOT NULL
	AssessmentfeedbackitemAdditionalcomments	VARCHAR	500	FOREIGN KEY
	AssessmentfeedbackitemGrade	INT	2	CHECK(AssessmentfeedbackitemGrade<=10)
	AssessmentfeedbackitemCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Alerts	AlertID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	AlertTitle	VARCHAR	100	NOT NULL
	AlertMessage	VARCHAR	500	
	AlertAssessmentID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AlertUserTypeID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AlertCreatorID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	AlertCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Messages	MessageID	INT	9	PRIMARY KEY
	MessageContent	VARCHAR	500	NOT NULL

	MessageSenderID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	MessageRecipientID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	MessageCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Contacts	ContactID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	ContactType	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
Links	LinkID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	LinkType	VARCHAR	50	NOT NULL
Usercontacts	UsercontactID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UsercontactUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsercontactContactID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UsercontactContactaddress	VARCHAR	250	NOT NULL
	UsercontactCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())
Userlinks	UserlinkID	INT	5	PRIMARY KEY
	UserlinkUserID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserlinkContactID	INT	5	FOREIGN KEY
	UserlinkContactaddress	VARCHAR	250	NOT NULL
	UserlinkCreateddate	DATETIME	-	DEFAULT(CURRENT_TIMESTAMP())

Table R.8 Final Data Dictionary for System

Appendix S – Activity Diagrams

View User Profile:

Figure S.1 Activity Diagram for View User Profile

Edit User Profile:

Figure S.2 Activity Diagram for Edit User Profile

View Profile:

Figure S.3 Activity Diagram for View Profile

Edit Personal Profile:

Figure S.4 Activity Diagram for Edit Personal Profile

View Groups:

Figure S.5 Activity Diagram for View Groups

Delete Group:

Figure S.6 Activity Diagram for Delete Group

View Group Profile:

Figure S.7 Activity Diagram for View Group Profile

Create Group:

Figure S.8 Activity Diagram for Create Group

Edit Group:

Figure S.9 Activity Diagram for Edit Group

View Panels:

Figure S.10 Activity Diagram for View Panels

Delete Panel:

Figure S.11 Activity Diagram for Delete Panel

View Panel Profile:

Figure S.12 Activity Diagram for View Panel Profile

Create Panel:

Figure S.13 Activity Diagram for Create Panel

Edit Panel:

Figure S.14 Activity Diagram for Edit Panel

View Rubric:

Figure S.15 Activity Diagram for View Rubric

Delete Rubric:

Figure S.16 Activity Diagram for Delete Rubric

Create Rubric:

Figure S.17 Activity Diagram for Create Rubric

Edit Rubric:

Figure S.18 Activity Diagram for Edit Rubric

View Rubric Item:

Figure S.19 Activity Diagram for View Rubric Item

Create Rubric Item:

Figure S.20 Activity Diagram for Create Rubric Item

Edit Rubric Item:

Figure S.21 Activity Diagram for Edit Rubric Item

Delete Rubric Item:

Figure S.22 Activity Diagram for Delete Rubric Item

View Feedback:

Figure S.23 Activity Diagram for View Feedback

View Feedback:

Figure S.24 Activity Diagram for View Feedback

Create Feedback:

Figure S.25 Activity Diagram for Create Feedback

Assign Groups to Panel:

Figure S.26 Activity Diagram for Assign Groups to Panel

View Assessment:

Figure S.27 Activity Diagram for View Assessment

Delete Assessment:

Figure S.28 Activity Diagram for Delete Assessment

Edit Assessment:

Figure S.29 Activity Diagram for Edit Assessment

Publish Assessment Feedback:

Figure S.30 Activity Diagram for Publish Assessment Feedback

Unpublish Assessment Feedback:

Figure S.31 Activity Diagram for Unpublish Assessment Feedback

Export Grades:

Figure S.32 Activity Diagram for Export Grades

View Assessment Students:

Figure S.33 Activity Diagram for View Assessment Students

Create Assessment Student:

Figure S.34 Activity Diagram for Create Assessment Student

Delete Assessment Student:

Figure S.35 Activity Diagram for Delete Assessment Student

Create Assessment Assessor:

Figure S.36 Activity Diagram for Create Assessment Assessor

View Assessment Assessors:

Figure S.37 Activity Diagram for View Assessment Assessors

Delete Assessment Assessors:

Figure S.38 Activity Diagram for Delete Assessment Assessors

Create Assessment:

Figure S.39 Activity Diagram for Create Assessment

View Assessments:

Figure S.40 Activity Diagram for View Assessments

Favourite Assessment:

Figure S.41 Activity Diagram for Favourite Assessment

Unfavourite Assessment:

Figure S.42 Activity Diagram for Unfavourite Assessment

Create Module:

Figure S.43 Activity Diagram for Create Module

View Module:

Figure S.44 Activity Diagram for View Module

Edit Module:

Figure S.45 Activity Diagram for Edit Module

Delete Module:

Figure S.46 Activity Diagram for Delete Module

Appendix T – Sequence Diagrams

Edit User Profile:

Figure T.1 Sequence Diagram for Edit User Profile

Edit Personal Profile:

Figure T.2 Sequence Diagram for Edit Personal Profile

Create Group:

Figure T.3 Sequence Diagram for Create Group

Edit Group:

Figure T.4 Sequence Diagram for Edit Group

Create Panel:

Figure T.5 Sequence Diagram for Create Panel

Edit Panel:

Figure T.6 Sequence Diagram for Edit Panel

Create Rubric:

Figure T.7 Sequence Diagram for Create Rubric

Edit Rubric:

Figure T.8 Sequence Diagram for Edit Rubric

Create Rubric Item:

Figure T.9 Sequence Diagram for Create Rubric Item

Edit Rubric Item:

Figure T.10 Sequence Diagram for Edit Rubric Item

Edit Feedback:

Figure T.11 Sequence Diagram for Edit Feedback

Create Feedback:

Figure T.12 Sequence Diagram for Create Feedback

Assign Groups to Panel:

Figure T.13 Sequence Diagram for Assign Groups to Panel

Edit Assessment:

Figure T.14 Sequence Diagram for Edit Assessment

Export Grades:

Figure T.15 Sequence Diagram for Export Grades

Create Assessment Student:

Figure T.16 Sequence Diagram for Create Assessment Student

Create Assessment Assessor:

Figure T.17 Sequence Diagram for Create Assessment Assessor

Create Assessment:

Figure T.18 Sequence Diagram for Create Assessment

Create Module:

Figure T.19 Sequence Diagram for Create Module

Edit Module:

Figure T.20 Sequence Diagram for Edit Module

Appendix U – Integration Testing

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
1	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of User records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON User objects, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "UserID": 1, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Cherianne", "UserMiddlename": "Mella", "UserLastname": "Girvan", "UserEmail": "" }, { "UserID": 2, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Olivette", "UserMiddlename": "Galen", "UserLastname": "Temprell", "UserEmail": "" }, ...]	Pass
2	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single User record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON User object, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "UserID": 1, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Cherianne", "UserMiddlename": "Mella", "UserLastname": "Girvan", "UserEmail": "" },]]	Pass
3	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of User records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessors HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON User objects, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – records of type user with role 'assessor' must be created
4	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single User record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessors/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON User object, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – user of ID 1 is not of role 'assessor'
5	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of User records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessmentleaders HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON User objects, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "UserID": 1, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Cherianne", "UserMiddlename": "Mella", "UserLastname": "Girvan", "UserEmail": "" }, { "UserID": 2, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Olivette", "UserMiddlename": "Galen", "UserLastname": "Temprell", "UserEmail": "" }, ...]	Pass

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
6	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single User record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessors/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON User object, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "UserID": 1, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Cherianne", "UserMiddlename": "Mella", "UserLastname": "Girvan", "UserEmail": "" }]	Pass
7	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of User records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/students HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON User objects, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "StudentID": 11, "StudentTitle": "Mr", "StudentFirstname": "Silva", "StudentMiddlename": "Llywellyn", "StudentLastname": "Oxberry", "StudentEmail": "" }, { "StudentID": 12, "StudentTitle": "Ms", "StudentFirstname": "Gerhardine", "StudentMiddlename": "Neala", "StudentLastname": "Fautley", "StudentEmail": "" }]...]	Pass
8	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single User record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/students/11 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 11 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON User object, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "StudentID": 11, "StudentTitle": "Mr", "StudentFirstname": "Silva", "StudentMiddlename": "Llywellyn", "StudentLastname": "Oxberry", "StudentEmail": "" }]	Pass
9	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of User records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/administrators HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON User objects, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – records of type user with role 'assessor' must be created
10	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single User record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/administrators/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON User object, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – user of ID 1 is not of role 'administrator'
11	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of User records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON User objects, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "UserID": 6, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Alexi", "UserMiddlename": "Pam", "UserLastname": "Goulborn" }, { "UserID": 35, "UserTitle": "Mrs", "UserFirstname": "Jenelle", "UserMiddlename": "Conny", "UserLastname": "Rowlstone" }]...]	Pass

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
12	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of User records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules/1/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON User objects, containing fields {"UserID", "UserTitle", "UserFirstname", "UserMiddlename", "UserLastname", "UserEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "UserID": 1, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Cherianne", "UserMiddlename": "Mella", "UserLastname": "Girvan" }, { "UserID": 8, "UserTitle": "Professor", "UserFirstname": "Cassy", "UserMiddlename": "Nananne", "UserLastname": "Chiswell" }, ...]	Pass
13	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Module records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Module objects, containing fields {"ModuleID", "ModuleCode", "ModuleName", "ModuleLevel", "ModuleDescription", "ModuleLeaderID", "ModuleLeaderFullName"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "ModuleID": 1, "ModuleCode": "QJ3349", "ModuleName": "IBM iSeries", "ModuleLevel": 0, "ModuleDescription": null, "ModuleLeaderID": null, "UserTitle": null, "UserFirstname": null, "UserMiddlename": null, "UserLastname": null, "UserEmail": null, "UserTypeID": null, "UserTypeName": null, "UserTypeDescription": null }, { "ModuleID": 2, "ModuleCode": "KU2915", "ModuleName": "Flash", "ModuleLevel": 0, "ModuleDescription": null, "ModuleLeaderID": null, "UserTitle": null, "UserFirstname": null, "UserMiddlename": null, "UserLastname": null, "UserEmail": null, "UserTypeID": null, "UserTypeName": null, "UserTypeDescription": null }]	Fail – incorrect returned attributes
14	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Module record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Module object, containing fields {"ModuleID", "ModuleCode", "ModuleName", "ModuleLevel", "ModuleDescription", "ModuleLeaderID", "ModuleLeaderFullName"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: [{ "ModuleID": 1, "ModuleCode": "QJ3349", "ModuleName": "IBM iSeries", "ModuleLevel": 0, "ModuleDescription": null, "ModuleLeaderID": null, "UserTitle": null, "UserFirstname": null, "UserMiddlename": null, "UserLastname": null, "UserEmail": null, "UserTypeID": null, "UserTypeName": null, "UserTypeDescription": null }]	Fail – incorrect returned attributes
15	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Module records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1/modules HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Module objects, containing fields {"ModuleID", "ModuleCode", "ModuleName", "ModuleLevel", "ModuleDescription", "ModuleLeaderID", "ModuleLeaderFullName"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "ModuleID": 4, "ModuleCode": "XK3040", "ModuleName": "Videography" }, { "ModuleID": 4, "ModuleCode": "XK3040", "ModuleName": "Videography" }, ...]	Fail – incorrect returned attributes

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
16	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Module record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1/modules/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Module object, containing fields {"ModuleID", "ModuleCode", "ModuleName", "ModuleLevel", "ModuleDescription", "ModuleLeaderID", "ModuleLeaderFullName"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "ModuleID": 1, "ModuleCode": "QJ3349", "ModuleName": "IBM iSeries" }]	Fail – incorrect returned attributes
17	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Assessment records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Assessment objects, containing fields {"AssessmentID", "AssessmentName", "AssessmentStartdate", "AssessmentEnddate", "AssessmentImageURI", "AssessmentLeaderID", "AssessmentModuleCode", "AssessmentModuleName", "AssessmentLeaderName"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "AssessmentID": 1, "AssessmentName": "React Native LFT App Assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-09-26T00:43:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-10-22T00:00:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/167x100.png/ddd/000000", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 4, "AssessmentModuleCode": "XK3040", "AssessmentModuleName": "Videography", "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Cherieanne Girvan" }, { "AssessmentID": 2, "AssessmentName": "Universal leading edge analyzer assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-10-12T16:18:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-11-09T07:19:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/194x100.png/ddd/000000", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 37, "AssessmentModuleCode": "SD6043", "AssessmentModuleName": "Software Development Practice", "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Cherieanne Girvan" }]...	Pass
18	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Assessment record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Assessment object, containing fields {"AssessmentID", "AssessmentName", "AssessmentStartdate", "AssessmentEnddate", "AssessmentImageURI", "AssessmentLeaderID", "AssessmentModuleCode", "AssessmentModuleName", "AssessmentLeaderName"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "AssessmentID": 1, "AssessmentName": "React Native LFT App Assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-09-26T00:43:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-10-22T00:00:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/167x100.png/ddd/000000", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 4, "AssessmentModuleCode": "XK3040", "AssessmentModuleName": "Videography", "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Cherieanne Girvan" }]	Pass

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
19	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Assessment records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/leader/1/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Assessment objects, containing fields {"AssessmentID", "AssessmentName", "AssessmentStartdate", "AssessmentEnddate", "AssessmentImageURI", "AssessmentLeaderID", "AssessmentModuleCode", "AssessmentModuleName", "AssessmentLeaderName"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "AssessmentID": 1, "AssessmentName": "React Native LFT App Assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-09-26T00:43:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-10-22T00:00:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/167x100.png/ddd/000000", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 4, "AssessmentModuleCode": "XK3040", "AssessmentModuleName": "Videography", "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Cherieanne Girvan" }, { "AssessmentID": 2, "AssessmentName": "Universal leading edge analyzer assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-10-12T16:18:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-11-09T07:19:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/194x100.png/ddddd/000000", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 37, "AssessmentModuleCode": "SD6043", "AssessmentModuleName": "Software Development Practice", "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Cherieanne Girvan" }...]	Pass
20	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Assessment records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Assessment objects, containing fields {"AssessmentID", "AssessmentName", "AssessmentStartdate", "AssessmentEnddate", "AssessmentImageURI", "AssessmentLeaderID", "AssessmentModuleCode", "AssessmentModuleName", "AssessmentLeaderName"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "AssessmentID": 35, "AssessmentName": "Configurable asynchronous projection assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-09-30T00:07:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-11-05T23:10:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/215x100.png/cc0000/ffffff", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 24, "AssessmentModuleCode": "SF8844", "AssessmentModuleName": "BPWin", "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Cherieanne Girvan", "AssessmentEnrollmentID": 60, "AssessmentFavourite": 0 }, { "AssessmentID": 1, "AssessmentName": "React Native LFT App Assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-09-26T00:43:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-10-22T00:00:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/167x100.png/ddd/000000", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 4, "AssessmentModuleCode": "XK3040", "AssessmentModuleName": "Videography", "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Cherieanne Girvan", "AssessmentEnrollmentID": 109, "AssessmentFavourite": 0 }...]	Pass

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
21	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Assessment records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules/1/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Assessment objects, containing fields {"AssessmentID", "AssessmentName", "AssessmentStartdate", "AssessmentEnddate", "AssessmentImageURI", "AssessmentLeaderID", "AssessmentModuleCode", "AssessmentModuleName", "AssessmentLeaderName"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "AssessmentID": 3, "AssessmentName": "Centralized well-modulated paradigm assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-09-25T05:20:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-10-15T07:56:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/189x100.png/cc0000/ffffff", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 1, "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Cherieanne Girvan" }, { "AssessmentID": 126, "AssessmentName": "Programmable actuating knowledge base assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-09-14T22:42:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-11-10T10:46:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/193x100.png/ffa444/ffffff", "AssessmentLeaderID": 8, "AssessmentModuleID": 1, "AssessmentLeaderName": "Professor Cassy Chiswell" }, ...]	Pass
22	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Panel records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Panel objects, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "PanelID": 1, "PanelName": "test panel", "PanelImageURI": "https://www.poop.com/image.png", "PanelBiography": "goat", "PanelAssessmentID": 1, "PanelLeaderID": 2, "PanelLeaderName": "Dr Olivette Temprell", "PanelLeaderEmail": "" }, { "PanelID": 2, "PanelName": "1234", "PanelImageURI": "https://www.box.com/image.png", "PanelBiography": "bio goes here", "PanelAssessmentID": 3, "PanelLeaderID": 4, "PanelLeaderName": "Dr Anabelle Quantrell", "PanelLeaderEmail": "" }, ...]	Pass
23	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Panel record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/panels/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Panel object, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "PanelID": 1, "PanelName": "test panel", "PanelImageURI": "https://www.poop.com/image.png", "PanelBiography": "goat", "PanelAssessmentID": 1, "PanelLeaderID": 2, "PanelLeaderName": "Dr Olivette Temprell", "PanelLeaderEmail": "" }, ...]	Pass

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
24	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Panel records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules/1/assessments/1/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Panel objects, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – no panels have been created for assessment 1 and/or assessment 1 is not associated with module 1
25	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Panel record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules/1/assessments/1/panels/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Panel object, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – no panels have been created for assessment 1 and/or assessment 1 is not associated with module 1 and no panel 1 exists
26	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Panel records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Panel objects, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – user 1 is not enrolled in any panels
27	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Panel record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1/panels/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Panel object, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – user 1 is not enrolled in panel 1

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
28	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Panel records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Panel objects, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "PanelID": 1, "PanelName": "test panel", "PanelImageURI": "https://www.poop.com/image.png", "PanelBiography": "goat", "PanelAssessmentID": 1, "PanelLeaderID": 2, "PanelLeaderName": "Dr Olivette Temprell", "PanelLeaderEmail": "" }, { "PanelID": 5, "PanelName": "testing 123", "PanelImageURI": "https://www.poop.com/image.png", "PanelBiography": "goat", "PanelAssessmentID": 1, "PanelLeaderID": 2, "PanelLeaderName": "Dr Olivette Temprell", "PanelLeaderEmail": "" }]	Pass
29	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Panel record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/panels/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Panel object, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – panel 1 is not enrolled in assessment
30	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Panel records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1/assessments/1/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Panel objects, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – user is not enrolled on assessment 1 and/or assessment 1 does not have any panels
31	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Panel record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1/assessments/1/panels/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Panel object, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – user is not enrolled on assessment 1 and/or assessment 1 does not have any panels and/or panel 1 is not enrolled on assessment 1

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
32	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Panel records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/leader/1/assessments/1/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Panel objects, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – leader is not enrolled on assessment 1 and/or assessment 1 does not have any panels
33	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Panel record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/leader/1/assessments/1/panels/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Panel object, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – leader is not enrolled on assessment 1 and/or assessment 1 does not have any panels and/or panel 1 is not enrolled on assessment 1
34	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Group records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/groups HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Group objects, containing fields {"GroupID", "GroupName", "GroupImageURI", "GroupBiography", "GroupAssessmentID", "GroupLeaderID", "GroupLeaderName", "GroupLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – no groups have been created
35	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Group record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/groups/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Group object, containing fields {"GroupID", "GroupName", "GroupImageURI", "GroupBiography", "GroupAssessmentID", "GroupLeaderID", "GroupLeaderName", "GroupLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – group 1 has not been created

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
36	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Group records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1/groups HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Group objects, containing fields {"GroupID", "GroupName", "GroupImageURI", "GroupBiography", "GroupAssessmentID", "GroupLeaderID", "GroupLeaderName", "GroupLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "Failed to execute query: You have an error in your SQL syntax; check the manual that corresponds to your MariaDB server version for the right syntax to use near 'DISTINCT Userassessments INNER JOIN Groups LEFT JOIN Users ON Groups.GroupLea...' at line 1" }	Fail – error within SQL syntax
37	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Group record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/users/1/groups/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Group object, containing fields {"GroupID", "GroupName", "GroupImageURI", "GroupBiography", "GroupAssessmentID", "GroupLeaderID", "GroupLeaderName", "GroupLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "Failed to execute query: You have an error in your SQL syntax; check the manual that corresponds to your MariaDB server version for the right syntax to use near 'DISTINCT Userassessments INNER JOIN Groups LEFT JOIN Users ON Groups.GroupLea...' at line 1" }	Fail – error within SQL syntax
38	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Group records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/groups HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Group objects, containing fields {"GroupID", "GroupName", "GroupImageURI", "GroupBiography", "GroupAssessmentID", "GroupLeaderID", "GroupLeaderName", "GroupLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – no groups exist and/or have been enrolled in assessment 1
39	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Group record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/groups/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Group object, containing fields {"GroupID", "GroupName", "GroupImageURI", "GroupBiography", "GroupAssessmentID", "GroupLeaderID", "GroupLeaderName", "GroupLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "Failed to execute query: You have an error in your SQL syntax; check the manual that corresponds to your MariaDB server version for the right syntax to use near 'DISTINCT Userassessments INNER JOIN Groups LEFT JOIN Users ON Groups.GroupLea...' at line 1" }	Fail – group 1 does not exist and/or has not been enrolled in assessment 1
40	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Rubric records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/rubrics HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Rubric objects, containing fields {"AssessmentrubricID", "AssessmentrubricCtierion", "AssessmentrubricDescription", "AssessmentrubricWeighting", "AssessmentrubricAssessmentID"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – no rubrics have been added to assessment 1

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
41	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Rubric record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/rubrics/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Rubric object, containing fields {"AssessmentrubricID", "AssessmentrubricCtierion", "AssessmentrubricDescription", "AssessmentrubricWeighting", "AssessmentrubricAssessmentID"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – rubric 1 does not exist and/or has not been added to assessment 1
42	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of Comment records	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/rubrics/1/comments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one or more JSON Comment objects, containing fields {"AssessmentrubriccommentID", "AssessmentrubriccommentComment", "AssessmentrubriccommentAssessmentrubricID"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – no comments exist and/or rubric 1 does not contain comments and/or assessment 1 does not exist
43	Test backend API retrieve (GET) method successfully returns an array of a single Comment record with the corresponding URL ID value	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/rubrics/1/comments/1 HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: 1;1;1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Comment object, containing fields {"AssessmentrubriccommentID", "AssessmentrubriccommentComment", "AssessmentrubriccommentAssessmentrubricID"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "No record(s) found" }	Fail – no comments exist and/or rubric 1 does not contain comments and/or assessment 1 does not exist and/or comment 1 does not exist and/or is not enrolled in assessment 1

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
48	Test backend API create (POST) method successfully inserts a new Group record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1/groups HTTP Method: POST URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: { "GroupName": "Test Group 2", "GroupImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "GroupBiography": "Test group 2 biography...", "GroupAssessmentID": 1, "GroupLeaderID": 1 }	Status Code: 201 Created Body: Contains an array of one JSON Group object, with next ID value, containing fields {"GroupID", "GroupName", "GroupImageURI", "GroupBiography", "GroupAssessmentID", "GroupLeaderID", "GroupLeaderName", "GroupLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: Could not get response - Error: read ECONNRESET Body: N/A	Fail – could not insert record, due to fatal server-side error
49	Test backend API create (POST) method successfully inserts a new Module record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules HTTP Method: POST URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: { "ModuleCode": "C14123", "ModuleName": "Test module 1", "ModuleImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "ModuleLevel": 4, "ModuleDescription": "Test module 1 description...", "ModuleLeaderID": 1 }	Status Code: 201 Created Body: Contains an array of one JSON Module object, with next ID value, containing fields {"ModuleID", "ModuleCode", "ModuleName", "ModuleLevel", "ModuleDescription", "ModuleLeaderID", "ModuleLeaderFullname"}	Status Code: 201 Created Body: { "ModuleID": 55, "ModuleCode": "C14123", "ModuleName": "Test module 1", "ModuleLevel": 4, "ModuleDescription": "Test module 1 description...", "ModuleLeaderID": 1, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Cherianne", "UserMiddlename": "Mella", "UserLastname": "Girvan", "UserEmail": "", "UserTypeID": 2, "UserTypeName": "Assessment Leader", "UserTypeDescription": "An academic responsible for setting an assessment" }	Fail – returned object does not match that expected
50	Test backend API create (POST) method successfully inserts a new Rubric record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/rubrics HTTP Method: POST URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: { "AssessmentrubricCriterion": "Test rubric criterion 1 criterion", "AssessmentrubricDescription": "Test rubric criterion 1 description", "AssessmentrubricWeighting": 100, "AssessmentrubricAssessmentID": 1 }	Status Code: 201 Created Body: Contains an array of one JSON Rubric object, with next ID value, containing fields {"AssessmentrubricID", "AssessmentrubricCriterion", "AssessmentrubricDescription", "AssessmentrubricWeighting", "AssessmentrubricAssessmentID"}	Status Code: 201 Created Body: { "AssessmentrubricID": 1, "AssessmentrubricCriterion": "Test rubric criterion 1 criterion", "AssessmentrubricDescription": "Test rubric criterion 1 description", "AssessmentrubricWeighting": 100 }	Fail – fails to return AssessmentrubricAssessmentID attribute
51	Test backend API create (POST) method successfully inserts a new Comment record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/comments HTTP Method: POST URL Parameters: n/a Request Body: { "AssessmentrubriccommentComment": "Test assessment rubric comment 1 comment", "AssessmentrubriccommentAssessmentrubricID": 1 }	Status Code: 201 Created Body: Contains an array of one JSON Comment object, with next ID value, containing fields {"AssessmentrubriccommentID", "AssessmentrubriccommentComment", "AssessmentrubriccommentAssessmentrubricID"}	Status Code: 201 Created Body: { "AssessmentrubriccommentID": 1, "AssessmentrubriccommentComment": "Test assessment rubric comment 1 comment", "AssessmentrubriccommentAssessmentrubricID": 1 }	Pass

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
52	Test backend API update (POST) method successfully modifies an existing Assessment record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/1 HTTP Method: PUT URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: { "AssessmentName": "Test Assessment 1 Update", "AssessmentStartdate": "2020-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2020-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "https://www.testupdate.com/image.png", "AssessmentLeaderID": 2, "AssessmentModuleID": 2 }	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Assessment object, containing fields {"AssessmentID", "AssessmentName", "AssessmentStartdate", "AssessmentEnddate", "AssessmentImageURI", "AssessmentLeaderID", "AssessmentModuleCode", "AssessmentModuleName", "AssessmentLeaderName"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "AssessmentID": 1, "AssessmentName": "Test Assessment 1 Update", "AssessmentStartdate": "2020-07-29T17:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2020-07-29T17:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "https://www.testupdate.com/image.png", "AssessmentLeaderID": 2, "AssessmentModuleID": 2, "AssessmentModuleCode": "KU2915", "AssessmentModuleName": "Flash", "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Olivette Temprell" }]	Pass
53	Test backend API update (POST) method successfully modifies an existing Rubric record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/rubrics/1 HTTP Method: PUT URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: { "AssessmentRubricCriterion": "Test rubric criterion 1 criterion update", "AssessmentRubricDescription": "Test rubric criterion 1 description update", "AssessmentRubricWeighting": 50, "AssessmentRubricAssessmentID": 1 }	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Rubric object, containing fields {"AssessmentRubricID", "AssessmentRubricCriterion", "AssessmentRubricDescription", "AssessmentRubricWeighting", "AssessmentRubricAssessmentID"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "AssessmentRubricID": 1, "AssessmentRubricCriterion": "Test rubric criterion 1 criterion update", "AssessmentRubricDescription": "Test rubric criterion 1 description update", "AssessmentRubricWeighting": 50 }]	Fail – fails to return AssessmentRubricAssessmentID attribute
54	Test backend API update (POST) method successfully modifies an existing Comment record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/comments/1 HTTP Method: PUT URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: { "AssessmentRubricComment": "Test assessment rubric comment 1 comment update", "AssessmentRubricCommentAssessmentRubricID": 1 }	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Comment object, containing fields {"AssessmentRubricCommentID", "AssessmentRubricComment", "AssessmentRubricCommentAssessmentRubricID"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "Failed to execute query: Unknown column 'AssessmentRubricID' in 'where clause'" }	Fail – error within SQL statement
52	Test backend API update (POST) method successfully modifies an existing Group record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/groups/1 HTTP Method: PUT URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: { "GroupName": "Test Group 1 update", "GroupImageURI": "https://www.testupdate.com/image.png", "GroupBiography": "Test group 1 biography update...", "GroupAssessmentID": 1, "GroupLeaderID": 1 }	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Group object, containing fields {"GroupID", "GroupName", "GroupImageURI", "GroupBiography", "GroupAssessmentID", "GroupLeaderID", "GroupLeaderName", "GroupLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 400 Bad Request Body: { "message": "Failed to update record 1" }	Fail – unknown error within database
53	Test backend API update (POST) method successfully modifies an existing Panel record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/panels/1 HTTP Method: PUT URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: { "PanelName": "Test Panel 1 update", "PanelImageURI": "https://www.testupdate.com/image.png", "PanelBiography": "Test panel 1 biography update...", "PanelAssessmentID": 1, "PanelLeaderID": 1 }	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Panel object, containing fields {"PanelID", "PanelName", "PanelImageURI", "PanelBiography", "PanelAssessmentID", "PanelLeaderID", "PanelLeaderName", "PanelLeaderEmail"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "PanelID": 1, "PanelName": "Test Panel 1 update", "PanelImageURI": "https://www.testupdate.com/image.png", "PanelBiography": "Test panel 1 biography update...", "PanelAssessmentID": 1, "PanelLeaderID": 1, "PanelLeaderName": "Dr Cherieanne Girvan", "PanelLeaderEmail": "" }]	Pass

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
54	Test backend API update (POST) method successfully modifies an existing Module record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules/1 HTTP Method: PUT URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: { "ModuleCode": "C15987", "ModuleName": "Test module 1 update", "ModuleImageURI": "https://www.testupdate.com/image.png", "ModuleLevel": 5, "ModuleDescription": "Test module 1 description update...", "ModuleLeaderID": 1 }	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Module object, containing fields {"ModuleID", "ModuleCode", "ModuleName", "ModuleLevel", "ModuleDescription", "ModuleLeaderID", "ModuleLeaderFullname"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "ModuleID": 1, "ModuleCode": "C15987", "ModuleName": "Test module 1 update", "ModuleLevel": 5, "ModuleDescription": "Test module 1 description update...", "ModuleLeaderID": 1, "UserTitle": "Dr", "UserFirstname": "Cherianne", "UserMiddlename": "Mella", "UserLastname": "Girvan", "UserEmail": "", "UserSerTypeID": 2, "UsertypeName": "Assessment Leader", "UsertypeNameDescription": "An academic responsible for setting an assessment" }]	Pass
54	Test backend API update (POST) method successfully modifies an AssessmentFavourite record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessmentfavourites/1 HTTP Method: PUT URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: { "AssessmentFavourite": 1 }	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains an array of one JSON Assessment object, containing fields {"AssessmentID", "AssessmentName", "AssessmentStartdate", "AssessmentEnddate", "AssessmentImageURI", "AssessmentLeaderID", "AssessmentModuleCode", "AssessmentModuleName", "AssessmentLeaderName", "AssessmentEnrollmentID", "AssessmentFavourite"}	Status Code: 200 OK Body: [{ "AssessmentID": 83, "AssessmentName": "Automated web-enabled archive assessment", "AssessmentStartdate": "2022-09-22T19:07:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2022-11-13T21:42:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "http://dummyimage.com/180x100.png/ddd/000000", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 23, "AssessmentModuleCode": "HQ2331", "AssessmentModuleName": "Emergency Nursing", "AssessmentLeaderName": "Dr Cherianne Girvan", "AssessmentEnrollmentID": 1, "AssessmentFavourite": 1 }]	Pass
55	Test backend API delete (DELETE) method successfully deletes an Assessment record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/assessments/166 HTTP Method: DELETE URL Parameters: 166 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains message of "Record successfully deleted"	Status Code: 200 OK Body: { "message": "Record successfully deleted" }	Pass
56	Test backend API delete (DELETE) method successfully deletes a Module record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules/55 HTTP Method: DELETE URL Parameters: 55 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains message of "Record successfully deleted"	Status Code: 200 OK Body: { "message": "Record successfully deleted" }	Pass
57	Test backend API delete (DELETE) method successfully deletes a Comment record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/comments/1 HTTP Method: DELETE URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains message of "Record successfully deleted"	Status Code: 200 OK Body: { "message": "Record successfully deleted" }	Pass
58	Test backend API delete (DELETE) method successfully deletes a Rubric record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/rubrics/1 HTTP Method: DELETE URL Parameters: 1 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains message of "Record successfully deleted"	Status Code: 200 OK Body: { "message": "Record successfully deleted" }	Pass

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
59	Test backend API delete (DELETE) method successfully deletes a Module record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules/55 HTTP Method: DELETE URL Parameters: 55 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains message of "Record successfully deleted"	Status Code: 200 OK Body: { "message": "Record successfully deleted" }	Pass
60	Test backend API delete (DELETE) method successfully deletes a Panel record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/panels/6 HTTP Method: DELETE URL Parameters: 6 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains message of "Record successfully deleted"	Status Code: 200 OK Body: { "message": "Record successfully deleted" }	Pass
61	Test backend API delete (DELETE) method successfully deletes a Group record	Backend API (via Postman)	URL: http://localhost:5000/api/modules/3 HTTP Method: DELETE URL Parameters: 3 Request Body: n/a	Status Code: 200 OK Body: Contains message of "Record successfully deleted"	Status Code: 200 OK Body: { "message": "Record successfully deleted" }	Pass

Table U.1 Integration Testing for Backend API

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
62	Test frontend homepage successfully displays assessment items retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/	Assessment records "Bright Ideas Competition", "Commercial Awareness Pitch" are displayed on homepage	Assessment records "Bright Ideas Competition", "Commercial Awareness Pitch" are displayed on homepage	Pass
63	Test frontend assessments page successfully displays assessment items retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/assessments	Assessment records "Bright Ideas Competition", "Commercial Awareness Pitch" are displayed on assessments page	Assessment records "Bright Ideas Competition", "Commercial Awareness Pitch" are displayed on assessments page	Pass
64	Test frontend panels page successfully displays panel items retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/panels	Panel records "Test Panel 1 update", "testing 123" are displayed on panels page	Panel records "Test Panel 1 update", "testing 123" are displayed on panels page	Pass
65	Test frontend groups page successfully displays group items retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/groups	Group records "Test Group 1 update", "testing 123" are displayed on groups page	Groups page displays 'No groups found'	Fail – Logged-in user is not enrolled in groups
66	Test frontend modules page successfully displays module items retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/modules	Module records "KU2915 - Flash", "NX4343 - Amazon EC2" are displayed on modules page	Module records "KU2915 - Flash", "NX4343 - Amazon EC2" are displayed on modules page	Pass
66	Test frontend rubrics page successfully displays rubric items retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/rubrics	Rubric records "Test Rubric 1", "Test Rubric 2" are displayed on rubrics page	Rubrics page displays 'No rubrics found'	Fail – Pre-defined assessment does not have rubrics

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
67	Test frontend rubric comments page successfully displays rubric comment items retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/comments	Rubric comment records "Test Rubric Comment 1", "Test Rubric Comment 2" are displayed on rubric comments page	Rubric comments page displays 'No rubric comments found'	Fail – Pre-defined rubric does not have comments
68	Test frontend alerts page successfully displays alert items retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/alerts	Alert records "Test Alert 1", "Test Alert 2" are displayed on alerts page	Alerts page displays 'JSON.parse: unexpected character at line 1 column 1 of the JSON data'	Fail – List error handling not working
69	Test frontend login page successfully logs in user with defined credentials	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/login	User is logged in, homepage displays, and all pages contain user-specific database data	Login form does not accept account email and login form submit performs no action	Fail – Login functionality has not been created
70	Test frontend profile page successfully displays user profile retrieved from database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/profile	User profile record's name and biography are displayed on profile page	Profile page displays '404 – Page Not Found!'	Fail – Page has not been created
71	Test frontend log out successfully logs out user with defined credentials	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/logout	Landing page displays, and user is unable to access their personal account details or protected routes, such as assessments	Logout page displays '404 – Page Not Found!'	Fail – Page and functionality have not been created
72	Test frontend new assessment button on assessments page successfully creates a new assessment record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/assessments Form Input Data: { "AssessmentName": "Test Assessment 1", "AssessmentStartdate": "2019-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2019-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 1 }	New assessment record is created in database containing form input data, with assessments page refreshing to display new assessment record	New assessment record is created in database containing form input data. Page refreshes but does not display new assessment record	Fail – User account is not enrolled in created module, thus is not fetched
72	Test frontend new panel button on panels page successfully creates a new panel record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/panels Form Input Data: { "PanelName": "Test Panel 1", "PanelImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "PanelBiography": "Test panel 1 biography...", "PanelAssessmentID": 1, "PanelLeaderID": 1 }	New panel record is created in database containing form input data, with panels page refreshing to display new panel record	New panel record is created in database containing form input data. Page refreshes but does not display new panel record	Fail – User account is not enrolled in created panel, thus is not fetched

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
73	Test frontend new group button on groups page successfully creates a new group record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/groups Form Input Data: { "GroupName": "Test Group 1", "GroupImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "GroupBiography": "Test group 1 biography...", "GroupAssessmentID": 1, "GroupLeaderID": 1 }	New group record is created in database containing form input data, with groups page refreshing to display new group record	New group record is created in database containing form input data. Page refreshes but does not display new group record	Fail – User account is not enrolled in created group, thus is not fetched
74	Test frontend new module button on modules page successfully creates a new module record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/modules Form Input Data: { "ModuleCode": "C14123", "ModuleName": "Test module 1", "ModuleImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "ModuleLevel": 4, "ModuleDescription": "Test module 1 description...", "ModuleLeaderID": 1 }	New module record is created in database containing form input data, with modules page refreshing to display new module record	New module record is created in database containing form input data. Page refreshes but does not display new module record	Fail – User account is not enrolled in created module, thus is not fetched
75	Test frontend new rubric button on rubrics page successfully creates a new rubric record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/rubrics Form Input Data: { "AssessmentRubricCriterion": "Test rubric criterion 1 criterion", "AssessmentRubricDescription": "Test rubric criterion 1 description", "AssessmentRubricWeighting": 100, "AssessmentRubricAssessmentID": 1 }	New rubric record is created in database containing form input data, with rubrics page refreshing to display new rubric record	New rubric record is created in database containing form input data. Page refreshes but does not display new rubric record	Fail – Rubric is not added to defined assessment, thus is not fetched
76	Test frontend new rubric comment button on rubric comments page successfully creates a new rubric comment record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/comments Form Input Data: { "AssessmentRubricComment": "Test assessment rubric comment 1 comment", "AssessmentRubricCommentAssessmentRubricID": 1 }	New rubric comment record is created in database containing form input data, with rubric comments page refreshing to display new rubric comment record	New rubric comment record is created in database containing form input data, with rubric comments page refreshing to display new rubric comment record	Pass
77	Test frontend new alert button on alerts page successfully creates a new alert record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/alerts Form Input Data: { "AlertTitle": "Assessment panels now published", "AlertMessage": "Assessment panels are now available to view. Be sure to check out your panel, to see more about their experience.", "AlertUsergroup": 1 }	New alert record is created in database containing form input data, with alerts page refreshing to display new alert record	New alert record is not created in database, with alerts page not displaying new alert record	Fail – POST alerts endpoint has not been created
78	Test frontend edit assessment button on assessments page successfully edits an existing assessment record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/assessments Form Input Data: { "AssessmentName": "Test Assessment 1 Update", "AssessmentStartDate": "2019-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentEndDate": "2019-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "AssessmentLeaderID": 1, "AssessmentModuleID": 1 }	Existing assessment record is updated in database, containing form input data, with assessments page refreshing to display edited assessment record	Existing assessment record is updated in database, containing form input data, with assessments page refreshing to display edited assessment record	Pass

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
79	Test frontend edit panel button on panels page successfully edits an existing panel record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/panels Form Input Data: { "PanelName": "Test Panel 1 Update", "PanelImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "PanelBiography": "Test panel 1 biography...", "PanelAssessmentID": 1, "PanelLeaderID": 1 }	Existing panel record is updated in database, containing form input data, with panels page refreshing to display edited panel record	Existing panel record is updated in database, containing form input data, with panels page refreshing to display edited panel record	Pass
80	Test frontend edit group button on groups page successfully edits an existing group record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/groups Form Input Data: { "GroupName": "Test Group 1 Update", "GroupImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "GroupBiography": "Test group 1 biography...", "GroupAssessmentID": 1, "GroupLeaderID": 1 }	Existing group record is updated in database, containing form input data, with groups page refreshing to display edited group record	Groups page displays 'No groups found'	Fail – No groups are available to update
81	Test frontend edit module button on modules page successfully edits an existing module record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/modules Form Input Data: { "ModuleCode": "C14123", "ModuleName": "Test module 1 Update", "ModuleImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png", "ModuleLevel": 4, "ModuleDescription": "Test module 1 description...", "ModuleLeaderID": 1 }	Existing module record is updated in database, containing form input data, with modules page refreshing to display edited module record	Existing module record is updated in database, containing form input data, with modules page refreshing to display edited module record	Pass
82	Test frontend edit rubric button on rubrics page successfully edits an existing rubric record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/rubrics Form Input Data: { "AssessmentrubricCriterion": "Test rubric criterion 1 criterion Update", "AssessmentrubricDescription": "Test rubric criterion 1 description", "AssessmentrubricWeighting": 100, "AssessmentrubricAssessmentID": 1 }	Existing rubric record is updated in database, containing form input data, with rubrics page refreshing to display edited rubric record	Rubrics page displays 'No rubrics found'	Fail – No rubrics are available to update
83	Test frontend edit rubric comment button on rubric comments page successfully edits an existing rubric record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/comments Form Input Data: { "AssessmentrubriccommentComment": "Test assessment rubric comment 1 comment Update", "AssessmentrubriccommentAssessmentrubricID": 1 }	Existing rubric comment record is updated in database, containing form input data, with rubric comments page refreshing to display edited rubric comment record	Rubric comments page displays 'No rubric comments found'	Fail – No rubric comments are available to update
84	Test frontend edit alert button on alerts page successfully edits an existing alert record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/alerts Form Input Data: { "AlertTitle": "Assessment panels now published", "AlertMessage": "Assessment panels are now available to view. Be sure to check out your panel, to see more about their experience.", "AlertUsergroup": 1 }	Existing alert record is updated in database, containing form input data, with alert page refreshing to display edited alert record	Alerts page displays 'JSON.parse: unexpected character at line 1 column 1 of the JSON data'	Fail – No alerts are available to update

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
85	Test frontend delete assessment button on assessments page successfully deletes an existing assessment record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/assessments	Existing assessment record is deleted in database, with assessments page refreshing to display remaining assessment records	Existing assessment record is deleted in database, with assessments page refreshing to display remaining assessment records	Pass
86	Test frontend delete panel button on panels page successfully deletes an existing panel record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/panels	Existing panel record is deleted in database, with panels page refreshing to display remaining panel records	Existing panel record is deleted in database, with panels page refreshing to display remaining panel records	Pass
87	Test frontend delete group button on groups page successfully deletes an existing group record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/groups	Existing group record is deleted in database, with groups page refreshing to display remaining group records	Groups page displays 'No groups found'	Fail – No groups are available to delete
88	Test frontend delete module button on modules page successfully deletes an existing module record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/modules	Existing module record is deleted in database, with modules page refreshing to display remaining module records	Existing module record is deleted in database, with modules page refreshing to display remaining module records	Pass
89	Test frontend delete rubric button on rubrics page successfully deletes an existing rubric record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/rubrics	Existing rubric record is deleted in database, with rubrics page refreshing to display remaining rubric records	Rubrics page displays 'No rubrics found'	Fail – No rubrics are available to delete
90	Test frontend delete rubric comment button on rubric comments page successfully deletes an existing rubric comment record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/comments	Existing rubric comment record is deleted in database, with rubric comments page refreshing to display remaining rubric comment records	Rubric comments page displays 'No rubric comments found'	Fail – No rubric comments are available to delete
91	Test frontend delete alert button on alerts page successfully deletes an existing alert record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/alerts	Existing alert record is deleted in database, with alert page refreshing to display remaining alert records	Alerts page displays 'JSON.parse: unexpected character at line 1 column 1 of the JSON data'	Fail – No alerts are available to delete

Integration Test ID	Integration Test Description	Integration Test Type	Input Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Integration Test Passed?
91	Test frontend favourite assessment button on assessments page successfully favourites an existing assessment record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/assessments	Existing assessment record is favoured in database, with assessment item favourite button displaying gold star on assessments page	Existing assessment record is favoured in database, with assessment item favourite button displaying gold star on assessments page	Pass
92	Test frontend unfavourite assessment button on assessments page successfully unfavourites an existing assessment record stored in the database	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/assessments	Existing assessment record is unfavoured in database, with assessment item favourite button displaying outlined star on assessments page	Existing assessment record is unfavoured in database, with assessment item favourite button displaying outlined star on assessments page	Pass
92	Test frontend help page successfully displays help content	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/help	Help page is displayed, containing help information	Help page displays '404 – Page Not Found!'	Fail – Help page has not been created
93	Test frontend terms of service page successfully displays terms of service content	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/terms	Terms of service page is displayed, containing terms of service information	Terms of service page displays '404 – Page Not Found!'	Fail – Terms of service page has not been created
94	Test frontend contact us page successfully displays contact content	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/contact	Contact us page is displayed, containing contact information	Contact us page displays '404 – Page Not Found!'	Fail – Contact us page has not been created
95	Test frontend cookie policy page successfully displays cookie policy content	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/cookie-policy	Cookie policy page is displayed, containing cookie policy information	Cookie policy page displays '404 – Page Not Found!'	Fail – Cookie policy page has not been created
92	Test frontend privacy policy page successfully displays privacy policy content	Complete system (via frontend React application)	URL: http://localhost:3000/privacy-policy	Privacy policy page is displayed, containing privacy policy information	Privacy policy page displays '404 – Page Not Found!'	Fail – Privacy policy page has not been created

Table U.2 Integration Testing for Frontend-Backend Coupling

Appendix V – Performance Testing

Performance Test ID	Performance Test Description	Performance Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Performance Test Passed?
1	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a specified single User record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users/:id HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 52ms Average Response Time: 6ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
2	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all User records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: N/A Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 38ms Average Response Time: 8ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
3	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a specified single Assessor record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessors/:id HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 20ms Average Response Time: 7ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
4	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all Assessor records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: N/A Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 12ms Average Response Time: 5ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Performance Test ID	Performance Test Description	Performance Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Performance Test Passed?
5	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a specified single Module record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/modules/:id HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 6ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
6	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all Module records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/modules HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: N/A Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 6ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
7	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's User records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 14ms Average Response Time: 5ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
8	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all module's User records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/modules/:id/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 9ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Performance Test ID	Performance Test Description	Performance Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Performance Test Passed?
9	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all user's Module records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users/:id/modules HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 8ms Average Response Time: 5ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
10	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all leader's Assessment records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/leader/:id/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 13ms Average Response Time: 5ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
11	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all user's Assessment records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/user/:id/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 6ms Average Response Time: 3ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
12	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all module's Assessment records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/modules/:id/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 10ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Performance Test ID	Performance Test Description	Performance Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Performance Test Passed?
13	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all user's Panel records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/user/:id/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 12ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
14	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's Panel records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 6ms Average Response Time: 3ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
15	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all user's Group records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/user/:id/groups HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 2ms Highest Response Time: 8ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
16	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's Group records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/groups HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 6ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Performance Test ID	Performance Test Description	Performance Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Performance Test Passed?
17	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's Rubric records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/rubrics HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 6ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
18	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a single assessment's Rubric record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/rubrics/:sid HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1; sid=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 6ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
19	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's rubric's Rubric Comment records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/rubrics/:sid/comments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1; sid=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 6ms Average Response Time: 3ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
20	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a single assessment's rubric's Rubric Comment record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/rubrics/:sid/comments/:tid HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1; sid=1; tid=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 25 Delay: 1000ms	Highest Response Time: 100ms Average Response Time: 10ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Lowest Response Time: 3ms Highest Response Time: 6ms Average Response Time: 4ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Table V.1 Performance Testing for Backend API

Performance Test ID	Performance Test Description	Performance Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Performance Test Passed?
21	Test frontend homepage loading performance	Frontend	URL: localhost:3000	5 browser tabs open of home page	Performance, Accessibility, Best Practices, SEO Metrics > 75 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Performance: 53 Accessibility: 56 Best Practices: 92 SEO: 73	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Fail – Website performance, accessibility and SEO requires significant improvement
22	Test frontend homepage render performance	Frontend	URL: localhost:3000	5 browser tabs open of home page	Render: < 50ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Render: 10ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Table V.2 Performance Testing for Frontend-Backend Coupling

Appendix W – Load Testing

Load Test ID	Load Test Description	Load Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Load Test Passed?
1	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a specified single User record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users/:id HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 426ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
2	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all User records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: N/A Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 1125ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
3	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a specified single Assessor record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessors/:id HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 867ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
4	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all Assessor records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: N/A Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 598ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
5	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a specified single Module record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/modules/:id HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 1647ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
6	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all Module records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/modules HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: N/A Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 624ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Load Test ID	Load Test Description	Load Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Load Test Passed?
7	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's User records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments /:id/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 1126ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
8	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all module's User records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/modules /:id/users HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 974ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
9	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all user's Module records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/users /:id/modules HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 753ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
10	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all leader's Assessment records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/leader /:id/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 637ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
11	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all user's Assessment records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/user /:id/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 893ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
12	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all module's Assessment records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/modules /:id/assessments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 786ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Load Test ID	Load Test Description	Load Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Load Test Passed?
13	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all user's Panel records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/user/:id/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 1178ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
14	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's Panel records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/panels HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 684ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
15	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all user's Group records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/user/:id/groups HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 982ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
16	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's Group records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/groups HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 1376ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
17	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's Rubric records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/rubrics HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 1134ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
18	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a single assessment's Rubric record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/rubrics/:sid HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1; sid=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 842ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Load Test ID	Load Test Description	Load Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Load Test Passed?
19	Test backend API GET method successfully returns all assessment's rubric's Rubric Comment records	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/rubrics/:sid/comments HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1; sid=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 997ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass
20	Test backend API GET method successfully returns a single assessment's rubric's Rubric Comment record	Backend API	URL: localhost:5000/api/assessments/:id/rubrics/:sid/comments/:tid HTTP Method: GET URL Parameters: id=1; sid=1; tid=1 Request Body: null	Requests Sent: 2500 Delay: 0ms	Average Response Time: 2500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Average Response Time: 945ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Table W.1 Load Testing for Backend API

Load Test ID	Load Test Description	Load Test Type	Input Data	System Test Conditions	Expected Response Time, Stability and Reliability	Actual Response Time	Actual Reliability/ Stability	Load Test Passed?
21	Test frontend homepage loading performance	Frontend	URL: localhost:3000	5 browser tabs open of home page	Performance, Accessibility, Best Practices, SEO Metrics > 50 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Performance: 53 Accessibility: 56 Best Practices: 92 SEO: 73	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Fail – Website performance, accessibility and SEO requires significant improvement
22	Test frontend homepage render performance	Frontend	URL: localhost:3000	5 browser tabs open of home page	Render: < 500ms 5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 75%	Render: 25ms	5xx HTTP Status Codes: 0 Response Success Rate: 100%	Pass

Table W.2 Load Testing for Frontend-Backend Coupling

Appendix X – System Testing

Test Case Number:	1					
Test Case Name:	View Assessments					
Test Case Description:	Test that the system displays a list of the user’s past, current and upcoming assessments on-screen					
Test Case Goals:	A list of the user’s past, current and upcoming assessments are displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes assessment name, date, module information and assessment leader.					
Test Case Requirements:	R1, R2					
Pre-Conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User is logged in • User is a member of a module • Module contains assessments 					
Expected Output:	View Assessments screen should be displayed with a list user’s past, current and upcoming assessments					
Actual Output:	View Assessments screen is displayed with a list user’s assessments					
Expected Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of assessments should be displayed within 5 seconds 					
Actual Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of assessments is displayed within 5 seconds 					
Test Case Passed?	Passed (Passed Processes: 100% [2/2]) (Passed Performance: 100% [1/1])					
Process ID	Process	Process Description	Inputted Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Process Passed?
1	Homepage navigation	Navigate to homepage (localhost:3000/)	URL: localhost:3000 /	Homepage is displayed	Homepage is displayed	Pass
2	View webpage content	View assessment card information displayed on webpage	N/A	User’s assessments are displayed on-screen	User’s assessments are displayed on-screen	Fail – Not grouped by time

Table X.1 System Test Case for View Assessments Use Case

Test Case Number:	2					
Test Case Name:	Favourite Assessment					
Test Case Description:	Test that the system displays a user's favourite assessments on-screen					
Test Case Goals:	A list of the user's past, current and upcoming assessments are displayed with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes assessment name, date, module information and assessment leader. Favourite assessments are signified by a yellow infilled star next to the card, and be easily accessible from the top of the homepage.					
Test Case Requirements:	R13					
Pre-Conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User is logged in • User is a member of a module • Module contains assessments • User has favourited assessments 					
Expected Output:	View Assessments screen should be displayed with a list user's past, current and upcoming assessments, with favourite assessments signified by a yellow infilled star and easily accessible from the top of the page					
Actual Output:	View Assessments screen is displayed with a list user's assessments, with favourite assessments signified by a yellow infilled star, but contained within the main assessment list					
Expected Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of assessments with favourites should be displayed within 5 seconds 					
Actual Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of assessments is displayed within 5 seconds 					
Test Case Passed?	Passed (Passed Processes: 50% [1/2]) (Passed Performance: 100% [1/1])					
Process ID	Process	Process Description	Inputted Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Process Passed?
1	Homepage navigation	Navigate to homepage (localhost:3000/)	URL: localhost:3000/	Homepage is displayed	Homepage is displayed	Pass
2	View webpage content	View assessment favourite information displayed on webpage	N/A	User's assessments are displayed on-screen	User's assessments are displayed on-screen	Fail – Not grouped by time

Table X.2 System Test Case for Favourite Assessment Use Case

Test Case Number:	8					
Test Case Name:	Create Assessment					
Test Case Description:	Test that the system accepts the creation and storage of a new assessment					
Test Case Goals:	The user should be able to add a new assessment with relevant, descriptive information. Information includes an associated image, assessment name, duration, and module.					
Test Case Requirements:	R53					
Pre-Conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User is logged in • User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' • Assessment module has already been created 					
Expected Output:	A new assessment should be created and stored within the system. The assessment should be retrieved and displayed on-screen.					
Actual Output:	A new assessment is created and stored within the system.					
Expected Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment information should be saved within 5 seconds • List of assessments should be displayed within 5 seconds 					
Actual Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment information is saved within 5 seconds • List of assessments is displayed within 5 seconds 					
Test Case Passed?	Passed (Passed Processes: 100% [5/5]) (Passed Performance: 100% [2/2])					
Process ID	Process	Process Description	Inputted Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Process Passed?
1	Homepage navigation	Navigate to homepage (localhost:3000/)	URL: localhost:3000/	Homepage is displayed	Homepage is displayed	Pass
2	Click 'New Assessment' button	Click on 'New Assessment' button on homepage	N/A	New assessment form is displayed on-screen	New assessment form is displayed on-screen	Pass
3	Complete form	Complete all form fields with valid data, as per advice messages	Field data: { "AssessmentName": "Test Assessment 1", "AssessmentStartdate": "2019-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2019-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png" }	Input field data is displayed within input fields	Input field data is displayed within input fields	Pass
4	Click 'Create Assessment' button	Click on 'Create Assessment' button on form	N/A	Form is hidden on webpage	Form is hidden on webpage	Pass
5	View webpage content	View assessment favourite information displayed on webpage	N/A	User's assessments , including created assessment, are displayed on-screen	User's assessments , including created assessment, are displayed on-screen	Pass

Table X.3 System Test Case for Create Assessment Use Case

Test Case Number:	13					
Test Case Name:	Edit Assessment					
Test Case Description:	Test that the system accepts the modification of an existing assessment					
Test Case Goals:	The user should be able to edit an existing assessment, replacing the previous relevant, descriptive information. Information includes an associated image, assessment name, duration, and module.					
Test Case Requirements:	R59					
Pre-Conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User is logged in • User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' • Assessment has already been created 					
Expected Output:	An existing assessment's information should be with new information and stored within the system. The assessment information should be retrieved and displayed on-screen.					
Actual Output:	An existing assessment's information is replaced with new information, stored within the system. The assessment information is retrieved and displayed on-screen.					
Expected Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment information should be updated within 5 seconds • List of assessments should be displayed within 5 seconds 					
Actual Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment information is saved within 5 seconds • List of assessments is displayed within 5 seconds 					
Test Case Passed?	Passed (Passed Processes: 100% [6/6]) (Passed Performance: 100% [2/2])					
Process ID	Process	Process Description	Inputted Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Process Passed?
1	Homepage navigation	Navigate to homepage (localhost:3000/)	URL: localhost:3000/	Homepage is displayed	Homepage is displayed	Pass
2	View webpage content	View assessment card information displayed on webpage	N/A	User's assessments are displayed on-screen	User's assessments are displayed on-screen	Pass
3	Click edit button	Click on edit button on assessment card requiring editing	N/A	Edit assessment form is displayed on-screen	Edit assessment form is displayed on-screen	Pass
4	Complete form	Complete all form fields with updated valid data, as per advice messages	Field data: <pre> { "AssessmentName": "Test Assessment 1 Update", "AssessmentStartdate": "2019-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentEnddate": "2019-07-29T18:29:00.000Z", "AssessmentImageURI": "https://www.test.com/image.png" } </pre>	Input field data is displayed within input fields	Input field data is displayed within input fields	Pass
5	Click 'Edit Assessment' button	Click on 'Edit Assessment' button on form	N/A	Form is hidden on webpage	Form is hidden on webpage	Pass

6	View webpage content	View assessment favourite information displayed on webpage	N/A	User's assessments , including updated assessment, are displayed on-screen	User's assessments , including updated assessment, are displayed on-screen	Pass
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Table X.4 System Test Case for Edit Assessment Use Case

Test Case Number:	18
Test Case Name:	Delete Assessment
Test Case Description:	Test that the system accepts the deletion of an existing assessment
Test Case Goals:	The user should be able to delete an existing assessment, preventing it from being displayed on the system.
Test Case Requirements:	R86
Pre-Conditions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User is logged in • User is of user type 'Assessment Leader' • Assessment has already been created
Expected Output:	An existing assessment should be removed from the system's storage. The assessment should not be retrieved and displayed on-screen.
Actual Output:	An existing assessment information is removed from the system's storage. The assessment is not retrieved and displayed on-screen.
Expected Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment should be deleted within 5 seconds • List of assessments should be displayed within 5 seconds
Actual Performance:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment should be deleted within 5 seconds • List of assessments is displayed within 5 seconds
Test Case Passed?	Passed (Passed Processes: 100% [3/3]) (Passed Performance: 100% [2/2])

Process ID	Process	Process Description	Inputted Data	Expected Output	Actual Output	Process Passed?
1	Homepage navigation	Navigate to homepage (localhost:3000/)	URL: localhost:3000/	Homepage is displayed	Homepage is displayed	Pass
2	View webpage content	View assessment card information displayed on webpage	N/A	User's assessments are displayed on-screen	User's assessments are displayed on-screen	Pass
3	Click delete button	Click on delete button on assessment card requiring deletion	N/A	User's assessments, excluding deleted assessment, are displayed on-screen	User's assessments, excluding deleted assessment, are displayed on-screen	Pass

Table X.5 System Test Case for Delete Assessment Use Case

Participant Information Sheet (PIS):

Participant Information Sheet (PIS) For Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool For Group Presentations

What is this Participant Information Sheet (PIS) about?

This Participant Information Sheet (PIS) explains the purpose and duration of the study conducted by Kingston University ("we", "us"), and the commitment required from you ("you", "your") in taking part. It outlines some of the potential risks or discomfort you may endure.

This document also details how the study collects, uses, processes and shares your personal data (information) and your rights in relation to this data. The notice relates to the processing of personal data we hold about you regarding the collaborative marking and feedback tool for group presentations study.

This Participant Information Sheet (PIS) answers the following questions:

- What is the role of the study?
- What is the expected duration of the study?
- What is the expected of you in the study?
- What potential risks or discomfort might you endure in the study?
- What information will we collect about you?
- How will we collect information from you?
- How will we use your information?
- How long will we keep your information for?
- How will we store your information?
- Who will have access to your information?
- What legal basis do we have for processing your information?
- How will we make sure your information remains accurate?
- What are your rights?
- Who can you contact about your information?

Kingston University is the data controller of your personal data and is subject to the General Data Protection Regulation (the "GDPR") and the UK Data Protection Act 2018. We are listed on the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) register of fee payers. A copy of the Kingston University Data Protection Policy is available online.

What is the role of the study?

The study is intended to investigate the feasibility of creating an application to promote consistent marking and feedback from assessment panels when assessing student presentations.

Many university courses have incorporated module assessments involving the delivery of a live presentation to a panel of assessors, where both the student's understanding of their produced works and their presentation skills are reviewed, resulting in the student obtaining feedback and credit towards a student's module grade.

However, assessors within a panel are given freedom to deliberate and record their feedback, leading to a lack of consistency, hindering student feedback and grades. Assessors within a panel may make digital or paper notes during the presentation individually, before discussing their ideas with the other panel members to produce a unified feedback document, which can lead to inexperienced assessors struggling, or a lack of consistency or best practice within the feedback produced.

As panels gain experience with the assessment format and generating feedback comments, through assessing multiple groups, their feedback consistency and accuracy typically improves. Panels generally lack time between talks to fully discuss each group's performance and feedback, often leading to rushed and inaccurate feedback, or a delayed start to the next presentation, disrupting the event's schedule. Feedback collation from panels, to disseminate to each group and formally assign students' grades, is a lengthy process for the lead assessor.

The study seeks to resolve these issues, through creating a common platform to address the lack of standardisation and consistency across feedback gathering methods currently used, and promote consistent marking and feedback from assessment panels when assessing student presentations.

The intended solution would facilitate collaboration between panel members during assessments to better support inexperienced panellists and enable the creation of consistent, agreed feedback and grades during the presentation, without contributing to delays to presentation schedules. The common platform would make it easier and faster for feedback to be disseminated to students.

What is the expected duration of the study?

The study will commence in late September 2022 and conclude by May 2022. You are not expected to be required for the duration of the study.

What is the expected of you in the study?

You are expected to be available to provide feedback and answer questions, during regular intervals of the study's duration. The study will operate using an iterative approach, therefore you will be contacted typically once every three weeks, to obtain feedback on the features implemented into a prototype application and gather information relating to the current issues and potential solutions surrounding group presentation assessment.

Contact may range from an email asking you if you could complete a survey, which should take no longer than ten minutes to complete, or a one-to-one interview, which should last no more than fifteen minutes. Your commitment is highly appreciated, although if you are unavailable to participate in the study for a short duration, this is perfectly acceptable, and you are under no obligation to be involved in the study each time you receive contact from us.

Surveys may be conducted at your convenience, whilst interviews will be arranged for a mutually convenient time, either in-person, or via online videoconferencing applications, such as Microsoft Teams. Consequently, there is no requirement for you to physically travel to be involved in this study. Unfortunately, as this study is not funded, there is no monetary compensation available for your time or travelling expenses.

What potential risks or discomfort might you endure in the study?

The likelihood of risks or discomfort affecting participants involved in the study is very low, although there are some key risks that have been identified. In all cases, mitigating action has been taken, therefore the effects and probability of the risk occurring have been minimised.

Data Breaches:

One potential risk involves the possibility of a data breach, with your personal information or responses linked to you being stolen, leaked or viewed by unauthorised persons. This would lead to a breach of confidentiality, potentially causing reputational damage, unsolicited messages, social stigma or affecting current employment. This is very rare, as measures have been taken to ensure data is stored securely and only authorised users may access the data. More information regarding data security can be found in the 'Data Management' section in this document.

Psychological or Emotional Discomfort:

You may endure potential psychological or emotional discomfort when discussing the topic of assessment. Assessment can be a particularly stressful process for all involved. Students who have faced challenges in past groupwork activities, or received negative feedback for previous assessments, may feel sensitively about this topic, whilst academic staff may recall the stresses of coordinating assessments. This would lead to the potential for you to be depressed, either in the short or long term. This is rare, as measures will be taken to ensure you feel supported throughout their involvement in the study, and only feel obliged to share what you are comfortable with saying.

Fatigue:

A further potential risk relates to you feeling fatigued, based on having an already busy schedule, and attempting to find time to participate in the study. Often, you already have a significant amount of work to do outside of participating in studies and may feel obliged or wish to participate in the study, to assist as much as possible. This would lead to the potential for you to feel fatigued or stressed, either in the short or long term. This is rare, as measures will be taken to ensure you are aware of your ability to take breaks from participating in the study, and you will be offered short questionnaires or interviews, so as not to hinder your other work. Furthermore, you will only be contacted once every three weeks.

What information will we collect about you?

This study will require the collection of your basic personal information, including your title, first and last name, and contact information, including your email address and/or contact telephone number.

Any responses you make to provided study questions, whether as part of a survey or interview, will be collected and recorded. Any documentation or other items you show or demonstrate in interviews may be photographed for the purposes of later analysis. Furthermore, any interactions you make when using or testing provided prototypes will be screen recorded.

At any time, you may request a copy of all the data we hold on you, which will be provided within five working days of your request. Should any data we hold on you be inaccurate or incorrect, please contact us, and we will ensure the relevant information is updated.

If you wish to withdraw from the study, or delete all or parts of your provided information, please contact us, and we will be happy to fulfil this request. If you wish to withhold selected information, such as not provide us with a contact telephone number or not participate in a particular survey, please contact us and we will strive to accommodate your request.

How will we collect information from you?

You will expect to receive a link to an online survey, sent to your provided email address, from a reputable GDPR-compliant survey company, Microsoft Forms. These surveys will be short, typically taking no more than ten minutes of your time to complete. They will be formed of either free-text questions, such as 'What current problems do you face when providing or receiving feedback?', multiple-choice questions, such as 'How satisfied are you with the current feedback systems used?' or both.

The data will be exported from the survey website, for use in the study. If you do not have, or have not supplied, an email address, a paper version of the survey will be provided, which should be completed and returned to the research team. When using either the online survey website or paper-based survey form, you should fill out the form yourself, although if there are reasons why this is not possible, feel free to recruit a suitable scribe, or contact the research team, who will be able to record your answers for you. Response data will be associated with participants through means of a provided ID, preventing responses from being directly linked to an individual.

Interviews will be conducted with you individually, with some interviews being structured, with you being asked pre-prepared questions, and your responses being recorded. Semi-structured interviews will also be used, where you will be asked some pre-prepared questions, but will be given flexibility to discuss other aspects of the study, where you feel necessary, with all responses being recorded.

Interviews will collect data through the use of notetaking, with the research team member interviewing you, manually recording response information in a Microsoft Word document. No audio or video recording techniques will be used, and interviewees are free to review, or request copies, deletion, or modification of the transcribed document at any time. Response data will be associated with participants through means of a provided ID, preventing responses from being directly linked to an individual.

Photographs may be taken of key documentation, or other such items, provided by you during an interview, although you or any of your identifiable information will not be included within a taken photograph.

Screen recordings, including static screenshots, will be taken of your screen whilst you are using the prototype application, for testing and validation purposes of the produced application, although you or any of your identifiable information will not be included within a taken screen recording.

Email communications will be used, with any messages being sent or received from the research team to you being recorded, for the purposes of keeping you informed about the status of the study. These will be stored and treated securely and in confidence. In the event an email address has not been provided, telephone communications will be used.

How will we use your information?

We use your personal data in different ways depending on the stage of your interaction with us. For example, we process your contact information to send you the interview or survey request. We then process the personal data you choose to provide via the interview or survey for the purposes of the study.

Your collected data will only be used for the purposes of gathering and validating user requirements and validating any produced application implementations or features contained within these. Any published data, such as in a report, will be fully anonymised and, where appropriate, aggregated, to ensure confidentiality and prevent identification of yourself.

How long will we keep your information for?

The study is expected to conclude by May 2022, and information will only be stored for as long is necessary – the duration of the study. Once the study has concluded, all Microsoft Word documents containing your contact, interview or survey information will be securely destroyed. Any screen recordings, screenshots, associated data, email messages or telephone call history logs will also be securely destroyed. Furthermore, any survey responses contained within Microsoft Forms will be securely destroyed.

If you provide us with a completed paper survey, upon successful entry of the survey information into a Microsoft Word document for electronic storage, within two working days of receiving the paper form, the paper document will be securely destroyed.

Photographs will be taken using a smartphone device and transferred into a Microsoft Word document for electronic storage, within two working days. Any copies of the photograph stored within the smartphone or managed device will be securely destroyed upon successful insertion into Microsoft Word document.

Secure destruction of data will be performed in line with industry best practice and the recommended guidance of the software provider. Personal information collected about you that can identify you, such as your name or email address, will be destroyed upon the study's completion, and only anonymised and aggregated information you provide during interviews and surveys will be retained, contained within the unpublished report.

How will we store your information?

All collected data will only be accessible by the research team, and will be stored securely in an encrypted, password-protected directory on a Kingston University-owned, managed device. Interview textual data and pictures taken will be securely and confidentially contained in encrypted, password-protected Microsoft Word documents stored locally on secure device.

These documents will be stored in a private folder location, only accessible by the research team, and the document passwords will not be stored, and only known by the research team, preventing unauthorised access. Kingston University devices are secure, well-maintained and regularly checked for viruses, whilst their Acceptable Use policy is adhered to at all times, to ensure your data is used and stored appropriately.

Documents will only be accessed and viewed in private locations, from a password-protected, encrypted device, where unauthorised persons are unable to inadvertently view the content of the documents. Upon completion of accessing the documents, the device will be locked, to prevent unauthorised access. Documents will not be copied, duplicated, or sent to any other locations or devices.

Stored data recorded on the website of Microsoft Forms, a reputable GDPR-compliant survey company, will be contained in accordance with their terms and conditions and privacy policy, which will be outlined to the user prior to taking the survey. Should you not consent to these policies, or not provide a contact email address, paper copies of the survey will be provided to you upon request.

All paper copies of completed surveys will be held in a locked bag on the researcher's person and processed securely. During this process, the document will only be visible to the researcher, who will enter the form data into an encrypted, password-protected Microsoft Word document stored securely on the managed device, within two working days of receiving the paper form in a private location. Upon successful entry of the paper survey into the Microsoft Word document, within two working days of receiving the paper form, the paper document will be securely destroyed.

Photographs will be taken using a smartphone device and transferred to the managed device containing the Word document, before being inserted into the associated Word document, within two working days. Any copies of the photograph stored within the smartphone or managed device will be securely destroyed upon successful insertion into Word document. Screen recordings and screenshots will be saved to encrypted, password-protected secure directory contained within the managed device.

Email communications will be stored securely via on Microsoft Outlook's email servers in the cloud, whilst telephone call logs will be retained on the telephone used to make the call to you.

Who will have access to your information?

All collected data will only be accessible by the research team, although anonymised and aggregated information will be included within an internal, unpublished report. Information used within the report will not be identifiable or contain any reference to you.

What legal basis do we have for processing your information?

We rely on three legal bases for processing your personal data.

The first is legitimate interests, which we rely upon for the collection and processing of your personal data. We believe that we have a legitimate interest in conducting academic research and have considered the potential impact on you. You can ask us to stop processing your personal data and we will remove them.

The second legal basis is consent in relation to any personal data that you provide to us either via the interview or survey response or any subsequent communications with us. You can withdraw your consent at any time, and we will stop processing your personal data and remove it from the conducted research.

The third is explicit consent in relation to any special category (sensitive) personal data that you may disclose to us during the interview or survey.

How will we make sure your information remains accurate?

We will hold your data only for a short period of time, which reduces the likelihood that any data will become inaccurate. Furthermore, aside from your publicly available contact details all personal data will be provided by you. Should your information change, please contact the research team, who will be happy to update information held on you.

What are your rights?

Under the GDPR and the UK Data Protection Act 2018, you have the following rights:

- to access from us the personal data we hold about you;
- to require us to correct the personal data we hold about you if it is incorrect;
- to require us to erase your personal data;
- to require us to restrict the conducted data processing activities (and, where processing is based on your consent, you may withdraw that consent, without affecting the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal);
- to receive your personal data, which you provided to us, in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and the right to transmit that data to another controller;
- to object, on grounds relating to your particular situation, to any particular processing activities where you feel this has a disproportionate impact on your rights;
- to not be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which has a legal effect on you.

Please note that the above rights are not absolute and we may be entitled to refuse requests where exceptions apply.

If you have given your consent and you wish to withdraw it, please contact Mr. Tug O'Flaherty via email, explicitly stating your intention to withdraw from the study, at k2012185@kingston.ac.uk. Your request to withdraw from the study, including secure destruction of all data we hold on you, will be completed within five working days.

Who can you contact about your information?

The study is managed by, and research team is formed of, Mr. Tug O'Flaherty. If you wish to request access to the personal data we hold about you, please contact Mr. Tug O'Flaherty at k2012185@kingston.ac.uk in the first instance. Alternatively, you can use the Kingston University [Subject Access Request Form](#) available online. For any other queries about this privacy notice or how we process your personal data you can contact the Data Protection Officer by email: DPO@kingston.ac.uk or by post: Data Protection Officer, Vice Chancellor's Office, River House, 53–57 High Street, Kingston upon Thames, Surrey KT1 1LQ.

If you are not satisfied with how we are processing your personal data, you can make a complaint to the Information Commissioner.

You can find out more about your rights under data protection legislation from the [Information Commissioner's Office](#) website.

Figure Y.1 Usability Testing Participant Information Sheet (PIS)

Consent Form:

Informed Consent For Collaborative Marking and Feedback Tool For Group Presentations

Please tick the appropriate boxes Yes No

1. Taking part in the study

I have read and understood the study information dated 12/11/2022, or it has been read to me. I have been able to ask questions about the study and my questions have been answered to my satisfaction.

I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study and understand that I can refuse to answer questions and I can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give a reason, and without penalty.

I understand that taking part in the study involves providing feedback on current practices or methods used for marking and/or feedback for group presentations, and expressing opinions on features required, screen designs, and testing a prototype of a new, experimental tool to provide or receive group presentation feedback.

During this study, information will be collected using survey questionnaires completed by the participant, either via an online third-party survey tool (Microsoft Forms) or a paper-based form, which will be transcribed and stored in an electronic format. Participants may also be individually interviewed, with information recorded via written notes, stored electronically. These interviews may include photographs being taken of relevant documentation or items produced by the interviewee, or screen recordings or screenshots of a participant's usage of a prototype. No participants or identifiable information will be included within a taken photograph, screen recording or screenshot.

I understand and consent to the above information collection methods being used and am aware that I may request a paper survey questionnaire form, should I not wish to use provided online third-party survey tool.

2. Use of the information in the study

I understand that information I provide will be used for the purposes of furthering knowledge relating to the marking and assessment for group presentations, and will be fully anonymised, before being published in an unpublished, internal report viewable only by the researcher, up to four University academics, and any external examiners.

I understand that information I provide may be included in the report as fully anonymous direct quotations or may be aggregated with other participants' responses to provide anonymous quantitative data.

I understand that personal information collected about me that can identify me, such as my name or email address, will be used by the researcher only. Personal information will be used strictly for the purpose of contacting the participant to participate in aspects of the study, and to identify participant responses prior to response anonymisation, to remove a participant's responses in the event they withdraw from the study.

I understand that all information I provide will be handled and governed in accordance with GDPR and the Data Protection Act (2018) and stored securely.

I understand that personal information collected about me that can identify me, such as my name or email address, will be destroyed upon the study's completion, and only anonymised data will be retained, contained within the unpublished report.

3. Signatures

Name of participant [IN CAPITALS] Signature Date

I have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant and, to the best of my ability, ensured that the participant understands to what they are freely consenting.

Name of researcher [IN CAPITALS] Signature Date

4. Study contact details for further information

Name: Mr. Tug O'Flaherty

Email: K2012185@kingston.ac.uk

Figure Y.2 Consent Form

Appendix Z – Usability Testing Results Tables

Assessment Leader Participant Usability Testing Results:

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
1	View Assessments	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	30 seconds	2	1	Initially happy, then became confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	None	User studied navbar and (currently displayed) homepage for a significant amount of time	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although was confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	Yes	Pass
2	View Assessment Panel Profile	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Panels page and click on panel	2 minutes	1 minute	3	3	Initially happy, then became confused at what to click on panel card to navigate to panel profile	User mumbled 'hmm' to themselves multiple times throughout	User was clicking panel card background and not text or image within card	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the clickable area of the panel card was too small, and background should also be clickable	Yes	Pass
3	Create Assessment	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page and create a new assessment	3 minutes	2 minutes	4	3	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User quickly located Create Assessment button and inputted appropriate assessment details	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the Create Assessment button should be positioned at the top of the page, as with many assessments displayed within the list, it would be difficult and time consuming to find, and the form should be displayed within a modal or a new page, for increased readability and to prevent distractions from the page content	Yes	Pass
4	Create Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and create a new rubric	3 minutes	1 minute 30 seconds	2	2	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User quickly located Create Rubric button and inputted appropriate assessment rubric details	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the Create Rubric button should be positioned at the top of the page, as with many rubrics displayed within the list, it would be difficult and time consuming to find, and the form should be displayed within a modal or a new page, for increased readability and to prevent distractions from the page content	Yes	Pass
5	Edit Assessment	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page and edit an existing assessment	3 minutes	1 minute 30 seconds	2	2	Happy	User mumbled 'hmm' to themselves multiple times throughout	User quickly located Edit button and inputted appropriate assessment details	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the form should be displayed within a modal, for increased readability and to prevent distractions from the page content	Yes	Pass
6	Edit Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and edit an existing rubric	3 minutes	1 minute	2	2	Happy	User mumbled 'hmm' to themselves multiple times throughout	User quickly located Edit button and inputted appropriate assessment rubric details	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the form should be displayed within a modal, for increased readability and to prevent distractions from the page content	Yes	Pass
7	Delete Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and delete an existing rubric	2 minutes	30 seconds	1	1	Happy	None	User quickly located Delete button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were of a good size and easy to use	Yes	Pass
8	Delete Assessment Group	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Groups page and delete an existing group	2 minutes	1 minute	2	1	Happy	User mumbled 'hmm' to themselves multiple times throughout	User located Groups page and subsequently quickly located Delete button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were of a good size and easy to use	Yes	Pass

Table Z.1 Assessment Leader Usability Test Participant's Test Results

Assessment Leader Participant Usability Testing Results:

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
9	View Assessments	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	1 minute	2	1	Initially happy, then became confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User studied navbar and (currently displayed) homepage for a significant amount of time	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although was confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	Yes	Pass
10	View Assessment Panel Profile	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Panels page and click on panel	2 minutes	2 minutes	3	3	Initially happy, then became confused at what to click on panel card to navigate to panel profile	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User was clicking panel card background and not text or image within card	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the clickable area of the panel card was too small, and background should also be clickable	Yes	Pass
11	Create Assessment	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page and create a new assessment	3 minutes	3 minutes	4	5	Confused when required to input assessment details	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User struggled to locate Create Assessment button and read form field advice messages	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the advice and error messages should be bigger, as they were difficult to read, and the start and end time fields needed to match the other input fields	Yes	Pass
12	Create Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and create a new rubric	3 minutes	3 minutes	3	4	Initially happy, then became confused when required to input assessment rubric details	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User struggled to locate Create Rubric button and read form field advice messages	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the advice and error messages should be bigger, as they were difficult to read, and the start and end time fields needed to match the other input fields	Yes	Pass
13	Edit Assessment	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page and edit an existing assessment	3 minutes	3 minutes	3	2	Initially happy, then became confused when required to input assessment details	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User struggled to read form field advice messages	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the advice and error messages should be bigger, as they were difficult to read, and the start and end time fields needed to match the other input fields	Yes	Pass
14	Edit Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and edit an existing rubric	3 minutes	2 minutes 30 seconds	4	3	Initially happy, then became confused when required to input assessment rubric details	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User struggled to read form field advice messages	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the advice and error messages should be bigger, as they were difficult to read, and the start and end time fields needed to match the other input fields	Yes	Pass
15	Delete Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and delete an existing rubric	2 minutes	1 minute	2	1	Happy	User mumbled "hmm" to themselves multiple times throughout	User located Delete button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were of a good size and easy to use	Yes	Pass
16	Delete Assessment Group	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Groups page and delete an existing group	2 minutes	1 minute	3	1	Happy	User mumbled "hmm" to themselves multiple times throughout	User located Groups page and subsequently quickly located Delete button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were of a good size and easy to use	Yes	Pass

Table Z.2 Assessment Leader Usability Test Participant's Test Results

Assessment Leader Participant Usability Testing Results:

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
17	View Assessments	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	1 minute 30 seconds	1	1	Confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	User mumbled 'hmm' to themself multiple times throughout	User studied navbar and (currently displayed) homepage for a significant amount of time	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although was confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	Yes	Pass
18	View Assessment Panel Profile	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Panels page and click on panel	2 minutes	1 minute 30 seconds	2	1	Happy	User mumbled 'hmm' to themself multiple times throughout	User located Panels page and clicked on panel card text	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating that the panel cards were of an appropriate size	Yes	Pass
19	Create Assessment	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page and create a new assessment	3 minutes	2 minutes 30 seconds	3	3	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themself multiple times throughout	User quickly located Create Assessment button and inputted appropriate assessment details	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the form was intuitive, with useful error and help messages, and the date time selector and text editor were useful	Yes	Pass
20	Create Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and create a new rubric	3 minutes	2 minutes 30 seconds	3	3	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themself multiple times throughout	User quickly located Create Rubric button and inputted appropriate rubric details	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, appreciating the percentage input field, although stated that the percentage field should be less wide	Yes	Pass
21	Edit Assessment	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Assessments page and edit an existing assessment	3 minutes	2 minutes	2	2	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themself multiple times throughout	User quickly located Edit button and inputted appropriate assessment details	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface	Yes	Pass
22	Edit Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and edit an existing rubric	3 minutes	2 minutes	2	2	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themself multiple times throughout	User quickly located Edit button and inputted appropriate assessment rubric details	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface	Yes	Pass
23	Delete Assessment Rubric	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Rubrics page and delete an existing rubric	2 minutes	1 minute	1	1	Happy	User mumbled 'hmm' to themself multiple times throughout	User located Delete button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were of a good size and easy to use	Yes	Pass
24	Delete Assessment Group	Assessment leader must successfully navigate to Groups page and delete an existing group	2 minutes	1 minute	1	1	Happy	User mumbled 'hmm' to themself multiple times throughout	User located Groups page and subsequently quickly located Delete button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were of a good size and easy to use	Yes	Pass

Table Z.3 Assessment Leader Usability Test Participant's Test Results

Assessor Participant Usability Testing Results:

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
25	View Assessments	Assessor must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	1 minute	1	1	Confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	User mumbled 'hmm' to themself multiple times throughout	User studied navbar and (currently displayed) homepage for a significant amount of time	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although was confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	Yes	Pass
26	View Assessment Group Profile	Assessor must successfully navigate to Groups page and click on group	2 minutes	1 minute 30 seconds	2	2	Initially happy, then became confused at what to click on panel card to navigate to group profile	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themself multiple times throughout	User was clicking group card background and not text or image within card	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the clickable area of the group card was too small, and background should also be clickable	Yes	Pass
27	Create Assessment Favourite	Assessor must successfully navigate to Assessments page and favourite an assessment	1 minute	1 minute	1	1	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themself multiple times throughout	User located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were easy to use	Yes	Pass
28	Edit Assessment Panel Profile	Assessor must successfully navigate to Panels page and edit their existing panel profile	4 minutes	3 minutes 30 seconds	3	4	Initially happy, then became confused when required to input panel profile details	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themself multiple times throughout	User struggled to read form field advice messages	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the form field advice messages should be larger and the form should be displayed in a modal	Yes	Pass
29	Delete Assessment Favourite	Assessor must successfully navigate to Assessments page and unfavourite an assessment	1 minute	30 seconds	1	0	Happy	None	User located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were easy to use	Yes	Pass

Table Z.4 Assessor Usability Test Participant's Test Results

Assessor Participant Usability Testing Results:

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
30	View Assessments	Assessor must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	1 minute	0	1	Confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	User mumbled 'hmm' to themselves multiple times throughout	User studied navbar and (currently displayed) homepage for a significant amount of time	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although was confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	Yes	Pass
31	View Assessment Group Profile	Assessor must successfully navigate to Groups page and click on group	2 minutes	1 minute	1	1	Happy	User mumbled 'hmm' to themselves multiple times throughout	User located Groups page and clicked on group card text	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating that the panel cards utilised a good internal layout	Yes	Pass
32	Create Assessment Favourite	Assessor must successfully navigate to Assessments page and favourite an assessment	1 minute	30 seconds	1	1	Happy	None	User quickly located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the filled and unfilled icon to show favourites provided useful feedback	Yes	Pass
33	Edit Assessment Panel Profile	Assessor must successfully navigate to Panels page and edit their existing panel profile	4 minutes	3 minutes	2	2	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User quickly located Edit button and inputted panel profile details	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface	Yes	Pass
34	Delete Assessment Favourite	Assessor must successfully navigate to Assessments page and unfavourite an assessment	1 minute	30 seconds	0	0	Happy	None	User quickly located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the filled and unfilled icon to show favourites provided useful feedback	Yes	Pass

Table Z.5 Assessor Usability Test Participant's Test Results

Assessor Participant Usability Testing Results:

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
35	View Assessments	Assessor must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	30 seconds	0	1	Happy	None	User quickly identified 'Assessments' link in navbar	User was very satisfied with the design and layout of the user interface	Yes	Pass
36	View Assessment Group Profile	Assessor must successfully navigate to Groups page and click on group	2 minutes	1 minute	1	1	Happy	User mumbled 'hmm' to themselves multiple times throughout	User located Groups page and clicked on group card image	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating that the journey to view a panel profile was clear and easy	Yes	Pass
37	Create Assessment Favourite	Assessor must successfully navigate to Assessments page and favourite an assessment	1 minute	30 seconds	0	1	Happy	None	User quickly located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were easy to use	Yes	Pass
38	Edit Assessment Panel Profile	Assessor must successfully navigate to Panels page and edit their existing panel profile	4 minutes	2 minutes 30 seconds	3	2	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User quickly located Edit button and inputted panel profile details	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface	Yes	Pass
39	Delete Assessment Favourite	Assessor must successfully navigate to Assessments page and unfavourite an assessment	1 minute	30 seconds	0	0	Happy	None	User quickly located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were easy to use	Yes	Pass

Table Z.6 Assessor Usability Test Participant's Test Results

Student Participant Usability Testing Results:

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
40	View Assessments	Student must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	30 seconds	0	1	Happy	None	User quickly identified 'Assessments' link in navbar	User was very satisfied with the design and layout of the user interface	Yes	Pass
41	View Assessment Panel Profile	Student must successfully navigate to Panels page and click on panel	2 minutes	1 minute	0	2	Happy	User mumbled 'hmm' to himself multiple times throughout	User located Panels page and clicked on panel card image	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating that the panel cards were of an appropriate size	Yes	Pass
42	Create Assessment Favourite	Student must successfully navigate to Assessments page and favourite an assessment	1 minute	30 seconds	0	0	Happy	None	User quickly located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were easy to use	Yes	Pass
43	Edit Assessment Group Profile	Student must successfully navigate to Groups page and edit their existing group profile	4 minutes	1 minute 30 seconds	2	0	Happy	None	User quickly located Edit button and inputted panel profile details	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, saying the icons were easy to use	Yes	Pass
44	Delete Assessment Favourite	Student must successfully navigate to Assessments page and unfavourite an assessment	1 minute	30 seconds	1	0	Happy	None	User quickly located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the icons were easy to use	Yes	Pass

Table Z.7 Student Usability Test Participant's Test Results

Student Participant Usability Testing Results:

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
45	View Assessments	Student must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	1 minute	1	1	Initially happy, then became confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	User mumbled 'hmm' to himself multiple times throughout	User studied navbar and (currently displayed) homepage for a significant amount of time	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although was confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	Yes	Pass
46	View Assessment Panel Profile	Student must successfully navigate to Panels page and click on panel	2 minutes	1 minute 30 seconds	2	2	Initially happy, then became confused at what to click on panel card to navigate to panel profile	User mumbled 'hmm' to himself multiple times throughout	User was clicking panel card background and not text or image within card	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the clickable area of the panel card was too small, and background should also be clickable	Yes	Pass
47	Create Assessment Favourite	Student must successfully navigate to Assessments page and favourite an assessment	1 minute	1 minute	1	2	Happy	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the filled and unfilled icon to show favourites provided useful feedback	Yes	Pass
48	Edit Assessment Group Profile	Student must successfully navigate to Groups page and edit their existing group profile	4 minutes	3 minutes 30 seconds	5	3	Initially happy, then became confused when required to input group profile details	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User struggled to read form field advice messages	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the form field advice messages should be larger and the form should be displayed in a modal	Yes	Pass
49	Delete Assessment Favourite	Student must successfully navigate to Assessments page and unfavourite an assessment	1 minute	30 seconds	1	1	Happy	None	User quickly located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the filled and unfilled icon to show favourites provided useful feedback	Yes	Pass

Table Z.8 Student Usability Test Participant's Test Results

Student Participant Usability Testing Results:

Usability Test ID	Test Requirement	Usability Test Task Description	Expected Completion Time	Actual Completion Time	Number of mis-clicks or incorrect navigation or decisions	Number of pauses (>10 seconds)	Facial Expressions During Task Completion	Speech During Task Completion	Screen Observations During Task Completion	Overall Opinions	Task Achieved?	Usability Test Passed?
50	View Assessments	Student must successfully navigate to Assessments page	2 minutes	2 minutes	1	3	Initially happy, then became confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User studied navbar and (currently displayed) homepage for a significant amount of time	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although was confused about the difference between the homepage and Assessments page	Yes	Pass
51	View Assessment Panel Profile	Student must successfully navigate to Panels page and click on panel	2 minutes	1 minute 30 seconds	2	1	Initially happy, then became confused at what to click on panel card to navigate to panel profile	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User was clicking panel card background and not text or image within card	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the clickable area of the panel card was too small, and background should also be clickable	Yes	Pass
52	Create Assessment Favourite	Student must successfully navigate to Assessments page and favourite an assessment	1 minute	1 minute	2	2	Happy	User mumbled "hmm" to themselves multiple times throughout	User located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the filled and unfilled icon to show favourites provided useful feedback	Yes	Pass
53	Edit Assessment Group Profile	Student must successfully navigate to Groups page and edit their existing group profile	4 minutes	4 minutes	4	3	Initially happy, then became confused when required to input group profile details	User talked through what they were seeing on-screen to themselves multiple times throughout	User struggled to read form field advice messages	User was satisfied with the design of the user interface, although stated that the form field advice messages should be larger and the form should be displayed in a modal	Yes	Pass
54	Delete Assessment Favourite	Student must successfully navigate to Assessments page and unfavourite an assessment	1 minute	30 seconds	1	0	Happy	None	User quickly located Favourites button	User was very satisfied with the design of the user interface, stating the filled and unfilled icon to show favourites provided useful feedback	Yes	Pass

Table Z.9 Student Usability Test Participant's Test Results